

**THE EXPERIENCES OF FEMALE MUSLIMS WEARING THE HIJAB IN
SCOTLAND**

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"Sometimes, carrying on, just carrying on, is the superhuman achievement." Albert Camus

Abstract

Although often related to Islam, the practice of head-covering has been common in various parts of the world for a range of cultural, pragmatic, and religious reasons. The Hijab is arguably the most visible and politicised aspects of Islam in the 21st Century. This study explores the experiences of a sample of Muslim women who wear hijabs in Scotland by conducting and analysing twenty in-depth interviews in three major cities where Muslims in Scotland are highly concentrated, namely Edinburgh, Glasgow, and Dundee.

Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is used to fully contextualise and understand the empirical data that is gathered for this project, and to explore how the women interviewed experience the Hijab in contemporary Scottish society. The analysis explores the significance, purposes, motivations, and impacts of wearing Hijab. Furthermore, the interviews focus on experiences of prejudice and discrimination related to their appearance, perceptions by others, and possible impacts from negative stereotypes and media portrayal of veiled Muslim women. Finally, the current study employs a critical conceptual lens to gain a critical understanding of women's experiences and to this end, applies critical theories such as feminist standpoint theory, intersectionality, and the matrix of gendered islamophobia. This tripartite theoretical framework allows for a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of the data.

In terms of key findings, the results are divided into three main chapters. The first data chapter deals with the participants' own accounts of the significance, motivations, purposes of wearing the Hijab. The second chapter explores the wearing of the Hijab from a feminist perspective, Muslim women's perceptions the Hijab, and their interpretations of the perceptions of the community and the media in Scotland. The last data chapter is dedicated to the many different challenges that face Muslim women in Scotland by exploring the various types of gendered Islamophobia that are encountered by them on a day-to-day basis, including direct forms of Islamophobia such as the verbal and the physical aspects, as well as covert or indirect forms of prejudice, including microaggressions and institutional Islamophobia.

A key motivation for conducting this research is the relative lack of evidence available regarding the practice of the Hijab. Although, there has been research conducted on Muslim women's experiences in Scotland (Syswerda, 2017 and Hengameh, 2017) the literature is lacking in terms of the practice of Hijab specifically except for Siraj's (2011) contribution. The current study adds to the existing literature by emphasising the importance of foregrounding research from the varied standpoints of veiled Muslim women themselves to best understand the practice of the Hijab.

To achieve this aim, the study employs different methodological and theoretical tools such as in-depth interviews, interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA), feminist, and intersectional theories. Together they allow for new insights into the everyday experiences of Hijabi Muslim women in Scotland. The findings suggest that focus should be shifted onto the gendered aspects of veiling, along with other identity categories within the Scottish Muslim communities. Moreover, based on the qualitative findings, it is suggested that a future quantitative study might provide additional data in relation to attitudes held by veiled Muslim women in Scotland regarding personal, social, and political nuances surrounding the Hijab.

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1. General Introduction:

1.1. Research Background: A Brief Introduction.

Throughout history, clothes have served various functions such as insulating the body from cold weather and identifying the person's status, personality, style, values, and beliefs. There are various religious and scientific perspectives on why human beings invented clothes. Gilligan (2023, p.1) argues that people wear clothes for different purposes and among them is "to cover themselves due to a sense of modesty, or shame about nakedness". Although some studies have shown that the main reason for inventing clothes was mainly to keep people warm, Ham (2021) suggests that weather conditions were not the primary reason human beings created clothes, but because of sin and shame. From theological perspective, the first mention of clothing is related to the original sin¹ of Adam and Eve that follows the fall from the Garden of Eden (Pike,1951). As per Ambrosio (2019, p.3) "The Scriptures certainly do not fail to mention the importance of dress. They even see it as fundamental, in the sense that it plays a key role at certain important points in the biblical narrative, according to which, dress, or the lack of it, was linked to Adam and Eve and the Garden of Eden."

According to some biblical accounts, mankind was created naked, but after Adam and his wife ate from the tree of knowledge of good and evil, they become aware of their nakedness "The eyes of them both were opened, and they knew that they were naked; and they sewed fig leaves together and made themselves aprons." (Gen, chapter 2 cited in Velleman, 2001). Consequently, nakedness started to be seen as a shameful state and clothing served the purpose of covering the body to avoid shame. The Islamic account of Adam and Eve becoming aware of their nakedness is mostly like the biblical accounts of the story. Because the concept of nakedness is related to the wrath of God, the concept of "Haya"² or modesty in Islam is crucial.

In Islamic culture, the history of Islamic modest dress dates to "the 7th century" (Khan, 2023, no page), when the Quran unveils the guidelines for modesty. Thus, the Hijab³ implies that both genders are instructed to cover their Awrah⁴. The body parts that should be covered vary between men and women (Rizvi, 1992) and they differ based on different Islamic schools (Hasmad and Alosman, 2020). In men's case, the awrah refers to the area between the navel and the knees while opinions concerning what body parts that Muslim women should cover differ between Islamic schools of thought. For instance, the Madhhab of Imam Maliki⁵ believes that women should cover their entire body except for the face and the palms in front of non-blood relative males (Hasmad and Alosman,2020). However, the meaning of the Hijab encompasses more than just a visual representation of the Islamic religion. It differs from one individual to another and often stands as a symbol of modesty, cultural identity, and personal expressions (Safdar, 2022). The Hijab is more than just a piece of clothing because it is accompanied by specific behavioural requirements including speech and countenance. For instance, it requires both genders to be modest and not engage in "obnoxiousness, boisterous behaviour, resisting flirtations, prolonged staring, and idleness with the opposite sex" (AbuShaban, 2017, no page). Although the meaning of the Hijab or Islamic veil is primarily religious, its meaning has been appropriated and shaped by sociopolitical discourses throughout history (Woldesemait, 2013). In fact, it has become the subject of controversy across different countries and various policies have been proposed to ban it or make it mandatory. In addition, it has been at the centre of political movements, particularly in

European countries, where the garment is perceived by many as a threat and as a representation of a political ideology, rather than marker of identity, religion, and culture (Hameid, 2022). Therefore, the Hijab viewed by many in the West as a political tool, enabling discriminatory laws against Muslims to be enacted (Sadlowski, 2022).

During the Colonial era, the Hijab was perceived as a peculiar Islamic practice that symbolized the inferiority and backwardness of Islam, Muslims, and the oppression of Muslim women (Ahmed, 1992). As a result, it was used as a symbol of colonial resistance and revolution “in Algeria in the 1950s and Iran in the 1970s” (Bullock, 2002, p.87). Although it was related to colonial discourses, the topic of the Hijab and women’s rights in Islam has experienced a revival in the media since the 9/11 attacks on the World Trade Centre. Post 9/11, Hijab has become a demonised symbol of terror (Zempi, no year available). According to Sohail, Anjum, and Aziz (2023, p. 2), following the 9/11 terrorist attacks, there was an intense rise in violence in the United States of America towards people perceived to be Arabs or Muslims, with over “700 incidents reported within nine weeks”. Despite the backlash on the Hijab, many Muslim women regarded the Hijab as a symbol of pride and authenticity. For instance, Haddad's (2007) study shows that post 9/11, the process of re-Islamization⁷ has escalated, and this was manifested by American Muslim women who chose to reclaim their Islamic identity by wearing the Hijab in public.

Although the 9/11 event took place in the USA, it had a profound global effect. Western countries, such as the United Kingdom, have witnessed the rise of anti-Muslim sentiment with the Muslim community viewed with suspicion. In their work *Muslims under Siege: Alienating vulnerable Communities*, Osborn and Jones (2008) demonstrate that the fear of terrorism, racial attacks and abuse have escalated since the 9/11/2001 and 7/7/2005 (London Bombings) terrorist outrages that have generated a deeper hate and resentment towards British Muslims than existed before “The presence of Muslim communities in Great Britain has gained great social and political visibility in the past thirty years, especially after the Honeyford Affair in 1984 and the Rushdie Affair in 1989 and, from 2001 onwards, following the various Islamist terrorist attacks in the United States and Europe” (Bonino, 2015, p.2). More recently, various policies have been introduced to battle terrorism in the UK, such as the controversial counter-extremism and counter-terrorism program Prevent⁸, which have left many Muslims and people of South Asian heritage feeling heavily scrutinized and policed (Alam, 2021). Whilst 9/11 was an international event that affected the United Kingdom, there have been other national events, like the 7/7/2005 London bombings, that also contributed to the rise of Islamophobia in the UK. A report, by the *European Monitoring Centre on Xenophobia and Racism*, illustrates that there was an increase in faith hate crimes in the UK, which left minority communities, mainly Muslims, feeling unsafe and vulnerable (European Union M 2005). As such many ethnic minority communities, including Muslims in Scotland, were affected by international and national events, such as 9/11 and 7/7.

According to the 2011 Census, Muslims make up to “1.45 %” of the Scottish population, which makes it the largest religious minority in Scotland (El Shayyal, 2016, p. 7). The Scottish Muslim population comprises of individuals from diverse ethnic, cultural, and theological backgrounds. Compared to England, Scotland is viewed as a welcoming country to Muslims. According to Bonino (2016, no page), data from Census 2011 suggests that Muslims in Scotland have experienced a “relatively smoother settlement”. Moreover, some studies argue that Muslims in Scotland are more likely to identify as Scottish compared to

Muslims in England (Hussain and Miller, 2006). Furthermore, a study by Masud (2005), following the London Bombing of 2005, suggests that “it was widely acknowledged and appreciated that compared with other parts of the country, especially England, Scotland was a tolerant place” (Masud, 2005, p. 12).

In contrast to the evidence presented so far, McCrone (2008) refers to the idea of Scotland being a “more egalitarian society than England” as a “Scottish myth” that renders the experiences of discrimination in Scotland less likely in support of this argument. A range of factors support this idea. For instance, Hopkins and Smith (2008) express that the difference in treatment of ethnic minorities in Scotland compared to England does not signify the absence of racism in Scotland, rather it is due to the distinctive racialisations of politics in Scotland. Miles and Dunlop (1987, p.199) point out that “what distinguishes Scotland from England is the absence of racialization of political processes since 1945, rather than the absence of racism per se”. In other words, the concentration on the historical sectarian tension between Catholics and Protestants in Scotland has led to “unwarranted complacency amongst Scottish decision takers” (Hopkins and Smith, 2008, p.105) in relation to other forms of discrimination and prejudice.

However, this historical tension, which predated the settlement of South Asian communities in Scotland, according to Bonino (2016, no page), “partly cushioned Muslims” and other ethnic minorities from being the target of racism (Bonino, 2016). Other reasons that also led to the smooth settlement and the easy integration of Muslims in Scotland are the community's small number, the lack of ethnoreligious clustering, lower fear of terrorism, the preference of self-employment over competition in public sectors (Bonino, 2019), and the friendly disposition and positive attitudes of the Scottish people (Homes et al.,2010). Furthermore, Bonino (2019) presumes that Islamophobia might be displaced with Anglophobia in Scotland, thus providing Scots with a “common, external and very significant other” (Bonino, 2016, no page). Although Scotland can serve as a good model to other European countries for its integration and accommodation of Muslims and Islam in the West, “the active involvement of Scotland in the British Empire, the historical prejudice against migrant labour, high levels of racism suffered by Pakistanis and the overzealous scrutiny of Muslims at airports” (Bonino ,2016, no page) all highlight the dangers of portraying Scotland as a uniquely tolerant and inclusive society.

Muslim women can be an easy target for discrimination due to their visible Muslim identity through wearing the Hijab (Read & Bartowski, 2000). Alimahomed Wilson (2017), Chakraborti and Zempi (2012) suggest that wearing the Hijab is viewed by non-Muslims as a sign of ‘Muslimness’⁹ and ‘foreignness’, which signifies an assumed unwillingness to assimilate. Additionally, it makes women vulnerable to Hijab-phobia¹⁰ (Hamzeh,2012). Jamieson and Kidd (2011) in their study of the experiences of Muslims in Scotland, demonstrate that gender is a crucial factor in the formation of social identity, therefore for Muslim women experience the intersection between religion, race and gender leads to further challenges. Additionally, El Nakla (2007) states that Muslim women in Scotland differentiate between experiences of colour racism and Islamophobia and that they believe these types of experiences are unpreventable (El Nakla et al.,2007).

These findings are supported by Masud’s report (2005), which indicates that the *Muslim Women's Centre* noted an increase in complaints, especially post 9/11 and the London

bombings, about receiving “stares and glares” while wearing the Hijab (Masud, 2005, p.12). Furthermore, many Muslim women reported a general feeling of insecurity and unsafety when going outside because of an increase in verbal abuse such as being called “Taliban” (Masud,2005, p.13). As a result, some of the women living in Glasgow considered leaving the United Kingdom (Masud, 2005).

A recent report on Islamophobia in Scotland indicates that Muslim women are more likely to experience Islamophobia compared to men (Hopkins, 2023). Hopkins (2023, p.2) shows that about “56%” of the survey respondents believe that Muslim women are at greater risk when it comes to Islamophobic attacks and calls for awareness-raising initiatives in schools, to counter the impact of Islamophobia, particularly due to the escalating violence and conflict in the middle East. Anas Sarwar, the head of the Scottish labour party, who launched the initial inquiry on Islamophobia in 2019 in Scotland, states that “right now, with the tragic escalation of violence in the Middle East, families in Scotland are living in fear of rising anti-Semitism and Islamophobia.” (*BBC NEWS*,2023, no page). Similarly, Zara Mohammed, secretary general of the Muslim Council of Britain, suggests that Islamophobia in Scotland has become increasingly prevalent and its influence on the lived experiences of every Scottish Muslim is intense (*BBC NEWS*, 2023).

As explained above, Muslim women are particularly vulnerable to Islamophobic attacks (Wing and Smith, 2006; Githens-Mazer and Lambert, 2010). This is in part due to the negative associations and stereotypes related to the veil (Zempi, 2020) such as the assumption of compliance and/or submissiveness (Masud, 2005). Contrary to the prevailing stereotypes, many Muslim women assert dominance over their own lives (Masud,2005) and aspire to achieve equality within Islam (Parker Jenkins and Haw in Choudhury et al 2004). After the intensified event of 9/11, diasporic or American and British Muslim women re-affirmed and re-deconstructed the meaning of the veil as a tool of resistance. According to Macdonald (2006, p.15),

the veil was reconstructed, variously, as a form of resistance to Western ideology and secularism; as a fashion accessory; or as evidence of Muslim women’s agency and freedom of choice. Incorporated within discourses of Western-style freedoms and lifestyle choices, it was resurrected as feminist- and consumer-friendly accoutrement.

Although the Hijab is seen either as a symbol of control or empowerment, Mernissi (1991) suggests that it is a social construction with different political, spiritual, spatial, visual, and ethical representations, which depends on the context in which it's worn. Similarly, Siraj’s (2011) research on *the Meaning of the Hijab and Modesty amongst Muslim Women in Glasgow*, finds that “wearing the hijab does not represent a homogeneous discursive reality for Muslim women around the world, but instead the fluid and the changing meaning of the hijab depends upon the spatial context in which it is worn” (2011, p.728). The Hijab can signify different meanings to different women who choose to wear it in a certain context. As a result, this research seeks to add to the existing knowledge about the practice of the Hijab in the Scottish context by exploring the lived experiences of Muslim women who were born, raised, live, and/or work in Scotland. The following section explains and presents the research aims and questions guiding the present study.

1.2. Research Aims and Questions:

The purpose of the study is to investigate the experiences of Muslim women wearing hijabs in Scotland by focusing on three major sites where Muslims reside and are highly concentrated, namely Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee, with the use Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a method of data analysis (Smith et al., 2009). The objectives for investigating the practice of the Hijab in Scotland are guided by the relative lack of literature as pertains to Scotland. As a result, the project attempts to delve into the individualistic and subjective experiences of wearing the Hijab in Scotland and has the following aims and objectives:

- 1- To explore Muslim women's individual understanding of the Hijab by analysing its significance, purpose, and rationale according to the participants.
- 2- To explain how Muslim women perceive the negative stigma and stereotypes attached to the Hijab and how they perceive female freedom, gender equality, and feminism in relation to the Hijab.
- 3- To understand the impact of geopolitical events and policies regarding the Hijab on their lived experiences.
- 4- To highlight the challenges and impacts of wearing the Hijab in their everyday life and interpersonal interactions.

Due to the gender-specific focus and nature of this study, this research employs a critical lens to further understand women's experiences by applying Feminist Standpoint Theory (Harding, 2004), Intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989), and the Matrix of Gendered Islamophobia (Alimohamed-Wilson, 2020).

Considering the study's main aims and objectives are to provide insight into the subjective experiences of Hijabi Muslim women in Scotland, the key research questions are framed in the following way:

1. What does wearing Hijab mean to Muslim women living in Scotland?
2. What are the motivations and purposes of wearing a Hijab in Scotland?
3. How do media representations, stereotypes of Muslim women, and global policies on Hijab affect the experiences of Hijabis in Scotland?
4. What are the main challenges faced by the wearers of Hijab in Scotland?

Having discussed the main objectives and research questions of this dissertation, the following section presents a brief overview of the theoretical framework and methodology used to achieve this study.

1.3. Brief Methods and Theoretical Framework Overview:

As explained in the previous section, the data for this research project is sourced via fieldwork conducted in three major Scottish cities, namely Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee. The methodology used for data collection comprises of semi-structured interviews using a recruitment strategy based on non-probability sampling and snowball sampling. The selection of these sites is based on the relative size of the population in each of the cities, as they are

home to the largest Muslim communities in Scotland with the highest population residing in Glasgow (Siraj, 2011). The rationale for choosing these sites is to increase the chances of finding potential participants. The initial plan was to interview twenty-five participants in total, which included 9 participants in Glasgow, 8 in Edinburgh, and 8 in Dundee. However, the sample size was reduced to twenty participants due to the nature of Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis and due to data saturation. Furthermore, because of the highest population of Muslims being in Glasgow (10) and Edinburgh (7), only 3 participants were interviewed from Dundee. The sample is varied and includes women from different ages and cultural, ethnic, professional, and social backgrounds. Due to Covid 19, most of the interviews were held online via Zoom, which has advantages and disadvantages that are highlighted in the methods chapters as well as in the general conclusion of the thesis.

Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) offers a useful way to analyse the data. Although it is an extensive and time-consuming method of analysis (Smith et al., 2009), IPA allows for a deep understanding of individualistic experiences due to its theoretical underpinnings that consist of ideography that stresses the importance of examining in-depth individual accounts of a subjective phenomenon in a certain context (Moses and Knutsen, 2012). In addition to the use of IPA, feminist theories are employed to understand the experiences from gender-specific and intersectional perspectives. The rationale for using feminist standpoint theory in the Scottish context is to understand how Muslim women make sense of their experiences of wearing hijab from their own individual standpoints. It allows them to speak from their own social positions instead of being defined by dominant discourses. Harding (2012) argues that feminist standpoint theory focuses on the importance of the lived daily experiences of women and how their social understanding is shaped by different societal structures. Furthermore, intersectional theory (Crenshaw, 1989) and gendered Islamophobia (Alimohamed-Wilson, 2020) provide practical frameworks for understanding how different identity categories intersect to create either a system of privilege or oppression in the lives of the participants. The following section presents the current study's significance and key contributions to the existing literature on Muslim women in Scotland.

1.4. Contribution to Knowledge:

The most important and unique contribution to knowledge in this body of work is the use of Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a method of data analysis along with feminist and intersectional theories. This allows for a deep and close insight into the subjective lived experiences of Muslim women who wear the Hijab in contemporary Scotland. The reason for utilizing IPA stems from its ideographic nature, which helps in understating how each participant makes sense of the practice of the Hijab in the Scottish context. In addition, IPA focuses on the shared experiences of the participants by targeting a homogenous sample that has some characteristics in common. For the purposes of the current study, the participants are females, Muslims, wearing the Hijab, and living in Scotland for a period of at least of two years. Moreover, based on hermeneutics, IPA offers a new and useful approach to examining the experiences of the participants because of its focus on double hermeneutics, which suggests that the researcher attempts to make sense of how the participants make sense of their own lived experience (Montague et al., 2020). As a result, the analysis of the data requires extensive reading and re-reading of the transcripts to make sense of the participants' experiences. To understand the participants' perspectives from gender-

specific and intersectional perspectives, feminist and intersectional theories were employed. For instance, the use of Feminist Standpoint Theory suggests that although dominant and powerful discourses attempt to define women “on the margin of society” (Droogsma, 2007, p.294), women’s cultural positions offer them a heightened awareness of the contradiction between their experiences and the way dominant discourse attempts to define them. Therefore, this theory allows for the emergence of alternative definitions of the Hijab from the standpoints of Muslim women instead of relying on dominant discourses. Using feminist theory is also supported by intersectional theories. Both the theories of intersectionality (Crenshaw,1989) and the matrix of gendered Islamophobia (Alimohamed-Wilson, 2020) examine how different social identities intersect to create either a system of privilege or oppression in the lived experiences of veiled Muslim women in the Scottish context. This study allows for the rise of unique empirical data which is summarised in the following sections.

1.4.1- Understanding the Meanings and the Purposes of The Hijab:

This study contributes to the understanding of how Muslim women’s experiences of the Hijab vary from one another. In other words, while dominant discourses present Muslim women as a homogenous group (Koopmanschap, 2010, p. 1), the current study argues that their experiences and decisions to wear the Hijab were shaped and re-shaped through time and location (spatial context). For example, while some participants wear the Hijab as a cultural garment that was shaped lately into a religious one, others decided to wear the Hijab mainly for religious reasons. The decision to wear the Hijab, in most cases, was shaped by the context from which everyone came, for instance, those who came from predominantly Muslim countries wore the Hijab without a prior understanding of its religious motives, while most of the participants who lived most of their lives in Scotland wore it out of religious understanding. Another important empirical contribution is understanding the Hijab as a medium for Muslim women’s well-being. Some participants related the Hijab to some significant and emotional events in their lives, such as losing a family member to cancer and becoming a mother. Moreover, different opinions were shared regarding the concept of modesty, attractiveness, fashion, and body image. Most participants expressed the importance of the Hijab in maintaining their modesty. They also discussed some points regarding the Hijab and their body images, some participants believed that the Hijab protected their body images, and others felt less attractive with the Hijab.

1.4.2. Understanding Gender Issues in Relation to the Hijab:

The current study contributes to the understanding of the Hijab in Scotland from a gender specific perspective. The findings demonstrate an understanding of how Muslim women viewed the Hijab from a feminist lens. It discusses ideas of female empowerment, gender equality, media stereotyping, and portrayals of the Hijab. Unlike dominant ideas of the Hijab as a symbol of oppression (Amiriaux, 2007; Mitchel, 2019; Bullock, 2010), most women in the study identified themselves as “strong”, “confident”, and “powerful” while wearing the Hijab. Moreover, the results indicate that Muslim women possessed varied and contradictory understandings of what a feminist identity and gender equality are. This chapter also adds to the existing literature by discussing the perspectives of participants on how they are portrayed as Hijabi women by the Western media with a specific focus on the British media.

1.4.3. Exploring the Different Challenges and the Impacts of Islamophobia on Muslim Women in Scotland:

Finally, this study adds to the existing literature on the experiences of Muslim women in Britain by examining the phenomenon of gendered Islamophobia in Scotland. The theory of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989) provides a useful lens through which the participant's experiences were approached. As previously explained, while Muslim women are viewed as a homogenous group, this research argues for the importance of recognizing differences among them, which lie in the intersection of other identities with their gender identity, including religion, race, ableism, and language. Moreover, Muslim women in this study identified several types of Islamophobias. It is important to mention that the intensity of Islamophobia varied from covert forms of islamophobia to more direct forms. Examples of these types are discussed in the third chapter of the findings, which include verbal and physical attacks such as insulting and Hijab pulling, micro-aggressions like unpleasant facial expressions, and institutional Islamophobia, for example, having difficulty finding a job and feeling excluded from social interactions and events. Additionally, Muslim women compared their experiences in Scotland to England and other places they visited such as France, Moreover, it shows that the experiences differ even at the local level, for example, the difference between Islamophobia in Edinburgh and Glasgow.

To sum up, this thesis seeks to add to the existing knowledge of the practice of the Hijab in the Scottish context. There is significant literature about Muslim women in Scotland. Hengameh Ashraf (2017), for instance, explores the intergenerational relations between Muslim women in Scotland by studying the differences, similarities, and transformations between Muslim generations. Syswerda (2017) also studies Muslim women in Scotland by examining the role of "Other" women in shaping the subjectivities of recent migrant Muslim women. However, few focus on the practice of the Hijab (Siraj, 2011; Hopkins and Greenwood, 2013). Unlike previous research on the Hijab, this study focuses essentially on Muslim women who practice the Hijab in Scotland. Consequently, this study is important in the present context, essentially because the number of Muslims in Scotland is set to double according to academics in this decade (El Shayyal, 2016; Donnelly, 2017), which requires understanding the needs and the challenges of veiled Muslim women, especially due to the rise of Islamophobia in Scotland (Barrie, 2021; Hopkins, 2023). The study also acknowledges the importance of gender and other intersectional identities in defining the experiences of Islamophobia.

1.5. Thesis Chapter Outlines:

This research is divided into nine chapters in total. The first chapter is the introduction of the study, and it presents the significance of the study, the research aims and questions, a brief account of the methods and theories used, and outlines the rest of the chapters that make up the study.

The second chapter presents the background of the study by providing a critical glimpse into different bodies of literature dealing with the early settlement of Muslims in Scotland, their growth, and their current status, dealing mainly with the census 2011 (as full data from the 2022 Census is not yet widely available). Furthermore, the chapter explains how Muslims are often welcomed in Scotland, whilst, on the other hand, it illustrates how international and national events help perpetuate prejudice and inequality against Scottish Muslims, such as

9/11 attacks in the USA, the London bombings, the Glasgow airport incident, and the earlier Rushdie Affair in 1989.

Chapter three reviews the various historical and religious literature regarding the practice of the veiling (Hijab). It discusses its origin in the Assyrian code of laws, its references, and interpretations in the three Abrahamic religions, namely Judaism, Christianity, and Islam. This literature is crucial to understanding this practice, especially because the practice of the Hijab (veiling), which is now mostly attributed to Islam, pre-existed Islam. In addition, it has several meanings according to different religions and cultures. Furthermore, this chapter examines two polarized views regarding the Hijab, which are the traditionalists and feminist views. The last sections deal with important concepts that are closely related to the practice of the Hijab: both Islamophobia and Secularism are discussed with a specific focus on the Scottish context.

The fourth chapter presents the theoretical framework of this thesis. It presents three critical theories through which the lived experiences of Muslim women in Scotland are analysed, namely feminist standpoint theory (Harding, 2005), intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989; Collins, 1990), and the matrix of gendered Islamophobia (Alimahomed-Wilson, 2020). These frameworks are important to investigate the participants' experiences because they allow Muslim women to share their experiences from their individualistic and subjective standpoints and provide an important lens through which to examine how various identity categories intersect to influence the lived experiences of Muslim women who choose to wear the Hijab in the Scottish context.

The fifth chapter explores the methodological aspect of the study. Firstly, it discusses the research paradigm by identifying suitable philosophical grounds for this research. Secondly, it justifies using qualitative research, which is the most suitable and flexible research approach to tease out possible answers to the set research questions. Thirdly, the chapter establishes the justification for the data collection method and explores how the participants were recruited, the rationale for choosing certain research settings, and the sample size. Furthermore, it provides the rationale for choosing Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a method for analysing the data. It also sketches out the limitations of using IPA in conducting this research and explains how these limitations can be overcome. This chapter also demonstrates the positionality and reflexivity of the researcher, and it addresses the ethical considerations and measures that need to be taken to ensure this research is conducted ethically. Finally, this chapter provides insights and reflections regarding the post-fieldwork period. It describes the process of recruiting the participants via different organisations, describing the period of interviewing the participants, transcribing, and analysing the data.

The findings and discussion are introduced in chapters six, seven, and eight. These chapters discuss in detail the themes that emerged from analysing the participants' perspectives. Chapter Six is the first empirical chapter of the thesis and identifies the numerous ways in which Muslim women perceive and interpret the aspect of the Hijab from their individualistic and subjective perspectives. Although there are common reasons why the participants choose to wear the Hijab such as religious and cultural purposes, the experiences leading to wear the Hijab differ. This chapter also introduces the sub-theme of modesty and its meaning from the participants' perspectives and how both genders are required to be modest in Islam.

Moreover, it provides a discussion on the relation of the Hijab to body image, attractiveness, and fashion.

The seventh chapter of the thesis investigates how the participants conceptualise female empowerment, feminist identity, and gender equality in relation to the practice of Islamic veiling. The results show the majority of the participants have unique perspectives through which they understand feminism and gender equality. Moreover, it explores the participants' perspectives on the portrayal of Muslim women in the Western Media in general and the Scottish media in particular.

The final findings chapter highlights an important aspect regarding the practice of the Hijab in Scotland, which is Islamophobia. The findings show that most of the participants faced Islamophobia due to wearing the Hijab, in addition to the intersection of other identity categories, such as race, disability, and language. Furthermore, the types of gendered Islamophobia, in this study, were categorised from the direct forms such as physical and verbal Islamophobia to the covert forms, which include micro-aggression behaviours and institutional Islamophobia. This chapter is crucial in understanding how Islamophobia operates in Muslim women's lives and how it affects their well-being. In addition, chapter eight highlights the positive aspects of living in Scotland as Muslim women who choose to wear the Hijab. In this section, some participants compare their experiences in Scotland to England and other places they have been to, such as France.

The closing chapter of this research is dedicated to the general conclusion. It identifies the most important findings of this study in relation to the set research questions. Furthermore, the final chapter presents the contribution to the existing literature on Muslim women in the Scottish context, the implications of the research on how to use the research findings effectively, the limitations, and the recommendations for future research in the field of gender and Islam in the Scottish context.

1.6. Conclusion:

This chapter was devoted to the introduction of the dissertation. To begin with, it gave a broad overview of the topic by providing some knowledge on the theological and historical developments of the hijab. Furthermore, it provided the contextual factors that lead to investigating and examining the research problem, which is the practice of wearing the Hijab in Scotland. After discussing the research background, the second section of this chapter dealt with the research aims and questions. Having stated the aims and research questions, the third section located the research in the broad context of literature on Muslim women and the Hijab in Scotland by highlighting the significance of the study and its key contribution to knowledge. Subsequently, an outline summarised the main ideas of each chapter starting from the background context to the concluding chapter. The following chapter deals with some literature regarding the background context of Muslims in Scotland moving from their early settlement to their present status.

2. Chapter Two: The Background Context of Muslim Presence in Scotland

Examining the presence of the Islamic garb and Muslim women in a western context like Scotland demands providing an overview and context of Muslims and Islam in Scotland. This section provides a critical reading through the previous literature that has dealt with the early settlement of Muslims in Scotland, their growth, and their present status. It then presents an overview of the statistics of Scottish Muslims and provides a discussion of data dealing with it the 2011 census¹¹ (Recent data from census 2022 is added). On the one hand, the evidence suggest that Muslims feel welcomed in Scotland but on the other hand, it provides instances of discrimination, inequality, and prejudice that Scottish Muslims encounter, in part due to both global and local events like 9\11, the Rushdie Affair in 1989, and the Glasgow airport bombing in 2007.

2.1. Muslims' Early Settlement in Scotland

Maan (2014) explains that the early presence of Muslims in Scotland is traced back to the realm of King James IV (1488-1513). King James IV employed black Moors as Musicians. There is also evidence of the existence of Black trumpeters in the 17th century. Hopkins (2017) states that these trumpeters were a part of the Scottish lifeguards and Moorish musicians of the 17th and 18th century. Maan (2014) supposes that their religion was Islam because they were migrants from North Africa. However, they did not stay in Scotland, and they returned to their home countries once the contract of their employment ended.

The 1920s witnessed the early settlement of Muslims in Scotland. They were of Indian Sub-continent backgrounds including parts of Bangladesh, Bhutan, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Maldives (Mann, 2014). Ansari (2018) discusses the motives behind the early settlement of Muslims in Scotland, their situation, and the population of Scottish Muslims. According to Ansari (2018), the majority of Muslim Migrants who arrived in the United Kingdom in the mid-19th century were either maritime workers or lascars (a sailor or militiaman from the Indian subcontinent). During the Napoleonic wars, large numbers of Indian sailors were recruited by Britain as cheap labourers, the majority of which were Muslims. Muslims were referred to by the Evangelical circles as “the followers of licentious doctrine of a false prophet” (Ansari, 2018, p. 39). The number of Muslim Lascars increased considerably in 1873, “with 3,271 lascars” from India, Egypt, and Turkey (Ansari, 2018, p.39). Another survey was conducted in 1874 showing that 4,685 lascars came from India, 1,440 from Egypt, 225 from Turkey and 85 were Malays. Providing good wages was the main reason why many Indian Muslim sailors came to Britain. However, Ansari (2018) reports that they were brutally treated on ships, which led most of them to escape hard labour. Ansari provides examples of terrible treatment including that they were: “hung with weights tied to their feet, flogged with a rope and forced to eat pork” (Ansari, 2018, p. 40).

In the mid-19th century, significant numbers of Indian Muslim sailors resided in Scotland (Ansari,2018). Glasgow witnessed an enormous number of Muslim sailors due to its need to recruiting lascars to contribute to the production of heavy capital goods. Many Indian sailors were also attracted to Dundee because of work relating to the exportation and importation of jutes (a type of textile) from Bengal. The evidence of the existence of Muslim sailors at that time is found in Glasgow sailors' home records of 1875. Not only had maritime jobs attracted Muslims into Scotland but Bailey et., al (1995) state that Scottish shipping industries

facilitated in the settling of the Muslim population in Glasgow, which was known for its successful shipping trade.

The western educational system played a key role in the process of Muslim migration to Scotland. According to Ansari (2018, p. 35), “the pull of Western systems of thought and knowledge was strong on these professional Muslim families who had traditionally enjoyed a privileged position in society and exercised considerable power”. Western education for Indian Muslim families that enjoyed a higher class than others in their society seemed to be the key for playing a role in running the colonial system. There was a considerable number of Muslim students in 1840s in Scotland. According to Ansari (2018) Scottish universities were preferable and popular among Indian Muslim students because of the substantial number of Scottish teachers in India. After discussing the situations and the reasons for the early settlement of Muslims in Scotland, the following section provides data about the Muslim population in Scotland based on 2001, 2011 and 2022 Censuses.

2.2. Scottish Muslims in Numbers: Discussion and Observation of 2001, 2011 and 2022 Census Data:

There has been a long-running debate concerning the inclusion of religion as an affiliation in the British national census (Thorvaldsen, 2014). The question on ethnicity was already listed in the Census of 1997, which many have opposed, such as the Board of deputies of the British Jews (Thorvaldsen, 2014). The question on religion was introduced in the United Kingdom national Census in 2001, which helps to provide more accurate data on the Muslim population and other religious minorities. Diamond (2010) discusses the inclusion of questions on ethnicity and religion by stressing the importance of the census as the main source for a “decent small-area data” (2010, p.3). Moreover, Diamond (2010) explains the role of census in guiding policy makers to identify the areas of deprivation and racial discrimination. The question of ethnicity is crucial according to Diamond because it allows for the discernment of the different ethnicities in Britain “We were able to distinguish between Black-Caribbean, Black-Africans, Black-Others, Indians, Pakistanis, Bangladeshis, Chinese, and that strange group of Other-Others” (Diamond, 2010, p. 4). Furthermore, Diamond (2010) suggests that there was a need for another question in the Census that includes religious affiliation although the number of questions is limited in the Census. Although the ethnicity question is important, the ethnicity measurement is extremely difficult and that is why there was a necessity of adding the question of religion to the Census.

As mentioned earlier, the question of religion was included until Census 2001 and 2011, which introduced being a Muslim as an option. El Shayyal (2016) discusses in detail the statistics generated from the Census 2001 and 2011 through giving observations on the heterogeneous Scottish Muslim population. Furthermore, El Shayyal (2016) produces her work based on prior work *British Muslims in Numbers* (Ali, 2015), which discusses the numbers of Muslims in the United Kingdoms. This work includes a discussion on the demographic details and qualities of Muslims in Scotland and is a key source in conducting research on Muslim women and the presence of Hijab in Scottish society. It helps in providing knowledge about unique qualities of Scottish Muslims and the geographical dispersion of Muslims within Scotland. The following section deals with the statistics of the population of Muslims in Scotland compared to other parts of the United Kingdom, geographical distribution, the diverse ethnicities, age profile and national identity. It also

provides the growth and the decline of the Muslim population in Scotland between the data provided in Census 2001 and 2011 (it will also include the new census when released in 2022-23) and the reasons for that.

El Shayyal (2016) specifies two important reasons for the lack of statistical data on Muslims in Scotland. First, the lack of statistical data about Muslims in Scotland is due to the introduction of the question of religion only in 2001, which makes it impossible to get any accurate data before that date. Secondly, the lack of interest from individuals and organisations in Scotland is a barrier as most of the interest is directed towards Muslims in England because of their larger population size. In addition, El Shayyal (2016) stresses the importance of developing a better understanding of the Muslim population and other minority groups especially due to some political events taking place in Scotland like devolution¹². Developing an understanding of minority groups provides Scotland with an understanding of its evolving self-awareness.

The data that is used from 2001 and 2011 is now outdated and census 2021 may be available to consult new data in 2022-23. Firstly, it is important to present and discuss the percentage of Muslims in Scotland compared to other parts of the United Kingdom. Ipsos Mori Social Research institute (2018) conducts a survey to examine the Muslim population in the United Kingdom, the British Muslim's views, and the public views on Muslims. It states that according to Census 2011, Islam is the largest religion after Christianity in the UK with a percentage of 4.4% of the total population. Scotland's Muslims make around 1.45% of the Muslim population of the United Kingdom. Most Muslims in the United Kingdom reside in England with about 2,660,116 Muslims, while Northern Ireland seems to have the lowest population with just 3,832 of the Muslim population living there.

In a discussion about the growth of the Muslim population in the United Kingdom between the Census of 2001 and 2011, Ali (2015) states immigration as one main reason for the growth of Muslim population in United Kingdom between the years 2001-2011. Moreover, Ali (2015) mentions five other principal factors. Firstly, most of the immigrants from the Muslim population and other minorities have a youthful age profile, which makes them more likely to start families. Besides, the proportion of births outweigh the proportion of deaths. Secondly, immigration from unstable Muslim countries like Somalia, Iraq and Afghanistan helps in that growth. Thirdly, adoption of Muslim faith is a factor with more people becoming Muslim. Fourthly, some ethnic groups believe in the traditions of giving birth for many children (large family). Lastly, Ali (2015) suspects that the results from the 2001 Census may not reflect the actual figure of Muslim population in the UK and the real figure may be reflected in 2011, where a lot of Muslims responded to the Census.

Muslims in the United Kingdom are ethnically diverse with Asians representing 8% of the total Muslim population. The number of Muslims of Pakistan and Bangladesh origins is on decrease while Muslims with Black African, Black others or Asian others is on the rise. The term 'Arab' was included until 2011 (Ali, 2015) "BME/BAME – Black and Minority Ethnic or Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic is the terminology normally used in the UK to describe people of non-white descent" (Institute of Race Relations, 2020, no page). Muslims constitute 2.49 (1/3) million of the BME/BAME's total 7.87 million. The presence of Muslims in this group usually has to do with sharing similar experiences "cementing alliances and coalitions

across civil society to address shared concerns relating to continuing race inequalities and colour and cultural racism” (Ali, 2015, p.25).

Al Shayyal (2016) produces an important Scottish report that highlights two main elements. It provides a comprehensive profile on Muslims in Scotland based on Census 2011 and highlights and provides a deeper understanding of the unique features of Scottish Muslims. Census 2011 shows that around “1.45%” of the Scottish population are Muslims, which means Islam as a religion is the largest among the other religious minority groups. Scotland is a country with a majority Christian population, Church of Scotland has about 32.44% of the followers, followed by Roman Catholic “15.88 %” and other Christians “5.50%”, yet the 2011 Census witnessed a decline in Christian faith and the growth of people identifying themselves as non-religious (National Records of Scotland, 2011, no page). There was a rise of Muslim population between Census 2001 and 2011 by 34,000, nevertheless Muslims remain a small population compared to the overall Scottish population. The number of Muslim men 41,241 outweighs that of women 35,496, and most of them are UK born with a percentage of 44,6% (National Records of Scotland, 2011). Muslims are characterised by having a youthful age profile and are ethnically diverse.

Like other parts in the United Kingdom, most Muslims are from South Asia with 65% of the major Muslim population, followed by those identified as Arabs 9.8 %, white 7.8 % and Black 7%. Because Scottish Muslims constitute 90% of the BME population, El Shayyal (2016) believes that it is important for the policy makers and the civic society groups to consider intersectional elements, such as race, culture, age, and gender, when addressing issues of prejudice and discrimination of these groups. Moreover, the views of these ethnic groups - especially of women and youth - needs to be considered when thinking about policy and decision-making issues. Concerning geographical distribution, Muslims are significantly concentrated in three main parliamentary regions. Glasgow hosts about 43.6% followed by Lothian and North-East Scotland. Within Glasgow Muslims mostly condensed in places like Pollokshields 27.8 % and Southside Central 15.7% (National Records of Scotland, 2011).

In terms of national identity, about 71% of Muslims recognise themselves as either Scottish or British. Muslims in Scotland are more likely to be identified with their Scottishness unlike English Muslims with their Englishness (Hussein and Miller, 2006). The Islamic tartan is one example of how Muslims in Scotland are more tied to Scottish national identity. It was officially registered in 2012 and it weaves together the colours of Muslim and Scottish heritage “The theological explanation of the design is as follows: blue represents the Scottish Flag; green represents the colour of Islam; five white lines running through the pattern represent the five pillars of Islam; six gold lines represent the six articles of faith; the black square represents the *Holy Kabbah* (The sacred house)” (Tartan register, 2021, no page). According to the Islamic Tartan website (2021), Muslims in Scotland are communities with dual heritage, they seek to overcome religious intolerance and cultural discrimination. They are more likely to identify themselves as Scottish, unlike English Muslims and that can be due to the educational system and media that are more enlightened and open-minded (Islamic Tartan, no year available). The Islamic tartan is evidence that Scotland is working hard to create an environment where citizens are more comfortable with their nationality, their religion, and their ethnicity. In addition, it is a means to explain the great contribution of both the Muslim scholarship and the Scottish culture in the construction of a common civilisation.

Bonino (2016), in *Muslims in Scotland: Demographic, social and cultural characteristics*, discusses the settlement of the Muslim population in Scotland. Bonino (2016) argues that Scotland can serve as a model of integration and inclusion to other European countries. Furthermore, Muslims in Scotland have experienced a smooth settlement due to: “Lower settlement numbers, fewer worries about terrorism and the welcoming disposition of Scots have made Muslim integration into society easier than in England” (Bonino, 2016, p.3). Concerning national identity, Bonino (2016) believes that Muslim national identity varies across Scotland by giving examples. For instance, Pakistani people seem to prefer their Scottishness or Britishness than their origin ethnicity, while Arabs are more likely to identify themselves with their ethnic identity.

Furthermore, Bonino (2016) provides an explanation of the smooth integration of Muslims in Scotland, including the lack of the ethno-religious clustering and the lack of the community numbers that have facilitated the connection between the Muslims and non-Muslims. For example, most of the Muslims who came from Faisalabad (Punjab) are self-employed means they are not competing over public services, therefore, staying away from problems and Scotland has not witnessed the same violent events caused by the Rushdie Affair (1988-1989) and the English Riots (2001-2011), even the clashes between South Asians and white people did not reach the same violent actions as for instance, in Birmingham and the North East of England. The relatively straight forward integration of Muslims in Scotland can be seen as smooth due to the fact Scottish identity was “A historical oppressed identity” (Bonino, 2016, p. 4) and in this case Islamophobia is displaced by Anglophobia. Scotland was historically a victim of English dominance, and this idea enhanced the solidarity between Scotland and Islam (Bonino, 2016).

The National records of Scotland (2024) recently released demographic data on faith and ethnic groups (date of release is the 21st of May 2024). The population of Muslims in the 2022 Scottish census makes of “119,878”, which means 2,2 % of the major Scottish population with “54,39,842”. The number of Muslims has increased between the years 2011 and 2022 by “56%”. Furthermore, Muslims are highly concentrated in Glasgow with “40 %”, followed by other councils namely Edinburgh “15,0 %”, Aberdeen “5,4 %”, Dundee “5.9%” and North Lanarkshire “4,6%” (National Records of Scotland, 2024). While there is an increase in the number of Muslims identifying as Muslims, Scotland witnessed, for the first time, the rise percentage of people with no religion with the percentage of “51%”. This percentage coincide with a decrease in the followers of other religions, including the church of Scotland with the percentage of “20,4 %” down from “32,4%” in 2011 and “42,4%” in 2001.

2.3. The Protection of Religions and Beliefs: The 2010 Equality Act

The right of Muslims and other minority groups to practice or display their religion, including the wearing of hijab and veiling, is protected under the Equality Act of 2010. *Religion or belief: a guide to the law* (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2016) provides an overview of the protection offered by the 2010 Equality Act and 1998 Human Rights Act to people with religion or belief or those without religion or belief. Moreover, it provides analysis of the meaning of direct discrimination, indirect discrimination, harassment, and if they can be justified.

Regarding religion, the act prohibits discriminating against people based on their religion or belief. For example, it protects Christians or Muslims if they are persecuted or treated unfairly. The protection of non-religious people is also stated. The 2010 Equality Act states clearly that a person should not be discriminated against for belonging to a particular religion or sect, or they follow a particular philosophical belief (it specifies that the philosophical belief needs to be qualified as widely known belief and not a mere opinion and not affecting other people's rights). Furthermore, discrimination by perception is prohibited by the act, which is discrimination because a certain person was thought to belong to a particular religion or belief. The last aspect is religion by association, which signifies that discrimination takes place in case the person is a relative or friend with a member of certain religion or belief. The act protects any religion with a structure like Christianity, Islam, Judaism, and Buddhism, even small groups of religions are protected, for instance Rastafarianism and Paganism.

The act differentiates between two types of discrimination, namely direct and indirect discrimination. Direct discrimination occurs when one person is treated unfairly than the other in a similar situation or when the two persons holding the same religion are treated differently by the person who holds similar religion or belief. Indirect discrimination on the other hand occurs when the person is discriminated against by an organisation that has a particular policy that applies to everyone, but him/herself because of belonging to a certain religion. On the other hand, indirect discrimination can be justified in cases where the organisation provide evidence that the work is necessary for the achievement of the purpose (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2016; Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2020). Article 9 of the Human Rights Act (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2021) protects the rights of people to manifest their religion or belief either in the way of behaviour or manifesting religious symbols like crucifix, headgear, or hijab, nevertheless, it limits the use of these symbols for some reasons like public safety (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2016). Moreover, the limitation of wearing certain religious symbols is included under a justification for indirect discrimination in the Equality Act 2010.

Several research studies (e.g., Hussain and Miller, 2006; Homes et al, 2010; Hopkins, 2007) show that the experiences of Muslims in Scotland and their integration is significantly smoother and easier than in England, however this does not mean that there is no discrimination or prejudice against them. According to Bonino (2016) Scotland risks being seen as an intolerant country because of the historical prejudice against migrant labour, racism against Pakistanis, and the excessive inspection of Muslims at the airports.

Bonino (2019) explores the ethno-religious discrimination among Scottish Muslims based on their everyday interaction with indigenous Scottish communities. His work examines the history of discrimination against Muslims and other ethnic minorities. To measure anti-Muslim sentiment, he focuses on the global event of 9/11. Bonino (2019) states the exclusion practices against people of colour in Scotland dated back to the 18th and 19th centuries, one example of such exclusion is the ban of colours in dancing halls of 1920s, but the discrimination shifts from being primarily racial discrimination to an ethno-religious prejudice against Muslims (Bonino, 2019). British Muslims, including Scottish Muslims, started to be recognised, and dealt with as an ethno-religious group due to different events like 9/11 and the Rushdie affair in 1989.

Moreover, Marranci (2008) believes that discrimination and prejudice against Muslims and the common perception that it is impossible for them as communities to integrate into civilised and modern countries develops by the end of 1980s. Three major events reinforced this idea and took place before 9/11. The less known event is the Honeyford affair 1984, followed by the Rushdie affair of 1989 in the United Kingdom, and L'Affaire du Foulard (the headscarf affair) in France in 1989. Marranci (2008) notes that these events marked the history of Muslims in Europe and heightened the supposed incompatibility of Western and Islamic values. Ray Honeyford was a principal in Drummond Road Middle school, where "90% of the pupils were non-Muslims" (Parkinson, 2012, no page). In 1984, he published an article for the right-leaning *Salisbury Review* that attracted the attention of English Muslims and fuelled their anger. The article mentions the rejection of some Islamic customs that he considered as barbaric such as the slaughter of animals, hence he called for the assimilation of Muslim children and the rejection of their religious identity (Marranci, 2008). Honeyford rejected multiculturalism in educational spheres and called for the assimilation of ethnic minority pupils (Parkinson, 2012). The article was largely criticised and caused him to retire early. For instance, Mohammed Ajeeb told the BBC that "The article was very critical of the Muslim culture and the race relations situation in the city was not very good at that time" (Parkinson, 2012, no page). Additionally, Lewis (1994) believes that the Honeyford affair 1984 shows that Islam as an identity was not relevant only to immigrants, but to their children as well.

The second most prominent event stated by Marranci (2008) was the Rushdie affair of 1989. According to Anthony (2009), the Rushdie affair of 1989 caused a great debate concerning the freedom of speech and expression in the United Kingdom. The affair started when Salman Rushdie, a British Indian novelist, published his novel *The Satanic Verses* in 1988. The publication of the novel was followed by a pronouncement of Ayatollah Khomeini to execute Rushdie for insulting Islam. Muslims throughout the world, and Muslims in United Kingdom, were offended by Rushdie's deed and caused disastrous protestations through burning books and firebombing (Anthony, 2009). Marranci (2008) suggests that this event questions the loyalty of Muslims to the United Kingdom and reinforces the idea that British Muslims are a threat to freedom of expression and speech "the people who were involved in the riots and book burning rituals were unable to foresee the socio-political consequences of their acts of protest" (Marranci, 2008, p.58). Finally, the event mentioned by Marranci (2008) that shows the contradictory nature of Islam and secularity is L'affaire de Foulard (The headscarf affair of 1989). The presence of Muslim girls wearing Hijab in French Schools was challenging to the French concept of *laïcité* (secularism). The ban was imposed in 24th of September 1989 and it involves other religious symbols like Sikh's Turbans and Jewish's Yarmulkes (Vaisse, 2004). The following section provides an overview of the situation of Muslims post 9/11 and post-Glasgow airport attack 30/06/2007.

2.4. The Post-911 Impact on the Muslim Community:

Marranci (2008) also mentions the backlash that Muslims suffered and are still suffering due to 9/11 and other subsequent events, stating that he visited one of the mosques in Belfast in Northern Ireland right after the event "Instead of the usual joyful laughs and high-pitched voices of children, lugubrious silence and smashed windows welcomed me" (Marranci, 2008, p. 62). In addition, the author (2008) explains that Muslims after the incident preferred to stay in their homes, because most of the mosques and the Islamic centres were vandalised.

Similarly, Flint (2002) comments on the feelings after the attacks by mentioning that there were feelings of shock, fear, and anger. In addition, Halliday (2002, p.31) expresses his opinion concerning the profound effect caused by 9/11 via these words:

The crisis unleashed by the events of 11 September is one that is global and all encompassing. It is global in the sense that it binds many different countries into conflict, most obviously the USA and parts of the Muslim world. It is all-encompassing in that, more than any other international crisis yet seen, it affects a multiplicity of life's levels, political, economic, cultural, and psychological.

Rosie and Clegg (2005) state that the 9/11 attacks marked a shift from discrimination based on race to a religious-based prejudice. People who wear religious dresses or symbols were targeted the most. Further discrimination and harassment against Muslims were the result of different terrorist incidents that took place after 9/11, and that were attributed to Islamic terrorism like the Bali bombing of 2002, the Madrid train bombing of 2004, and the London underground bombing of 2005 (Wolff and Larsen, 2014, p. 201). Peek (2003) notes that these events resulted in innocent Muslims becoming the victims of harassment, physical abuse, and verbal assaults in public places.

Different studies have examined the effects of 9/11 and other world events on Scottish Muslims. For instance, Hopkins (2007) explores the lives and the experiences of Muslim men after the two major events of 9/11 and Iraq war and how this can impact their political participation. Hopkins's (2007) aim was to include minority ethnic young voices in geographies and the understanding of the wider political climate. The negative consequences of 9/11 come in different shapes and forms in Scotland. For example, Maan (2014) mentions an example of death threat received by a contractor, who was working on the construction of a mosque in Lanarkshire, which caused him to resign. Homes et al., (2010), in their survey about the integration of Muslims in Scotland, state that most Scottish people argue that the Glasgow airport bombing of 2007 increases an intolerance towards Scottish Muslims "There has been much debate about the extent of Islamophobia in Scotland and there are those who believe in the real rise of Islamophobia, particularly post 9/11 and/or the attempted bombing at Glasgow Airport in July 2007" (Homes et al, 2010). The fact that Scotland is a welcoming country does not hide the fact that there are instances of prejudice and discrimination, including discrimination against Muslim women who wear hijab, which is the central focus of this PhD study.

2.5. Conclusion

To conclude, this chapter has dealt with four fundamental issues. Firstly, it discussed the Scottish Muslim population, their early settlement, the current context, and the data generated from censuses 2001, 2011. It also included some recent data based on the 2022 Census, which was released on the 21st of May 2024. Secondly, it explored the inclusion of the Muslim community in Scotland and the opposite of that, which means issues of discrimination and prejudice that target them. Lastly, it provided the policies that protected their rights to religion based on the 2010 Equality Act. Finally, it illustrated the main global and local events that played a role in targeting the Muslim community and the discrimination against them. Having discussed some background information on the Muslim population in Scotland. The following chapter presents a review on previous literature dealing with the practice of the Hijab.

3. Chapter Three: Literature Review

3.1. Introduction:

This chapter provides a historical and religious background to the concept of veiling, focusing on its origin in the Assyrian code of laws and its references and interpretations in the three Abrahamic religions, namely Judaism, Christianity, and Islam. In addition, it offers traditionalist and feminist interpretations regarding the requirement of wearing the Hijab and discusses it within the context of Western Islamophobia and gendered Islamophobia. Focus is placed specifically on Islamophobia in Scotland. Finally, this section offers a discussion on the notion of secularism within the Scottish context, particularly in relation to the visibility of religious identity in public.

3.2. The Origin of Veiling: Assyrian Code of Laws as the First Reference of Veiling

There are multiple definitions and discussions in the literature aimed at understanding and deconstructing the meaning and semiotic representation of Hijab. Although the veil did not originate in Islam, it is now attributed to Muslim women, and it is sometimes considered to be a marker of their identity. Muslim women are sometimes forced to wear or not to wear it according to the context in which they live. Conversations and debates around Hijab reached their peak after the terrorist attacks on the World Trade Centre on the 9th of September 2011, with resulted in multiple social consequences for Muslims in general and Muslim women who wear the Islamic garb in particular, especially those living in Western countries. It is therefore worthwhile discussing the origin of the hijab (Islamic veil) and its significance. This section focuses on the origin of veiling in the Assyrian code of laws.

The concept of veiling is generally attached to Islam; however, studies have shown that the idea of veiling pre-existed Islam. The first reference to veiling, according to Keddie (1991), is found in Assyrian legal texts of the 13th century B.C, where it is linked to individuals of high social status. Veiling was prohibited for those with a low social status, such as: peasants, slaves, and prostitutes, and was a punishable offence (Keddie, 1991). The Assyrian law code has been found on tablets by *Kaleh Shergat* in the site of Assur, which was the capital of the Assyria. The German oriental society excavated this region from 1903 to 1914 and an additional southern site from 1899 until 1917. Their work was suspended by the advance of the British troops to Mesopotamia. Like Hammurabi's code in South, specifically in Babylonia, the Assyrian code brings about a collection of laws that govern Assyria in the North. Two tablets were found, one of which was in good condition, and comprising of Assyrian law code in the form of eight columns consisting of one hundred lines each. The two tablets are labelled Text No 1 and 2 in *Schroeder's* edition. Text No 1 consists of different themes, among which laws that are related specifically to women, while Text No 2 includes regulations relating to property.

Multiple regulations relating to the status of women in Assyrian society were collected during the realm of *King Tiglath I* under the title *Harem Edicts* (Stol, 2016). The tablets include different laws which are assigned different numbers "The number of subjects covered is varied: theft (§§ 1–6); assault (§§ 7–11); sexual offences (§§ 12–24); marriage law (§§ 25–49); other criminal law (§§ 50–59)" (Stol,2016). For example, in (Text No. 1, 3) the husband or the father is allowed to decide the type of punishment of his wife or daughter, if they found to be guilty of an offense. Furthermore, (Text No.1, 4) and (Text No.1, 14) state that the

husband is free to resolve whether or not to cut off his wife's ear after committing a theft and whether or not to punish her if she is guilty of adultery (finding her with another man) respectively, the same applied for the daughter "Wife and daughters in the Assyrian Code are regarded entirely from the early point of view as forming part of the possessions of a man, over whom he has full authority" (Jastrow, 1921, p.7).

Laws relating to women are varied and numerous dealings with matters such as cheating, adultery, divorce, theft, and veiling. As mentioned earlier, the first known legal text mentioning veiling is the Assyrian code which includes regulations regarding the female dress code, especially when appearing in public places (Text No.1, 39). The veiling and unveiling of women depend on their marital or social status. Wives and daughters were marked as property of the husband or the father by covering their heads or veiling, while those who remain unveiled are either "harlots"¹³ (prostitutes) or the hierodule¹⁴ (the woman who remains unmarried and thus belong to the temple). To veil a wife or a daughter was to send an indirect message to other men not to approach them (Jastrow, 1921).

The process of veiling also marks social distinctions. For example, a slave who would wear a veil in public would be punished, as would anyone who witnessed the veiling and did not report it to the palace. In addition to the previous explanations, Jastrow (1921) mentions other types of veiling and unveiling cases and the punishment stated in case of law breaking. Furthermore, Jastrow (1921) uses Muss Arnolt's *Assyrian Dictionary* to clarify Assyrian concepts such as the term *La-a-tu* which refers to the "unclean woman", or *Su-ku-ut-ta* which means precious or costly. The "unclean women" (*La-a-tu*) or the one who is possessed by demons or has uncleanness within her, are required to warn others not to approach her by shouting "unclear, unclear". In addition, harlots are seized and punished if ever found wearing a veil. The punishment is described as comprising of fifty lashes, a pitch (*Ki-ra-a* in Assyrian) or tar poured on her head and her garment being taken off. Any man who sees a covered harlot must report her to the palace, under penalty of 50 lashes and the removal of his garment "his ear they pierce, boring it with a drill and attaching it (i.e., the lobe) to the back of his ear and he must perform one month's royal service" (Jastrow, 1921, p.37). In addition, concubines were required to cover their heads when going out in public with their mistresses, captive women (captured during a war) also required veiling once they become the property of a man. "If a man places his captive woman veiled among five (or) six of his companions' (and) in their presence veils her and says, 'she is my wife,' -then she is his (legal) wife" (Jastrow, 1921, p.38).

Similarly to Jastrow, Stol (2016) discusses the Assyrian laws, but there is a difference concerning stating the laws, for instance regarding the law of veiling, Jastrow (1921) mentions veiling in law 39, while Stol (2016) does not start discussing it until stating the law 40 and that applies it to all the other laws. Correspondingly, Melville (2004) discusses the status of royal women and male identity according to the Neo-Assyrian codes by focusing on status as a social tool. Melville (2004) states that the Assyrian society was male-oriented ruling because all activities including commerce, politics, religion, and military were conducted by men. Records on women are obscure and accounts on them seem to be peripheral. The Assyrian ideology supported gender roles and those assigned to women are difficult to be discerned. This is why she focuses on the way in which their ideology classified women within the domestic sphere and the way they treated royal women publicly. Women (the king's dependants) at the Assyrian empire had separate courts that were built by

the Neo-Assyrian kings, who had an enormous wealth. The architecture of the courts had a special design to distinctive them from that of men. Parpola (2012), in *The Neo-Assyrian Royal Harem*, explains that female quarters in the Assyrian royal palaces resemble that of harem in the later oriental Abbasid and the Ottoman harems. These quarters were labelled “*Betisate*”, which means “house of women” or “women’s apartment” (Parpola, 2012 ,p. 613-614).The idea of constructing special places for women in the royal palaces has to do with the concept of seclusion and harem “Often all women who are living in the palace (royal women, personnel of the palace and other women of the palace) are labelled together as “harem” (Parpola, 2012, p.613-614).

Like the veil, *harem* is generally associated in the Western thoughts with Islamic practices. However, this concept pre-dated Islam and served to describe the private quarters assigned to women in the pre-Islamic Middle East (Britannica, 2024). “In pre-Islamic Assyria, Persia, and Egypt, most of the royal courts included a *harem*, consisting of the ruler’s wives and concubines, their female attendants, and eunuchs” (Britannica, 2024, no page). There are multiple views concerning the seclusion of women at the Assyrian royal palace, for example Westenholz (1990) states that there is not enough evidence concerning this seclusion and that Royal women enjoyed considerable degree of freedom. The fact that royal women had private quarters does not negate the option of them having an external connection with the outside world. In addition, the limitations and restrictions placed on the movements of the high-ranking ladies is difficult to discern. This view on the restrictions can be proven by the existence of female staff at the palace which signifies that some women had limited contact with men (Teppo, 2005). *Harem* is especially important to state when tackling issues on veiling because both serve the idea of seclusion and privacy.

Women at the royal palace gained prestige and agency depending on their relationship to the king or to other women. Melville (2004) gives an example of *Abi Rami* who identifies herself as the sister of the queen’s mother and *Sammu Ramat* had the highest rank of them all because she was the daughter in law of a king, wife of a king and a mother of a king. As mentioned above, the Assyrian society had a male-oriented way of governing which gave males agency over females. Veiling to them was a tool of identifying women as property of their males (Husband or father), recognising the social ranking of women, or pointing out the unclean women (those possessed by demons or sick women). Veiling in Assyria, according to the different scholarly interpretations, related to both male honour and class. Jastrow (1921) for example perceives veiling as related to male honour and woman’s virtue, any women who causes offence like adultery or theft is going to be punished as her husband or father pleases.

A further issues worthy of exploring is the extent of veiling. Assyrian women did not wear a face veiling because the Assyrian sculptures do not show this type of veiling. Face veiling had its root in the Greek era because its representation or depiction is manifested in the Greek Goddesses or upper-class Athenian women (Brooks, 1923). Brooks (1923) unfolds the concept of head covering based on Jastrow’s opinion on head veiling. Jastrow has indicated that head covering expresses that a woman belongs to a man and that from where the sense of bridal veil originated. According to Brooks (1923), Assyrian sculptures fail to depict veiling as covering the face, which is a common oriental custom. The most described women through the sculptures are captive women, who are sometimes depicted as wearing head veils. Children and goddesses are also sculptured with a head covering (Paterson, 1912-1913). Goddesses as well are represented with their head covered and that what makes Brooks

(1923) interrogates the idea of relating head covering to social distinction. If this would be true, then applying Jastrow's idea that captive women belong to men means that goddesses to belong to gods.

Multiple sculptures of head-covered goddesses were found in king *Sennacherib's* palace. Assyrian sculptures capture women with or without head covering, one example is the sculpture of Inanna, the Sumerian goddess, who is depicted in some cases with her head covered. The *Warka or Uruk* vase, which dated back to approximately 4000 years B.C, depicts Inanna with no face veiling receiving offerings from naked men and her attendants standing next to her. Nudity appears as something normal and has no relation to taboos or shame during that period. Lima (2013) demonstrates in, *Sumerian art: The Warka Vase*, that nudity in the context of the Mesopotamian art is a sign of frailty and destitution (poverty), however, in the Warka vase nudity takes another context and represents a part of religious rituals. In Mesopotamian Art, nudity is presented as an expression of frailty and destitution. For instance, in the Warka Vase, the nude figures are presented in a different context, and therefore with a different meaning and expression. The display of the naked human body in a religious context "anticipates," so to speak, the role of the nude in Greek Art (Lima, 2013). The nude men are represented as making offerings to their Goddess Ishtar and her attendants with their head covered. Her myth of seven gates (3500-1900 B.C) told the story of visiting her sister *Ereshkigal* in the underworld after the death of her husband.

'Because... of **my** older sister **Ereshkigal**,

Her husband, Gugalanna, the **Bull of Heaven**, has died.

I have come to witness the funeral rites.

Let the beer of his funeral rites be poured into the cup.

Let it be done. (Wolkstein and Karmar, 1983, p.55)

There are various explanations concerning the reason of Inanna's journey to the nether world. Ishtar visited the underworld to mourn her sister's husband, however different scholars find other interpretations to the story. Campbell (1964) explains that she was going to visit her opposite self, Lipinkivi (2004) believes that she wanted to deprive her sister from her powers, others like Parera (1981) and Karmar and Wolkstein (1983) interpret her decision as her desire to search for knowledge.

Each time she reaches a new level, she removes one layer of veiling (one article of clothing) until she is naked. The idea of covering and veiling can be illustrated here from the point of the sacred and the cursed. She keeps unveiling herself until she reaches the earth which signifies moving downward after being in elevated position. *Somatic Desire: Recovering Corporeality in Contemporary Thought* (2019) explains that the myth of Inanna was written in the form of a poem in cuneiform, under the title *The Descent of Inanna*. Inanna (Ishtar, Astarte or Aphrodite), where the goddess took her journey to the underworld both clothed and bejewelled with her divine powers. However, her sister instructed the gatekeepers to lock the gates when she arrived at the gate of *the Land of no Return*, Inanna was allowed to enter only if she removed one article of her clothes. She kept moving from one gate to another until she reached her sister, the Goddess of the Dead, naked. "They looked at her-it was the look of death-they spoke to her-it was the speech of anger. They shouted at her- it was the shout of

guilt. The afflicted woman was turned into a corpse and the corpse was hung on a hook” (Manoussakis, 2019, p. 132). The concept of veiling and garments is related with power and weakness. *Inanna*, being in heaven, was clothed, bejewelled, and had multiple powers, but when descending to the underworld her veils, jewels and even her powers disappeared. In an article entitled *Inanna's Descent to the Underworld*, Stuckey (2015) explains that if a goddess wishes to enter the underworld means that she will be humiliated, stripped of means, abject and naked. Thus, stripping the goddess of her garments and jewels made her vulnerable and fragile. Apropos of her descent, another interpretation relates stripping Inanna from her clothes to the concept of charka. Each time she takes off one article of her cloth, her energy is weakened. For instance, to pass through the gate of authority, she is asked to remove her crown “symbolizing the surrender of the blocks to her connection to heaven, to her spiritual self and to her divine Goddess Light” (Nielsen, 2020). Kahf (2008) explains in her introduction that the goddess of death knew the power of the veil. Veiling, in this case, has a sacred and divine meaning because ancient statuses of ancient goddesses including Sumerians, Egyptians, Phoenicians and Babylonian were regularly covered during holy or ceremonial processions.

As per Heath (2008), the mystery of the veil started alongside the discovery of the mysteries of nature like the eclipses of the moon, shedding or the moulting of the feather, skin or horns of animals and the ocean waves, and this can appear through different Goddesses like the Yemaya, the veiled Orisha and the West African goddess of creation that is associated with the moon and the sea, the Greek Goddesses Nyx (Night) and Selene (Moon). In this regard, there is one interpretation of the veiled goddess Inanna that may justify the nature’s inspiration of people to produce myths.

In summary there is a long-held belief that veiling is originated with Islam, however this concept has its root in the old religions and civilizations. The first reference to veiling was found in the Assyrian code of laws *Harem Edicts*. Harem edicts were collected during the realm of King Tiglath Pileser in about 1100 B.C, which set different laws that deal with women and their status in their society. At that time, veiling was not related to religion, but it represents classes, shame, sacred, divine, power, weakness and honour. The following chapter discusses the concept of veiling in the Abrahamic religions starting with Judaism, Christianity, and Islam.

3.3. Veiling Reference in the Abrahamic Religions:

3.3.1. Veiling in the Old Testament (500-400 B-C):

This section of the literature review provides the references and the interpretations of veiling in Judaism. The Old Testament or *Torah* gained its recognition as a scripture only after the destruction of the Second Temple in 70 B.C. It contains the same books as *Tanakh* or the Hebrew bible, but their arrangement is different (Cohen, 2019). There is a lack of any legislations regarding the veil in the Old Testament, which makes it a matter of custom rather than a biblical requirement as explained by Hurley (1981) in his book *Man and woman in biblical perspectives*. However, there are some instances in which veiling is mentioned. It is important to provide some brief information about women in the Old Testament, their social status, and their treatment.

Assyrian laws stressed the importance of veiling for women and prohibited women of low rank or harlots from veiling. It is stated previously that there are no legal codes on the necessity of veiling in *Torah*, however there are cases in which the veil is mentioned. According to Hurley (1981), the Islamic garb was not practised by Israelites at the time of Abraham and there are several incidents that prove that. For instance, *Sarah* is described as a beautiful woman when appearing in Egypt, *Isaac* describes *Rebekah* as a beautiful woman (Genesis 24:16) and *Jacob* preferred *Rachel* over her sister *Leah* because he saw her. They would not be able to describe them if they were totally veiled. However, these instances do not negate the existence of the veil.

There are two incidents where face veiling acts as an obstacle to recognise the woman's identity. Firstly, there is the biblical story of *Judah* and *Tamar*, which is mentioned in Genesis 38 of the Old Testament (Wassen, 1994). *Tamar* was the daughter-in-law of *Judah* and the wife of his older son *Er*. After the death of *Er*, she got married to his brother *Onan* because it was a custom in the Hebrew society that the widow gets married to her husband's brother after his death and his first-born child would be considered as his dead brother's first son and carry his name, this custom is called "Levirate". Weisberg (2009, p. ix), in *Levirate marriage and family in ancient Judaism*, defines the term Levirate widow as "a woman whose husband has died without children" and who therefore must be available to her brother-in-law for marriage". *Onan* was punished by the Lord for spilling his offspring on the ground by practicing *Coitus Interruptus* "But *Onan* knew that the offspring would not belong to him; so whenever he would sleep with his brother's wife, he would spill his seed on the ground so that he would not produce offspring for his brother" (Genesis 38:9), he eventually died. The only son remaining was *Shelah*, the youngest one. *Judah* believed that she was the cause of his two sons' death and feared that the same fate will happen to his only left son (Skinner, 1910), so he sent her to her father's home and asked that she put on the widow's garment. Realizing that *Shelah* had grown up and she was not asked to marry him and that *Judah's* wife passed away "When *Tamar* was told, "Your father-in-law is going up to *Timnah* to shear his sheep," she removed her widow's garments, covered her face with a veil to disguise herself, and sat at the entrance to *Enaim*, which is on the way to *Timnah*. For she saw that although *Shelah* had grown up, she had not been given to him wife". *Tamar* seized the chance to raise seeds for her dead husband, she put off her widow garment and wore a veil that covers her face. She presented herself to *Judah*, who follows his lust and sought a harlot that he did not recognize because of her facial veil "When *Judah* saw her, he thought she was a prostitute because she had covered her face. Not realizing that she was his daughter-in-law, he went over to her and said, "Come now, let me sleep with you." (Genesis 38:13-15).

There are multiple interpretations concerning the death of *Tamar*. Some of them condemn her as a prostitute or a harlot, others praised her for fulfilling her duty of raising seeds to her husband by tricking her father-in-law to sleep with her (Pietersen and Forrie, 2015), thus performing his levirate duty. When realizing her pregnancy, *Judah* declared that she was guilty of adultery and called for her open humiliation and that she must be burned (Collins, 2004). *Tamar* proved her child's paternity by providing the things that he gave her to sleep with him "Your signet and your cord, and the staff that is in your hand" (Genesis, 38:19). *Judah* was also condemned of being a lustful patriarch who did not practise his duties and promises in the right way and time (Hurley, 1981).

Brenner (1985) explains that veiling was used to disguise the common harlots, similarly Skinner (1910) mentions that *Tamar* wore the garb of the common prostitute through covering herself with the veil, which gives a hint that facial veiling was practised by harlots unlike the ancient Near East. In a similar vein, Skinner (1910) *Tamar*'s veil or harlot's veil is a dedication to the veiled goddess *Ishtar*. Von Rad (1973) believes that she was not playing the role of Harlot, but that of a veiled married woman observing the Babylonian custom, which suggests that a married woman should give herself once in her life to a stranger. Furthermore, the widow's garb during that period is unknown, but it did not include a veil. *Tamar* is conceived as a sacred prostitute which is different from the ordinary harlots. Skinner (1910) thinks of it as a devotion to *Ishtar* (the veiled goddess).

Such sacrifices of chastity, in the service of the goddess of love *Astarte*, were considered different from ordinary prostitution even though they were repulsive to Israel. They were strictly forbidden by law, and the teachers of wisdom warned urgently against this immoral custom, which was apparently at times fashionable even in Israel (Von Rad, 1937, p.395). The biblical story of *Judah* and *Tamar* is one example of a mistaken identity due to the presence of the veil. As explained above, it involves a certain amount of ambiguity that leads to the rise of multiple questions regarding the veil, the deceptive action, the courageous woman.

In addition to this biblical tale, another important story that includes the veil, which is that of *Jacob and Rachel*. It is mentioned in Genesis 29. The veil acts here as a mean of deception. *Jacob* asked to marry *Rachel*, but instead her older sister *Leah* was presented to him veiled on his wedding night. He came to realize the mistake only in the morning. Veiling here is associated with marriage because the bride wears a veil at the wedding night. *Jacob* was tricked by *Laban*, who deceived him by giving him the wrong bride, which signifies that the veil could be a tool of deception "When morning came, there was Leah! "What have you done to me?" Jacob said to Laban. "Wasn't it for Rachel that I served you? Why have you deceived me?" (Genesis, 29:24).

The veil is also referenced in another biblical story, namely the one of *Jacob*'s mother and *Bethuel*'s daughter *Rebekah*. It is also associated in this case with the concept of marriage. Like the previous examples, this tale has multiple interpretations and commentaries. The verse from the Old Testament with reference to veiling is stated in Genesis (24:65) "and asked the servant, "Who is that man in the field coming to meet us?" "It is my master," the servant answered. So she took her veil and covered herself" the question being raised here is what did *Rebekah* cover? And what is the significance of veiling. Clarke (1831) believes that it is the first time in which the word "veil" or *מַעֲטָפֶה* appears in *Torah*. The cloak or the veil was used by women in the East to signify modesty, chastity, and subservience. *Rebekah* tried to look more modest and honourable when she met *Isaac* for the first time. Veiling, in the case of both biblical couples *Jacob*, *Leah*, *Rebekah*, and *Isaac*, is linked to bridal veiling ritual. The deception of *Jacob* had inspired the Hasidic rituals "Because of this duplicity, during Hasidic wedding ceremonies, the groom lifts the bride's veil, just to make sure he is getting the wife he expects" (Chico, 2000, p.23).

As formerly mentioned, Hurley (1981), in considering various hairstyles and veiling practices in Judaism, states that veiling was not practiced as a religious requirement. Discussing the head covering, he doubts that it was only required among the wealthy Jews of the city.

According to Hurley (1981), the styling and the length of the women's hair at that period had a certain significance in three cultures, Jewish, Greek and Roman, for instance the loosed hair woman was marked as an adulteress "Her hair was publicly loosed to mark her off as one suspected of being 'unclean' by virtue of adultery, of repudiating her relation to her husband by giving herself physically to another man" (Hurley, 1981,p.169). If *unclean* woman was found innocent of adultery, then her hair is going to be put up as before.

To summarize, the veil was mentioned in the Old Testament or the Hebrew bible (Torah) in different cases. In each case it was used to serve a certain purpose (marriage or to hide an identity (deception). Behind the veil identities differ and change according to the targeted purpose. Tamar deceived Judah to raise seeds and Laban tricked Jacob to marry off his elder daughter and Rebekah wore a veil out of modesty. Although the veil was stated multiple times, there is no religious instruction on its donning which makes it a matter of social or political life, rather than religious life. This part discusses the interpretation and significance of veiling in the Old Testament, the following chapter discusses veiling in Christianity.

3.3.2. Veiling References in Christianity:

Unlike Judaism, Christianity depends on both the Old Testament and the New Testament. The source for head covering in Christianity exists in *Paul the Apostle's* first epistle to Corinthians. The book of the *1 Corinthians* is written in the form of an epistle (formal letter) where *St Paul* addressed his Christian followers in the highly cosmopolitan Greek city *Corinth*. Blackaby et al., (2008) state that during Paul's time, *Corinth* was known for sexual vice or sacred prostitution. Corinthian is a term adopted by the Greek language, which signifies the practice of sexual immorality. Blackaby et al., (2008) add that St Paul was not satisfied with what was happening in *Corinth*, so he wrote to them as their spiritual father to give instructions on how to deal with the division in the Church and sexual immorality. Among the epistles that St Paul wrote to the Corinthians is a controversial one on veiling for women when prophesying or praying. *St Paul's* views on veiling, in 1 Corinthians 11 2-16, have generated diverse kinds of translations, consequently, various interpretations. This is translation from the New International Version:

² I praise you for remembering me in everything and for holding to the traditions just as I passed them on to you. ³ But I want you to realize that the head of every man is Christ, and the head of the woman is man,^[a] and the head of Christ is God. ⁴ Every man who prays or prophesies with his head covered dishonours his head. ⁵ But every woman who prays or prophesies with her head uncovered dishonours her head—it is the same as having her head shaved. ⁶ For if a woman does not cover her head, she might as well have her hair cut off; but if it is a disgrace for a woman to have her hair cut off or her head shaved, then she should cover her head. ⁷ A man ought not to cover his head,^[b] since he is the image and glory of God; but woman is the glory of man. ⁸ For man did not come from woman, but woman from man; ⁹ neither was man created for woman, but woman for man. ¹⁰ It is for this reason that a woman ought to have authority over her own^[c] head, because of the angels. ¹¹ Nevertheless, in the Lord woman is not independent of man, nor is man independent of woman. ¹² For as woman came from man, so also man is born of woman. But everything comes from God.

¹³ Judge for yourselves: Is it proper for a woman to pray to God with her head uncovered? ¹⁴ Does not the very nature of things teach you that if a man has long hair, it is a disgrace to him, ¹⁵ but that if a woman has long hair, it is her glory? For long hair is given to her as a covering. ¹⁶ If anyone wants to be contentious about this, we have no other practice—nor do the churches of God (Living Saviour Misoula, 2017, p.2)

Multiple interpretations have been raised to interpret what the apostle means by covering and uncovering the head of the Christian women during prayer. This passage of *St Paul* is referred to as enigmatic and mysterious (Finney, 2010). There are two opposing views concerning whether women must cover their hair during prayer and what type of coverage is required. Scholars like Padgett (1984), Gardner, (2013) and O’Connors (1980) depend on different shreds of evidence to support their ideas and among them translating the verses. Translation plays a pivotal role in understanding the meaning of the verses. Some interpreters believe that *St Paul* requires Christian women to cover their heads when praying or prophesizing (Padgett,1984), while others understand that he orders them to wear their hair in a specific style in church.

Padgett (1984) rejects the translation of 1 Corinthians 11-4 *Kata Kephales Echon*, which means covering the hair with a veil and states three reasons for not considering this translation. Firstly, the word "*Kata*" does not mean on; it signifies down. Secondly, the word veil has its equivalent in the Greek language as *Kalymma*, and this word does not appear anywhere in the chapter. In verse 14 of the passage, the idea of men having their hair (Koma) long and not covered is mentioned. Padgett (1984) does not use the universal or international version of 1 Corinthians 11:2-16 because it replaces the word covered or veiled with bounded or unbounded hair. For example, 1 Corinthians 11-4 is the following: “Every man who prays or prophesies with his head covered dishonours his head” Padgett uses this translation of the verse “Every man who prays or prophesies with long hair dishonours his head”. In the case of women, he replaces the word covered with bound up. For instance, the fifth verse of Corinthians 11 states that any woman who prophesies or prays with her hair uncovered dishonours her head. Padgett (1984) prefers to use the following translation “But every woman who prays or prophesies with unbound hair dishonours her head; for she is the same as a woman with a shaved head”.

When searching for other translations of the verse 1 Corinthians 11:4-5 in *the Bible Hub*, different versions have different translations. The one stated above is the *New International Version* that uses the word covered and uncovered without specifying the type of head covering. Among all the versions, there are three different translations of the verses. Versions that insist on the need for covering up the head without stating which item to put on like *New Living Translation, English Standard Version, Berean Study Bible, New King James Version*. Other versions describe head covering by mentioning two words which are “covering the head with “something” or “anything” like *Berean Literal Bible and Christian Standard Bible*. The remaining example is the versions that use either “with a veil” or “veiled/unveiled.” Thus, there is an indication of the nature of the item, which is a veil instead of bound or unbound hair.

Padgett (1984) states that he owes his understanding of this interpretation to Jerome’s Murphy-O’ Connors ‘s work *Sex and logic in 1 Corinthians 11:2-16*. Like Padgett (1984), O

Connors (1980, p.484) opposes the translation of the term *Kata* as an indication of something that rests upon the head “His Usage, therefore, retains the nuance of motion proper to *kata*, making it unlikely that he would have employed this preposition with the genitive to designate something "resting upon" the head”. Hurley (1981) shares the same idea by explaining that older translation generally understood *St Paul's* view on covering to mean veiling. According to Hurley (1981), *St Paul* does not mention veiling except in verse 15, where he says that a woman’s long hair is given to her as a covering “but that if a woman has long hair, it is her glory? For long hair is given to her as a covering.” Hurley (1981) insists that Paul does not require an artificial veiling by explaining:

Paul is specifically rejecting the idea that women must have an additional covering over their hair. So strong was his feeling about the sufficiency of hair that he went on to say that if anyone wished to argue about it, neither he nor the churches of God had any *such* *cl.1stom (toiauten sunetheian)*. Most translations substitute 'other' for 'such' because they think that Paul required veils rather than forbade that they be required (1981, p.197).

The contrasting idea to the previous arguments is that women must wear a veil or a headgear during the time of prayer. Gardner (2013), the founder of the head covering movement and the author of the book *Head Covering: A Forgotten Christian Practice for modern times*, suggests that women are told in the scriptures to cover during prayer or prophecy using an artificial cover. Gardner (2013) shows two types of coverage that are mentioned in this chapter. The first example is (1 Cor 11:14-15), in which Paul states that a woman's covering is her long hair that is natural, permanent, and glory to her. The second instance is (1 Cor 11: 5), in which he explains that covering is a fabric or artificial cover which is removable, and he adds that it is a symbol of her authority in 1 Corinthians 11-10.

The Significance of Covering the Head of Women during Prayer or Prophecy:

In verse 3, *St Paul* explains the significance of head covering for a woman by relating it to the concept of biblical headship and the order of creation "But I want you to realize that the head of every man is Christ, and the head of the woman is man, [a] and the head of Christ is God". The concept of the head" has engendered a controversial debate. It is explained sometimes in terms of submission and inferiority, which means that a woman should cover her head during prayer because she is submitted to her husband's authority. Lee (1984) demonstrates that Paul, in verse 3, manifests the divine governmental ordination where Christ submits to God, man to Christ, and a woman to her husband (man). By covering her hair, a woman is under the headship of her husband. Furthermore, Lee (1984) believes that head covering has no relation to neither religious practice nor human customs. Head covering is related to the concept of headship and authority in God's governmental administration.

In addition, Lee (1984) contradicts any belief that the apostle suggested hair covering because it was common among people at that time (Jews and Greeks). Jewish priests and Greek men used to wear a head covering during praying or offering a sacrifice. Further, sisters should observe head covering at the church to recognize God's authority and do not rebel against his orders. Merkle (2006) explains that *St Paul* uses the argument of creation to argue concerning two different issues either to not allow women to hold the position of a pastor or for the sake of prayer or prophecy "To prove his point, the apostle argues from creation that the woman was created from man “For man does not come from the woman, but the woman from man”

and for man “For man was not created for the woman but the woman for the man” (Merkle, 2006, p. 527).

As highlighted above, the covering of a woman’s head during prayer signifies her obedience and submission to the authority of man in church. However, some regard that biblical headship has nothing to do with the concept of submission and woman’s inferiority. Brown (1976) and Witherington (1995) provide an explanation of the hierarchy of order in the church by pointing out that *St Paul* instructs men not to cover up their heads, otherwise they are failing to fulfil their position and abdicating the dignity given to them by the creator. Women, on the other hand, are required to observe veiling during prayer not to dishonour their metaphorical head (husband). Besides the order of creation, Brown (1976) and Witherington (1995) discuss the concept of glory. According to them, the image of God is a man that is why he should not be covered, and because a woman is the image and glory of man, she needs to be veiled so only the glory of God can be reflected. When a woman wears a veil or her hair as a veil, she becomes equal to man in Christ. As a result, their idea reflects the celebration and the manifestation of gender in the church.

According to Walker, St Paul's arguments regarding the role of women is resumed by women's liberation movement as " All time male Chauvinist" (Walker ,1975, p.94). Reid (2008) finds it difficult to discern if St Paul is a chauvinist or egalitarian regarding women because of his patriarchal attitudes towards women that are shaped by Greco-Roman culture and Jewish background. Furthermore, Reid (2008) Justifies that by explaining that the apostle requires women to be silent in the church to restrict their leadership. Unlike, Reid (2008), Scroggs (1972) does not consider St Paul as an egalitarian who seeks equality for women. Furthermore, the distinction in dress code or head covering in the church is not linked to female subordination; but rather is a way of asserting women's equal position and complete freedom to participate in the act of worshipping God.

In Conclusion, this section focused on the concept of veiling in Christianity. It attempts to understand chapter 1 Corinthians 11:2-16 in which head covering in the church is mentioned. The first part gives a quick introduction into the life of the apostle and the place in which he addresses head covering (Corinth). The second section deals with a question regarding if women are required to wear a veil or long hair. Next, it moves to understand the significance of veiling and the arguments that the apostle provided to support his stance. The last section questioned the position of the apostle regarding women in the church. The following section deals with the concept of veiling or Hijab in Islam.

3.3.3 The Meaning of the Hijab in Islam:

This section provides an exploration of the meaning of the Hijab and its reference in the Islamic sacred texts Quran and Hadith. It is important to understand the term Hijab (the Islamic veil) before going into further details. There are various meanings for Hijab, the literal meaning signifies “a veil,” “a curtain” and a “partition” or a “separation” (Sulaiman and Fatai,2020, p.3: Ruby, 2006). In metaphysics, Hijab refers to the veil or barrier that separates man or the world from God and the illusionary creations (Glasse,1989). Hijab is widely used today to signify adherence to specific standards of modest dress according to the legal system Shariah (Glasse,1989; Rahardjo,2019), it does not require wearing a veil but covering everything except the face and the hands in public, this practice originated in the Middle East (Glasse,1989).

As per Sulaiman and Fatai (2020), the term Hijab is used synonymously with the word scarf, nevertheless this term is not restricted to a scarf only, it is more than that. The Hijab is a broad concept that covers several types of covering from around the world. Amer (2014) presents distinct types of Muslim dress and veils, for instance, the Afghani Burqa, which signifies a face veil that is worn by conservative Muslim women. Besides, it is a long garment that is worn by Muslim women in Taliban-controlled areas in Afghanistan and Pakistan, which covers every part of the body except for the eyes. In addition, the Iranian Cloak or Chador, which is worn from head to toe and held in a place with one hand and the Haik, which is a traditional long and loose white scarf that covers the parts of the body and face, it is also held in a place with one hand, it is common in Algeria and Morocco. There is also the Pakistani Shalwar Khamis and other types of Hijabs among the Muslim communities that have cultural connotations (Amer, 2014; Sulaiman and Rafai, 2020). As a result, the term Hijab is used as an umbrella term for what is regarded as an appropriate Muslim dress, it refers to both the body and all types of hair cover (Amer, 2014).

Al-Ghalayini (1960) explains that whenever a Muslim woman covers “her adornment, she is said to be wearing Hijab (Cited in Sulaiman and Rafai, 2020, p.3). Like Sulaiman and Rafai (2020), Ruby (2006) explains that although the terms Hijab and veil are used interchangeably, Hijab is different because it has an Islamic connotation. While the veil is used widely to describe head covering, this term is not able to cover the complexities of the practice. Hijab does include women’s behaviours and attitudes and considers modesty as a vital part to fulfil it (Ruby, 2006). In the same vein, Sulaiman and Rafai (2020) explain that Islam is concerned with sustaining community cohesion and the respect of the moral boundaries between unrelated men and women, which makes it more than a scarf or a dress code. To better understand Hijab in Islam, it is required to understand its reference in Islamic sacred texts.

3.3.3.1. Hijab’s References in Quran and Hadith:

Quran insists on modesty and chastity for both Muslim men and women (Nasr, 2004). There are two main chapters that include references on covering and modesty, Surah Al-Nur (verses 30-31) and Surah Al Ahzab (verse 95). The first chapter is that of Surah Al-Nur and it is translated by Ali (1989) as the following:

Say to the believing men that they should lower their gaze and guard their modesty: that will make for greater purity for them: and God is well acquainted with all that they do. And say to the believing women that they should lower their gaze and guard their modesty: and they should not display beauty and ornaments except what (must ordinarily) appear thereof; that they must draw their veils over their bosoms and not display their beauty except to their husbands, their fathers, their husband’s fathers, their sons, their husband’s sons, or their men, or their slaves whom their right hands possess, or male servants free of physical needs, or small children who have no sense of the shame of sex; and that they should not strike their feet in order to draw attention to their ornaments

In this chapter, both modesty and lowering the gaze are prescribed upon both Muslim men and women (Hassan, 1995). In the second verse, there is an emphasis on Muslim women and in what situations they are allowed and not allowed to display their beauty. They are instructed to draw their veils over their bosoms and not to display their beauty except to their husbands, other women, children, *eunuchs*¹⁵, and *mahram*¹⁶ (Sulaiman and Rafai, 2020). In

addition, the verse instructs Muslim women not to show their Zeenah (adornment) only what may be naturally shown (Sulaiman and Rafai, 2020) and to protect their private parts from zina (adultery) and nakedness (Hoffman-Ladd, 1987). There is also another interpretation for that, which suggests that if the display of beauty is unintentional, thus it does not violate modesty (Hassan, 1995; Ad-Din, 1928).

Muslim women are also advised not to walk in a manner that attracts the attention of others (Hussain, 2016). The chapter is called Al Ahzab: “O Prophet! Tell thy wives and daughters, and the believing women, that they should cast their outer garments over their persons (when outside): that they should be known (as such) and not molested” (Asad, 1984). In this verse, the prophet’s wives and daughters and the believing women are ordered to cover with a full veil (outer garments) when going outside (Sulaiman and Rafai, 2020). The outer garment in Arabic is *Jilbab* “to draw their Jalabib” (Maudoodi, 1972). There are various opinions regarding the appropriate ways to wear *Jilbab*. Imam Al Hassan, for instance, explains that *jilbab* refers to covering half of a woman’s face. Furthermore, Ibn Abbas and Qatadah suggest that *Jilbab* should cover the woman’s forehead and turned around her nose, it also covers most of the face and the chest. Others believe that the woman is required to cover all her head and her face except one eye (Hanbal, 1955 and Sulaiman, 2016). Regarding Al-Hadith, there are various Al Hadiths about covering. One of them, is narrated by *Aisha*, the wife of the prophet, that when the riders who would pass by them when they were with the prophet. When they got close to them, they would draw outer cloaks from their heads to toes. They would not uncover until they passed by (Haddad, 2007). After discussing the references of Hijab in Islamic sacred texts, the following section presents different debates between the opponents and proponents of the Hijab in Islam.

3.3.3.2. Traditionalist and Feminist interpretation of Hijab

There are mixed opinions about the obligation of wearing a Hijab. Javed (2014) explains that some Muslim women see Hijab as not compulsory, while others believe that hijab is obligatory. The proponents of Hijab point out that Hijab is needed for taming the untamed sexual desires of both men and women. A great emphasis is placed on women. According to Tseeolon (1995), a woman’s entire body is loaded with sexuality, which includes bodily movements, styles, shapes, and the colours of their clothing which have the potential to provoke male sexual arousal. Furthermore, Doi (1989) believes that Hijab is intended to guard not only women, but also the spiritual virtue of men. This explanation is provided by Hassan on the importance of Hijab,

Muslims in general, tend to believe that it is best to keep men and women segregated – in their separate, designated spaces. The intrusion of women into men’s spaces is seen as leading to the disruption, if not the destruction, of the fundamental order of things. If some exigency makes it necessary for women to enter men’s space, they must make themselves ‘faceless,’ or at least as inconspicuous as possible. This is achieved through ‘veiling,’ which is, thus, an extension of the idea of the segregation of the sexes. (Hassan, 1995, p. 252).

Although there are various viewpoints that support Hijab, some Muslim feminists do not regard hijab as an obligation. Roald (2001) explains that some feminists, like Ahmed (1992) and Mernissi (1987), regard Hijab as not compulsory and directed only to the wives and the daughters of the prophet. Ahmed (1992), for instance, explains that chapter 24 (31-30)

supports the idea that not all women are instructed to cover, and that the Hijab is an obligation only for the prophet's wives (Ruby,2016). Moreover, Ahmed (1992) believes that the practice of veiling is related to culture and existed long ago before Islam in Arabia. Women of higher status practiced it.

In addition to Ahmed (1992), Mernissi (1987) criticizes the Hijab by arguing that there is no straightforward evidence that makes it an Islamic obligation. Instead, it is a tradition that asserts patriarchy and male dominance and does not measure or judge women's commitment to *Allah* (God). In addition to the previous arguments on Hijab, Roald (2001) believes that some Muslims held women accountable for an immoral society, while some non-Muslims believe that Hijab oppresses women. In addition, it raised debates among feminists who see that Islam treats men and women unequally by commanding them to dress modestly (Bartkowski and Read, 2003). However, this may not be true because Quran instructs men, too, to lower their gaze and guard their private parts (Quran, Al Nur: 30-31). In contrast to feminists' opinions, many Muslim women see themselves as feminists and feel empowered by Hijab (Bouma and Bracegovan,2000). The interpretations of Hijab as obligatory and non-obligatory, oppressive, and empowering differ among different discourses.

This section provided a discussion about Hijab in Islam. Firstly, it discussed the meanings and the types of the Hijab and its interpretations, and references in Islamic sacred texts including the Holy Quran and The Hadith. Secondly, it examined the proponents and the opponents of wearing Hijab and provided a discussion on the various discourses around it. The following section provides a discussion on an important concept that is related to the concept of Hijab, which is Islamophobia.

3.4. Islamophobia: Definition and Features in Global Context and Scotland

When discussing the presence of the Islamic religious attire in a western context, it is crucial to bring about discussion on Islamophobia. This section presents the following themes: First, it tackles the origin of the concept, its features, and consequences. Secondly, it questions its nature after 9/11, its most recent definitions and types. Thirdly, it gives important instances of Islamophobia from the UK and Global context, especially during the covid-19 period. Finally, it focuses on Islamophobia and its existence in the Scottish context.

3.4.1. Islamophobia: Origin and Controversies

Islamophobia has been introduced in different Western and non-Western contexts to define hostility and hatred against Muslims, like anti-Semitism or anti-Hinduism. According to Al Shammari (2013), the term Islamophobia was firstly defined by the *Runnymede Trust Commission on British Muslims and Islamophobia*. The *Runnymede Trust Commission on Islamophobia* was launched by Professor Gordon Conway and other members in 1996. In February 1997, they produced a consultation paper under the title *Islamophobia, its Features, and Dangers in Britain*. It was a successful work, about "3500 papers" were distributed to country councils and metropolitan authorities, police forces, Muslim organizations, and individuals (Runnymede Trust et al., 1997, no page). The term was not coined by the commission, because it was already used among Muslim communities to describe acts of prejudice and discrimination that they experienced in their everyday lives. Moreover, it was coined in the 1980s and its first appearance was in a 1991 periodical in the United States. Islamophobia is defined in the report as: "Unfounded hostility towards Islam. It refers also to

the practical consequences of such hostility in unfair discrimination against Muslim individuals and communities, and to the exclusion of Muslims from mainstream political and social affairs” (Runnymede Trust, 1997, p. 4). This definition signifies that Islamophobia is an act of either hate or prejudice against Muslims, however the term was criticised for not being an ideal term. The commission (1997) states facing a challenge because the term was criticised for suppressing any kind of criticism against Islam, which means that anyone who wishes to criticize Muslims or Islam would be demonized or stigmatized. They were accused by the “*Independence Magazine*” of wishing to be “Islamically Correct” (Runnymede Trust, 1997, p.4).

3.4.1.1. Closed and Open Views of Islam:

The idea behind introducing such a term was a result of growing hostility towards Muslims. Besides, it was not used to prevent any tragedy from taking place, but as a tool to correct wrong perceptions and improve relationships. As a result of that accusation, the Runnymede Trust (1997) explains the difference between legitimate criticism of the Islamic faith on one hand and the hostility and the prejudice against Muslims on the other hand. They believe in the existence of two main views “the closed views of Islam and the open views of Islam” in which the legitimised criticism of Islam goes with the open views and the other one with the hostility and the prejudices against Islam.

Distinctions	Closed views of Islam	Open views of Islam
1-Monolithic/ Diverse	Islam seen as a single monolithic bloc, static and unresponsive to new realities.	Islam seen as a diverse and progressive with internal difference, debates and development.
2- Separate/ Interacting	Islam seen as separate and other- (a) not having any aims or values in common with other cultures (b) not affected by them (c) not influencing them.	Islam as interdependent with other faiths and cultures- (a) having certain shared values and aims (b) affected by them (c) influencing them.
3-Inferior/ different	Islam seen as inferior to the west – Barbaric, irrational, primitive, sexist.	Islam seen as distinctively different, but not deficient, and as equally worthy of respect.
4- Enemy/ Partner	Islam seen as violent, aggressive, threatening, supportive of terrorism, engaged in a clash of civilization.	Islam seen as actual or potential partner in joint cooperative enterprises and in the solution of shared problems.
5-Manupulative/ Sincere	Islam seen as a political ideology, used for political or military advantage	Islam seen as a genuine religious faith practiced sincerely by its adherents.
6- Criticism of the West rejected/ considered	Criticisms made by Islam of the West rejected out of hand	Criticism of “the West” and other cultures are considered and debated.
7-Discrimination defended /Criticised	Hostility towards Islam used to justify discriminatory practices	Debates and disagreements with Islam do not diminish efforts to combat discrimination and exclusion

	towards Muslims and the exclusion of Muslims from mainstream society.	
8-Islamophobia seen as natural/ problematic	Anti-Muslim hostility accepted as natural and normal	Critical views of Islam are themselves subjected to critique, lest they be inaccurate and unfair.

Table 1: Close and open views on Islam according to Runnymede Trust commission on British Muslims in 1997

The commission (1997) believes that the closed views of Islam are a continuity of the feeling that the West had on Muslims from the time of the crusades. Furthermore, they give examples by quoting some of Cardinal Bessarion's views on Muslims when *Constantinople* fell into the hands of the *Ottoman* Empire. Bessarion wrote to *the Doge of Venice* to express his distress that *Constantinople* was once a developed city, and that inhuman barbarians and wild beasts destroyed it. As a result, stories from the past are revived in both Muslim and non-Muslim minds to explain the fears, feelings, and animosities of the present (Runnymede Trust, 1997, p.4). The commission (1997) discusses the table thoroughly by examining each of the closed views and its opposition by giving different shreds of evidence and comparisons.

The report also set out various outcomes or consequences of Islamophobia and suggest some recommendations to deal with it. The table below summarised these consequences.

The outcomes of Islamophobia	
Injustice	Islamophobia has a negative impact on a society that is characterised by diversity (in this case is Britain). This can raise a sentiment of exclusion among British Muslims.
Effects on youth	Media's Islamophobic portrayal of Muslims can negatively affect the minds of young people. They may feel inferior and lose confidence. As a result, they may join extremist groups where they will feel more welcomed.
Dangers of disorder	Islamophobia increases some serious social disorders.
Muting of mainstream voices	Islamophobia does not give a chance for members of Muslim community to voice their concerns or to express themselves.
Waste in economy	Losing different talents that may contribute in the economy and national trade.
Obstructing cooperation and interchange	Islamophobia affect the cooperation between Muslims and non-Muslims and prevent them from sharing valuable and beneficial traits that each of them have.
Harming international relations	Islamophobia makes it difficult for both Muslim and non-Muslim countries to come into a solution for shared international problems, for instance: Ecological issues.

Table 2: *The Outcomes and the impacts of Islamophobia according to Runnymede Trust report (1997)*

3.4.1.2. The Concept of Islamophobia: Challenge, Denial and Rejection:

Islamophobia, its features, and consequences are defined by the commission in 1997, which means before 9/11 and the ‘War on Terror’¹⁸. It is necessary to consider other definitions and criticism of Islamophobia, especially post-9/11. According to Allen (2020), the concept of Islamophobia was first introduced to the political and public arenas in 1997 to describe discrimination and racism against Muslims. As a result, a body of literature was introduced to discuss this recent phenomenon in different political and social contexts. Allen (2020) explains that the concept was subjected to denial, castigation, challenge, and rejections. Islamophobia was perceived as a negative concept by many politicians, scholars, and journalists. For instance, the journalist Melanie Philips (2018) refers to Islamophobia as “fiction” that hinder the legitimate and valid criticism of Islam and Muslims. In the same veins, the Quilliam foundation believes that Islamophobia is “a propaganda and coup to Islamists who can... present themselves as ordinary Muslims who are victims of Islamophobia” (Readings, Brandon, and Phelps, 2011, p. 24). Murray (2018, no page) supports Christopher Hitchens's view that “Islamophobia is a word created by fascists and used by cowards to manipulate morons”.

3.4.1.3. New Definition of Islamophobia:

In November 2018, the All-Party Parliamentary Group, at Westminster, attempted to give an agreeable definition to the concept of Islamophobia. In their third report, *Islamophobia defined: The inquiry into a working definition of Islamophobia*, the party hoped to make history by putting forward a working definition of Islamophobia (Allen, 2020). To achieve that, they explain that the definition took about two years of consultation and evidence gathering using different views of lawyers, officials, Muslim activists, and communities. They aimed to imitate the Runnymede Trust report of 1997 and give “a meaning to the word and the nature of the thing we call Islamophobia” (All-Party Parliamentary Groups on British Muslims, 2018, p.8). Consequently, they produced the following definition “Islamophobia is rooted in racism, and it is a type of racism that targets expressions of Muslimness or perceived Muslimness” (All-Party Parliamentary Groups on British Muslims, 2018, p.11; Parker-Jenkins, 2020, p.3).

This definition raised various positive and negative criticisms. On the one hand, sixty British academics support the definition, some authorities welcomed it but explained that they could not find what the meaning of "Muslimness" is (Allen, 2020). On the other hand, the definition received some negative responses. The conservative party, for example, suggests that the definition was not broadly accepted and needs more consideration. Others relate this definition to the limitation of the freedom of expression. Martin Hewitt, for example, explains his concerns about this definition and how it is going to limit the freedom of speech concerning historical and theological matters. In addition, this definition will make confusion among the police for the meaning is too vague and broad (Dodd, 2019). In the similar vein, Sajid Javid demonstrates in a letter that this definition has the potential to influence free speech in both academia and journalism and that it will affect the social cohesion (Allen, 2020).

3.4.1.4. Is Islamophobia a Type of Racism?

Many authors argue that Islamophobia is a type of racism (Goldberg, 2006; Malik, 2000; Klug, 2012). For example, Goldberg (2006) defines Muslims as a race alongside Jews and black. In his article entitled, *Racial Europeanization* (2006), Goldberg (2006) discusses the representation of these racial groups on the European imaginary. Lauwers (2019) produces an article criticising the previous works by distinguishing between two problematic types of Islamophobias. Lauwers (2019) believes that the previous works on Islamophobia lack conceptual clarity due to the difference between Anti-Muslim racism and anti-Islam bigotry. According to Lauwers (2019), religious and cultural bigotry do not involve the assumption that group memberships are innate and natural, which means it can be changeable because religion is a matter of choice, unlike racism where a group of people experiences exclusion because they share certain innate and fixed stereotypes or characteristics, like skin colour, language, and religious attire.

3.4.1.4.1 Islamophobia as Anti-Muslim Racism:

Lauwers (2019) defines racism as the naturalization of stereotypes attached to a marker-based group, to justify social exclusion. Lauwers mentions the term Muslimness as a marker to identify Muslim racial characteristic, which causes these stereotypes to be naturalized and ultimately causing social consequences. The quality of being a Muslim (Muslimness) is not defined by if the person is a practicing Muslim if his parents are Muslims and if she or he is an Arab. Lauwers (2019), as well as Goldberg (2016), mention three major attributes of Muslimness: Foreignness, backwardness, and danger. Muslims are perceived as inherently different from Europeans, violent and dangerous (Shooman and Spielhaus, 2010). Besides, they are perceived as being disloyal to Europe (Meer and Noorani, 2008). Muslims are also depicted as terrorists, especially in media, in which the term terrorism is used interchangeably with Islamic fundamentalism. They are identified by two different markers (somatic and non-somatic markers). Non-somatic markers are related to religious and cultural attire. Hijab, for example, is a strong visual identifier of Muslims. The image of the exotic orient as well serves as a non-Islamic identifier (Lauwers, 2019). Some non-somatic identifiers are related to ethnic attributes like Skin colour. Muslims are usually identified as individuals with dark skin (Arabs and Middle Eastern), language (the use of Arabic language), and Middle Eastern names and nationalities (Lauwers, 2019). Some people can be subjected to Anti-Muslim racism just because they are mistaken for being Muslims. For instance, Sikh wearing turbans are also victims of such hostility (Allen and Neilsen, 2002, p.8; Suri and Wu, 2017).

3.4.1.4.2. Religious Bigotry: Anti-Islam Bigotry

The other type of Islamophobia is religious discrimination that does not include racism. Religious bigotry is directed primarily toward a certain religion and not the followers of that religion. The distinction between racism and religious bigotry is explained in Arendt (1951). Arendt (1951) highlights a difference between anti-Semitism and anti-Judaism, the latter is described as hostility towards Judaism and not Jews. Lauwers (2019) believes that anti-Islam bigotry targets Islam as a religion. It focuses on the inferiority of Islam to other religions and emphasizes that Islam cannot be suitable for secularism. Such Islamophobes have no problem with racism; they believe that Islamic culture conflicts with democratic and humanist beliefs.

Knowing the difference between the two is crucial, but sometimes anti-Islam bigotry is used to hide behind anti-Muslim racism. Lauwers (2019) gives examples from the European political arenas and how they targeted Muslims through anti-Islam bigotry by using the expression “We are not against Muslims, we are merely against Islam” (Lauwers, 2019, p.22). Similarly, Mahmood (2018) suggests that the expression of “I can’t be racist, Islam is not a religion” (Mahmood, 2018, no page) is used by those who are usually accused of using expressions that demonize Muslims. Furthermore, Mahmood (2018) maintains that Islam is not a race, nevertheless the prejudice used against Muslims and Muslim-like is a form of racial prejudice. This prejudice is referred to by Mahmood (2018) as cultural racism that discriminates people not based on their skin colour, but on their appearance, their attire, the food they eat, their names and nationalities.

3.4.2. Global Instances of Islamophobia (Statistics from the British and the global contexts):

Islamophobia has been subjected to rejection, denial, and connected to terrorism, brotherhood, and extremism. Describing Islamophobia as both propaganda and fiction might be denied due to the rates of attacks on Muslims. In the light of the UK context, Tell MAMA UK ¹⁹ (2018) presents some data that show the rise of hate crimes against Muslims. The non-stationary organization explains that the victim of the Islamophobic hate crime wants four main things: to be treated with dignity, to keep being informed about the development of their cases, to be believed by their employers, to be believed when reporting discrimination or hate crimes incidents to the police and to ensure that other actions are made available to them if the Crown Prosecution Service chooses not to proceed with legal proceedings (Tell MAMA,2018). Tell MAMA (2018) explains that from 2012 onwards, there has been a rise in hate crimes towards Muslims. The incidents that they collected from 2017 involved offline attacks, which means physical attacks. Anti-Muslim discrimination and hatred increased by 56%, and vandalism raised by 88%. Unlike previous years, 2017 data shows that 12% of anti-Muslim actions took place around or in private households. In addition, most of the victims were female Muslims, and most perpetrators were white males (including teenagers). Other data from a report entitled *Gendered Islamophobia and Anti-Muslim hatred, published on 29 November 2018*, shows that between January and June 2018, Tell MAMA has reported about 685 reports, from which 608 were verified as anti-Muslim hate crimes and that they occurred in the UK. 65 % occurred offline and 34 % Online. In 2019, terrorist attacks on Muslims took place in New Zealand. The Christchurch attacks were conducted by Brenton Tarrant (the far-right inspired extremist” on 15th March 2019).

A year later, Tell MAMA UK (2019) produces an interim report under the title *The impact of the Christ church terrorist attack*. The report includes statistics of hate crimes incidents against Muslims. It shows that between the 8th and 14th March (one week before the event), about 12 incidents of hate crimes were reported (El-Shafey, 2020). The number of the incidents raised to 95 right after the Christ church event. The event had a substantial influence on the UK and resulted in a huge rise of anti-Muslim hate crimes. January 1st to 30th knew about 705 hate crimes incidents, 592 were verified as anti-Muslim hatred, some of which occurred offline, and 155 took place online (Tell MAMA, 2019). Police forces also received reports of anti-Muslim hatred, about 1028 took place offline, 91 online, and 94 cases were not revealed (Tell Mama, 2019). Some attacks targeted mosques, Islamic institutions, and they increased by 433% between February and March 2019.

3.4.2.1. The Rise of Islamophobia During the Covid-19 Epidemic:

In a recent article under the title *Muslims falsely blamed for Covid-19 Spread*, Mahmood (2020) discusses Tell MAMA's findings regarding anti-Muslim hate crimes during this pandemic in the UK context. According to Tell MAMA, 40% of online hate crimes were reported because of some viral false videos and photos that accused Muslims of not observing social distancing rules. Mahmood (2020) gives an example of a video of British Muslims praying before the lockdown claiming that they were not observing social distancing rules. Many Muslims were facing verbal abuse, bullying, and death threats (Mahmood, 2020). What fuels this claim is an interview with Craig Whittaker –Conservative MP- who claims that “Sections of community that is not taking the pandemic seriously” when asked if he was referring to Muslims, he replies “Of course” (Braddick, 2020, no page). Harun Khan shows his concern regarding the rise of Islamophobia during the pandemic and accused the far-right of their conspiracy theories about Muslims spreading the virus.

Iman Atta, the director of Tell MAMA, called off Craig to apologize for the BAME and Muslim community after his accusation by telling the Newsweek magazine that: “I think the claim that Muslim communities and Ethnic minority communities are not taking the pandemic seriously is problematic” (Mahmood, 2020). Furthermore, Atta points out that social media companies are not doing enough to fight hate speech and online abuse that perpetuate racism, Islamophobia, and anti-Semitism. Muslims and other ethnic groups are blamed for spreading the virus not only in the UK. Other parts of the world like the United States of America, Canada, and India claim the same issue.

3.4.2.2. Islamophobia in the Global Context During the Covid-19 Pandemic:

In India reports indicated that discrimination against Indian Muslims has been intense since the selection of *Modi Navenda* as the prime minister of the country in 2014 (for example, Jha and Dixit, 2020). This election gave power to the rise of Hindu nationalism and a decline in secularism which made Muslims suffer during his administration. The Indian government suspects that the virus was spread because of the congregations of the *Tablighi Jamaat* group at a mosque in Nizamuddin Neighbourhood of New Delhi at the beginning of March. At that period, India was still in the wake of the Covid-19 phenomenon. The government started the lockdown on the 24th of March “While the Tablighi Jamaat is far from the only group in India that has ignored social distancing instructions across the country, it is the only one that has been singled out as a scapegoat” (Jha and Dixit, 2020, no page). At the time when Muslims were blamed for breaching the rules and spreading the virus, the president of India attended an award ceremony, and the chief minister attended a Hindu celebration at a temple on 25th March.

Similarly, Islamophobia became prevalent in Canada during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Al Qazzaz, (2020), discusses some islamophobia instances. Muslims have been targeted during that period, essentially by far-right supporters. Additionally, Al Qazzaz (2020) attributes the rise of anti-Muslim hatred to media coverage that portrays Muslims as the super-spreaders of the virus. Furthermore, AL Qazzaz (2020) gives examples of a Canadian new channel that used a video of Muslims in the mosque to report a Canadian Hookah lounge that failed to comply with the restrictions. Fake news was posted online through Facebook and Twitter platforms to claim that Muslims are the main spreaders of the virus because they do not respect social distancing. One example of some Islamophobic reactions is a video, which

went viral on social media, of a far-right extremist who run “A Ramadhan Bambathon.” The man on the video tried to monitor the mosque of Edmonton to make sure Muslims are respecting social distancing during this pandemic (Al Qazzaz, 2020, no page) “So it's April 24th — the start of the Ramadan 'Bombathon' and I'm just performing my civic duty to make sure that no one's actually showing up at the Al Rashid mosque,” said the man, who had taken it upon himself to make sure worshippers were following a health order to contain the coronavirus (Huncar, 2020).

Women were subjected to hate during this pandemic. Al Qazzaz (2020) also reported some gender-Islamophobic and hijabophobic incidents that took place in Canada. For instance, a hijabi woman reported that she was punched repeatedly in transit (Snowdon, 2020) and a Muslim woman of special needs was attacked by another woman for setting on the swing in a park in Toronto during a family trip (Kavac, 2020). Mosques as well were attacked and vandalized through breaking glass and painting racist slurs.

3.4.2.3. Islamophobia in Scotland:

It is complicated to discuss the concept of Islamophobia in Scotland because Scotland already had other previous challenges like Anglophobia, multicultural nationalism, and devolution. All these have been discussed in a book by Asifa Hussain and William Miller (2006) under the title *Multicultural Nationalism, Islamophobia, Anglophobia, and Devolution*. The book (2006) suggests a comparison between Islamophobia in England and Scotland. Hussain and Miller (2006) believe that Islamophobia is considerably lower in Scotland than in England although there is a growth in Scottish national identity and the separation of the Scottish parliament. Furthermore, compared Scottish nationalism, English nationalism is more related to Islamophobia. Scottish nationalism is “civic” and “benign” while English nationalism is “Ethnic.” Kumar (2003) proposes that Scottish nationalism can stimulate the rise of English nationalism, while Heath and Curtice (2000) argue that the growth in English nationalism is due to the influence of the far right-wing and the French national front.

Hussain and Miller (2006) also discuss the death of Multiculturalism and the growth of Islamophobia since 9/11. Multiculturalism received different criticism. It was introduced by Jenkins, in 1966, who explains the difference between integration and assimilation. Jenkins supports the term integration and explains that it should not mean that the immigrants are going to lose their culture and national characterizes. Assimilation is the opposite of integration and does not support cultural diversity in the country (Banton, 1985). Others disagree with the term Multiculturalism and warn about it. Greenfeld (2000) and Barry (2001) believe that Multiculturalism endangers liberal democracy. Trevor Philips, the former chair of CRE, argues that the concept of Multiculturalism is outdated because it encourages difference instead of supporting minorities to be British (Baldwin, 2004). Multiculturalism knew its death with the event of 9/11 when Muslims start to be perceived as the enemy within (Fekete, 2004).

Hussain and Miller (2006) use indicators to measure Islamophobia in England and Scotland. The participants from England are identified as white and non-Muslim living in England, while the participants from Scotland are identified as White, non-Muslims, and Scottish born (Their partners are Scottish if applicable). Six main indicators of Islamophobia were pointed out. The first measure relates to economic resentment towards Muslims, 2nd and 3rd national distrust indicators, 4th suggests the fear for national identity, the 5th measure social exclusion

and the 6th measure how Muslims contribute to condemn Islamic terrorism. The results show that Islamophobia in England is higher than that in Scotland. Around 1/3 of Scottish people feel economic resentment and express social exclusion towards Muslims. Besides, half of them feel that Scotland may lose its identity if Muslims' number grows, and the same percent feel that Muslims are not committed to Scotland the way they are committed to their faith. Moreover, some indicators were close between Scotland and England like the feeling of national distrust and the condemnation of terror. A significant difference was between the indicators of social exclusion, national distrust, and economic resentment. Hussain and Miller (2006) conclude that Scotland is more confident about retaining its unique national identity and family ties.

Islamophobia indicators	Islamophobia in Scotland	Islamophobia in England
Take jobs	30	46
Not really committed	53	62
More loyal to own	79	86
Scotland (England) lose identity if more Muslims come	52	69
Unhappy for relative to marry a Muslim	32	52
Average: Strictly comparable indicators	49	63
Muslims not done a great deal to condemn terror	55	63

Table 3: Islamophobia in England and Scotland (Hussain and Miller, 2006)

In a similar way, Bambery (2014) explains that, since 9/11, Islamophobia has become the main subject of both politicians and media. The politics of exclusion has returned to Europe including, the banning of the *Burqa*, and the construction of minarets. Furthermore, Bambery (2014) uses the term *Clash of Civilizations* to describe the new tension between the enlightened Europe and the Islamic world. According to Bambery (2014) Muslims have been subjugated to several ways of Islamophobia including targeting individuals, vandalism, and others. Like Hussain and Miller (2006), Bambery (2014) explains that there is a divergence between the level of Islamophobia in both Scotland and England. Bambery (2014) supports his ideas by mentioning an incident of a soldier has been killed by two men claiming to be Muslims in 2013. This event caused Hate crimes against Muslims to rise in England while there were no reports of hate crimes in Scotland. Moreover, Bambery (2014) refers to a survey, conducted in 2005, that inquires if Muslims are loyal to Scotland, about 46% of the participants agreed. Both Muslims and non- Muslims believe that integration is easier in Scotland than in England “‘Scottishness’ was identified with friendliness, sociability and having a welcoming disposition” (Bambery, 2014, p. 314). This does not mean that there are no negative attitudes towards Muslims. Some believe that Muslims cannot be integrated into Scottish life because they do not drink alcohol, others believe that the presence of Muslims may influence the Scottish identity.

Hussain and Miller (2006, p. 46) explain “The genuinely inclusive nationalism of the Scottish political elite may not apply down ‘at street level’”. At street level means at the public level. There are multiple examples of Islamophobia in Scotland. For example, in 2013, The

Scotsman reported that Muslim women's Hijabs (headscarves) were torn off by one teenager and a child. The event took place at Wester Hails Park in Edinburgh (Scotsman, 2013). The Islamophobic acts might be a result of events like 9/11, for example, Bambery (2014, p.315) mentions that a young man from Glasgow explains that although he does not like to judge people according to their religion or race, the event of the terrorist attacks made him change his mind about Muslims.

A report about the level of Islamophobia in Scotland published by Holyrood in 2020. Clegg (2019) shows that a third of Muslims in Scotland experience Islamophobia daily. The public inquiry was launched by *the Scottish Parliament Cross Party on Islamophobia* in cooperation with the *University of Newcastle* and show that around 83 percent of Scottish Muslims said that they experience Islamophobia either in public or online. 344 Muslims out of 435 participants submitted their responses. The report shows that the attention was directed towards women who wear hijab and how they were subjected to public abuse. Another question was raised in the inquiry about the impact of media on the rise of Islamophobia. 90 percent of the participants said that Newspapers make it worst, while 86 believe that TV and Radio do the same thing.

Children and youth also expressed their concerns to live in a society where they will be marked as outsiders (Holyrood, 2020). Anas Sarwar, the leader of the Scottish labour party, expresses his concerns about the results of the inquiry by insisting that a lot of work must be done to end racism and Islamophobia "These findings will be used in the next stage of the inquiry, in which we must redouble efforts to challenge and overcome hatred and prejudice" (Holyrood, 2020, no page). Hopkins, who analysed the results of the inquiry, shared the same concern "There is a lot of work to do - across many different sectors - in order to address the problem of Islamophobia in contemporary Scotland." (Holyrood, 2020, no page). The following section discusses Islamophobia from a gendered-specific perspective by exploring the concept of gendered Islamophobia in Scotland.

3.4.2.4 Gendered Islamophobia in Scotland:

The term gendered Islamophobia is defined by Zine (2006) as specific form of ethnic-religious and racialized discrimination directed towards Muslim women. It is formed by historically and contextually stereotypes that create individual and systematic forms of oppression. The discourse roots of gendered Islamophobia are established through the oriental representations that consider Muslim women as backwards, oppressed and victims of misogynist societies (Said, 1979; Hoodfar, 1993). These representations are used to justify the imperial domination over colonized Muslims through the emancipatory effect that European hegemony was expected to grant to the Muslim women (Zine, 2006; Mustafa, 2020). Zine (2006) asserts that these political representations cause material consequences for Muslim girls and women. Muslim women are both hyper-visible but simultaneously invisible. Their bodies, their clothing and religious attire have become a political battleground in Europe. Anti-Muslim legislation has severely affected how they live their daily lives, as evidenced in their collective experience of gendered Islamophobia (Mustafa, 2020).

There are numerous studies that dealt with the impact of gendered Islamophobia on Muslim women. For instance, Parker-Jenkins (1999) shows that Muslim women who wear hijab suffer discrimination at workplace. In addition, Smith (2002) identifies significant barriers to Muslim women accessing jobs in Toronto. In Scotland, various studies have been conducted

on gendered Islamophobia. For instance, Sarwar (2019) reports that approximately two-thirds of Muslim women in Scotland have witnessed a hate incident or crime. Among the incidents reported, those that are directly related to wearing the Hijab. “Asked about the nature of the incident, 78% said it involved shouting and swearing. Women said they had their hijab pulled off, were spat at, and women born here were told to ‘go back to where you came from’” Sarwar (2019, no page). In addition, Finlay and Hopkins (2019) investigate young Muslim women’s political participation in Scotland through exploring the intersection of gender, religion, class, and place that shape the political participation of Muslim women in Scotland.

This section discussed the concept of Islamophobia which is linked to the presence of the religious attire in the Western context. It gave different definitions and views regarding Islamophobia, its type, its dangers, and results. Besides, it focused on various data on Islamophobia from the UK and Global context using India and Canada as examples. Finally, it provided an insight of its existence in the Scottish society through providing some data from previous works. The next section tackles another important topic when discussing the term Hijab, which is secularism in Scotland.

3.5. Secularism and Islam in Scotland:

Researching the Islamic practice of veiling in a western society calls for examining the nature of the context. The nature of the context means the religious, social, and political spheres. The Scottish society is becoming widely secular. According ²⁰ to the 2022 census, most people in Scotland report that they do not belong to any religion “the first-time secular attitudes have overtaken religious identity” (Carrell, 2024, no page). Bruce (2014) believes that the reason for this secularization²¹ is religious pluralism. Consequently, it is crucial to define the term Secularism to understand how things operate in the Scottish context. This section will deal with three major themes: The meaning of secularism, The contention between religion and secularism in Europe, the secularization of Scotland and Scottish Muslims views regarding secularism.

3.5.1. Definitional Approaches to Secularism:

Secularism has different definitions. Zuckerman (2017, p.7) explains that secularism can signify “unorthodoxy, blasphemy, apostasy, irreligion, religious criticism, agnosticism, atheism, naturalism, earth-centred-isms, humanism (and trans and post-humanism), rationalism, scepticism, scientism, modernism, human rights causes, liberalism, and different kinds of church-state separation all around the world”. Furthermore, what makes the term relevant is the growth of irreligion and secularity in most regions. It was first introduced in the mid-19th century in England by an English teacher, writer, and Editor George Jacob Holyoake. It is an opposing stance against churchly and spiritual matters and degradation to worldly and materialistic ways. Holyoake (1896) debates the preference of the term secularism over atheism. Secularism better defines his understanding of the world because it is larger than atheism. “Secularism is peculiarly the work we have always had in hand which is Larger than atheism and includes it” (Zuckerman, 2017, p.3). George Cooper explains that Holyoake has rejected the term atheism because it carries a negative connotation of disowning principles along with religion; it has a combative stance against religion (Cited in Zuckerman (2017). Thus, Holyoake’s definition of secularism is as follow:

Secularism is a code of duty pertaining to this life, founded on considerations purely human, and intended mainly for those who find theology indefinite or inadequate, unreliable or unbelievable. Its essential principles are three: (1) the improvement of this life by material means. (2) That science is the available Providence of man. (3) That it is good to do good. Whether there be other good or not, the good of the present life is good, and it is good to seek that good (1896, p.41)

In addition to Holyoake's definition that gives a positive understanding of secularism, multiple scholars give their opinion regarding secularism. Some of them propose that it is a separation between the state and the government. Jacques Berlinerblau defines it as "a political philosophy, which, at its core, is preoccupied with, and often deeply suspicious of, any relations between government and religion" (2012, p. xvi). Others view it from a different angle. They relate it to atheism by explaining that it means being sceptical about the existence of any God, deity, or divine powers. Kitcher, for instance, believes that "Secularism claims that there are no supernatural entities" and it entails the expression of doubt in the existence of "deities, divinities, spirits ghosts, and ancestors ... and the supernatural forces to which the world's various religions, past and present, make their varied appeals" (2011, p.24).

Secularism is adopted by multiple Western societies that seek to exclude religion from public and civic affairs, thus limiting it to private and personal matters. It is considered as a constructive sign of both modernity and democracy that characterize most Western societies. Additionally, it is a way of ensuring tolerance in societies that are globalized and multicultural (Custers, 2006). The West has a history full of conflict between religion and state. It started when Constantine legalized Christianity. The term secular has its origin in the Latin language as "*Saecularis*," which means age or generation, yet now it is approached from different angles. Europeans approach this term from different angles such as "Differentiation, hierarchization, and privatization" (Caraballo-Resto, 2010, p.151). differentiation suggests that secularism attempts to construct a society where both religion and politics need to operate separately. hierarchisation is the idea that secularism is the imposition of the state's power on religion and privatization in which secularism is defined as the act of privatizing religion, which means that religion becomes a private matter that cannot be practiced publicly.

As previously mentioned, secularism does not always have a positive connotation and can be destructive sometimes. It is mostly accepted in a context in which its majority are non-religious. In contrast, it would be challenging to adapt secularism in a country with a religious majority (Caraballo-Resto, 2010). Therefore, secularism has various meanings depending on the cultural, historical, ethical, and religious contexts (Asad, 2003)

3.5.2. The Secularization of Scotland:

3.5.2.1. A History of Divisions and Religious Pluralism:

it is important to understand how the concepts of religion, secularism, and secularization operate in the Scottish society. Bruce (2014), in an article which discusses Secularism in Scotland and the reasons for its secularization, finds that the history of religion in Scotland is interesting because of the link between Secularism and secularization. Converting a country to a secular one is called Secularization; it is common for modern industrial and liberal

countries like the United States of America (Voas and Chaves, 2016). Bruce (2014) explains that Scotland's case is intriguing for two reasons. Firstly, the Scottish government was reluctant to pursue a secular provision for social areas (education and social welfare). However, religious pluralism is one factor in Secularizing Scotland. Secondly, the fact that migration helped in the growth of religious pluralism. Besides, Religious pluralism was pre-1900 and resulted in schisms (church divisions) to purify the Church. Bruce (2014) adds that besides religious fragmentations, religious orthodoxy had ironically helped in the drift to religious voluntarism and the extension of a secular public sphere. Furthermore, Bruce (2014, p.194) states three causes of secularizations, which are the changes in "general culture, social institutions, and social psychology". One of the causes is the change in general culture and the introduction of technology, which led people to have more agency over and develop a sense of mastery over the fate (Martin, 1978). People start to use science and knowledge to find solutions for early problems, which led to a reduction in interest in religion. Bruce (2014) states examples of the Church's responses. In the 14th century, Church responded to the black plague by fasting and praying. However, in the 1980s it responded to HIV/AIDS by investing in medicines and scientific research, which gives power to science and knowledge. Besides, what weakens the position of the world-oriented religions are: the growth of egalitarianism and individualism, the spread of literacy, and the improvement in health and life expectancy (Bruce, 2014).

Scotland witnessed a history of factionalism and schisms at the kirk (Scottish Church), it endured a reformation movement. Catholicism existed at small percentages in places like Moray, Aberdeenshire, Western highlands, and Islands, however the most modern parts of the country converted to Protestantism. The Presbyterian Church conflicted with the Scottish Episcopal Church (Protestant in doctrine yet has a catholic structure that is like that of England). The Presbyterian Church ended up winning over. There was also another conflict between the kirk and the extremist Presbyterians (covenanters) because the latter thought that the national church was not close enough to be the right God-pleasing church and rejected the issues of the imposition of religion by the state. In 1733, Ebenezer Erskine decided to split from the Church of Scotland and establish The Secession Church. The Secession church split later into various fractions (Burghers and Anti-Burghers). There was another split in these fractions as well. The second century knew the re-union of Presbyterian. The re-union shows a tolerance between the different schisms. The Church of Scotland became the national church, but this does not mean that other churches (Free Church, Presbyterian, Episcopal) ceased to exist. Catholicism grew from 6600 Roman Catholics in 1780 to 800,000 according to the 2001 census.

3.5.2.2. Secularism, Migration and Religious Pluralism in Scotland:

Religious Pluralism in Scotland was not the result of church schisms only. Migration was also a reason for such diversity. Bruce (2014) mentions that migrants become more connected to their religions because their religious institutions play a vital role in battling minority stress. Meyer (1995); Mirowsky and Ross (1989), and Pearlin (1999) believe that minority stress develops from social and psychological theoretical orientations. It is viewed as a conflict between the social environment (the dominant values) and the minority group members that develop minority stress. One example of the effect of migration in secularising the Scottish society is the Irish migration. The early Irish migration was the result of the great famine of 1846-47, census of 1841 shows that about 4.8% of the Irish-born population were in Scotland

(John Gray Centre, 2014). This migration added to religious pluralism and asserted the role of the Catholic Church. Bruce (2014) states that the Catholic Church played a significant role in the lives of the early Irish population; its language and rituals were familiar to them. Being faithful to the Catholic Church functioned as a cultural defence to remain loyal to their national and ethnic identity. Being in a multi-cultural and multi-faith place like Scotland, religion plays a crucial role in maintaining religious and cultural identity. John Bird and Grace Davie (1994) believe that religious identity provides immigrants with a sense of belonging and cultural identity. Bird suggests five reasons for maintaining religiosity by minority groups 1- Immigrants belong to less- secular countries where religion is essential. 2- The great attachment to their religion provides them with a sense of community and cultural identity. 3- Maintaining traditions. 4- Religious socialization: Children come under pressure to maintain their parent's religion. 5- Religion provides a way to deal with oppression.

Bruce (2014) also explains that Scots nowadays have minimal understanding of Christianity. Sunday schools replaced religious instructions with philosophical reflections on the nature of different religions. Moreover, religion becomes restricted to some groups (including immigrants). According to Bruce (2014), the carriers of religion in Scotland are: 1- Elderly women: most of the church congregations are old and female. 2- The inhabitants of rural peripheries: the Gaelic speakers of the western isles and highlands (Calvinists). 3- Poles: Polish migrants to Scotland helped in the increase of the church attendance and in major cities most of the priests are Polish. 4- West Africans: Black Africans attend Pentecostal churches. 5- Muslims: The recent change is the growth of a Muslim community, and which led in Scotland being more religious and there is no exact number of Scots that convert to Islam.

Bruce (2014) adds that Scotland now is a secular government that masks its change with the respect it shows to religious leaders and organizations. The religious decline may lead to division among the population. Early secularization did not result in a lack of interest in religious knowledge compared to the recent one. People at the time were still attached to the Christian faith. However, the recent secularization contains a division between religious people and those who are not. Consequently, if secularization operates in an opposite term, non-religious people are going to be converted. Furthermore, Scotland's case is doubtful because Religion is not carried by Scottish people themselves but by a demographically and ethnically distinct population (Bruce, 2014).

3.5.3. Is Islam Compatible with Secularism?

In his Article *Europe, Islam, and Radical secularism*, Friedman (2016) explains that Europe witnessed a history of conflicts between Christianity and Islam that started from Early Muslim conquests in the 8th century to the European crusades in the 12th, 13th centuries and continues to the 19th and 20th century. Post-second world war, Europe followed a secular orientation, and the conflict between Christians and Muslims transforms into a conflict between Muslims and European secularists. Europe accepts the principles of the French enlightenment, which supports the idea that religion is a private matter.

The main religion in Europe was Christianity, but after secularism, many Christians decide to express their religious matters privately with keeping the neutrality of the public sphere. Muslims cannot follow what Friedman (2016) refers to as *hedonism*, which signifies the private life as a realm of pleasure for secularists because the personal discipline they follow in their private life must be followed in public life as well. Muslims consider secularism as a

way of life that is alien and unbearable. Like Friedman (2016), Gole (2017) seeks to find a bridge between the religious and the secular by dealing with debates that developed from issues like Prayer, Sharia laws, building mosques, and wearing the Islamic veil in public spheres. Besides, Gole (2017) suggests what makes secularists uncomfortable is the public visibility of Muslims, although it is a positive sign of their integration into European society.

The question of integrating Muslims in a secular society was also raised in an interview with Talal Asad (2015). In an interview *Do Muslims belong in the West?* Conducted by Hazan Azad (2015) with Talal Asad, the former asked Asad “Do Muslims belong to the west”? And if “Muslims as Muslims cannot be represented in Europe.” Asad (2015) explains that 90 % of the time when people talk about the problems of Muslims, they always refer to the fact that Muslims cannot be integrated into a secular society. It is either that they must try hard to integrate or it is their fault that they cannot integrate. Muslims are bound with illiberal religion that does not go hand in hand with the secular, egalitarian society. The issue is always the challenge of assimilating Muslims into Europe.

Scottish Muslims opinions about, secularism, Islam, and Muslim religious practices in Scotland (Specifically in Dundee), has been raised by Caraballo-Resto (2010). Caraballo-Resto (2010) attempts to understand the connotation and the rhetoric that Scottish Muslims living in Dundee held about the concept of Secularism. Caraballo-Resto conducted his study before the 2011 census. The statistics illustrate that there were around 42,521 Muslims in Dundee, however some estimate that their number was about 60,000 Muslims.

Pakistani Muslims are the largest Muslim ethnic group in the region. Dundee has different Islamic spaces, including three mosques, five prayer rooms, *Al Maktoum institute*, An Arabic School for children, three Quranic schools, and several halal butchers. Muslims in Dundee follow different doctrines. Most of them follow a Sunni school. Some groups are more restricted than others in terms of stating Islamic laws. Caraballo-Resto (2010) mentions a mosque in Dundee that follows a doctrine called *Minhaj Al Quran*. *Minhaj al Quran* follows a progressive approach towards religion. They believe in Ijtihad in religion rather than accepting traditional interpretations. In other words, they believe in finding alternatives for Islamic laws that suit the modern world. This approach makes them in conflict with other Muslim groups. Caraballo (2010) has interviewed the first generation of Muslims in Dundee to figure out their opinions about secularism and concludes that Muslims there have a negative connotation towards the term secularism.

Since there is no exact equivalent to the term Secularism in Arabic, the informants refer to the term as “*Ilhad* “atheism” or *Alamaniyah* “the process of separating the worldly and the divine. Pakistani refers to secularism as *Ladiyanat* (the earthly). Furthermore, Caraballo-Resto (2010) states that the reason for the different meanings is because Muslim majority cultures lack the blazing ruptures, which took place between Europe and Christianity during the 16th century. They see secularism from three views: 1- as being opposed to Islam and if Islam exists along with secularism than it is corrupted. 2- They consider Secularism as an attitude that abolish and neglect the existence of God, prophet-hood, and revelation. 3- It considers Islam as a part of Muslims’ private life while neglecting its importance in society and politics.

Caraballo-Resto (2010) explains that some participants have extended the term secularism to be *Kufr* (disbelief). The analogy between *Kufr* and secularism lay in the fact that both are

considered as the conscious decision to refuse god's message. Many sociologists believe that secularism as a sign of modernity is related to the decline in religiosity (Weber, 1958 and Bruce, 2014). In contrast, the 1st generation of Muslims in the case study contradicts this opinion and believe that "One can live in modernity, sustain democratic political systems, live in pluralistic society and still consider religion to be a social religion of great important" (Caraballo-Resto, 2010, p. 156). Islam and politics cannot be a separate entity for Muslims because the prophet Muhammed peace be upon him was both a prophet and political leader. As a result, it is challenging to separate religion from politics or public sphere. Allah's instructions cannot be ignored and whatever bad for Muslims is what Allah and Prophet Mohammed peace be upon him considers as Haram (wrong). Islam for Muslims is not a mere religion, it is *Deen* (a complete code of life). Some participants referred to Muslims who follow secularism as hypocrites because it is an act of apostasy.

Caraballo (2010) reveals that Muslims try to live in harmony in the secular environment of Dundee. They consider that the life around them is corrupted, however they and non-Muslims live together and produce a sense of a community. Although there is a tension between Islam and Secularism, Muslims in Dundee does not perceive themselves as a segregated group. They express that they do not have to follow a secular lifestyle to be integrated. Instead, they follow an Islamic system of order and discipline using both Quran, Sunnah and through the act of filtering.

3.5.4. The Rise of Secularism in Scotland According to the 2022 Census:

Secularism is on a rise in Scotland according to Census 2022 (Cook, 2024). The respondents identified with no religion emerged from "36,75 to 51,1%" (Cook, 2024, no page) between Census 2011 and Census 2022. This increase in the percentage is due to the decline of the followers of the Church of Scotland and the Roman Catholic Faith. On the other hand, the followers of the Islamic faith raised by "43,100 to 119,872", which makes 2,2% from the overall population (Muslim Council of Britain, 2024, no page). The rise of secularism in Scotland can be positive or negative to many people (Caraballo-Resto, 2010), however it is important for the government to follow the type of secularism that does not prohibit the visibility of the religious symbols including the Hijab in public. Zucca (2012) identified two types of secularism, positive and negative.

The negative secularism is defined in opposition to religion. It establishes a separate domain for religion and one for secular politics. In other words, it is when a secular state free itself from one dominant religion. An historical example is when the French state had to distance itself from the catholic church in "1905" (Zucca, 2012, p.143), which shaped what is known as "*Laïcité*" (Roy, 2009, p.22). However, today, *Laïcité* comes to represent restricting religion in any place in public sphere and securing its liberty only in private sphere. Opposite to negative secularism, positive secularism is not defined in opposition to religion. It does not signify the separation of the church and the state nor the privatization of religion. In fact, this type of secularism seeks to protect and promote diversity "its point is not to deny the place of religion in the public sphere, but to promote diversity of worldviews" (Stepan and Taylor, 2014 cited in Zucca, 2012, p.142). Distinguishing between the types is important specifically to the rights of people to wear the Hijab in public.

In conclusion, this section covers three main point. Firstly, it deals with the various definitions of the term secularism that differ from one scholar to another. Secularism has both

a negative and a positive connotation, which depends mostly on the context. Most religious countries view it as a standing against the existence and the principles of God, while non-religious countries view it mostly as something positive. Secondly, this section addressed the standpoints of Muslims regarding a secular society. Most of the Muslims in Europe view it as something negative because they cannot separate religion from their public life. They have different religious practices that cannot be practiced in private only including the practice of veiling. At last, the third theme that was covered in this part is the secularization of Scotland and the viewpoints of Muslims regarding the meaning of a secular society. As previously mentioned, Muslims in Dundee have a negative perception towards Secularism. Besides, they try to engage in their society through the act of filtering their daily relationships from what they believe is corrupted. The last part discusses the rise of secularism in Scotland according to census 2022.

3.6. Conclusion:

This chapter was dedicated to the reviewing of the existing literature. It started by providing a historical and religious background of the concept of veiling focusing on its origin in the Assyrian code of laws and its references and interpretations in the three Abrahamic religions, namely Judaism, Christianity, and Islam. The section on Hijab in Islam presented traditionalist and feminist interpretations regarding the obligation of wearing the Hijab. The next section provides a crucial concept when discussing Hijab in a Western context, which is Islamophobia. It represented the meanings and features of Islamophobia, its consequences. In addition, it provided some examples of Islamophobic incidences and statistics in the world focusing mainly on Scotland. Additionally, it discusses the concept of gendered Islamophobia and provides some scholarly studies that have been produced on it. The last section represented another important concept, which is secularism in Scotland. It defines it and provide some opinions around it and tackles its relation to the religious visible identity in public, which is in this case the hijab.

4. Chapter Four: Theoretical Framework

4.1. Introduction:

This chapter outlines the theoretical framework of this PhD study. It introduces the theories, namely feminist standpoint theory (Harding, 2009), intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989; Collins, 1990), and the matrix of gendered Islamophobia (Alimahomed-Wilson, 2020) in relation to the lived experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland. These theories offer important critical lenses. For example, feminist standpoint theory is used to give Muslim women chances to share their knowledge from their own standpoints. Using it together with intersectionality and the matrix of Islamophobia allows for an investigation of the intersectional elements that influence their experiences. Therefore, this chapter discusses the definition and the importance of feminist standpoint theory and explains the significance of adopting this theory by using its major key concepts such as epistemic advantage, situated knowledge, and double consciousness as useful tools in understanding and analysing the findings. Moreover, it considers the intersectional approach, which is introduced by Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989), as an additional framework to help understand the experiences of Hijabi Muslim women in Scotland. Finally, it introduces the theory of the matrix of gendered Islamophobia (Alimahomed-Wilson, 2020) that is inspired by Collin's theory of the matrix of domination (2006), and how it is going to contribute to understanding the different challenges, which Hijabi Muslim women face due to the intersection of various identity categories.

4.2. Feminist Standpoint Theory, Intersectionality, and the Matrix of Domination:

Ardiner (2014) demonstrates that feminist theory falls under the umbrella of critical theory, which has the purpose of dismantling systems of power and oppression. Moreover, it has its roots in Marxist and socialist theories, especially that of Engels (Burton, 2014). Furthermore, it provides a lens through which to examine how people interact within a system and find solutions to face these oppressive structures. Feminist theory does not only focus on the lived experiences of women, but it also considers the lived experiences of the oppressed more broadly (Ardiner, 2014). Additionally, feminist theory is informed by the concepts of "gender discrimination, social institutional, political factors influencing women's position in a society: oppression and inequality of women; hegemony and patriarchy" as mentioned in Grant and Oslanoo (2014, p. 22). Feminist theory is more interested in unravelling and deconstructing systems of power, and this is one particular purpose of feminist standpoint theory.

Feminist standpoint theory informs the examination and understanding of the experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland in the context of their social positions by giving them the chance to express their perspectives on wearing hijab. Applying Feminist standpoint theory (Harding, 2004) as a lens provides a practical tool to examine and value the position of the marginalised because of the priority it gives to the position of the marginalised as informed, accurate and representative. Harding (2012) argues that feminist standpoint theory focuses on the importance of the daily experiences of women and how their social understanding is shaped by different structures. In addition, Swingonski (1994) defines a standpoint as a social position that one can see things more clearly than others can. A standpoint emerges from the person's social position relating to their gender, culture, race, ethnicity, class, and sexual orientation and the way these factors intersect to affect their/her

everyday experience. Hence, this theory is particularly important for this study because it focuses on daily realities of the marginalised and oppressed (Swingonski, 1993).

Intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989; Collins 1990) and the matrix of domination (Collins, 2006) are useful in examining how the structures of power may influence hijabi women experiences in a western context like Scotland. The dominant contexts tend to have certain stereotypical images about Muslim women who wear Hijab. Cloud (2004) points out that many Americans believe veiled women are often used to symbolise the oppression of women in various Muslim cultures and justify that these cultures need to be 'saved'. Similarly, EL Guindi (1999) and Steet (2000) explain that images of covered women have often been associated with the 'backwardness' or 'barbarism' of Muslim societies. Likewise, Bilge (2010) states that the figure of veiled Muslim woman has been paradoxically portrayed both as passive of her oppressive patriarchal culture/religion and as an active 'threat' to western modernity and freedom.

4.2.1. Feminist Standpoint Theory:

This section provides the significance of using feminist standpoint theory in studies that deal with Muslim women and veiling. In addition, it explains and defines each of the important concepts that relate to feminist standpoint theory and how they will be practical tools to help examine the experiences of Muslim women who wear hijab in Scotland.

Standpoint theories suggest that the perspectives of the subordinated social groups are epistemologically advantaged vis-à-vis politically challenging issues that are related to their marginalisation (Anderson, 2000). This theory has multiple uses through different fields of social science. Harding (2009) points out that standpoint theory is considered as a logic of inquiry and a transdisciplinary ideal that is broadly applied in research projects that focus on race, sexuality, class, as well as studies in post-colonial research. Traditionally, standpoint theories focus on these important points. First, it claims that the position of the subordinated is advantageous and superior in exploring the social regularities. Secondly, it can be used to identify the social arrangements that are contingent and capable of change through concrete actions, and, thirdly, it represents the world through universal human interests (Anderson, 2000). On the other hand, standpoint theory claims that the position or standpoint of the dominant parties shows only the surface level of social regularities that are related to their ruling interests. Therefore, they are redeemed and accepted as 'natural,' 'universal' and 'necessary' (Anderson, 2000, no page).

Different theorists have developed different standpoint theories such as Marxism (proletariat) standpoint theory, indigenous standpoint theory (Nakata, 1998) and, feminist standpoint theory (Hartsock, 1983; Smith, 1999; Collins, 1990; Harding, 1991). The current study utilises feminist standpoint theory to examine the standpoints and the experiences of twenty Muslim women who wear the Hijab in Scotland. Various works (Droogsma, 2007 and Marzouk, 2021) used feminist standpoint theory to understand the experiences of Muslim women and their standpoints in relation to veiling.

Feminist standpoint theory is particularly important in the study of women and people of the marginalised positions in society. Multiple researchers argue the importance of approaching research on minorities using feminist standpoint theory as a theoretical lens to understand meaning, experience and lived realities. Bilic (2012), for instance, argues for its significance

as an extremely useful approach from which to commence theorising about women's lives. In her study, Bilic (2012) uses standpoint theory as a theoretical framework to analyse the problems of minority culture women from Liberia and Afghanistan in South Australia. Furthermore, Bilic (2012) uses three principal elements in her analysis namely, strong objectivity, double consciousness and heterogeneous experiences. Strong Objectivity explains that women as knowers produce a more objective account of reality. This can help in unravelling the multiple oppressions that women of minority cultures suffer from in a multicultural society like Southern Australia. Moreover, Bilic (2012) adopts double consciousness to analyse how women develop double perspectives that include both their views and the dominant culture. Both Afghan and Liberian women adopt this strategy to cope with their gender role in their countries and to secure their lives in diasporas. Bilic (2012) also argues that women have heterogeneous experiences which is recognised by standpoint theory. Standpoint theorists emphasise that knowledge should start from women's lives including recognising and appreciating the diversity therein (Harding, 1991). Difference is a vital component in studying women's standpoints. For instance, Collins (2000) argues for a Black feminist standpoint and explains that there is no such a thing as a homogenous Black women's standpoint. However, Black women may share some collective and political issues in common and refers to the concept as Black women's collective standpoint "there are themes or core issues that all Black women can recognise and integrate into their self-identity" (Collins 2000, p.26).

Like Bilic (2012), Pence (1996) uses Smith's (1987) standpoint approach to assess how safe assaulted or battered women feel after reporting their abuse to the police. Smith's (1987) point is not to assess how individual workers perform their duties, but how the institution is placed to manage domestic violence and the safety of the victim after reporting such crimes to the police. Pence (1996) suggests that although the judicial procedures are more successful in bringing the abusers to justice, they are less successful in providing safety for the victims after their initial reports. She suggests a "method of engaging criminal justice professionals and community advocates in an investigation of local criminal justice settings with the intent of making changes in practices which fail to attend to the safety needs of women who are battered" (Pence, 1996, p.190).

Likewise, Therese et al., (2014) apply feminist standpoint as a conceptual/theoretical framework to investigate how single mothers in the United States, especially women of colour, face the risk of homelessness. They conduct a study with eleven participants who have had repetitive episodes with homelessness. Therese (2014) concludes that on the one hand, political and ideological arguments tend to attribute homelessness of young mothers to their supposed lack of motivation and poor life choices. On the other hand, the research's findings and the participants' experiences indicate that the recurrent episodes of homelessness are due to varied factors including poor quality housing, rental hikes, sales of homes, abuse and people entering and leaving rentals. By using feminist standpoint theory, the results of this research challenge the stigmatising beliefs and portrayals about homeless women being neglectful mothers and unwilling to be employed. Feminist standpoint theory is a useful tool to examine the experiences of women of colour and marginalised populations. Among these marginalised populations and unheard voices are Muslim women who wear Hijab in Western societies.

Some studies conduct research on Muslim women and Hijab by using feminist standpoint theory as a theoretical framework. Marzouk (2021) applies feminist standpoint theory along with the choice of feminism theory to analyse the contextualization of Hijab in Quran and present the experiences of three Muslim women who wear the Hijab in America, namely Alia Alshammari, Nadeen Alostaz, and Yasmeen Sedeek. The results of study suggest that the stereotypes and inaccurate portrayals of Hijabi women in the West are the production of the lack of knowledge about Hijab in Western societies, which negatively affects Muhajabat's (women who wear the Hijab) lives. Furthermore, women who participated in the study show that Hijab is part of their faith, and they wear it to follow the commands of Quran. As such, they should have a total freedom to wear it in Western societies.

Likewise, Droogsma (2007) applies the feminist standpoint theory as a critical lens in his work, where American Muslim women redefine Hijab from their own standpoints. Droogsma (2007) further explains that even though powerful discourses and narratives try to define women on the margins, their cultural standpoints provide them with a greater understanding of their own experiences and the ways the dominant discourses portray them. The study was conducted with thirteen American veiled participants who share their experiences using this theory, their definitions of Hijab develop. Various themes emerge from Droogsma's (2007) study on the function of Hijab in their lives including, a marker of Muslim identity, a reminder of behaviour check, a resister of sexual objectification, a provider of respect, a preserver of intimate relationships, and a source of freedom.

This section discusses the major concepts of feminist standpoint theory and how they can be incorporated to analyse and understand Muslim women's experiences of wearing hijab in Scotland. Harding (1997) points out that feminist standpoint theory has made a significant contribution to feminist theory and has defined diverse ways through which to understand the production of knowledge in local and global economies. Although different scholars of feminist standpoint are from various disciplines, Gurung (2020) maintains that their major concern is insisting that people of marginalised groups occupy an advantaged position, and their perspectives are less partial than those of the dominant groups. In addition, this theory accounts for women's diverse perspectives and experiences as explained by Hawkesworth (1999). Feminist standpoint theory is guided by these major concepts.

4.2.1.1. Strong Objectivity:

The term "strong objectivity" is coined by Harding (1987) who argues for the importance of starting any inquiry from the experiences of women or those who have been left outside the institutions in which knowledge is generated and classified (Naples, 2007). By doing so, Naples (2007) argues that more objective and relevant knowledge can be produced. Similarly, Brooks (2011, p.11) demonstrates that women's subordinated status in society allows them to develop "double consciousness", which places them in a unique position to produce an accurate, comprehensive, and objective interpretation of social reality. Jaggar (2000, p. 56-57) and Harding (1991) mention that women's "distinctive social position" renders possible "a view of the world that is more reliable and less distorted" than that of the dominant group or of men. The interests and the values of the ruling class are enhanced by hiding ways in which they exploit the dominated group (Brooks, 2011) and how they rule the prevailing reality in any given society. Therefore, "suffering of the subordinated classes will be ignored, re-described as enjoyment or justified as freely chosen, deserved or inevitable" (Jaggar, 2004,

p.56). Jaggar (2004) also asserts that women as an oppressed group are not inclined to misinterpret reality unlike men who, as a dominant group, have constructed distorted interpretations of reality to protect their male interests and to maintain power.

Brooks (2011) provides some useful examples of these standpoints. One of the examples is *Harriet Jacobs's* ²² standpoint on slavery. Brooks (2011) explains if examining the institution of slavery via Jacobs' eyes, a new interpretation of slavery may arise that is highly different from the contemporary explanation of slavery at that time. Brooks (2011) explains that slave owners built a paternalistic and subjugated image/discourse about the concept of slavery and the people who were slaves. They portrayed slaves as being helpless, weak-minded, and subhuman and the white masters were considered as 'caring fathers' who provide and take care of them. The same applies for slave women who were characterized as animal-like, hyper sexualized and needing to be tamed. *Harriet Jacobs'* account of slavery challenges the distorted accounts that were produced about slaves at that time through exposing the cruelty and brutal treatments of slaves by their masters.

Moreover, Brooks (2011) provides another example of Betty Friedan's (1963) *The Feminine Mystique*, which illustrates how women's marginalised position in society grant them the privilege to construct a more accurate knowledge of reality. Friedan (1963) studies the standpoints of American housewives and their portrayal as 'happy housewives' by the dominant ideologies and the media. In contrast to their portrayal, women were feeling unhappy, dissatisfied, and restricted by their roles, which make them challenge that discourse. Because of their feelings of disappointment, women could question the reality of the 'happy housewives' narrative and to build new knowledge that depend on their lived experiences.

There is a useful theoretical connection between research that examines the lives of slaves and housewives and research that seeks to examine the lives of Muslim women in Scotland who wear Hijab. The connection is a desire to discover more accurate knowledge on the topic and to find out how this can be achieved both theoretically and methodologically. Muslim women can provide new knowledge that might be different from how the dominant discourses tend to define and represent them. Droogsma (2007, p. 295) maintains that "while dominant conception of veiling assumes that Hijab functions to oppress women, women who wear veils can probably possess qualitatively different understanding of how hijab actually functions in their lives". Furthermore, Droogsma (2007, p. 295) argues that Muslim women possess what is referred to as "constrained agency". This concept suggests that although powerful discourses attempt to influence women's choices, women are never fully controlled by these discourses (Hallstein, 1999). Droogsma (2007) also suggests that while veiled women are currently defined by powerful discourses, there situated or located knowledge may be different from dominant conceptualisation. As a result, this concept is important for this study because it grants Muslim women who wear the veil the chance to share their experiences and views in relation to the practice of veiling.

4.2.1.2. Situated Knowledge:

Situated knowledge is a central tenet of feminist standpoint theory. According to Wylie (2013), knowledge is achieved from a specific social position, which is why social location influences, shapes, and limits our experiences and knowledge. When identifying three epistemological concepts that form the feminist standpoint theory, Wylie (2013) identifies two genres of situated knowledge theses. The first thesis is generic situated knowledge,

which demonstrates that the point of departure from standpoint theorising is the recognition that there is no “view from nowhere” (Wylie, 2013, p.61). This illustrates that the contingent histories, social contexts, and social relations influence the epistemic agent and form the hermeneutic resources, inferential heuristic, and various epistemic recourses that they generate as knowledge claims. The second thesis is a systematic situated knowledge, which differentiates standpoint theory from other epistemological theories. It mainly focuses on the epistemic effects of the systematic structures of social hierarchy. Further, Wylie (2013) believes that standpoint theorists are mainly interested in understanding what individuals know or how they know, often based on their location in a hierarchical system of power relations that creates their identity and epistemic capacity. Gurung (2017) demonstrates one example of the situated knowledge about Dalit women by illustrating that by starting an inquiry from their economic and social development of the nation, the researcher might gain knowledge that is different from common assumptions. By recognizing Dalit women’s situated knowledge, it means appreciating their experiences and voices. Harding (1992) asserts that knowledge is socially located, and some knowledge is more accurate because of its ability to challenge the assumptions of dominant scientific worldviews. The example of the Dalit women has a direct relation to veiled Muslim women’s case. Muslim women’s situated knowledge can offer an insight into their experiences, choices, and struggles in relation to wearing hijab in a western context. Droogsma (2007) explains that while dominant discourses attempt to define and restrict veiled women, their socially marginalised positions offer them a way to criticise the dominant discourses and to formulate their own standpoints based on the knowledge they gain in their everyday lives.

4.2.1.3. Epistemic Advantage:

This concept is one of the core concepts of feminist standpoint theory, which explains that women have an epistemic advantage because of their marginalisation. Intemann (2010) states that women have an epistemic privilege by virtue of being oppressed. Moreover, Intemann (2010) and Rolin (2006) suggest that not all women who have been marginalised or oppressed experience the same form of marginalisation because of social location, context, and history. All these factors impact experience, thus influencing their production of knowledge. Similarly, Wiley (2013) believes that standpoint theorists are more concerned with the types of the epistemic knowledge that may stem from those who are socially marginalised. This concept suggests that the dominant group has limited epistemic perceptions that focus mainly on their interests and values, whilst the marginalised group has a ‘double vision’, which includes both their views and the dominant group’s ideologies (Gurung, 2017). Naples and Gurr (2013) maintain that the dominant group has restricted vision due to the rejection of downward mobility and the ignorance of the work performed by other social classes.

Epistemic advantage is illustrated through the work of Martin et al., (2002) on federal judges which shows that female judges are more aware of gender inequality because of their gender location and how this can cause a negative experience. Furthermore, they are conscious about the cases of gender-bias and discrimination that they examine more than male judges, and this is due to the intersection of their social location, consciousness, observations, and experiences. In addition to Martin et al., (2002) and other scholars examine women who work in the legal system and their awareness of gender discrimination, like Shen (2020) who examines the experiences of women judges who judge women, a study that has been

conducted in China and Berger's et al., (2018) work on the integration of feminist theory in the legal system. Epistemic advantage serves as a tool to provide Muslim women who wear the veil with a chance to articulate their experiences. Joosub and Ebrahim (2020) investigates professional, personal, and feminist interpretations and experiences of wearing the hijab as a symbol of religious expression by two Muslim psychotherapists practicing in Johannesburg. The aim of this study is to privilege the interpretations that the two women develop to explain their standpoints in relation to the concept of hijab instead of the dominant assumptions about it. By privileging these personalized and situated interpretations, Joosub and Ebrahim (2020) demonstrates the need for questioning and resisting hegemonic representations of the hijab that have been appropriated by various international political and religious institutions for their own agendas, often to manipulate women's sense of agency. With Western societies banning the hijab and Islamist societies making it compulsory, the agency of the wearer of the hijab is undermined.

4.2.1.4. Power Relations:

In defining the previous terms, the term 'power relations' was mentioned several times. According to Gurung (2020), feminist standpoint theory considers power relations as a hindrance to knowledge production and access as "it urges feminists to reflect on relations of power as a distinctive kind of obstacle to the production of scientific knowledge" (Rolin, 2009, p.219). Harding (2004) asserts that the researcher needs to examine the position of the marginalized to understand how power relations function in society. Furthermore, the issue of power relations is insufficiently defined as a cognitive bias that a researcher has, it is more common as a social phenomenon that is aboriginal in the world of power relations (Rolin, 2009). Rolin (2009) explains that domination is not necessarily a part of power relations, these power relations may function as harmful means to hegemonies and dominate the choices of the marginalised groups and it can mobilise a range of inclinations that cause potential informants to conceal evidence. Like Rolin (2009), Harding and Norberg (2005) maintain that standpoint theory is crucial in feminist research because it takes into consideration the accounts of the powerless by reducing or minimising the power relations between the researcher and the researched.

4.2.1.5. Double Consciousness (The Outsider Within):

Du Bois (1903, no page) introduces the term 'double consciousness' or 'behind the veil' to refer to a peculiar condition that African American people experience. He suggests that those who live behind the veil have knowledge about their own lives, the functioning of the veil, and the activities of those who live on the other side of the veil, white people (Bhambra, 2015). Feminist standpoint theorists adopt this term to argue that women, as members of an oppressed group, have developed a double consciousness, which signifies a heightened awareness not only of their own lives but of the lives of the dominant group as well (Brooks, 2011). Similarly, Nielsen (1990, no page) maintains that women's daily activities that include cleaning the house, cooking, doing the laundry are invisible to the dominant group (men), while they are associated with "the dominant worldview of the society and their minority perspectives". Smith (1990) also explains that women are moderated between two worlds; the one that is oriented towards taking care of the household and the children and the male world of the marketplace, which she refers to as a world of rationality and abstraction. Furthermore, women, Nielson (1990) argues, develop double consciousness to protect themselves and

ensure their survival in a world that is dominated by men. To understand how men view their world, women need to be able to “read, predict, and understand the interests, motivations, expectations and attitudes of men” (Nielsen, 1990, p.10).

Brooks (2011) provides two different examples of double consciousness. The first account is that African Americans working in white people’s areas and required to get back to their areas and homes at the end of the day. *Bell Hooks* and her neighbours were seeking shelters in abandoned houses by the edge of the town because they were not allowed to stay in White people’s areas when finishing their work. Brooks (2011, p.10) explains, by doing so, *Bell Hooks*²³ and her neighbours develop “work consciousness” that permits them to understand the world from both their perspectives and white people’s. Hooks (2004), in her account, applies more to the issue of race rather than that of gender, nevertheless, Nielsen (1990) believes that there is a fundamental relationship between the two identities.

Given that African American people in North American culture are exposed to dominant white culture in school and through mass media as well as in interaction with whites, we can see how it is possible that blacks could know both white and black culture while whites know only their own. The same might be said for women vis-à-vis men (Neilson,1990, p.10).

Double consciousness is pivotal to understand social inequalities and injustices. Brooks (2011) contends that knowledge arising from women and marginalised groups can be applied to diagnose social inequalities and to find solutions for them. Moreover, this concept was introduced to this theory by the Black feminist Patricia Hill Collins under the concept of the “outsider within”²⁴ (Rogers, et al., 2010, p.1). Howell (2001) explains that Collins (1990) considers Black feminist academics as having double visions. On the one hand, is the position of the insider due to their occupation of a position of an authentic academic, which grants them some authority to understand how things work in the academy, on the other hand, is the position of the outsider who is marginalised because of the other issues like gender and race. The concept of double consciousness is helpful to understand how Muslim women who wear hijab develop strategies to cope and to fit within a western context as an outsider within.

4.3. The Intersectional Approach:

This section of the theoretical framework discusses the importance of acknowledging the differences among women by introducing Collin’s (1990) and Crenshaw’s (1989) theories of intersectionality and the matrix of domination. In addition, it explains the importance of adding such approaches of analysis to feminist standpoint theory to help examine the intersection of multiple identities that influence Hijabi Muslim women’s lived experiences. Although feminist standpoint theory provides a critical lens through which to examine the lived experiences of women and other marginalised groups, it concentrates more on issues of gender. Many scholars suggest that this theory serves the interests of white, middle class, heterosexual feminists. For instance, Stanley and Wise (1993) criticize some versions of feminist standpoint theory for not taking into consideration silenced feminist standpoints such as Black feminists and lesbian feminists. In a section entitled *Silenced Feminist Standpoints*, Wise and Sue (1990) assert the importance of recognising difference in feminist standpoint theory by explaining:

The writings of black feminists as of black liberationists before them centre the related ideas of wearing 'masks' to seem 'other than you are'— of disclosure to one's own but silence to others— and of passing. However, for feminists there are additional components – a recognition and valuing of 'difference', the centring of both 'black' and 'feminism', and knowledge as a shared process – within the development of a black feminist epistemology (Stanley and Wise, 1993, p.29).

The arguments of Stanley and Wise (1993) in terms of appreciating the difference in standpoints and acknowledging them can have a direct relation to the concept of veiling and feminism. Many white feminists tend to think of veiling as a tool of patriarchal oppression, which results in excluding the voices of Muslim women. Amer (2014) criticizes Euro-American feminists for neglecting veiled Muslim women's voices: "The battle veiled Muslim women are waging is not just to combat general societal presuppositions about the meaning of *hijab* and Islam but surprisingly also to challenge the views of some Euro-American feminists" (Amer, 2014, p.124). In addition, Amer (2014) points that the first wave of feminism fought for the right to shed corset and bras, to wear short skirts and pants and the idea of women who choose to wear clothes that are not compatible with the movement seem extraordinary. Likewise, Scott (2007) explains that some Euro-American feminists do not consider Muslim women equal partners in the feminist struggle. Further, El-Hibri (1994) writes an article under the title *Tear off your Western Veils* to criticize Western feminists for their inability to appreciate and hear from Muslim and Arab feminists because of the stereotypes that are firmly established in their minds and for not educating themselves about Islam. Muslim women, particularly veiled Muslim women, may have many different opinions from some white feminists concerning the veil and they may experience different oppressions. To fully understand these differences and oppressions, it is vital to adopt an intersectional approach.

4.3.1. Intersectionality, the Matrix of Domination, and the Matrix of Islamophobia:

Patricia Hills Collin introduces two important concepts to understand the diverse types of intersectional oppressions that Black women experience, black feminist epistemology and the matrix of domination (Collins, 1990). Collins (1990) introduces Black feminist standpoint epistemology, which argues that black women are situated in a position where two important forms of oppression are related, which are race and gender. Intersectionality is defined by Collins as "analysis claiming that systems of race, social class, gender, sexuality, ethnicity, nation, and age form mutually constructing features of social organization, which shape Black women's experiences and, in turn, are shaped by Black women" (2000, p.299). However, Hess Bieber (2012) explains Black feminist standpoint epistemology focuses mainly on the intersection of race and gender and neglects other social categories like ethnicity, nationality, social status as 'oppressive forces. It was not until the 1990s, when young feminists called for the inclusion of other social categories as race, ethnicity, and class, which contribute to women's oppression were fully appreciated (Dean and Aune, 2015). Crenshaw (1989) argues to include other social categories and introduced the concept of intersectionality. Intersectionality means the interaction between gender, race, class, social status, and other types of differences in individual lives, social practices, institutional arrangements, and cultural ideologies, and the results of these interactions in terms of power relations (Davis, 2008; Dill & Kohlman, 2012; Sang, 2016). This theory suggests that people experience disadvantages by multiple sources of oppression because of their identity markers

like race, sexuality, religion, gender identity, sexual orientation, and each identity marker is dependent of the other and have a mutual influence, for instance the category black and woman cannot exist independent of each other (YW Boston Blog, 2017). As a result, intersectionality provides a valuable tool to be universally applicable to understand different social practices as argued by Davis “intersectionality promises an almost universal applicability, useful for understanding and analysing any social practice, and any cultural configuration” (Davis, 2008, p.72).

Veiled Muslim women may experience multiple forms of oppression due to observing hijab as a religious or cultural social practice. Donegan (2020) explains that a headscarf acts as the “paradigm symbol” of intersectionality because Muslim women are discriminated against on the grounds of their religion, their sex, and their ethnicity in Europe. Furthermore, Donegan (2020) states that Muslim women who wear the veil are one example of individuals who face intersectional discrimination. Compared to Muslim men, Muslim women who cover do not only experience discrimination because of displaying their religious identity, their marginalisation is developed to include the category of gender (Donegan, 2020). In this case, two intersectional categories of oppression are experienced due to gender and religious manifestation. This is referred to as gendered Islamophobia, nevertheless, as per Donegan (2020) this gendered discrimination that is related to wearing a headscarf is shadowed and obscured: “As the Eurocentric perception of the headscarf denounces the garment as incongruent with the principles of gender equality, the disadvantage Muslim women experience *as women* is generally disregarded” (Donegan, 2020, p. 148). Like Donegan (2020), Halrynjo and Jonker (2015) discuss intersectionality in Hijab cases to examine the discrimination that women who wear hijab encounter in Scandinavia and the Netherlands. According to Halrynjo and Jonker (2015), Hijab cases are used as a paradigmatic symbol of intersectionality because wearing a headscarf affects Muslim women, not Muslim men, or non-Muslims. In addition, Halrynjo and Jonker (2015) state that there are studies that discuss hijab in the workplace as an example. They suggest that Hijab forms a barrier to getting a job (Syed and Pio,2010; Unkelbach et al,2010), and the fieldwork by Ghumman and Ryan (2013) shows that applicants who wear Hijab are less likely to be offered a job, compared to those who do not.

As previously mentioned, the term ‘Gendered Islamophobia’ is used to signify the intersection of gender, ethnicity, and religion to oppress Muslim women. This term was coined by Zine (2006) who defines it as a form of “ethno-religious and racialised discrimination levelled at Muslim women that proceed from historically contextualized negative stereotypes that inform individual and systematic forms of oppression” (2006, p.240). Following Zine (2006) and their definition of Islamophobia, Alimahomed-Wilson (2020) explains that there are numerous studies discussing Islamophobia against Muslims in Western countries, however they do not incorporate the analysis of gender as a central axis of oppression. In addition, Alimahomed-Wilson (2020) believes that “The conceptualisation of Islamophobia as a gender-neutral form of racism underestimates the centrality of gender as an ongoing, co-constitutive axis of power that structures Islamophobia” (2020, p. 649).

Using the intersectional approach, this study examines how social categories like gender, ethnicity and the manifestation of religious identity intersect together to influence the lived experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland. According to a recent article by Ashraf (2021, no page), Muslim women in Scotland from ethnic minority backgrounds face a

battle against prejudice compared to their Scottish counterparts because of the intersectionality of gender, religion, and racial barriers. Furthermore, this article shows that there is a public inquiry on Islamophobia, which was conducted in 2020, shows that “80” (Ashraf 2021, no page), percent of Muslims report that a member of friend or family has experienced Islamophobia. The form of Islamophobia that was mostly reported after verbal abuse is aggression such as pulling off women’s headscarves. A community group, *Al Masar*, based in Falkirk, has reported that one of the crucial factors that contribute in Islamophobic abuse is religious appearance (Ashraf, 2011). Many Muslim women stopped wearing their hijab to conceal their religious identity (Ashraf, 2021). To understand the various levels of intersectional discrimination that Muslim women who wear headscarves in Scotland may experience, it is important to use the ‘matrix of domination’ (Collins, 1990; 2006).

4.4.1.1 The Matrix of Domination and the Matrix of Islamophobia:

The matrix of domination, which is applied to the current study was first proposed by Patricia Hill Collins (1999). This theory offers an analytical approach through which to understand systems of oppression that are situated at the intersection of gender, race, class, and other social categories. According to Lintangog (2016), since its introduction, the matrix of domination, which resembles intersectionality, has been used as analytical tool to understand and empower marginalised groups such as trafficked people, disabled people, transgender people, indigenous people, and migrants. Scholars use them interchangeably because of their common aims in unravelling the cultures of oppression and in asserting differences among feminist projects (Lintangog, 2016). The ‘matrix’ refers to the overall organisation of power in society. It consists of four interrelated domains that organise different intersecting systems of oppressions: structural, disciplinary, hegemonic, and interpersonal (Collins, 2006). These domains are organised at the macro level, yet they may influence individuals at micro level (Alinia, 2015). According to Lintangog (2016), oppression is organised at the level of the structural domain, and it is managed by the disciplinary domain. The hegemonic or cultural domain focuses on justifying oppression against the marginalised groups. Lastly, the interpersonal domain suggests that the cultural ideology of the dominant group is embedded through the everyday lived experiences and the interactions of the marginalised group. Collins explains how these domains are interrelated:

Individual biographies are situated within all domains of power and reflect their interconnections and contradictions. Whereas the structural domain of power organizes the macro-level of social organization with the disciplinary domain managing its operations, the interpersonal domain functions through routine, day-to-day practices of how people treat one another (2000, p.287).

To examine the experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland, it is important to explain how these matrices of domination influence their everyday lives. It is, therefore, important to relate the theory of the matrix of domination to the concept of gendered Islamophobia. Alimahomed Wilson (2020) proposes an analytical framework that combines the two concepts to understand how various domains of power influence Muslim women. This analytical framework is the matrix of gendered Islamophobia. Firstly, there is the structural domain which examines institutionalised Islamophobia and reflects the exclusion and limitations imposed on Muslim women which leads them to unequal opportunities and outcomes in social institutions like labour, education, family, media, politics and legal

systems. Secondly, there is the disciplinary domain which concentrates on surveillance and the counter-terrorism security devices that controls and monitors, targets and implants a societal ethos of monitoring Muslims because of the assumption of terrorism by producing gendered strategies of counterterrorism. This domain has the power of encouraging Muslim women to accept their collective marginalised position within a society that discourages their agency to resist the inequalities they experience. Thirdly, the hegemonic or cultural domain of power, and this domain produces Islamophobic ideologies that justify the demonisation of Muslim women in mainstream western culture. These ideological justifications for Muslim women's subordination stems from the ability to control the images of Muslim women through media, for instance. Lastly, the interpersonal domain, which reflects the everyday experiences of Muslim women, is described as double-sword oppression that includes sexism in Muslim communities and gendered islamophobia in public spaces such as aggression and violence. Wherefore, this important analytical tool provides a new framework to analyse the cross-cutting domains of power that impact Muslim women's everyday lived experiences. Following Collins (2006) and Alimohamed-Wilson's (2020) theories, this study seeks to investigate how the different levels of the matrix of gendered Islamophobia influence Muslim women's lives experiences due to the intersection of various identity categories namely, gender, religious manifestation, ethnicity.

4.4. Conclusion:

This chapter was devoted to the discussion of the theories that are going to be used as lenses to understand and analyse the empirical findings. The use of these theories together is crucial because the feminist standpoint theory sets a ground for the researcher to analyse the opinions/ standpoints of the women in the study by peritonising their standpoints/ opinions and giving them a platform to share their lived experiences, while adding intersectional theories as supportive frameworks through which to go deeper and analyse the intersectional elements of identity that may define the experience of Hijabi Muslim women in Scotland. Therefore, this chapter was presented as the following, firstly, the chapter discussed the importance of analysing the experiences of Muslim women wearing hijab in Scotland using both feminist standpoint theory (Harding and Norberg, 2005) and intersectional theories (Crenshaw,1980; Collins,2006; Alimohamed-Wilson,2020). Secondly, the chapter proceeded to define, understand, and explain the importance of using feminist standpoint as a critical lens to examine the perspectives of Muslim women in relation to the practice of wearing hijab. As such, the chapter also provides the key concepts of the theory and their relationship to the subject of veiling. Finally, this chapter has outlined intersectional approaches, and the matrix of gendered Islamophobia, as additive critical lenses that will help in understanding the challenges that may face Hijabi Muslim women due to the intersection of identity categories that may contribute to their marginalization in Scottish society. The subsequent chapter deals with the methodology of this study. It compromises the various methods used in data collection and analysis.

5. Chapter five: Methodology Chapter:

5.1. Introduction:

This chapter focuses on the methodology of this study. Firstly, it discusses the research paradigm by identifying suitable philosophical grounds for this research. Secondly, it explains the justification of using qualitative research, which is the most suitable research approach to find the answer to the research question of this study. Thirdly, it provides the rationale for choosing interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA) as a method for collecting and analysing the data. It also sketches out the limitations of using IPA in conducting this research and explains how these limitations can be overcome. Furthermore, it addresses the ethical considerations and measures that were taken by the researcher to ensure this research was conducted ethically. Finally, it provides an overview of data collection and analysis.

5.2. Research paradigm:

This section illustrates the research paradigms, namely Guba's (1990) critical paradigm and Burrell and Morgan's (1979) interpretive paradigm, used in this study. Alase (2017) suggests the use of two paradigms when conducting interpretive phenomenological analysis research, namely (Smith et al, 2009) project: Guba's (1990) critical theory and Burrell and Morgan's (1979) interpretive paradigm. The critical paradigm originates from the works of various thinkers such as Marx, Horkheimer, Adorno, Marcuse, Enrich, Forman, Habermas, Friere and Foucault (Elshafie,2013). Critical theory aspires to emancipation despite the diversity among all the various thinkers "critical inquiry remains a form of praxis a search for knowledge, to be sure, but always emancipatory knowledge, knowledge in the context of action and the search for freedom." (Crotty, 1998, p. 159). Guba's (1990) critical paradigm is influenced by the ontology of historical criticism, which suggests that reality is constructed and shaped by social, economic, ethnic, gender cultural factors and that it exists outside the mind. Guba's critical paradigm will help in investigating the concept of power relations in the phenomenon under study, which is the Hijab in Scotland.

The other paradigm is Burrell and Morgan's interpretive paradigm (1979), which suggests that there are multiple complex realities (Grix, 2004). This paradigm is developed as an opposition to the positivist paradigm (Cohen, et al., 2007). The interpretive paradigm argues that the researcher needs to acknowledge the differences among humans as social actors (Saunders et al., 2009) and that social reality is shaped by individuals, which suggests that everyone can interpret it. The main argument among interpretivists is that the ontology of this paradigm is relativist ontology (Cohen, et., al 2007), which views the reality as an intersubjective construct through which the meanings and the understandings developed socially and experientially. Furthermore, epistemology is known as subjectivism, which illustrates that both the researcher and the object of inquiry cannot be separated. In other words, the individuals' understanding of themselves, and the world is a central part of how they make sense of themselves, others, and the world (Cohen, et al., 2007). Therefore, it helped interpreting the impact of the phenomenon on the lived experiences of the participants. Together, these different paradigmatic approaches informed the underlying theoretical framework for the project. Using them together was helpful to investigate the concept of power and dominance from the different interpretive perspectives of the participants.

5.3. Qualitative research:

This study followed a qualitative research methodology using interpretive phenomenological analysis as an approach. This study is primarily concerned with understanding the subjective experiences of Muslim women who observe the practice of Hijab in Scotland; therefore, it relied on qualitative approach, which emphasizes the importance of the human experience. According to Jackson et al., (2007), qualitative researchers will be primarily interested in what Guba and Lincoln (1985) refer to as, “the human instrument” (Cited in Jackson et al., 2007, p. 22), which means that researchers rely on participants’ in-depth responses to questions about how they construct and reflect on their experiences (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). In addition, Jackson et al (2007, p. 23) refer to qualitative research as a “Thick descriptive” because it offers richness and details in a discussion. Quantitative research, on the other hand, is more concerned with answering finite questions that restrict the participant’s answers and limit their responses (Jackson et al., 2007).

Qualitative research has its roots in hermeneutics, phenomenology, and the *Verstehen* sociological tradition (Jackson et al., 2007). In addition, it is founded in both interpretivism and constructivism that stem from idealist ontology (Deshpande, 1983; Sale et al., 2002). The idealist ontology suggests that there is no access to reality independent on our minds, which means that both the researcher and the object of the inquiry are interdependent and interactively related (Guba and Lincoln, 1985), and they both influence each other. Furthermore, realities are understood as the forms of various social and mental constructions dependent on perceptions of reality that is held by certain individuals or group (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Additionally, qualitative research includes all types of social research that is associated with non-numeric data (words), containing various forms of textual analysis such as conversational analysis, narrative analysis, discourse analysis, and content analysis (Jackson et al., 2007).

In contrast, quantitative research is guided by positivism, which has a realist orientation and focuses on the concept of “God’s view” in searching for an ultimate and one truth (Slevitch, 2011, p.76). Its epistemology contends that the researcher and the researched are independent of each other, which signifies that the researcher can conduct a study without being influenced or influencing the subject of inquiry as explained by Sale et al., (2002). Unlike qualitative research, a quantitative positivist inquiry has both objectivity and generalization as to its core principles and that requires methods that are founded in statistical analysis such as inferential statistics, hypothesis testing, experimental and quasi-experimental designs (Slevitch, 2011). Consequently, examining the experiences of Hijabi Muslim women using qualitative research was suitable for this study because it did not seek to analyse numerical data, test hypotheses, or experiments. Instead, it aimed to explore the experiences of Hijabi Muslim women in Scotland by understanding the meanings that they attributed to their behaviour and actions of observing Hijab and what are their perceptions of certain issues, which are related to wearing Hijab. Among the diverse types of qualitative research is phenomenology, which this study will rely on.

5.3.1. Phenomenological approach:

Phenomenology as a qualitative research approach was useful to examine the lived experiences of Muslim women who observe the practice of wearing hijab in Scotland as it allowed participants to share the meanings they granted to the hijab, their motivations, and the challenges of wearing it. According to Guest et al., (2013, no page), phenomenology is associated with the earliest works of 20th century philosophers like “Husserl, Heidegger, Sartre, and Merleau-Ponty”. It designates the study of conscious experience. The works of the earliest phenomenologist were later used to understand behavioural and social sciences by various scholars like Amedeo Giorgi (1970). In contemporary era, phenomenology is used to imply a study of individual’s perceptions, feelings and lived experiences (Guest et al., 2013). Additionally, it is defined as,

A philosophical approach to the study of experience. There are many different emphases and interests amongst phenomenologists, but they have all tended to share a particular interest in thinking about what the experience of being human is *like*, in all its various aspects, but especially in terms of the things which matter to us, and which constitute our lived world (Smith et al., 2009, p.11).

Smith et al., (2009) explain that all the previously mentioned philosophers may share similar interests, however they all have distinctive ways of understanding phenomenology. Husserl introduces the significance and the relevance of focusing on experience and its perception. Heidegger, Merleau-Ponty, and Sartre develop it further to include the perceptions of the person as being implicated in a world of “objects and relationships, language and culture, projects and concerns” (Smith et al.,2009, p. 20). Hence, they progress from the transcendental and descriptive phenomenology of Husserl towards an interpretive one with an emphasis on the examination of the perspectival directness of being involved in the lived world, something that is personal to a certain individual, nonetheless focus on his relationship with other and not to himself as a creature in isolation (Smith et al., 2009). To get closer to the participants’ personal world and subjective experiences (Reid et al,2005) interpretive phenomenological analysis was employed as an approach to the analysis of the data. The following section discusses data collection methods and moves to discuss how interpretive phenomenological analysis was used as a data analysis method.

5.3.2. Data Collection:

The data was primarily collected using semi-structured in-depth interviews. According to DeJockheere and Vaughn (2019), semi-structured in-depth interviews are commonly used in qualitative research and consist of a flexible dialogue and communications between the researcher and the participant. Furthermore, Smith and Osborn (2007) state that although there are many ways to conduct an IPA qualitative approach, like diaries and personal accounts, most IPA studies have been conducted using semi-structured interviews. Likewise, Smith et al., (2009) maintains that since the primary concern of IPA is to get rich, detailed, and first-person accounts of experiences and phenomena under study, semi-structured interviews offer a useful method to collect data. Therefore, the rationale of using semi-structured interviews is to allow the researcher and the participants to engage in a flexible dialogue. The flexibility of semi-structured interviews allows new and unexpected issues to rise, which may be followed by further questions from the researcher (Smith et.,2009). Additionally, Smith et al (2009) state that an IPA research study should have a sample size of one to fifteen participants, it is not possible to have a large sample size. For instance, Alase

(2017, p.15) suggests that the IPA researchers should “conduct semi-structured and unstructured interviews with as many as twenty-five (25) participants, but as few as two”. Therefore, this study used a sample size of 20 participants, with each interview lasting at least 60-90 minutes.

5.3.2.1. The settings (Date, Place, and Time):

This study relied on twenty Muslim women who wear Hijab in the cities where Muslims are highly concentrated like Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee. To ensure that all three cities were covered, the sample size was divided into equal parts. The age range of the participants is 18-56 years old because it is particularly important to include different age ranges to get different accounts of the practice of wearing the Hijab. The interviews were conducted after the participants provide written consent of their participation after first reading the forwarded Project Information appendix. They were asked questions about wearing Hijab in Scotland, such as the significance of wearing a Hijab, their motivations for wearing a Hijab if they have ever experienced Islamophobia or racism that is directly attached to their Hijab. Participants were also asked about the role of media representations in shaping their experiences of wearing a hijab in Scotland. To collect data, Smith et al., (2009) suggest using devices like electronic voice or video recording, in addition to the traditional pen and paper to note down important observations during the interviews. In the case of face-to-face interview meetings, this research only used a voice recording device, pen, and paper (with informed consent agreed with all participants).

Due to Covid-19, most interviews were remotely conducted using Zoom application. According to Lupton (2020), online interviews can be done either via audio-visual interfaces such as skype and zoom (Janghorban et al., 2012) or through textual synchronicity such as using IRC (Barrat and Maddox, 2016). Using asynchronous interviewing is possible, nevertheless, it lacks live interaction and depends mostly on the participants to devote a considerable time to write down their responses, which may be considered as much labour (Bampton, et al., 2013; Burns, 2010 cited in Lupton, 2020). Therefore, conducting the interviews using audio-visual devices was useful because they allow the interviewer to seek clarification and follow threads of the conversation. In addition, it also allowed the interviewer to check that they understand the meaning of what the participant has said (Lupton, 2020). Otherwise, they were conducted face-to-face by taking into consideration social distancing measurements to protect both the researcher and the participants. When conducting an Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) of qualitative data gathered during interviews, Smith et al (2009) state some important considerations regarding the location of interview meetings. They (2009) believe that participant should decide upon the settings of the interview (date, time, place), however for the sake of safety, the researcher can suggest some safe and comfortable alternatives, for instance, restaurants, coffee shops and other convenient alternatives in public spaces. The choice of the suggested locations by Smith et al., (2009) were influenced due to the pandemic of Covid-19. As a result, most interviews were conducted remotely using Zoom software program.

5.3.2.2. The Justification of the Sample Size:

It is important to determine the size of the sample when selecting participants (Creswell, 2012). Following IPA as an approach for data collection and analysis requires a specific feature for sampling. The sample size that was chosen for conducting this study is twenty-

five (initially, was reduced to 20) participants between the ages of 18-56. Smith et al., (2009) suggest that as with any other phenomenological study, the maximum number of participants in IPA should be as many as twenty-five and as few as two, and the sample needs to be fairly homogenous. Therefore, using the maximum number suggested by Smith et al., (2009) was crucial to the richness and the saturation of the data.

Creswell (2013) stresses the importance of the homogeneity of the sample “It is essential that all participants have similar lived experience of the phenomenon being studied” (Creswell, 2013, p.155). The rationale behind the homogeneity of the sample is giving an insight into a particular experience that is shared by the participants under study (Smith et al, 2009). The researcher ensured Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee are represented by dividing the sample size into three and which makes it Glasgow (9), Edinburgh (9), and Dundee (8) (that was the initial intention, however due to the high concentration of Muslims in Glasgow (10) and Edinburgh (7), only 3 participants were from Dundee). According to El Shayyal (2016) Muslims in Scotland are highly concentrated in three major parliamentary regions, including Glasgow (43%), Lothian (19%), and Northeast Scotland (11, 8%), especially in cities like Glasgow, Edinburgh, Dundee, and Aberdeen. Data collection took place in Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee. Priority in the division was given to the place where Muslims were highly concentrated to increase the chances of getting the targeted number of participants.

Smith et al (2009) explain that participants need to be purposively selected to offer an insight into a particular experience, thus it was important to use purposive sampling instead of the probability sampling method “Obviously, it is inappropriate to think in terms of random or representative sampling when one is interviewing so few participants” (Smith, 2012, p.4). Purposive sampling is a qualitative technique for recruiting participants who can provide detailed information about the phenomenon under investigation. It is subjective because the researcher is the one choosing the conditions each participant must meet (Statistic Solutions, 2021). Therefore, it was important that all the participants in this project were women, Muslim, and have worn the hijab or currently are wearing the Hijab while living in Scotland. This study planned initially of including those women who stopped wearing the Hijab because they previously had an experience wearing Hijab and therefore, they fall into the inclusion criteria. However, most women in the study were wearing the Hijab during the time of the interviews.

The study also employed snowball technique to attract participants by asking the participants who already agreed to take place to suggest other participants that have experienced the phenomenon under study (Alase, 2017). Snowball technique is “a convenience sampling method. This method is applied when it is difficult to access subjects with the target characteristics. In this method, the existing study subjects recruit future subjects among their acquaintances. Sampling continues until data saturation” (Naderifar et al., 2017, p.2). Both sampling techniques were combined to increase access to the number of the targeted participants.

5.3.2.3 Recruitment process:

The recruitment of participants was achieved through contacting gatekeepers. According to Macfadyen and Rankin (2016), “gatekeepers have a role to ensure researchers gain access to potential participants and sites for research. Positive influences of the gatekeepers can be invaluable to the research process by facilitating the smooth running of the research activity

to completion” (2016, p.82). Hence, the participants were recruited via online social media platforms using Instagram and Facebook, for instance. Several organizations and communities were emailed via university email or contacted by phone to provide help to find potential participants. Using gatekeepers was a useful way of locating participants, this term is defined by Johnny Andoh-Arthur (2019) as essential mediators to access study settings and participants within social research. To find potential participants, contacting Muslim, interfaith, and women organizations, community groups, and local communities themselves in Scotland is important. There are various organizations and communities that are in Glasgow and Edinburgh. Some of them include Muslim Council of Scotland, Amina MWRC (Muslim Women Resource Centre) in Glasgow and Edinburgh, Muslim women’s Association of Edinburgh, Glasgow University Muslim Association, UWS Muslim Association, Beyond the Veil (Edinburgh). Interfaith Associations Interfaith Glasgow. Women’s associations: Glasgow women’s Library, Scottish women’s rights Centre, The young women’s movement in Glasgow, The Women’s Centre Glasgow. Most of these listed organizations were contacted by the researcher.

5.3.2.4. Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA):

Smith and Osborn (2007) suggest that interpretive phenomenological analysis is a valuable tool to understand how individuals make sense of their personal and social world. Furthermore, its importance lies in engaging with the participant’s subjective accounts of their experiences (Reid et al., 2005). In addition, its main concern is analysing raw data to produce an interesting narrative account of the developing themes. IPA has three major philosophical foundations: phenomenology, hermeneutics, and ideography. This general overview of what IPA is followed by an explanation of its link and usefulness to this research project.

What makes IPA different from other approaches to phenomenology is that it has three theoretical underpinnings: phenomenology, hermeneutics, and ideography (Smith, et al., 2009; Tuffour (2017). According to Tuffour (2017), IPA identifies mostly with Heidegger, Merleau-Ponty, and Sartre’s hermeneutic traditions because Husserl’s phenomenology is considered too difficult to decipher, especially his notion of reduction that requires the suspension of previous knowledge and pre-assumptions about the phenomenon under study. IPA stresses the importance of context in the study of experiences. Noon (2017) believes that IPA is not merely descriptive, but it requires the participants to interpret how to have certain experiences in a particular context. Moreover, this idea is illustrated through Heidegger’s concept of *Dasein*, which suggests the unique existence of human beings in a world of inter-relationship and inter-connectedness of human experience (Finlay, 2011). For that reason, researchers using IPA proceed to examine the concept of *Dasein* by immersing and involving themselves in the world of the participants through a lens of cultural and socio-historical meanings (Moran, 2000). In addition, it encourages them to be reflexive in their interpretations regarding their pre-understandings of the phenomenon under study (Moran, 2000). Like Husserl and Heidegger, Merleau-Ponty’s work has an influence on IPA approach. Merleau-Ponty stresses the importance of subjectivity, embodiment, and the individuals’ relationships to the world (Tuffour, 2017). He suggests that perception is a vital element in knowing and engaging in the world. Furthermore, Merleau-Ponty criticizes empiricism for inadequately conceptualizing the mechanisms of perception and judgment, which considers human existence as a vital element in knowing the world (Tuffour, 2017).

According to Tuffor (2017), IPA is influenced by Merleau-Ponty's understanding of the importance of the body in constructing and knowing the human experience. In addition to the previous philosophers, Sartre's phenomenologist approach is more focused on the importance of freedom and responsibility in constructing the individuals' lived experiences (Tuffor, 2017). Additionally, Sartre understands the existence in the world as a process of becoming and not being, which suggests the importance of taking into consideration the individuals' historical biography and their social situations (Tuffor, 2017). As a result, Sartre provides IPA researchers with an understanding of how phenomenological analysis of human experience should be in relation to the context of personal and social relationships (Smith et al., 2009).

Hermeneutics is the second philosophical ground for the foundation of IPA. IPA stresses the importance of double hermeneutics in the process of analysing the data. Smith (2004, p.9) explains this process as "the participant is trying to make sense of their personal and social world. The researcher is trying to make sense of the participant trying to make sense of their personal and social world." The researcher has a significant role in the interpretation as his previous experiences and perspectives are important for this process (Larkin and Thompson, 2011). Smith et al explain that:

IPA requires a combination of phenomenological and hermeneutic insights. It is phenomenological in attempting to get as close as possible to the personal experience of the participant but recognizes that this inevitably becomes an interpretive endeavour for both participant and researcher. Without phenomenology there would be nothing to interpret; without hermeneutics, the phenomenon would not be seen (2009, p.37).

In addition to phenomenology and hermeneutics, the third theoretical base is ideography, which aims to examine the individual account of a subjective phenomenon in-depth and in a certain context (Moses and Knutsen, 2012). Unlike the nomothetic approach that seeks to generate laws and generalizations, IPA aims at addressing the perceptions and understandings of a particular group of people (Smith and Osborn, 2007). In addition, it seeks to learn from each individual story through a deep understanding of the participants' emotions, behaviours, and thoughts. The following part explains the rationale of using IPA in this study.

5.3.2.4.1. The Rationale of Using IPA:

IPA was best suited for this study because it sought to understand how a particular person made sense of a particular phenomenon, which was in this case Hijab. According to Willig (2008), IPA is a newly developed approach that provides the researcher with guidelines to identify themes. Thus, it is considered as a methodology, which is accessible to those who have no philosophical background (Willig, 2008). What distinguishes IPA from other methodological approaches is its focus on idiographic analysis to construct a deep and rich account of the phenomenon under study (Lyons, 2007; Smith, 2011). For instance, when comparing discourse analysis to IPA, discourse analysis focuses mainly on the use of dialogue and how the participants' use of language. While IPA is more interested in understanding the lived experiences of the participants (Willig, 2008). Moreover, IPA shares various similarities with others like grounded theory and narrative analysis. Crossley (2007) explains that narrative analysis is more focused on the lived experiences and on identity constructions rather than how the participants experience or view certain phenomena. In addition, IPA was a suitable methodological approach for this research because it offered a

voice to a group of people who do not typically have a strong voice, and who, due to their cultural expectations, are typically considered to be subdued, quiet and withdrawn (Larkin et al, 2006; Luke et al, 2001). Hence, IPA was a useful tool to understand how Muslim women experience wearing Hijab in Scotland.

Different studies were conducted on women using IPA as an approach for qualitative research like understanding women's experiences with anger and aggression (Eatough and Smith, 2008) and examining women's identity change when transiting to the state of a mother (Smith, 1999). Some studies apply this approach to understand the experiences of women wearing hijab in western contexts like Canada and New Zealand (Litchmore and Safdar, 2016; Ash et al., 2019). This study attempted to investigate the experiences of women wearing hijab in Scotland using IPA. It endeavoured to understand the meaning that they ascribe to their hijab, what is it like wearing Hijab in Scotland, does it have an influence on experiencing Islamophobia or racism?

5.3.2.4.2. Stages of analysing the data using IPA:

This section described the process of using IPA to analyse the data. Smith and Osborn (2008) suggest steps to follow when conducting an IPA. The first step of coding is reading through the transcripts, identify the main themes and search for the patterns, which are words and phrases that are repeated during the interview. This process managed in narrowing down the words in the transcripts. The next step is re-reading the transcripts and re-listening to the recordings to make sure of the clarity of the transcripts. Furthermore, this step aided in identifying new themes and categorisations in the responses provided by the participants. The transcripts need to be read at least three times to capture the effect of the phenomenon on their lived experiences (Alase, 2017). Alase (2016) introduces three cycles of coding IPA data. To begin with, the lengthy responses of the participants were reduced into chunky sentences, this process helped to identify the keywords and the repeated patterns. Secondly, further condensation is required, which means reducing the previous chunks into fewer words to establish the core of what the participants mean or express. The third and last step is referred to as the category phase, which requires encapsulating the essence of the central meaning into one or two words. to make the process easier, using NVivo software helps in the process of coding and categorizing the themes and patterns (the analyses were conducted manually). Smith et al., (2009) state that there are four steps to analysing data transcripts. The first step is identifying the themes and annotating the main points in the transcripts. Afterward, combining themes that are related under an umbrella theme. Thenceforth, the emergent themes from the first transcript direct the analysis of the other transcripts, which assists in constructing a table with general themes. The last step involves the presentation of interpretive accounts of the participants using verbatim extracts from the transcripts.

Creswell (2013) suggests that the researcher needs to bracket his/her life from the lived experiences of the participants under study. To bracket means to "set aside our prejudgments, biases and perceived ideas about things" (Moustakas, 1994, p.85). For that reason, this process did not allow the researcher to interject his/her own experiences on the participants' lived experiences of the phenomenon under study. "The researcher should begin with a full description of his or her own experience of the phenomenon" (2013, p. 193). Like Smith et al (2009), Creswell (2013) suggests that the researcher needs to develop a list of significant statements about the phenomenon under study. The statements can come out of the interview

transcripts or from relevant sources and then grow them into meaningful units and themes. Later, the production of textual description is enhanced with verbatim extracts from the transcripts. The process of bracketing requires that the researchers reflect on their thoughts while interviewing and analysing the data. For that reason, their experiences do not intervene with that of the participants. Reflexivity is important to mitigate the effect of the researcher's background experiences on the data (Bonner and Tolhurst, 2002). The following section discussed the reflexivity and the positionality of the researcher in relation to this study.

5.4. Reflexivity and the researcher's positionality:

Reflexivity is a principal element when engaging in qualitative research. According to Shaw (2010), it is crucial that the researchers reflect on how they may influence their research process both when gathering and collecting data. Reflexivity is not an option in IPA, but it is a fully integrated process, and it is the responsibility of the researcher to know how to manage the data through the various analytical stages. However, the researcher is encouraged to mention how they are going to influence the research process and to acknowledge that any analysis is shaped by their preconceptions and experiences (Shaw, 2010). Smith et al., (2009) maintain that the role of the researchers in the analysis is dynamic, which reflects their attempts to make sense of the participants' interpretations of their lived experiences. As a result, the researcher maintained an informal diary to take notes directly after each interview. This helped in the process of being reflective and expressing how the researcher felt about the interview, how did the interview progress, what were the themes evolved from the first interview, and what could be improved for the following interviews. Smith et al., (2012) stress the importance of taking notes at the initial stages of listening to the records and reading the transcripts, this helped the researcher to recognize their reflections and observations of the interview experience and any other thoughts of significance. Taking notes and reflections in a diary was a good idea to help in the process of bracketing and setting aside previous biases and focusing mainly on what the participants are going to say. The diary in research methodology is a way of recording practical decisions taken during the data collection process, it is referred to as a vehicle for documenting personal reflections (Gibbs, 2007 cited in Browne, 2003). It was useful during the process of data collection and analysis.

Positionality signifies that the social, historical, and political location of the researchers impacts their research orientations (Holmes,2020), which suggests that they are not separated and cannot escape from the social world they live in it to study it (Hammersley &Atkinson,1995; Malterud, 2001). There were various beliefs and values that influence the researchers' positionality including their "political allegiance, religious faith, gender, sexuality, historical and geographical location, ethnicity, race, social class, and status, (dis)abilities and so on" (Sikes, 2004, Wellington, et al., 2005, Marsh and Ercan 2018 cited in Holmes, 2020, p. 02). The position of the researcher is an insider position, which has both benefits and drawbacks.

The researcher's position may be considered that of an insider because she is a part of the Muslim community, has studied in Scotland for two years, and most importantly wears Hijab in public. Shah explains that "A social insider is better positioned as a researcher because of his/her knowledge of the relevant pattern of social interaction required for gaining access and meaning making" (Shah, 2004, p.556). Therefore, the researcher was aware of the experience

of wearing a hijab in Scotland, and she had some previous understanding of the religious and cultural motivations and the purposes of wearing a hijab, which may facilitate the process of engaging with the participants. She is also female, which made the interaction with Muslim females who wear hijab comfortable. Reed and Proctor (1995) believe that being an insider is having a greater understanding of the culture being studied. Smith et al., (2009) explain that IPA attempts to grasp the perspectives of the insider, not only to be in their shoes but to stand next to them and enquire from different perspectives.

Being an insider has some disadvantages (Herrmann, 1989; Rooney, 2005). Among them is being biased and unconsciously making strong assumptions about the topic based on previous experiences and knowledge. According to Bonner and Tolhurst (2002), there are several advantages that are attached to being an insider researcher, among them are not seen as a researcher, but as an advocate by some, being biased when interpreting the findings, Reliance on participants with whom the researcher feels comfortable, focusing on dramatic events rather than the routine, Experiencing role conflicts. The effects of these disadvantages can be mitigated by the process of being reflective “Through being reflexive and critically examining my assumptions and actions in relation to both data collection and analysis the potential for researcher effect was minimized” (Bonner and Tolhurst, 2002, p. 6). As a result, the researcher was aware of her biases, and she was reflective through the process of data collection and analysis.

5.5. Quality issues in qualitative research:

There are many ways to judge the validity of qualitative research. Because there are no specific ways to measure the validity of the interpretive phenomenological analysis, Smith et al (2009) follow Yardley’s (2000) to assess the validity of IPA. It consists of four principles, which are sensitivity to context, commitment and rigor, transparency and coherence, and impact and importance (Gauntlett et al., 2017). Firstly, sensitivity to the context suggests that the researcher should demonstrate the context of the theory and the previous understandings that are created by previous researchers who either make use of similar methods or tackle the same topic. In addition to making clear the socio-cultural settings of the study, which means the ideological, historical, and socio-economic influences on the beliefs of both the participants and the researchers. Furthermore, how the researcher deals with the data collected from the participants needs to be illustrated (Smith et al., 2009, Lyons, 2007). To ensure the researcher's sensitivity to the context, she produced a literature review and theoretical framework which supports her orientations. In addition, sensitivity to the context also results from the immersive analysis of the data “making sense of how the participant is making sense of their experience requires immersive and disciplined attention to the unfolding account of the participant and what can be gleaned from it.” (Smith et al., 2009, p.180). Secondly, commitment that involves illustrating a continuous engagement with the research topic. In addition, it is important to ensure that the participants are comfortable, to ensure this principle the researcher made certain that the participants agreed to participate and were fully informed about the research project. Rigor signifies the completion of the data analysis (Lyons, 2007). To do that, the researcher followed the steps of data collection and analysis that are defined by Smith et al (2009) in conducting IPA. Thirdly, transparency and coherence that involve discussing and detailing every aspect of the research process, which includes data analysis and collection. The researcher ensured that every detail of the research process were reported. The final principle is impact and importance that are related to the

theoretical, practical, and socioeconomic influences of the impact of the study. Therefore, this research might have an impact on understanding the lived experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland by bringing about their perspectives, challenges, and effects of wearing hijab.

5.6. Ethical considerations:

The ethics approval was granted by the University of the West of Scotland under application number 16727 with some comments from the ethics committee on how to further improve the research. The researcher made sure to strictly follow the ethical guidelines of the university by applying the comments of the committee. The UWS ethics guidelines (2020) emphasize the importance of three principles when conducting research on human participants, which are autonomy, veracity, and informed consent. These elements are crucial for respecting the human dignity of the participant. The term autonomy recognises the right of the participants to determine their own course of action, which maintains the need for free informed consent (UWS Ethics Committee,2020). In addition, three main elements are important to follow to obtain informed consent that are:

- 1- The information provided by the researcher to the participants must be adequately detailed, accurate, and relevant. Moreover, the information sheet should state clearly and honestly all aspects of the research that are connected to the decision to consent.
- 2- Consent must be freely granted and may be withdrawn.
- 3- The potential participants should be given time to read and consider the information to ensure that they understand the nature of the research and to decide regarding their participation.

The participants were provided with a project information sheet about the aims of the research and based on that an informal discussion with the researcher, the participant made an informed choice of consent to take part in the project. In addition, the participants were provided with time to reflect on the information sheet before deciding to participate. They were also encouraged to ask questions and state their concerns prior to agreeing to participate in the project. Moreover, they were informed that they can withdraw whenever they want from participating without stating any reasons. Confidentiality applies when the researchers know the identity of the participants and make sure to protect their data from others (Coffelt,2017). Accordingly, the researcher ensured that the data of the participant is protected and safe by storing it in the university computer with a password to enter. To ensure the confidentiality of the participants, the use of pseudonyms was important. Before any interview, the participant was given a "participant information sheet" and according to that, she decided either to participate or not through signing a consent form. With regards to the confidentiality and handling of the data, only the researcher and her three supervisors were able to access it and the data were stored on password protected devices.

5.7. Disseminating the research outcomes:

Upon completion of the study the research outputs will be disseminated to academics and policymakers. Dissemination is defined as

a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences and the settings in which research findings are to be received and, where appropriate, communicating

and interacting with wider policy and...service audiences in ways that will facilitate research uptake in decision-making processes and practice (Wilson et al., 2010, p.91)

It is crucial to consider what audiences will be interested in the completed research. Since this work is about the experiences of Muslim women in Scotland, this means that it examines their lived experiences and tries to spot the light on the challenges they have been experiencing. As such, this work may contribute to understanding and improving their situation and addressing the challenges they might face. In this case, the audiences may be policymakers, social scientists, community organizations and services, charities, and academics in other fields. The results from this research will be disseminated through journal articles, possibly a book, conference presentations and academic events.

5.8. During the fieldwork:

5.8.1. Participant recruitment:

The purpose of interpretive phenomenological analysis is to gain insight into a particular shared experience. Therefore, to select participants “who represent a perspective rather than a population”, Smith et al (2009., p. 49) proposed purposive homogenous participant selection. To help access the desired sample, a list of potential associations and institutions was prepared, and they were contacted with a letter of introduction of the researcher and the project information sheet that were sent to different organizations such as the Edinburgh Mosque, Glasgow Mosque, UWS Muslim Association, Glasgow Muslim Association, Sisters’ Group in Dundee and AMINA (Muslim women resources centre. Subsequently, some organizations respond with an agreement to share the project’s poster in some Facebook groups, WhatsApp groups, and in Mosques. As a result, the researcher was contacted by some potential participants via email and through WhatsApp with an intention to participant. Furthermore, snowball sampling method was practical to reach participants via other participants who meet the criteria.

After some individuals show the intention to participate, they were approached by the researcher to appoint a possible date and time to interview. Due to the Covid 19 restrictions, most of the interviews were conducted via the Zoom applications and only three of them were done face to face. Prior to each interview, all the participants were provided with the consent form and the Project Sheet document, which explains what the project is about and what it is expected from them. They were also informed that they can withdraw at any time without stating the reason. The consent forms were signed by both parties. The entire process involved: establishing contact, obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, agreeing to date and time commitments, and obtaining permission to record and publish the data (Moustakas,1994).

The selection criteria applied in this study were:

- Muslim female
- Between the age of 18-56
- Wore the Hijab for a significant period
- Currently wearing the Hijab
- Lived in Scotland for at least the period of two years

The following table provides the number of participants and their background information. It presents their background information including their age, nationality, race, ethnicity, religious sect, the period they have stayed in Scotland, and their position. Pseudonyms are used to protect the participants' identities and to ensure confidentiality.

Participants' pseudonym	Age	Nationality	Race	Ethnicity	Religious sect	Social status	Period in Scotland	Position
Participant one: Nana	27 years old	Algerian	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Single	2 years and half (Glasgow)	PhD Student
Participant 02: Ziza	28 years old	Algerian	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Single	2 years and four months (Glasgow)	PhD Student
Participant 03: Sousou	26 years old	Algerian	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Engaged	2 years (Glasgow)	PhD Student
Participant 04: Zaynab	27 years old	Algerian	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Single	2 years and a couple of months (Glasgow)	PhD Student
Participant 05: Mimi	29 years old	Algerian	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Single	4 years (Glasgow)	PhD Student
Participant 06: Dr Zee	34 years old	Nigerian	Black African	Yoruba	Sunni	Married	One year (Glasgow)	Student/ Worker
Participant 07: Naz	43 years old	British	Pakistani	Pakistani	Sunni	Married with kids	Since she was 12 years old (Glasgow)	Not working currently
Participant 08: Nounou	37 years old	Pakistani	Pakistani	Punjabi	Sunni	Married	One year (Glasgow)	Finished her studies
Participant 09: Hadia	19 years old	British/ Scottish	Pakistani	Pakistani	Sunni	Single	Born and raised in Glasgow Motherwell	Student

Participant 10: Shay	38 years old	Palestinian	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Married with kids	Since October 2019 (Edinburgh)	Employed/ Dentist
Participant 11: Hania	36 years old	Yemeni	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Married with kids	Over 12 years (Edinburgh)	Employed
Participant 12: Fouz	42 years old	British	Indian	Indian	Sunni	Married	(Edinburgh) Since 2006	Employed
Participant 13: Fati	53 years old	British/ Scottish	Mozambique	African	Sunni	Married with kids	Since she was 8 years old (37 years in Dundee)	Employed
Participant 14: Nes	52 years old	British	Pakistani	Pakistani	Sunni	Married with kids	19 years (Dundee)	Employed
Participant 15: Lina	44 years old	Scottish	Scottish	Scottish	Muslim only (a revert)	Married	Scottish-born (Glasgow)	Employed
Participant 16: Nima	43 years old	Scottish	Scottish	Scottish	Sunni (Revert)	Married with kids	Scottish-born (Edinburgh)	Disability advocate
Participant 17: Hope	56 years old	Libyan	Arab	Arab	Sunni	Married with kids	Here since 1993 (Dundee)	Employed
Participant 18: Noun	48 years old	British	Pakistani	Punjabi	Sunni	Married with kids	Scottish-born (Edinburgh)	Student/Employed
Participant 19: San	40 years old	British	Palestinian	Palestinian	Sunni	Married with kids	Since she was 15 years old (1997)	Employed
Participant 20: Wino	40 years old	Indonesian	Asian	Botawa	Sunni	Married with Kids	3 years (Edinburgh)	Employed/ PhD student

Table 4: shows the background information of the participants

5.8.2. Data Collection Process:

This study involved conducting semi-structured interviews with each participant. The aim of using semi-structured interviews was to get in-depth details of the participants' lived experiences of wearing the Hijab in Scotland. The interview questions were thoughtfully worded to generate rich data. The semi-structured interviews are systematic but flexible approach, which allowed the interviewer to probe and explore the matter when required (Patton, 2002). As per Eatough and Smith (2008), semi-structured interviews are commonly used in IPA research which enable the participants to provide rich data through the contribution of the researcher's guidance and more open-ended framework.

The duration of each interview was planned to last between 60 to 90 minutes as an appropriate length for a semi-structured interview (Smith et al., 2009). With the participants consent, each interview was recorded to produce a verbatim account of each interview. Prior to conducting interviews, each participant was briefed on what could be expected in the interview. An interview was conducted as a part of a pilot. This allowed for the research questions to be tested, to practise the interview techniques and to identify any refinements or modifications. Although most of the participants were fluent in the English language, some of them were encouraged to use Arabic to explain some expressions that they could not convey in English, which was later translated in English.

5.8.3. Data Analysis:

After collecting the data, the interviews were transcribed into Microsoft Word files to produce verbatim accounts of the conversations. While transcribing, the names of the people involved were made anonymous. This is a part of the confidentiality. According to Smith et al (2008, p. 66): "in IPA research, the analyst does not necessarily aim to count the frequency of the topics but to understand the meaning of the conversation". As a result, it is crucial to learn about their mental and social world, those meanings are explicitly available and must be obtained through interpretation and a sustained engagement with the transcript.

IPA has different approaches to analysis, from the descriptive to the interpretive and from the particular to the general (Smith et al., 2009). The idiographic approach of IPA recommends moving from the detailed analysis of the first case to the next and so on. Smith et al., (2009) suggests moving from the most interesting, engaged and detailed case. However, the transcripts were analysed chronologically from the first interview to the last one. Although most of the transcripts were engaging and detailed, one unique experience stands out, which was that of Nima, the Hijabi woman with the wheelchair. After transcribing the interviews, each interview was copied into a table with four column that include: the transcript, the exploratory notes, emergent themes, and superordinate themes. The step-by-step analytical process (Smith et al., 2008) was followed in this research because it offered direct stages of analysis and interpretation, which is more convenient for a novice researcher.

Step one: Reading and Re-reading

This step is concerned with immersing oneself in the data through listening and transcribing each individual transcript. Each interview was listened to at least twice before the transcription process. The manual transcription of the data helped in getting familiar and feeling the data (Corbin and Straus., 2015). As per Conrad (1987), it is possible to immerse oneself in the original data and gain the crucial insider perspective by reading and re-reading

the transcripts and listening to the recordings, which prevents the pre-mature analysis of the data and jumping into conclusions. Furthermore, exploratory notes (initial thoughts) about the transcripts (Van Manen, 1990) were practical in tracking the participant transparency and reflexivity of the data. Having these initial thoughts about the data relates to what Gadamer referred to as “the hermeneutic circle”, which ensures that the initial reflections, possible connections and impressions were not missed and remained the focus of the analysis.

Step two: Initial noting (Exploratory notes)

The second step was initial noting, which was the most time-consuming process. It involved a detailed examination of semantic content and language use. A detailed line by line analysis was conducted which capture the essence of what was being said by the participants.

According to Smith et al (2009, p. 83), this process allows to “identify specific ways through which the participant talks about, understands and thinks about an issue”. To achieve this, exploratory notes (initial thoughts) (Smith et al., 2009) were added on the right-hand margin.

Hence, three types of comments were explored descriptive, linguistic, and conceptual comments. The purpose of the descriptive comments is to describe the content of the data.

According to Cooper et al, 2012, in the making of the descriptive comments, the researcher identifies key phrases, explanations, descriptions and emotional responses. The next level of the analysis is linguistic, in which the researcher focusses on the ways in which the meaning and the content were presented linguistically. The researcher paid specific attention to pronoun use, pauses, laughter, functional aspects of the language, repetitions, and metaphor use (Cooper et al., 2012; Smith et al., 2020). The third level of the analysis had a more interpretative focus “other exploratory notes can be more conceptual” (Smith et al, 2020, p.83). It engages at a more interrogative and conceptual level with the material. Interrogative suggests explicitly asking questions about the meaning of the data. This stage of analysis presents a move away from the explicit claims of the participant (Smith et al., 2020).

Considering Smith et al., 's (2009) suggestions, three colours were used to differentiate the three types of comments. Most of the transcripts were in the English language, which facilitated the interpretation process. The following table illustrates an example of one of the participants. It shows how the descriptive, linguistic, and conceptual comments were extracted and appointed. Descriptive comments, according to Smith et al., (2009), have a clear phenomenological focus and are likely to stay closer to the participant explicit meaning. One example of a descriptive comment is when the participant described the first day of wearing the Hijab by using adjectives such as “extraordinary day” and “exciting day.” Although these descriptive comments seem explicit, the researcher believed that these adjectives might allude to other interpretations, which allowed the rise of a conceptual comment “what does extraordinary and exciting means?” “What does the participant mean by that?” “Was she happy or sad?” “Was it that exciting? Why?” . The linguistic example lies in the use of pronouns. For instance, the participant used the pronoun “I,” “own” to avoid generalising or impose her choice to wear the Hijab on other girls in her home country, which they did not choose to wear it instead they forced to. Overall, this stage of analysis explored descriptive, conceptual, and linguistic comments. The following stage is concerned with developing emergent themes.

Maha

Initial themes	Transcript	Exploratory notes
<p>Descriptive Linguistic Conceptual</p> <p>Serious - emphasis on the woman I, Quran - A personal story Some girls - they - their parents - The other? - in what terms they are different</p>	<p>Q1: When did you first start to cover and wear Hijab? A1: So, good evening. The first time I started to wear Hijab was at the age of 17 years old, exactly at the 1st year of high school. It was a very EXCITING day and EXTRAORDINARY day also because I have NEVER been outside wearing a hijab. Also, I was like having a problem styling my Hijab and putting pins to be more stylish and to appear in a fashionable way, so it was also the first day at high school which makes it a very HARD day. FUQ: How did you feel? like how other people reacted to you when you first started wearing Hijab? A1: "It was something DIFFICULT, especially because my friends, my family, and neighbours did not get to see me wearing Hijab. I was like all the time getting outside with like... my hair, so oh yeah, it was something DIFFERENT, I appeared in a DIFFERENT APPEARANCE at that day. FUQ: So, it was strange A1: "YES, IT WAS STRANGE!" Q2: Were you forced to wear Hijab? A2: "NO! (With an emphasis) I was NOT FORCED to wear it. It was my own choice!" FUQ: So, it was your own choice? A2: "Yes, I am not generalizing, but some girls like hearing from my friends, cousins... they told me their parents or relatives forced them to wear Hijab, yet for my case, I was not forced to wear it. IT WAS MY OWN CHOICE!" (With an emphasis) Q3.P1: What does Hijab signify to you? A3: Participant: "You mean when I wear Hijab?" Interviewer: "Yes!" A3: "When I wear Hijab, I feel like I am more EMPOWERED and ACTING</p>	<p>Describing the 1st day of wearing the Hijab as exciting and extraordinary</p> <p>The use of Exciting - Extraordinary - is it that exciting? why? NEVER - transformation? The idea that there is a state of transformation - yet from what to what? Having a problem a problem styling my Hijab and putting pins - does it signify that the transition is challenging? Describing the 1st day at school high school wearing the Hijab - was it that significant? Hard day - in what terms? Fashionable / Stylish - is it that important to her to appear that way? Describing her feelings wearing the Hijab for the 1st time. Difficult. The use of a string of language to describe the 1st day of wearing the Hijab - was it that challenging? Did not get used to see me wearing the Hijab - transformation The idea of appearance transformation different or maybe not at all to others.</p> <p>Strange - The use of different - strange - does it signify discomfort or the opposite?</p>
<p>How this is meaningful</p>	<p>WITH WHAT ALLAH SWT told us to do in the Quran and the Sunnah! It also defines me as a BEING A MUSLIM and a person who follows his DEEN". Q3, Part 2: Has this significance changed over time? Like from the time you have worn your Hijab until now? A3. P2: "Umm, to be HONEST... The first time I have started wearing hijab until now... The HIJAB AS A CONCEPT has changed OVERTIME. Like for the first time when I wore it, it was just something...umm like what to say it... to IMMEDIATE my friends, especially my close friend, she used to wear Hijab at a very young age! We were all the time going to the school together! SHE WAS NOT LIKE ME! She was wearing Hijab and I was not... like I have just worn it to LOOK LIKE HER and the girls whom I saw wearing Hijabs. YET THROUGH TIME, its meaning has changed for me. So, it begins to have like Different meanings and that was through READING and SOCIAL MEDIA. The significance of Hijab has changed OVERTIME! FUQ: Could you please elaborate more on how it has changed for you now? A3.P2: "Because like Hijab was something that asked to BE WORN BY THE WIVES OF THE PROPHET PBUH and later by the Muslim women, which mean it has...umm like a RELIGIOUS SIGNIFICANCE for it to wear like to appear MORE MUSLIM" FUQ: You have said that you imitated your friend, like when you have worn it you were so young. So, have not you worn it for a religious purpose? A3.P2: "NO! (Laughing), at the beginning I just wanted to cover my hair and to LOOK THE SAME AS MY FRIEND! I WAS NOT AWARE of the REAL MEANING behind Wearing</p>	<p>Empowered - Strength? Acting with what Allah told us to do - commitment? Being a Muslim - Identity? The idea that Hijab signifies strength, commitment and identity. follows - her own commitment? - why is it important to allow that through Hijab? Am honest tone As a concept - what does it mean? in what terms? The idea that wearing Hijab is a long process. Learning new things each time Overtime? It was just something - does it important changed over time immediate, close friends young age, together - influence The idea that there the influence of her environment got her decision to wear the Hijab. "Look like her" - role model? Thoughting again the importance of taking in understanding Hijab. The significance of Hijab allowed from a simple imitation to gain a deeper meaning a religious meaning daughter - a sarcastic tone</p> <p>real meaning of wearing the Hijab? not only religious to her? to look the same as my friend - imitation again I was not aware of the real meaning - in the end</p>

Figure 1 The Process of Developing Exploring notes/ Initial Notes

Step 3: Developing emergent themes

At this stage of data analysis, the volume of the data was reduced, while the complexity was enhanced. The exploratory notes, written on the right-hand margin, shaped the initial points for the interpretation which was about creating the emergent themes. Smith et al (2009, p.92) recommends mapping relationships, patterns and connections between exploratory notes “the main task in turning notes into themes involves an attempt to produce a concise and pithy statement of what was important in the various comments attached to a piece of transcript”.

Due to the lack of space, the emergent themes were documented in another document. During this stage, short phrases were created, which the researcher considered captured the essence of the exploratory notes. As the example shows exploratory notes were reduced to emergent themes such as “the feelings while wearing the Hijab for the first time”, “transformation or transition (different appearance)” “the feeling of Otherness/ feeling different or strange”, “the role of the Hijab in empowering the participant”. The next step dealt with searching for connections across emergent themes.

Transcript	Emergent themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>Q1: When did you first start to cover and wear Hijab? A1: "So, good evening. The First time I started to wear Hijab was at the age of 17 years old, exactly at the 1st year of high school. It was a very EXCITING day and EXTRAORDINARY day also because I have NEVER been outside wearing a hijab. Also, I was like having a problem styling my Hijab and putting pins to be more stylish and to appear in a fashionable way, so it was also the first day at high school which makes it a very HARD day. FUQ: How did you feel? like how other people reacted to you when you first started wearing Hijab? A1: "It was something DIFFICULT, especially because my friends, my family, and neighbours did not get to see me wearing Hijab. I was like all the time getting outside with like... my hair, so oh yeah, it was something DIFFERENT, I appeared in a DIFFERENT APPEARANCE at that day" FUQ: So, it was strange A1: "YES, IT WAS STRANGE!" Q2: Were you forced to wear Hijab? A2: "NO! (With an emphasis) I was NOT FORCED to wear it. It was my own choice!" FUQ: So, it was your own choice? A2: "Yes, I am not generalizing, but some girls like hearing from my friends, cousins... they told me their parents or relatives forced them to wear Hijab, yet for my case, I was not forced to wear it. IT WAS MY OWN CHOICE!" (With an emphasize). Q3.P1: What does Hijab signify to you? A3: Participant: "You mean when I wear Hijab?" Interviewer: Yes! A3: "When I wear Hijab, I feel like I am more EMPOWERED and ACTING</p>	<p>The feeling of wearing Hijab for the 1st time</p> <p>- Transformation - Transition (different appearance)</p> <p>- Challenges of Hijab wearing</p> <p>- Fashion</p> <p>Otherness - The Other feeling different not strange</p> <p>Empowerment - Strength - (the role of Hijab in empowering the participant)</p> <p>commitment</p>	<p>The meaning of Hijab</p> <p>Choice to wear Hijab</p> <p>Otherness</p> <p>Empowerment</p>

Figure 2 Reducing Emerging Themes to Superordinate Themes

Step 4: Looking for connections across emergent themes

This step looked for connections amongst the emergent themes to form superordinate or master themes. It involved mapping the themes to fit together, which required moving forwards and backwards between the list of themes to establish a connection. This process was conducted manually instead of using a software. As per Clarke (2009), the manual analysis of the data enables the researcher to engage with the data at a deeper and richer level, which helps in developing familiarity and intimacy with the data. Furthermore, Smith et al., (2009) proposes that the analyst should be innovative and creative in looking for patterns across emergent themes. Reducing the expressions of the emergent themes into one concept helped in tracking the parts where some ideas need to be placed under a master theme. For instance: in Mimi's case "the feeling of being different or strange" was reduced to one single concept "Otherness". Thus, creating a master/ superordinate theme that might include other emergent themes like "the feeling of not fitting in". After conducting the analysis of the first transcript, the following focused on analysing a new transcript.

Figure 3 An Illustration of the Process of Establishing Connections between Emergent Themes in One of the Transcripts

choice

Modesty

Otherness

choice

FUC: You have said that you imitated your friend, like when you were young. So, have not you worn it for a religious purpose?
 A3.P2: "NO! (laughing), at the beginning I just wanted to cover my hair and to LOOK THE SAME AS MY FRIEND! I WAS NOT AWARE OF THE REAL MEANING behind Wearing."

FUC: How did you feel? like how other people reacted to you when you first started wearing Hijab?
 A1: "It was something DIFFICULT, especially because my friends, my family, and neighbours did not get to see me wearing Hijab. I was like all the time getting outside with like... my hair, so oh yeah, it was something DIFFERENT, I appeared in a DIFFERENT APPEARANCE at that day."

that was... READING and SOCIAL MEDIA. The significance of Hijab has changed OVERTIME!
 FUC: Could you please elaborate more on how it has changed for you?
 A3.P2: "Certainly! And I think it will be clearer with the upcoming years, the more we learn about something, the better we become."
 Q4: What would you say motivates you to wear Hijab?
 A4: "As I have said, it was out of imitation. The second thing is that I WANT TO HIDE MY BOOBS."

Modesty

your clothes, you put your hijab on and go so quickly, uhm... like I am talking about myself. I mean you do not have to follow FASHIONABLE

(laughing), especially because... um like we get so HARRASED, especial if you pass by a shop and there is a GROUP of BOYS, and they start looking at you. So wearing Hijab was a thing that would prevent these MEN from looking at my BOOBS me or saying BAD WORDS to me"
 FUC: So, do you mean that Hijab was a kind of a tool to protect you?

from harassment?
 A4: "Yes, I used it as a PROTECTOR and have said and to hide some of my BOOBS to protect me from HARRASSMENT AND ALL SORTS OF THINGS LIKE THAT! Also, I thought when I was 17 years old that those who wear hijab are GOOD MUSLIM WHO DO NOT COMMIT SINS OR MISTAKES, THEY ARE SO STRAIGHT AND THEY DO NOT LIKE BEHAVING IN A BAD WAY, THIS IS AS"

FUC: So, do you feel confident or satisfied when wearing hijab? How do you feel about your appearance?
 A7: "I make sure when I wear it that I wear something that is not TIGHT, that is very LARGE. Also, I make sure that I behave WELL in my environment."

another motivator! THEY ARE OSMODEST AND MORE PIOUS AND HAVE A HIGH LEVEL OF CHASTITY"
 Q5: What are the practical purposes of wearing Hijab to you?
 A5: "The 1st thing that maybe all girls agree upon is YOU DO NOT HAVE TO STYLE YOUR HAIR... uhm like you wake up directly and wear Hijab, yet now because of immersing in understanding the meaning of Hijab in Quran's verses and what does it MEAN in Islam, like for example why MUSLIM WOMEN SHOULD COVER THEIR HEADS AND BODIES, THIS THE SIGNIFICANCE HAS ABSOLUTELY"

FUC: So, it was strange
 A1: "YES, IT WAS STRANGE"
 Q2: Were you forced to wear Hijab?
 A2: "NO! (With an emphasis) I WAS NOT FORCED to wear it. It was my own choice!"
 FUC: So..."

FUC: So, are you saying that Hijab is protecting you from being exposed to the Western media beauty standards?
 A7: "YES EXACTLY (With assertion)"
 Q8.P1: Do you work or study?
 A8: "I study."
 Q8.P2: If yes, do you think that Hijab has an influence on your position in society? Can you please tell me more about your experience as a worker or a student?
 "Yes, BOTH HERE IN SCOTLAND AND ALGERIA. I would like to give examples. In Algeria, for example, when we were in schools, we were getting a very DIFFERENT TREATMENT from the parts of our teachers. I mean uhm... the girls who did not wear hijab used to get a SPECIAL TREATMENT and of course this is based on my OWN EXPERIENCE. I HAVE LIVED THAT. Those who do not wear hijab were all the time VALUED AND LOOKED AFTER! UNLIKE US, I mean even if you are a HARDWORKING STUDENT, YOU STUDY WELL AND ALL THE TIME ON TIME! (SEEMS UPSET)... YOU WILL NOT BE"

...as much PIOUS, so yeah! I can say to be DESCRIBED as a Muslim like when OTHER people see me as a so, they will not believe with me in another BEHAVIOUR LIKE THEY WILL RESPECT ME!
 Q7: 7. How has wearing Hijab affected, if at all, your own body image?
 A7: "Like for example when being in public wearing hijab, people will ALL THE TIME LOOK AT YOU"

and not OCCUPIED with the beauty standards that are imposed by the society

Figure 4 Examples of connection between emergent themes

stereotypes

Hijab's meaning

TREATED AS THE GIRLS WHO ARE MODERNIZED IN ALGERIA WE CALL WOMEN WHO DO NOT WEAR HIJAB "CIVILIZED" ... As for here in Scotland, for me like being a student here in Scotland and looking for a JOB is an OBSTACLE because of my hijab. I want also to share an anecdote. I was with a friend of mine, we were shopping and when passing the street, there was a car behind us, the driver started cursing and saying bad things to us. I assume this was because we were both wearing hijabs. I think if we were GIRLS OF HIS COUNTRY, he would not insult us this way. In addition, I lived in a

...especially in wearing it (especially) at the time like according to me and what I feel is UNDESIRABLE for wearing it. So, I have never tried my body image.

Q1: When did you first start to cover up your hair?
 A1: "So, I started wearing Hijab. The first time I started to wear Hijab was at the age of 17 years old, exactly at the 1st year of high school. It was a very EXCITING day and EXTRAORDINARY day and I have NEVER BEEN outside wearing a hijab. Also, I was like having a problem styling my Hijab and to appear in a fashionable way, so it was also the first day at high school which makes it a very HAPPY day."

Q3. Part2: Has this significance changed over time? Like from the time you have worn your Hijab until now?
 A3. P2: "Uhm, to be HONEST, The first time I have started wearing Hijab until now... The HIJAB AS A CONCEPT has changed OVERTIME. Like for the first time when I wore it, it was just something...umm like what to say it... to IMITATE my friends, especially my close friend, she used to wear Hijab at a very young age! We were all the time going to the school together. SHE WAS NOT LIKE ME! She was wearing Hijab and I was not... like I have just worn it to LOOK LIKE HER and the girls whom I saw wearing Hijabs, YET THROUGH TIME, its meaning has changed for me. So, it began to have like Different meanings"

...religious aims of wearing Hijab to you? And especially because you're now in a European country!
 A6: "To be IDENTIFIED AS A MUSLIM LIKE SHE WAS FOLLOWING THE SUNNAH! Because women at the age of PUBERTY at the time of our"

Religiosity

A3.P2: "Because like I have been something that used to be WORN BY THE WIVES OF THE PROPHET PRUH and later by the Muslim women, which mean it has... uhm like a RELIGIOUS SIGNIFICANCE for MUSLIMS."

Agency EMPOWERMENT

...things like you wear things ACCORDING TO YOU, YOU ARE NOT OBLIGED TO FOLLOW WHAT OTHERS DO."
 A8: "Who are the faith based partners of wearing Hijab to you? Elaborate more... would you like to interview? (What was the...)"

...I feel like wearing Hijab to you? Friends or relatives that I had met to wear Hijab for my creed. I was not forced to wear it. IT WAS MY OWN CHOICE! (MUM) ..."

...I feel like wearing Hijab to you? Friends or relatives that I had met to wear Hijab for my creed. I was not forced to wear it. IT WAS MY OWN CHOICE! (MUM) ..."

Figure 5 Establishing Connection between Emergent Themes part two

Step 5: Moving to the next case

This stage of analysis required focusing mainly on the new transcript. Due to the idiographic nature of the IPA, the previous steps were repeated for each transcript. However, it was important to set aside ideas that were developed from the analysis of the first transcript. That is a part of preserving the individuality and the uniqueness of each case and to abide to the idiographic nature of IPA (Smith et al., 2009).

Step 6: Searching for patterns across cases

The last step of the analysis focused on finding patterns across cases by comparing the table summary for each participant. This stage involved comparing individual cases to find commonalities that help in re-establishing and reconfiguring the themes. Furthermore, some of the emergent original themes were brought together while other sub-themes were upgraded to be a new theme. Colours were used to highlight similarities. The following figure illustrates the process of connecting cases. For instance, orange was used to point out the participants that mention the theme of “Hijab as a cultural garment” and blue was used to highlight “the personal choice to cover”.

NIMA	Zayneb	NAZ	Aroufou FATI	Shray
Hijab as a process that improve quality. Unique perspective. Hijab is a personal choice. Wearing long garments is a sign of modesty. Hijab is a journey (a process). Hijab is a sign of modesty (Hijab + fashion). Hijab is a journey (a process). Hijab is a sign of modesty (Hijab + fashion). Hijab is a journey (a process). Hijab is a sign of modesty (Hijab + fashion).	Hijab is more than a piece of fabric. Hijab is a personal choice. Hijab is a common practice. Hijab is a sign of modesty. Hijab is a journey (a process). Hijab is a sign of modesty (Hijab + fashion). Hijab is a journey (a process). Hijab is a sign of modesty (Hijab + fashion). Hijab is a journey (a process). Hijab is a sign of modesty (Hijab + fashion).	Hijab as a common practice of other cultures. A transition (Hijab is a process). The impact of Modesty (personal choice). Feeling more secure and powerful. Protection from sexual gaze. Hijab was an uncommon practice in Dundee. Increase in religious responsibility.	The feeling of other cultures. A transition (Hijab is a process). The impact of Modesty (personal choice). Feeling more secure and powerful. Protection from sexual gaze. Hijab was an uncommon practice in Dundee. Increase in religious responsibility.	Hijab was not a common thing in Libya. It was not the norm. Personal choice. Family disagreement. Desiring to wear the hijab as a sign of modesty. Identity marker.
SouSou	Zayneb	NAZ	Aroufou FATI	Shray
Wearing hijab at a mature age. For family pressure.	Personal choice/wearing hijab at an early age (totally her choice). A religious...	A very young age. Hijab as a part of the Saudi constitution (cultural).	Hijab was an uncommon practice in Dundee. Increase in religious responsibility.	Puberty (Hijab as a sign of stepping to adulthood). Hijab as a part of Rev...

Figure 6 Establishing Connections Across Cases

HANA	FOUZ	NEJ	SAN	NOU NOU	WINDO
<p>"culturally expected to wear Hijab in Yemen (spatial) when reaching puberty. -Thesis is it a personal choice? Never took it off since. The influence of her environment feeling different when moving to the West identity marker in the West changing a style to fit in modesty but does not protect from SA</p>	<p>Hijab as a marker of her Muslim identity. Modesty is a must when wearing the Hijab. Hijab as a tool to show or express her Muslim faith. A process that goes from cultural to religious (une petite)</p>	<p>-feeling weird when we are in the Hijab in public spaces. Hijab is a personal journey and a religious choice. A unique perspective (relating to Hijab to a terrible event (her boy's death). Hijab MUST be MODEST gradual change in her Hijab (becoming more cautious and modest) feeling more comfortable with her BI</p>	<p>wearing Hijab at a mature age (personal choice) pride in showing Muslim identity. sign of religion (people respect those who touch with their religion). Struggle to deal with otherness (difference) modesty (wearing Hijab from a part-tie to full tie) religious motives</p>	<p>Hijab is a part of her family's Norms. Reaching puberty a marker of Muslim identity. feeling of otherness w/ difference (her daughter as an example). Hijab was invested with political meanings esp post-9/11. Hijab as a means of modesty and protection from male gaze. The stereotype of the Hijab</p>	<p>Hijab was completely for personal choice. her family opposed her Hijab at first due to economic reasons. feeling of otherness with her family. Hijab was not a common practice in Indonesian. Restriction (Limits her opportunities). Hijab as a marker of her Muslim identity in the West (Scott). Hijab as a reminder to stay modest. FASLI ION</p>

Figure 7 Establishing Connections and Looking for Themes Across Cases part 2

5.9. Conclusion:

This chapter outlined the methodological issues of the study. It began by introducing suitable research paradigms for conducting this project, namely critical theory and interpretivism, and how they were combined to conduct this study. Furthermore, it defined and described the qualitative research design, provided the rationale for choosing it, and offered various principles for conducting rigorous qualitative research. Moreover, it discussed semi-structured in-depth interviews, through which data for this interview were collected. Furthermore, it explained the theoretical underpinnings of interpretive phenomenological analysis as an approach to data analysis and its usefulness for the study, providing the rationale for using it and discussed the limitations of this method. Furthermore, it addressed important ethical considerations that were required to conduct rigorous and ethical research. Finally, it overviewed the process of collecting and analysing data (during the fieldwork) by illustrating the various steps of conducting these important processes. Having considered and introduced the different methods used for data collection and analysis. The next chapter marks the first findings chapter and focuses on various issues related to the significance of wearing the Hijab.

6. Chapter six: Findings and Discussion:

6.The Significance and the Reasons for Wearing the Hijab:

6.1. Introduction:

This chapter deals with the significance and reasons that the participants attribute to the wearing of the Hijab. It starts with presenting the findings and it moves to establishing a discussion with the already existing literature and theories. First, the findings show that the choice to wear the Hijab is tackled from two fundamental areas or perspectives, the religious and the cultural. In addition, the participants add personal and psychological motives for why they choose to cover. Moreover, the concept of modesty is discussed in relation to the Hijab because the participants rigorously mentioned it. In addition, this theme was related to other ideas like fashion and body image. Finally, this chapter provides a discussion, in which previous literature is discussed in relation to the findings.

6.2.1 The Choice to Wear Hijab: A Cultural Perspective (A Process that Goes from the Cultural Understanding to the Religious one)

The analysis suggests that the motivation to wear the Hijab stems primarily from religious reasons. However, some of the participants explain that Hijab was a lengthy process that starts with imitating their surroundings such as imitating their mothers, big sisters, and relatives. Imitation meant that they wore it to comply the norms and traditions of their culture. It was until later that they understood the religious meaning of it. For instance, Naz (37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife) explained:

Well, I was quite young when I started wearing the Hijab probably 8 years old because I was born and brought up in Saudi Arabia, they have some restrictions. It all started from the country restrictions probably when I was 8 years old, I was raised in Saudi Arabia, and I have been to Pakistan many times I did my high school studies in Pakistan as well! In Pakistan, I was wearing Hijab out of my choice, but in Saudi Arabia, it was a part of the culture and the constitution (Naz,37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife).

The participant wore Hijab at 8 years old, which is a very young age. She explained that she only grasped the meaning of the Hijab later in her life. Because she was raised in Saudi Arabia, she was obliged to conform to the norms and the rules of the constitution. When asking the participant about the feelings she had when first covering, she explained that she was “happy” and “satisfied” because Hijab was a common thing, and she was about to hit puberty, which is the age at which most Muslim girls cover. “I mean it is a standard, which means I was a teenager, I was happy because we were raised in that culture, so we have seen every girl wearing it, few of my friends did not like wearing it at that time, but I was happy wearing Hijab, at that time I did not understand the meaning of the Hijab” (Naz, 37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife).

From her perspective, Hijab was a process that started with imitation and moved to a deeper level, a spiritual level. The participant stated: “I understood it only as a part of that culture, I understood that I need to wear it and cover when going out. Until later in my life” (Naz, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife). Using the expression “Until later in my life”

indicates that Naz (37 years old, Glasgow, Married, Housewife) wore Hijab for a long period of time without understanding the actual meaning of it. In addition, wearing Hijab seems to offer her a feeling of security after moving to Pakistan and using public transport.

I found that wearing the Hijab gave me a sense of security. From my own perspective, because I was going on my own to my college and I was using public transport and I had to walk like 10 mins to the bus, I felt more comfortable going on my own without my mother wearing the Hijab because in Saudi Arabia we used to go with our parents only using the car, but when I went to Pakistan to finish my studies I had to go on my own to the college! I feel more secure and comfortable when I am in my Hijab. (Naz, 37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife).

Naz explained that after understanding the real meaning of the Hijab, she wore it out of her choice. “In Pakistan, I did my bachelor and child qualification. In Pakistan, I was not wearing Hijab for some time, and I start saying that it is not right, so it was like that. And I started wearing Hijab full-time after getting married” (Naz, 37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife). The expression, “I start saying that it is not right” (Naz, 37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, Housewife), suggests that the participant experienced a moment of confusion about whether to wear her Hijab back or not.

The quote also demonstrates that Naz related wearing a Hijab full-time to her marriage. When asked about what she meant by a full-time Hijab, Naz explained: “I meant that I still wear it everywhere even at the gathering with my family and celebrations because earlier I was wearing Hijab when I go alone, but after getting married I started wearing it at gatherings” (Naz, 38-year-old, Glasgow, Pakistani, Married, housewife). The participant’s desire to wear her Hijab full-time at family gatherings is a way of showing respect to her marriage and husband.

Another participant explained that she wore Hijab at a very young age, even younger than the previous participant. Dr Zee (34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed) also shared her experience of wearing the Hijab from a cultural perspective at first “I grew up in a Muslim home where my mom uses the Hijab, so it has always been a part of my dressing, I have always covered my hair as a child, so I cannot say consciously when did I start to cover my hair”. The expression, “I cannot say consciously when did I start to cover my hair”, (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed) implies that the participant was unaware about the meaning of Hijab; it was a part of her Muslim family norms. For example, Dr Zee used the figure of her mother to identify and reflect. She grew up witnessing her mother wearing the Hijab, so it was not “out of place” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed). The participant utilized the idiom “out of place” to explain that Hijab was not something weird or uncommon in her home country, Nigeria “I don’t know, maybe because my mom used it, my mom’s friends used it, so it was not out of place” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed).

Conversely, the participant also used the idiom “Out of place” to show the feeling of difference and exclusion when becoming more aware about the Hijab. Like Naz, Dr Zee’s (34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed) understanding of the Hijab moved from a mere cultural garment to a religious garment. Dr Zee clarified that wearing Hijab was out of her choice until she graduated from secondary school, which means after she became more mature “I started wearing the Hijab at the age of 3 or 4 years old. The scarf was just a part of

my dressing, my mom will always make me wear it. At that time, I was wearing it without being conscious of its meaning. I started to be conscious about it in 2011 and I started wearing a full Hijab in 2012. I think I was 24 at that time” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed). The statement “My mom will always make me wear it” and the very young age of the participant, which is 3 /4 years old, implicate that the participant did not consent or choose to wear Hijab at that age.

Furthermore, Dr Zee demonstrated that she felt shy about it during high school, and she had to remove it to conform to the school’s dress code “I would say getting into the secondary school, I was not using it so, I think at that time I was getting self-conscious, I was so shy about it because it was not the norm in secondary school, so I was shy about it, I was not using it. it was difficult for me to use it by myself” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed). The participant’s repetition of the expression “shy about it” manifests how she was insecure and uncomfortable about being among the few students wearing Hijab and not conforming to the school’s uniform “At the age of 3 when they used to make me wear it, I did not honestly feel anything about it. I was so unconscious about it. As children, you know, we do not give things a lot of attention. We just follow what we think is normal. But when I started getting self-conscious about it in secondary school, I started to be shy about it” (Dr Zee,34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed).

The participant’s statement, “We just follow what we think is normal” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed), confirms that Hijab was not worn out of her choice at first, it was just a matter of norms and culture. Therefore, she went through a process of being unconscious/ unaware of what the Hijab is to understand the importance of it and wearing it out of choice. In addition, she clarified that she wore Jilbab²⁵, which her family found extreme.

The irony is that as I have said I am from a Muslim Family, I am the only daughter, so I remember there was an incident and as I have told you I was not wearing Hijab properly, so my father told me you either choose to wear Hijab properly or you remove it! yet when I started wearing *Jilbab*, my parents thought that it was too much. I got a bit of resistance. They were the ones introducing me to Hijab, but they felt it was too much. But gradually they accepted it, it was a bit of a challenge at some points. Sometimes they were afraid I am going to get to the extreme by adding more and more layers (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed)

The meaning of the Hijab transforms from an everyday normal garment to a religious identity marker. Dr Zee (34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed) explains:

The Hijab signifies my obedience to Allah, it also signifies my identity, I just see it as who I am. I think its significance changed over time, because initially when I was wearing it as a child it was a part of my dressing, I did not understand its significance, but over time, sometimes, I wore it as an adornment, I wore it as fashion. I did not wear it for religious purposes. Through time, I understood that it is not something that I can take whenever I want! It is a significant part of me! It is what makes me Muslim!

This shows that wearing the Hijab is a process that changes through time. Age also plays an important role in Dr Zee’s case. She illustrated four major stages of her journey of Hijab

wearing, being unaware of the Hijab meaning as a child, being aware of Hijab at secondary school and removing it, wearing Hijab as a fashion garment, and wearing what she refers to as an extreme Hijab, the *Jilbab*.

The participant also marked a liaison between the Western concept of freedom of choice and the traditional concept of the Hijab as a religious obligation. In other words, Hijab signifies both her personal choice and her commitment to her faith. In addition, she employed two figurative expressions to explain that Hijab is an important part of her religious identity “I just see it as who I am” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed) and “It is a significant part of me. It is what makes me Muslim” (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed). Therefore, the meaning of the Hijab developed from a normal cultural garment to symbolizing the participant’s religious identity.

Similarly, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. Student) believed that it was not her choice to put on Hijab when she first started wearing it. Wearing Hijab was a product of cultural and familial norms. She clarified that it was her family’s norms that girls must cover when reaching puberty “I mean my family was the one who suggested this. It was not like really forced. But it was not my choice either. So, my parents knew that I reached puberty, and they suggested to me that I need to start wearing the Hijab.” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. Student). The expression demonstrates mixed feelings about the participant’s desire to wear Hijab at the age of puberty.

When asked about how she felt when first putting Hijab, her tone was upset and she manifested a regret about putting Hijab on at some points in her life “At the beginning I was so excited about wearing the Hijab, I felt people would praise that because it is something that is pleasant and good, I feel like when people saw me wearing Hijab at a very young age, they will think like that. So that is why I was so excited to wear it. I was so happy at that time! Like my feelings about Hijab changed” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student). The participant’s decision to put Hijab at that age stemmed from the way other people think in her culture. Hijab seems to be a tool to measure religiosity, which means the degree a person is committed to a religion. Consequently, the participant showed excitement about wearing Hijab to be perceived as a pious or a good girl. Furthermore, the issue is that Mimi did not understand the true meaning of the Hijab at first, she wore the Hijab because of imitation. She described Hijab as widespread practice in her home country, Algeria.

In the beginning, it was out of imitation like I have my sisters and friends covering at the same age, it is common in my home country, I felt it was a way of imitation, I mean positive imitation, I mean people will receive it as a good thing, so at that time that was my understanding of Hijab. I have not understood the true meaning of the Hijab at that time (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student).

Moreover, the participant illustrated that wearing Hijab in her culture differs from one family to another. The role of gender is highlighted by Mimi, who described her father and brothers as “conservatives” for letting her cover at a very early age.

Not really, I was not forced, as I mentioned, it was not my choice. Because of my family and culture... because it depends on one family to another but let me be precise. It was my family; I mean my family is conservative and any girl that reaches

puberty needs to cover. Especially my father and brothers, they are so conservative, I consider them so. Because they let me cover my hair at that very young age (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student)

However, Mimi elucidated that she was not forced to wear Hijab, and her parent introduce her gently to it. Like the previous cases, Mimi identified with her mother and other women in her society. She described the way she viewed women who wear the Hijab as “wise and responsible.” The Hijab, here, is a sign of stepping into adulthood. In her cultural context, Hijab appears as a sign of adulthood and offers a girl appreciation and prestige.

Yes, but you know sometimes when we play, we imitate our sisters and mothers, like even when we are playing the games, we cover our heads to pretend that we are someone elder, someone, responsible. So at that age, I consider the person who wears Hijab as someone old, so maybe see that... someone who is really wise, responsible, mature and conscious about her decisions and actions...I accepted that my sisters also wear it and all of them are older than me, so I was kind of influenced by my friends and sisters (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student).

The above statement explains that the participant’s desire to wear Hijab was influenced by observing and mimicking the women in her circle. She wanted to imitate her sisters and friends. In addition, as Mimi explained before that woman in her family, are required to cover when reaching puberty. Puberty is a sign of stepping into adulthood. She was covered before her sisters because she reached puberty at different age. Therefore, puberty, here, is an important element that her family takes into consideration “All my sisters put on Hijab at puberty age, just to explain a point, not all of us reached puberty at the same age, so the age of putting on Hijab was certainly different. I believe my eldest sister put it even before she reached puberty. It was totally her choice. The others reached puberty at 15 years. So, the idea is not actually about the age, but about the age you reach puberty” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student).

Like Naz and Dr Zee, Mimi believed that the meaning of the Hijab changed through time from a mere piece of fabric to an essential element that defines her social image and displays her faith. “Now I feel that it is important because Hijab for me is a part of my life, it is important to me, and it is important as a social image, if I may say” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student). When asked what she meant by a social image, she stated “I mean as a Muslim girl, I feel it is necessary to complete this proper image, you need to cover your hair, it is a matter of identity, personally, I feel like it is an obligation to do that we are obliged to fulfil in our religion and our culture”(Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student) . Using the adjective “proper” shows that the participant perceives Hijab as an important marker of the Muslim women’s religious and cultural identity. In addition, Mimi shifted from using the singular pronoun “I” to the pronouns “we” and “our” to express a sense of belonging to her religion and culture.

Additionally, from her standpoint, Hijab is more of a cultural garment than a religious one because most of the women in her culture wear Hijab without understanding its true meaning “I would say both. But I believe it is more of a cultural thing because women in my culture, sometimes, do not know what the real purpose of putting a Hijab on. Because it is not only a piece of cloth to cover your hair, but it also has other requirements like dressing modestly by

covering parts of your body” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student). The participant uses the possessive pronoun “my” to identify with women in her culture and to be more specific. In addition, she mentioned three types of women who wear the Hijab in her culture “In Algeria, we have different cases, there are people who really understand it and wear it out of their choice and their behaviour matches the modesty of the Hijab, others who do not understand it, and those who wear it for the sake of fashion” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student). Like Naz and Dr Zee, Mimi also applied the term “full-Hijab” to show one stage of her Hijab journey. She described going through a process of confusion that led her to better understand the true meaning of the Hijab “So there were four stages of wearing Hijab, 12-18 imitation, 18-25 years old fashion, 25-27 wearing a turban out of fear, 28 a matter of identity and covering properly. Now I have understood Hijab from a religious perspective much better when I started wearing it out of imitation” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student).

Puberty as an expected time for a girl to start wearing Hijab, was also experienced by Hana (36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed). When describing the first time she put Hijab on, she mentioned that Hijab is “Culturally expected” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed), which means she was expected, by her culture and norms, to wear Hijab when reaching puberty. The participant sounded confused when asked whether it was her choice or not. She explained that it was her choice, but it was an automatic thing because she automatically knew that at one point in her life, she is required to cover “I felt okay because I felt it is a choice like I was not told by my parents that it is time for you to wear it. It is something that I grow up knowing that when time reaches, you know what I mean, I knew it was time for me to wear the Hijab. That is how I never take it off” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed). The expression “I felt okay” is a neutral response that lends itself to different interpretations. It gives the impression that the participant is confused about her feelings when she started wearing Hijab. In addition, Hana referred to the Hijab as “never a matter of discussion” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married) in her big family. It is culturally imposed on women to cover in their home country, Yemen, at that age “We have never discussed that. It is the culture that how it is. You have seen it done and you must do it and that’s it” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed). There is a tension between the Western concept of choice and the programmed meaning of choice. Furthermore, Hana identified with women in her culture. She mentioned that she grew up witnessing most women in Hijab and that is why she programmed herself to wear Hijab at that exact time. The definition of the Hijab shifts from a cultural garment to a religious requirement and identity marker.

Hijab signifies to me now my identity and religion. I would say it signifies my identity in the West. I mean it signifies my identity in general... it signifies that I am a Muslim! It signifies to me my connection to Islam because I am by the Quran, Hadith and Sunnah required to wear it because it is an order from God, that is what it means to my obedience to my lord. I had not understood Hijab the first I put it on, it was a cultural thing that everyone put on. It has changed from a cultural to a religious garment. From following the herd and the crowd to an affirmation that this is what I want to do because when you move to the West, It is completely different, you understand that you are seen as someone who is completely different because you

have that cloth on your head. But I keep it on because it is a confirmation of who I am (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed).

After moving to Scotland, Hana regarded Hijab not as a religious garment only, but an identity marker. This signifies that the participant shows a commitment to her identity after moving to the West. She compared the situation in her hometown and in Scotland by using the expression “completely different” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed). This shows a transformation from a society where Hijab is completely normal to one where Hijab is completely different. The participant’s statement, “But I still keep it on because it is a confirmation of who I am” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed), signifies an act of resistance by performing her religious identity in a Western country. Furthermore, Hana adapted double consciousness to live in the West by trying to westernize her clothing style “I mean a different style yes. I just put an under hijab on. My clothes changed when I used to be in Yemen, I used to wear Abaya you know the large dress, and since I moved to the UK. It has changed, I would say it is more Western clothing with a modest twist on it like wearing jeans, trousers, dresses...” (Hana, 36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married, employed).

The above examples show the Hijab as a process that develops from being a mere cultural garment to a religious and identity marker. The following participants may share similar experiences with the previous ones. However, the difference can be in providing primarily religious perspectives on their agency and choice to cover.

6.2.2.-The Choice to Wear Hijab: A Religious Perspective

Unlike previous participants’ that wore the Hijab because it was a common thing and tradition in their home countries, some participants chose to wear the Hijab themselves primarily because of religious motives. They understood Hijab from the beginning as a religious garment that is instructed by *Allah* (God in Islam). For instance, Fati (53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed) expressed that Hijab was totally her choice, and she wore it at a mature age.

I started wearing the Hijab when I was 25 years old, almost years ago, there were not a lot of people wearing a Hijab, I was going to Portugal and my mom’s sister was wearing Hijab, she was wearing Niqab when I saw her, I said what a beautiful woman, she is amazing! When I came back to the UK, I told my parents that I wanted to wear Hijab, they were so happy with my decision, then I started wearing it and a few weeks later my mother started wearing it (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed)

Fati’s agency to wear Hijab is demonstrated through the act of letting her parents know that she wanted to cover. She also associated wearing Hijab for the first time with motherhood “I was working. I was a single mother. It was after I had my son” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed). Furthermore, she utilized adjectives like “happy and satisfied” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed) to express her feeling when she first put Hijab on. Her choice is based on spiritual and religious motives “The way my aunt has said to me that showing one hair is like showing your whole body to your family and that stuck in my head for a very long time and that made me, like oh do not get me wrong I was not religious or anything like that, yet I just felt like I wanted to get

closer to Allah, out of the hundreds of sins that I am doing that one of the sins I am saving myself from” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed). The participant employed, a simile, a figure of speech, where she compares showing one’s hair to being naked in front of her family. This explains the spiritual importance and the beliefs that the participant held the meaning of the Hijab. Additionally, Fati described herself “a whole woman” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed) to explain the way she feels when wearing Hijab. This expression may lead to different interpretations like being a balanced woman, a mature woman, or a feminine woman. She went on to explain that being a complete woman is the courage to express her identity through Hijab “It is like I am so proud of my heritage; I am proud of who I am as a Muslim...Mashallah” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed).

Furthermore, she stated that the Hijab is a personal choice, but in some parts of the interview, she contradicted herself. She believed that the husband could decide if the woman takes off her Hijab or keeps it. The idea of gender relations is expressed in this passage “I think if she loves her husband so much and he asked her to put her Hijab on, I am not saying forcing her, but asking her out of love because when I got married to my second husband, he forced me and I can say that clearly...on our wedding day not to wear my Hijab, so for 12 years...I did not wear the Hijab” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed). Fati expressed a difference between the idea of forcing someone to wear the Hijab and asking someone to wear the Hijab, but this still shows how gender plays a role in her choice to wear Hijab. Additionally, the participant narrated how she was abused by her second husband to take her Hijab off and that is manifested through the relief she displayed when talking about wearing Hijab again when he left her “The minute me and him separated, the first thing I did is putting my Hijab back” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed). She also explained that her husband imposed his Asian identity on her by letting her wear Asian clothes “He wanted me to wear Asian Clothes”. The participant also relates wearing Hijab to being a mother “I decided to start wearing it again and you know I gave birth to my daughter, two weeks he was with me, my daughter was two months when he left and straight away, I put my Hijab on” (Fati, 53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed).

Likewise, Nes’s choice of wearing the Hijab is primarily religious, but unlike Fati’s association of hijab with motherhood, Nes related wearing Hijab to a sad event that she encountered, the death of her brother.

It was sometime in 2012, at the beginning of 2013 maybe I have been thinking about it for a long time, I had a colleague, who is a Muslim revert, she is lovely, and she is still a friend, but I remember once I talked to her and told her that I am thinking about wearing the Hijab...my brother was very sick, my brother had cancer, she told me that you do all the worships, but there is one thing you do not do. She said it is up to you and my brother passed away, then I started wearing Hijab (Nes, 52 years old, British/Pakistani, Dundee, Married, employed).

Although it was the participant’s agency to wear the Hijab, she expressed a feeling of confusion about wearing it for the first time. She felt uncomfortable and she used to forget to put it on some times “It was out of sudden; it took me a while to be ready for it because my daughter was very young, and she had to remind me like you have not got the scarf on! And I had to run and put it on! It took me a while to get used to it, I was very confused” (Nes, 52

years old, British/Pakistani, Dundee, Married, employed). Nes also regards Hijab as a personal thing, she repeated the expression many times throughout the transcript “It is a personal thing, it got to be a personal thing”.

Just as the previous participants, Nes also explained that Hijab signifies her religious identity “It is my faith definitely! When I go outside, I am a Muslim!” (Nes, 52 years old, British/Pakistani, Dundee, Married, employed). Again, the Western concept of choice is intertwined with faith. Like Fati, Nes explained that her brother, who lives in the USA, disagreed with her sudden choice of wearing the Hijab. The only difference is that her brother was worried about her safety in a Western setting “My brother was a bit upset, it was out of sudden, and he said if my husband has asked me to wear it! I said no you know me well I do whatever I want.” (Nes, 52 years old, British/Pakistani, Dundee, Married, employed). Gender relations are expressed through the way her brother assumed she was forced by her husband to wear Hijab.

The same as Nes and Fati, Hadia, who is 19 years old (the youngest participant in the sample), chose to wear Hijab on the first day of the university. The participant utilised the expression “felt right” (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student) to describe how she felt about her choice. This implicates that she was satisfied with her decision “I cannot really describe how I felt about wearing the Hijab for the first time, maybe because I was determined about wearing it. I did not feel any negative thing, I just felt happy in my heart like I was satisfied with it, and that is what matters the most” (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student). The environment around her was supportive of her choice “My parents were so happy with my choice, they have always wanted me to wear it because my mom does, my entire family and friends do, so they have always wanted me to wear it” (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student). The participant identified with her mother and the women around her. This could be an external influence on her decision-making process.

Furthermore, Hadia (19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student) illustrated that she had a desire of wearing Hijab in high school, however, she was not brave enough and ready for all the different questions “I was in high school, and I was not prepared for all the questions and the looks from people, so I just wanted to wait until I enter the university to avoid all that”. Hadia’s hesitation might be due to an external conflict and assumptions that she might be judged, excluded, or treated differently at high school. High school seemed a sensitive environment because her decision to wear Hijab at the university was smooth since no one at the university knows her before, she believed that Hijab transformed her “You have just done something, and it is a change in yourself. I felt like I start the university, nobody knows how my life was before, so I can totally get away with this” (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student). Moreover, she regarded Hijab as a demonstration of her religious commitment and identity “For me Hijab has a more religious meaning because it does help me get closer to my religion and go closer to God and it is like holding a high value in my life, it signifies my strength and courage to be able to wear it. I needed the confidence and putting Hijab on shows that I have great strength”. Using the statement “High value in my life” illustrates how important the Hijab is for the participant.

In addition, The Hijab acts as an identity marker and helps her be recognizable “Hijab also shows my identity to the world, but for me, it shows the religious, confident and strong part” (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student). The participant showed two meanings of

the Hijab, the religious commitment that she kept to herself and the identity expression that she displayed to the world. Like previous cases, the participant manifested a contradiction between the Western concept of choice and the religious meaning of the Hijab in Islam “I don’t think it should be forced, I mean it is compulsory in Islam, but there no women should be forced to wear it. We should be able to make our decisions when we are comfortable” (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student). The participant shifted from using the singular pronoun “I” to the plural pronoun “we” to express shared experience and solidarity with other Muslim women. Unlike Hadia, Wino’s (40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, employed) choice to cover was resisted by her Muslim family. She stated,

I think at that time there was an Islamic retreat and I just contemplated and told my mom I think I will start wearing the Hijab my mom got quite upset and angry and I think she kicked me from the house for some days and she cut off all my Hijabs because my seniors give me clothes and everything because clothes were so expensive at that time and my mom told me she did not have money to change all my uniforms (Wino,40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, employed)

The participant related her experience of wearing the Hijab with a frustrating event in her life. The financial issue was the reason her mother disagreed with the odea of Hijab “It is like money” (Wino,40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, employed). Furthermore, the participant utilized adjectives like “horrible” (Wino, 40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, employed) to describe that event and how she struggled due to her decision. However, her choice was not influenced or changed by her mother’s actions.

The participant also used interpersonal language to explain how Hijab challenged her position in work and social relations “At that time before the reform (Indonesia), it is still under the military reform if you use the Hijab most schools won’t accept you and it will be difficult for you to find a husband” (Wino, 40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, employed). Like the above cases, Wino wore Hijab out of religious understanding “I think it becomes more of a fashion statement. For me, it is about religion, it is my identity in the West... maybe because no I am an adult, and I am quite comfortable with my choice... so that is why I do not care what other people think. I am quite comfortable with my choice” (Wino, 40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, employed). The age factor also plays a significant role in the participant’s strong commitment to her choice. Additionally, Hijab means an identity marker in the West to Wino.

After discussing the cultural and religious agency and choice to cover. The following section shares the importance and reasons for wearing the Hijab with the participants.

6.2.3. Modesty, Protection, and Restriction

6.2.3.1. Modesty and Fashion

The Hijab as a means of modesty and protection was extensively discussed by the participants. However, some participants believe that Hijab also limits their social interactions. For instance, Lina (44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed) explained that, by the Quran and the *Sunnah* (the traditions and practices of the Islamic prophet Muhammad that constitute a model for Muslims to follow), she is required to be

modest. Modesty has a very practical side, which is protecting and saving her from unwanted male attention.

Sure, I have read Surah from Quran, but I do not know them by heart, and it says like tell your women to be modest and wears Hijabs. And with the practicality, there are several practicalities for the safety and modesty of the woman they are not sexual objects, they must be viewed for their minds and their intelligence, they should be viewed as a person and sexuality is just out of it (Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed).

From Lina's standpoint, what makes the Hijab interesting is the fact that it is addressed to both genders. In other words, both men and women are instructed to cover certain body parts and to sustain their modesty in Islam. Lina's perspective shows an aspect of gender equality in Islam "But the most important thing for me is that Hijab is not only for women, but it is also for men, they are not expected to wear scarves, but to be modest and veil their eyes" (Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed).

Furthermore, Lina mentioned that Hijab protects her privacy and her husband's opinion is the only perspective that matters "My husband is the only person that should be looking at me in that way. It is a kind of privacy" (Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed). To illustrate her opinion further about modesty and gender equality, she stated that her husband, too, maintains his modesty by wearing a *Jubbah*²⁶ "As my husband wears a *Jubbah* every day pretty much, he tries to be modest and sometimes he puts a shirt that is tight and my husband has always been a muscular person and I tell him I don't like that" (Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed). Lina also demonstrated power in asking her husband to be modest. Similarly, maintaining modesty is a principal aspect of the Hijab to Nima. Nevertheless, as a wheelchair person, Nima shared encountering difficulties with Hijab when first covering by describing the way she wore the Hijab.

My issues as a wheelchair user, that is why I thought my case will be so interesting to you... when I am trying to prepare my wheelchair. It is difficult when you got the fabric, that is why I wear the lone ones because they move with me when I am moving my head. The loose scarves are likely to cause me injury, so I had to work that out because my safety is important to me and to Allah (Nima, 43 years old, Scottish, married/revert Edinburgh, employed)

The participant's expression, "That is why I thought my case will be so interesting to you", insinuates the unique experience and standpoint of the participant. The participant did not only view the world from the perspective of a Hijabi woman but also a wheelchair user. Her situated knowledge about the Hijab is different and affected by her disability. Modesty also means being simple and humble "It does not matter what and how expensive the clothes are. It is not about showing off to other people. It is all about your relationship with Allah and my relationship with Allah does not change because of a piece of cloth on my head" (Nima, 43 years old, Scottish, married/revert Edinburgh, employed).

Hijab as a tool to sustain modesty was also expressed by Hope (54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, married, employed) who discussed how Hijab helped her to sustain a modest and simple life "For the practical thing, I think Hijab makes things simple". Moreover, she described the way she styled her Hijab by not sticking to Abayas only. The most important

thing is wearing large and loose clothes “When I wear Hijab... I am not sticking to Abaya... I wear different styles...outside I wear a short blouse with a trouser. I don’t feel like I am missing anything!” (Hope, 54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, married, employed). The expression “I don’t feel like I am missing anything” suggests that the participant is feeling satisfied with her Hijab and does not seem to be bothered with it. Hijab is a personal thing to Hope and that was manifested through this expression “I do swimming where people are completely exposed on the side I am completely covered” (Hope, 54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, married, employed).The challenge that Hope mentioned ,while sustaining her modesty through wearing the Islamic swimsuit Burqini in the Scottish context, was that it draws people’s attention to her. Hope mentioned this experience of people approaching her and touching the texture of her burkini “I go swimming in the general in a mixed pool, so I wear Burkini, they all ask me what this is, and some want to touch it”.

Additionally, she compared her experience of modesty to her daughter’s experience. She believed that young women are more likely to wear a fashionable hijab, which is not quite modest. To illustrate that she compared her daughters “I have two daughters, one is wearing Hijab, and one is not. The problem is the one who is wearing the Hijab is more fashionable and the one who is not is simple (laughing) It is amazing to see that, and she loved it. Hijab as well can be fashionable. And can be very difficult for young girls like they must match colours, and you see the internet is full of different styles.” (Hope, 54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, married, employed). The concept of the traditional Hijab versus the fashionable was also rigorously discussed by the participants. Consequently, three views rose. While some participants believed that the Hijab could be fashionable, others explained that it should not be, and the third point of view suggests that it could be balanced.

The modern or fashionable Hijab was discarded by some participants, who viewed it as unacceptable and improper. Nima, for instance, showed her total disagreement with the idea of a fashionable Hijab by considering it as a sin “I want to add something that Hijab in our era is not worn properly because fashion a big percentage, women are not wearing it according to the Hijab standards”. To her, Hijab requires certain criteria “wearing modest and large clothes that do not show parts of your body, you must not wear make-up, bright colours that attract attention, and do not wear for instance a turban like many girls show parts of their hair, neck, and ears... Hijab is also about behaving modestly when wearing Hijab, you must think before wearing anything”. Therefore, the concept of the Hijab does also require behaving modestly. Like Lina, Nima used sarcastic language and compared women who wear fashionable Hijab to “peacocks” “There are certain YouTube channels that show how to put, that is a style thing, that is not Hijab, if you are using that you are not doing what Allah asked us to do, it is more about fashion. I mean they are still modest with it...but it is like being a peacock.”

Conversely, other participants viewed the modern Hijab to fit in Western setting, for instance, Zaynab (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single, PhD student) saw fashionable Hijab as an important move by arguing that it is only the older generation that might disagree with that. She thought of modern Hijab as a way of encouraging young generation to wear it, especially in Scotland, so they could be accepted and fitted in “I think fashion encourages Muslim women to wear Hijab because they want to be stylish and beautiful. I mean to shift to another modern way of Hijab. I think Hijab needs to be kept in its traditional way, but for me I love wearing colours. It is something I like. I don’t think it is a bad thing to be fashionable. It is

like the older generation” (Zaynab, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single, PhD student). Zaynab stated age as a factor to be against the Hijab as a fashionable statement, however, the youngest participant seemed to go in favour of a traditional Hijab unlike Hope, who is among the oldest participants and seems to agree with the Fashionable Hijab.

I think Hijab becomes more about fashion; it has lost some of its significance. I think now there is a Hijabi beauty standard. They are all over social media like Instagram and TikTok. These Hijabies now are being sexualized for wearing Hijab that way. They like seeking attention, it has become more about fashion, especially for men and boys... I feel now like they target Hijabies more than non-Hijabies. I think it gives a bad idea about Hijab (Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student)

The participant expressed a strong disagreement with the modern concept of the Hijab. Many of the participants believed that the youngest generation is more prone to wear Hijab fashionably. However, from Hadia’s standpoint, the fashionable Hijab does not serve the real and true purpose of the Hijab. As a result, the situated views and meanings that the participants contribute to the Hijab differ from one participant to another.

6.2.3.2. Hijab and Body image:

The idea of the Hijab as both restrictive and protective was also discussed regarding the participants’ relations to their bodies. Some of the participants view the experience of the Hijab as a protection to their body image, while others feel unattractive with the Hijab on. One unique experience is that of Nima (43 years old, Scottish, married/revert Edinburgh, employed), the wheelchair user, she revealed how Hijab makes her feel at ease with her body image.

As I said, I was 32 stone in weight! I had a tumour, I was huge, massive. I have lots and lots of surgery. So, I had my tumour removed to be of normal size, but I still have a lot of extra skin. Having lots of weight means that I have a condition called body dysmorphia. So, when I look to the mirror, I still see 32 stone! You still see the worst bit! It is not delusional, but you still cannot get past it. So, your body image is quite worked in that respect. To do these surgeries, I must do some mental evaluation to be able to know if I am sane to undergo these surgeries! And that one around body image! It is very clear whenever I do these questionnaires, I struggle with my body image now! Hopefully, this time I undergo all these surgeries I will be able to hear from it, but when I look in the mirror with my Hijab on, I do not see the body dysmorphia. It is quite incredible.

The participant used personification, which is a literary device, to describe how body dysmorphia disappears once she puts Hijab on “And body dysmorphia just melts away.” In this case, wearing large and modest clothes provides her with a tool for covering and protecting her mind from seeing the extra weight, thus lowering the chances of getting exposed to body dysmorphia. In addition to Nima’s case, Nana shared a positive view of the Hijab regarding her body image. She mentioned that the second motive to wear Hijab was because she wanted to cover a part of her body that she felt uncomfortable showing “As I have said it was out of imitation is that I wanted to hide my boobs (laughing), especially because... uhm like we get harassed, especially if you pass by a shop and there is a group of boys and there is a group of boys” (Nana, 27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student).

Furthermore, the participant seems to relate feeling uncomfortable with being exposed to the other gender and feeling sexualized and objectified. Consequently, the Hijab acts as a shield that makes her feel comfortable with her body.

Some participants argue that the Hijab makes them look older than their actual age. Zaynab, Hana, and Wino, for example, expressed that they feel more attractive and younger without the Hijab “Yes absolutely, I will tell you how, for example, it influences my shape, like if I take it off now in front of you, you will totally see a different person a lot younger than I see with the Hijab on (laughing) like I am young, but I do look very old, very very very old with it” (Zaynab,). She employed repetition to show her irritation with looking old with her Hijab on. On the other hand, some participants believe that they look beautiful and attractive with Hijab on, Sousou (27 years old, Glasgow, Algerian, engaged) and Zizi, for instance, show satisfaction with the way they look with Hijab on. They expressed feeling comfortable in their own skin and not caring about the images promoted by the media “For me I do not care about the beauty ideals and standards that are promoted by the Western media or even in some Muslim countries, there are some advertisements in the media. I have always had a positive body image with my Hijab since I was a child.... I was always happy wearing it because when doing that I did not feel sad or insecure” (Zizi, 28 years old, Glasgow, Algerian, single).

Many participants also believed that the Hijab limits their interaction with people. The performance of the Muslim identity in Scotland can have both advantages and disadvantages. This will be thoroughly discussed in the next chapter which deals with identity performance in Scotland. The next section will include a discussion of this chapter. According to Smith et al., (2022, p. 116), “Usually in IPA studies the analysis or results section is discrete in the sense that the interpretive account provided is a close reading of what the participants have said. This is achieved without reference to the extant literature. Then in the discussion the register changes and you place your work in a wider context.” As a result, in the subsequent section, the results are engaged in a dialogue with the existing literature and theory.

6.3. Discussion:

The above findings suggest that women have different standpoints and reasons behind wearing the Hijab. Starting the research from their standpoints and lived experiences offer a distinctive description of their accounts “It is these distinctive resources, which are not used by conventional researchers, that enable feminism to produce empirically more accurate descriptions and theoretically richer explanations than does conventional research ”(Harding, 1991, p. 119). Therefore, understanding the reasons behind wearing the veil from these perspectives “offers the potential for a richer, more diverse understanding of women’s experiences” (Foss and Foss,1994,.no page). Muslim women are often viewed and defined as a homogenous group that shares the same experience “Just as the images of the veil reifying and otherizing, Muslim women are often perceived as a homogenous entity with similar cognition, effects, and behaviour” (Hoodfar,1993; Mincez,1980, no page). Khan (1995) explains that Muslim women are usually viewed as a part of an undifferentiated group, which is established in conflicting images that are placed within the perspectives of those invested in this image. The Hijab is primarily regarded as solely a marker of identity or resistance in a non-Muslim majority context, nevertheless, Baerveldt (2015) asserts that the Hijab is an

element of the overall expressive style of individual women, linked directly to their individual bodies and life histories. This study tries to dig out the different standpoints by dealing with the relationship that the chosen sample of women has with their Hijabs. Additionally, it provides these women with agency in that they are not situated or restricted within static and generalized meanings of the headscarf.

6.3.1. The Choice to Wear Hijab: A Cultural Perspective

Starting with the agency that the participants have regarding their choice to wear the Hijab, the participants' stories vary depending on the context in which they have covered. The results show that there are two types of agencies to cover. Some women like Dr Zee, Naz, Mimi, and Hana describe their choice to wear Hijab as being influenced by the cultural context in which they were raised before coming to Scotland. However, in Scotland, they explained that Hijab gained more of a mere cultural garment to them, it becomes a Muslim identity marker. Culture, in this case, has an influence on their agency to start wearing the Hijab. According to Shweder (1991) and Vygotsky (1962) (quoted in Valsiner, 2000, p.46), the concepts of culture and psyche dynamically, jointly, mutually, and dialectally build on each other. This suggests that the participants are bound by their cultural contexts. The mentioned participants spent most of their lives in Muslim-majority countries like Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Algeria, and Nigeria. They expressed how they were influenced by their surroundings, which means the reason for accepting the idea of veiling was because most of the women there were wearing the veil, so it was not "out of place" (Dr Zee, 34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married,), it was something normal and natural. As per Wagner et al., (2012), culture is what we experience to be natural; it impacts the individual's decision-making process and agency. Both culture and human agency are intertwined and influence each other, with culture shaping and being shaped by human agency (Dressler et al., 2019). Kashima et al., (2008) proposes that human agency is essentially cultural and acts within the context of culture.

The influence of culture on the agency of some participants is manifested in some participants' experiences of wearing the Hijab. Some participants mentioned the idea of imitation as their first motive to start wearing the Hijab. Hana, for instance, explained that the Hijab was "unnegotiable", which means she was mentally prepared to wear Hijab once she reached puberty. The idea, that the Hijab is "unnegotiable", relates culture to the concept of agency and power "Power, like 'culture' is neither an entity, nor an agent, but the total way in which our practices get coordinated and governed such that they produce possibilities for the agency" (Wagner et al, 2012, p.536). Wagner et al., (2012, p.536) also consider the veil or the hijab as a paradigm case and an example of what they refer to as "the cultural psychology of agency or meaningful expression gained through a language of effect, self-fashioning, cultivation, training, and discipline". The participants explain that when moving to Scotland Hijab becomes more of expressing their religious identities.

6.3.2. The Choice to Wear Hijab: A Religious Perspective

On the contrary, most of the participants who moved to Scotland at a very young age, or they are Scottish-born express that the main reason for choosing to wear a Hijab is primarily religious and their primary motive is to be recognized as Muslims in public. This does not mean that these women have similar experiences, they come from ethnically diverse backgrounds. Hengameh (2017, p.158) uses the term second generation "to identify those

born and brought up in the UK, or who immigrated to the UK at a young age”.

Unlike the previous cases, these women identify themselves as Scottish or British Muslims with diverse ethnic backgrounds, some of them are Scottish who reverted²⁷ to Islam. For instance, Hadia, the youngest participant, who is Scottish born, but from a Pakistani background explained that the main reason for covering is primarily religious and to identify as a Muslim in public. The relationship between Scottishness and Muslim identity is complex and incompatible constructs because they are based on both “self-perceived identity and feelings of belonging, and partly related to how others perceive one’s identity and its (in)compatibility with larger notions of national identity” (Sheikh and Kristiansen, 2017, p.34).

The incompatibility of the Scottishness and Muslim identity is illustrated in Virdee, Kyriakides, and Modood’s (2006) work on cultural codes of belonging and racialized national identities in one of the multi-ethnic Scottish neighbourhoods. The study’s (2006) findings show that being perceived by others as Scottish does not relate to adhering to any personal beliefs and identity, instead, it could be impeded by representing such behavioural and cultural codes “whilst white respondents did not object to the practice of Islam, or even to Islam being compatible with Scottish national identity, they did object to the enforcement of beliefs, which the burqa and the hijab are deemed to represent” (Virdee, Kyriakides, and Modood, 2006, p. 7). According to this study, being a visible Muslim, through wearing the Hijab, does contrast with the Scottish identity representation.

Hadia is not the only case that chooses to wear Hijab in Scotland to be identified as Muslim, also other women can be categorized as second-generation Muslims like Fati, Nes, Lina, and Nima. According to Dwyer (2008, p.145), the veil or the headscarf functions as a strong “signifier of identity” and this is what most women in the study mention. Like Hadia, Fati, who is among the oldest women in the sample and belongs to the second generation of Muslims in Scotland, explained that Hijab acts as an identifier through which she can be proudly recognized as a Muslim. Hijab in this case acts as a link between her Scottish national identity and her Muslim and Mozambican culture. Also, Nes stated that Hijab is a physical representation of her Muslim and Pakistani identity. Shields (2008) states that the expression of one’s identity is always formed by the intersection of various identities. Fati, Hadia, and Nes, for instance, consider themselves Scottish but are still linked to their countries of origin. Greenwood and Hopkins (2013) refer to this as a hybrid or hyphenated²⁸ identities. An example of this is the history of British Muslims. Many British Muslims are from an Asian background like Pakistan, they strongly identify as Muslim and with the UK national identities like British (Maxwell, 2006), or Scottish (Saeed, Blain, and Forbes, 1999). The performance of this hyphenated identity is moderated and achieved through wearing the Hijab according to the participants. Werbner (2004) demonstrates that the act of veiling can be a way of self-segregation that young British Asian adopt to be separated from non-Muslims.

Whereas the North Indian Islam of their parents, embedded in Sufi traditions, tended to be relatively relaxed, with veiling and purdah abandoned in large measure by the Muslim middle classes when they settled in Britain, these days the wearing by women of burqas, elaborate veils, North African-style headscarves, and of beards by men, are linked also to a total abstinence from drinking alcohol and a refusal to participate in British youth and student clubbing culture which celebrates music, dance, sexuality,

drink and drugs in a hedonistic pursuit of pleasure and excitement (Werbner, 2004 p.906).

Therefore, wearing the Hijab is among the practices that British Asian Muslims are still holding on to assert their religious and cultural identity. The Hijab is a reminder to avoid the Western way of life and to reinforce their own identities.

Hijab does not always mean the display of religious and cultural identity. Some of them relate that to some important and emotional events in their lives. Fati, for instance, linked it to motherhood and Nes explained that the decision to wear Hijab was also influenced by the death of her brother. Hence, Hijab does not only have one standard meaning, but it also has different profound meanings that depend on the individual experiences of each participant. The Hijab in these cases is associated with psychological well-being. Aydin (no year available, p.3) explains that the practice of the Hijab has been associated with increased psychological well-being among Muslim women. One study by Jaspers et al., (2012) in New Zealand sample reveals that individuals practicing the Hijab reported great life satisfaction and fewer symptoms of psychological distress. In addition, Eaton (2015) mentions that one way of expressing religiosity among Muslim women is the practice of the Hijab, and religiosity can have a positive impact on psychological and mental well-being. According to a study that was conducted in Kuwait, religiosity is associated with lower anxiety, high self-esteem, and subjective well-being (Abdel-Khalek, 2011). As mentioned above, both participants related the Hijab to emotional and notable events in their lives. Consequently, the Hijab functions as a coping mechanism through which they feel close to their religion, thus having stable mental health.

The mental health issue is also manifested in the relationship between the participants and their bodies. Some participants believe that Hijab has a positive influence on their body image, while others seem to oppose the idea. interviewees like Nima (43 years old, Scottish, married/revert Edinburgh, employed) and Nana (Algerian, 28 years old, Glasgow, Single, PhD student) expressed satisfaction with the way the Hijab helped them with their body image. Nima described the relationship between her disability, body dysmorphia, and the Hijab and Nana showed how the Hijab was useful to hide her chest and feel comfortable around men. As a result, wearing large clothes and maintaining modesty made them comfortable with their bodies. Wazni (2015) and Oren (2018) state that wearing the Hijab provides protection by buffering against appearance-based scrutiny and isolating Muslim women from being exposed to Western ideals and eating disorders.

6.3.3. Modesty, Protection and Restriction:

The question of attractiveness was also discussed among the participants. On the one hand, some participants like Zaynab, Hana, and Wino believe that Hijab makes them look older than their actual age, they feel more attractive without it. On the other hand, Sara and Zizi show satisfaction with the way they appear with the Hijab, which means they feel attractive with and without the Hijab. Different studies are conducted on the effect of the Hijab on facial attractiveness, for example, Swami and Mahmud (2010) investigate the influence of the Hijab on men's perceptions of women's attractiveness and intelligence in Britain. Muslim and non-Muslim men rated a series of images that include veiled and unveiled women. The findings of their study explain that Muslim women were rated negatively compared to unveiled women. Although Muslim and non-Muslim men refer to veiled women as more

religious, they perceived them to be less attractive, approachable, competent, sociable, and popular. The results can be an indicator that wearing the Hijab can negatively affect the personal qualities attributed to the individual. However, this can be due to conducting this research in a context where wearing the Hijab is rare and has a largely non-Muslim national population.

To confirm that another study was recently conducted in the United Arab Emirates, where Islam is the official and majority religion of the country. Sheen et al., (2022) investigates how native Muslim participants perceive Muslim women with the Hijab and without it. The results show that female faces were mostly perceived as less attractive with the Hijab worn. This negative association may indicate the disruption of perceiving human facial attractiveness when external features like hair and ears are obstructed and blocked (Toseeb, Brynat, and Keeble, 2014; Sheen et al., 2018) and the Hijab does cover these parts. Although the Hijab is perceived as making women less attractive, it was mostly associated with pleasant connotations. Accordingly, it has the cultural importance of reducing facial attractiveness in Muslim society (Sheen et al., 2022). In addition, the feeling of in-group membership and a sense of belonging can be one of the reasons why the Hijab is associated with these pleasant connotations. In other words, stereotyping physical attractiveness²⁹ does not depend on physical attraction only, but the individual can be favoured based on the qualities that are highly valued and shared among a certain community and culture³⁰ (Dion et al., 1999).

The Hijab is a crucial tool for maintaining modesty. Most of the participants mentioned the cultural importance of the Hijab in maintaining modesty and privacy. The concept of modesty has a significant relation to the Hijab, and it is addressed to both genders in Islam.

Participants like Lina, Nima, and Hope expressed how wearing the Hijab helped them in sustaining a modest, simple, and humble life. Khan (2023) and William and Vashi (2007) define modesty as a way of expressing reverence, respect, and obedience to God. In addition, it is perceived as an outward symbol of faith and its perception depends on the cultural contexts and sects in Islam. As mentioned before, modesty and Hijab are inscribed to both genders “In Islam, the observance of the modesty of men and women, and protecting privacy to the passers, has had a particular importance, inasmuch as women veil is considered in the religion” (Sadatmoosavi and Shokoohi, 2011.p, 2). Rizvi (1992) states two types of hijabs, namely the Hijab of eyes, which refers to lowering the gaze, and the Hijab of dress, which means covering modestly and properly. Casting down the gaze is required for both genders “The believer men must cast down their gaze and the believer woman must cast down their gaze. None is allowed to look at the opposite sex unless he or she is within the prohibited degree” (Rizvi, 1992, p.11).

Furthermore, wearing the Hijab has some criteria that differ depending on diverse cultures and sects. As per Siraj (2011, p. 728) “Indeed, wearing the hijab does not represent a homogeneous discursive reality for Muslim women around the world, but instead the fluid and changing meaning of the hijab depends upon the spatial context in which it is worn”. Modest dress is described as covering the body in a way that is not revealing or provocative. This consists of the hair and wearing loose-fitting clothes from the neck to the ankle, it should not also be tight because it could draw attention to her body (Khan, 2023). There are several opinions on the extent to which women should cover. Some scholars like Ibn Al Kathir (1981) argues that *Khimar* and *Jilbab* (Hijab) cover the whole body except one eye

and other scholars like Al Tabari (1994) states that women should cover their faces and hands can be exposed. The question, of whether the woman should cover her hands and face, differs from one sect to another “There is a group of Sunni and Shia sects, which says that Ma Zahara Minha means face and hands which according to them women are allowed to keep open. Another group says that it refers to any incidence when any part of her body or adornment becomes uncovered because of uncontrollable reasons such as blowing wind” (Rizvi, 1992, p.14).

The Hijab needs to cover what is referred to as *Awrah*³¹; both men and women are instructed to cover certain parts of their bodies “While the concept of nakedness in Islamic *Shari'a* (a body of Islamic law) has different rules between men and women, such as the limit of male ‘awrah is between the navel and the knees, while the limit of female ‘awrah is the entire body except the face and hands which should be closed using the hijab” (Karyono, Ahmad, and Asmai, 2017). For instance, Lina expressed her satisfaction with the Hijab being instructed for both genders and how her husband also maintains his modesty by wearing a *Jubbah*.

Along with the two previous issues, behaving modestly is another major aspect of the Hijab (Rita, 2017). The concept of the Hijab is more than a piece of cloth “However, it should be noted that Muslim women extend the Hijab to include behaviour that is modest, as the Hijab is intended to form a part of a Muslim’s character, behaviour and identity” (Akhtar, 2011). It helps keep the individual humble, modest, and simple as mentioned by Nima, Lina, and Hope. Additionally, the Hijab has various functions, one of them is maintaining respect and privacy “It shields women from the lustful gaze of men and affords them to gain the respect of their family and peers as it is a visible symbol of admired virtues as piety, chastity, and modesty. It also liberates them from perceived dictates of Western Fashion and from the pervasive sexualization of women’s bodies” (Laborde, 2006, p. 365) and this can be apparent in Mimi’s case where she explained that she wanted to wear the Hijab to be praised by her family and friends.

While Modesty is an essential part of the Hijab, Nima’s unique standpoint differs because she has a disability. As a wheelchair user, she expressed how she struggled to wear large clothes and stick to *Al Amira’s style* (A hijab type) because it is more practical. As mentioned earlier, both the Muslim and disabled identities intersect in Nima’s case and that causes her some challenges. Indeed, Shebaily (2015) explains that long dresses, *Jilbabs*, *Thobes* (jubbah- a long robe for men) and other articles of clothing are not safe to wear by wheelchair users because the materials are easily caught in moving parts of the wheelchair and may cause the wheelchair to stop moving, thus may cause harm to the body.

The concept of modesty was often associated with the concept of fashion. There were different views that opposed or go in favour of the modern or fashionable Hijab. For instance, Hope and Zaynab believe that it is okay for women to be fashionable, especially the younger generation, so they can easily accept and adapt to the Hijab. Zaynab mentioned that it is the younger generation that stick to the idea of the traditional Hijab, nevertheless, Hadia, the youngest participant explains that fashion and Hijab are incompatible. Same to Hadia, Nima used the sarcastic term “Peacock” to refer to those who exaggerate in their adornment. According to Tajudin, Yen, and Lee (2018), nowadays, Hijab is not a mere symbol of religious commitment but a fashion statement. Its styling is not influenced only by traditions,

culture, and religion but trends in modern fashion. Latiff and Alam (2013) believe that the true meaning of the Hijab has diverted, and it is not a fashion statement and never was meant to be. Moreover, Latiff and Alam explain (2013, p. 50) that “the headscarf practice as an embodiment of the Islamic culture has increasingly been stigmatized as the consumer culture in the modern secular society has become prevailed”.

Although Hijab and Fashion seem to be incompatible, modesty can create a balance between the two “Fashion is a form of self-expression, and the growing number of Muslim women leads to experimentation of blending modesty and attraction into their looks” (Chitsaz and Hanzaee, 2011, cited in Aisyah, 2016, p.3). Therefore, the fashionable Hijab can be referred to as a bridge between the East and the West “This recent interest in Muslim fashion also signals the changing dynamics of the ever-increasing interaction among Eastern and Western cultures” (Chitsaz and Hanzaee, 2011, cited in Aisyah, 2016, p.3). Unlike in the past, Muslims, especially Muslim women, can select from a wide selection of designs to create a look that fits their values, traditions, and tastes without compromising any of the three (Rosmah Mansor, 2010). One example is that of Hana, where she explained that she changed her style from wearing Abaya to wearing a more Westernized style of the Hijab to fit in Scottish society. Thus, establishing a balance between the Western and Eastern sense of style.

6.4-Conclusion:

This chapter dealt with the significance and reasons that the participants attribute to the Hijab. It started with presenting the findings and it moved to establishing a discussion with the already existing literature and theories. First, the findings showed that the choice to wear the Hijab is tackled from two main areas or perspectives, the religious and the cultural. Yet, the participants also add personal and psychological motives for why they choose to cover. Next, the concept of modesty was also discussed in relation to the Hijab because it was rigorously mentioned by the participant. In addition, this theme was related to other ideas like fashion and body image. Finally, this chapter provided a discussion, in which previous literature is discussed in relation to the findings. The subsequent chapter discusses the relation between the hijab and feminism. It shows how the participants' relation and understanding of gender equality and female empowerment. Furthermore, it provides a discussion on their standpoints regarding the representation of the veil in the Western media with a specific focus on the Scottish media.

7. Chapter Seven: Gender-specific Perspectives and Media Representations on the Hijab

7.1. Introduction:

The second chapter deals with how the concept of gender influences the conceptualisation of the Hijab from the participants' standpoints. The first part of the chapter is dedicated to the findings, where the views and opinions of the participants will be shared. It consists of a discussion of their opinions regarding how they feel when wearing the Hijab, their views regarding the concept of feminism and gender equality, and how they feel they are perceived by others and represented by the media. The second part of the chapter looks at the findings in the context the already existing theory and literature.

7.2.1. The Hijab and Female Empowerment:

The issues of female empowerment, feminist identity, and gender equality were heavily discussed. Most of the interviewees identified themselves as empowered Muslim woman. Nes (52-year-old, Dundee, Married, Employed) described that she felt powerful and confident while wearing the Hijab. In addition, she made a reference to the women in her circle, who also cover, by depicting them as "strong" women "In my circle, the ones that wear the Hijab are so strong. Confident and powerful. I feel powerful and confident when wearing the Hijab". Moreover, the participant explained how it is challenging to be identified as a Muslim in a Western context and how it is easier not to wear the Hijab "She asked me how you feel, and I said it is easier not to wear it, you are literally walking with a flag up saying this is my religion and this is my belief". Interestingly, one of the meanings of the concept of power and agency, according to the respondent, is the ability to decide who can see her without the Hijab "I think it is my choice whether to display my beauty and body or not. It is my decision to decide who can who is going to see my hair. It is my power and my decision".

Similarly, some participants, like Lina (44 years old, Glasgow, Scottish revert, employed). expressed how it is challenging for her to go outside as an identified Muslim "To me it must be a personal choice, and I also know people who have once the Hijab and removed it. I fully support them in that because it is difficult wearing the Hijab full-time in a Western country" (Lina, 44 years old, Glasgow, Scottish, revert, worker). Using the term "difficult" and relating to those who removed their Hijabs in Scotland, alludes to the courage and the power to be identified as a Muslim in public.

Another participant, Hadia, 19-year-old, Glasgow, student/ employed) when asked about the concept of the Hijab, power, and oppression, explained that Muslim women, like herself, have agency over their choices and it is the toxic culture and patriarchy that created and perpetuated oppression. Furthermore, the participant highlighted a difference between patriarchy and Islam by saying "I believe Islam does preach that we have our rights, and we make our minds, and we have our free will. I think we need to get rid of the cultural toxicity and the patriarchy" (Hadia, 19-year-old, Glasgow, student/employed). The notion of oppression to Hadia, was related to males using religion in their favour to impose their power on women. The youngest participant from this study's sample seemed frustrated with this issue "When forcing women to wear the Hijab, I think it has more to do with the cultural part, they kind of use religion the way they want to impose their power on women" (Hadia, 19-year-old, Glasgow, student/ employed). Hadia's perspective aligns with Nawal El Saadawi's

concept of patriarchal control. According to El Saadawi, religions are not the direct cause of female's oppression and exploitation, however, the patriarchal society uses religion as a tool to control women. Furthermore, El Saadawi argues that societies within Islam intentionally misinterpret Islamic principles to oppress and restrict women (Mazrui & Abala, 1997).

The feeling that the Hijab empowers Muslim women was also shared by Zaynab. As Zaynab (27 years old, Glasgow, Algerian, PhD student) put it: "Hijab empowers me, it makes me feel unique, maybe I am the only one in that group that is wearing the Hijab. It really has that power, it really, really empowers me, it gives me the power to show my identity." Hijab as a tool of self-identification is discussed by Hopkins and Greenwood (2013). Their study shows that the Hijab may be used as an identity performance to consolidate one's belonging to the Muslim community. Moreover, the repetition and the assertion of the term "power" and the verb "empowers" enhances the idea that Hijab gives her the power to perform her religious identity. In fact, previous studies illustrate that the Hijab is recognised as an important signifier of Muslim women's identity (Ahmed, 1992; Barlas, 2002; Othman, 2006; Wagner et al., 2012).

The most surprising aspect of this quote is using the adjective unique to refer to Zaynab's feelings of wearing the Hijab. Being different does not seem to be an issue for Zaynab because she associated being powerful and identifiable with adjectives like "unique" and "different." As discussed earlier in the previous chapter, one of the participants, Dr Zee (Nigerian, 34 years old, married, student/worker), used the term "out of place" to refer to Hijab as being both weird and common in her hometown. Zaynab (27 years old, Algerian, Arab, PhD student) also employed the term "unique" to celebrate the difference that she felt when wearing the Hijab in Scotland. By contrast, Wino expressed frustration with being different by expressing how she felt left out because of the way she dressed "I feel uncomfortable with that, sometimes I feel left out because the way I wear the hijab, and my principles do not match. I am the only one that wears the Hijab in my group and mine is quite bigger" (Wino, 40-year-old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, employed).

The importance of representation in the workplace in encouraging veiled Muslim women to be more confident and comfortable about showing their Muslim identity in public was also discussed by different participants. Having a representation at their workplace or being a representation, themselves helped them or other Muslim women to be comfortable showing their identity, which increase their self-esteem and create a sense of belonging³². For example, Nima (43 years old, Edinburgh, Employed) explained that she felt empowered when she was often the only person in the room. She said:

Whereas now the things that I do as a disabled advocate, I am often the only Hijabi person in the room and on Zoom. At that point, I am very identifiable as a Muslim and that is very important in terms of representation! In terms of furthering Islam that talking about disability with people like the Scottish government and they can see that I am well-spoken, very clear, and passionate and I am a Muslim and free to do whatever I want.

Using the expression "I am the only Hijabi person" signifies the feeling of pride in representing Islam at her workplace. In addition, wearing the Hijab seemed to be an act of resistance to show that Hijab does not restrict her from achieving her goals. Additionally, Fati (53 years old, Dundee, employed, and housewife) narrated an anecdote about a Muslim friend

that worked with her. Fati described her friend as “double standard” because she told her that you wear Hijab in front of her mother, while not wearing it at work “So I saw her one day outside and she had the scarf on when she comes to work on Monday her head was not covered, so I said to her, what is this? You are double standard”. Eventually, the participant’s friend wore Hijab to work and Fati referred to it as her positive influence “Now she is wearing the Hijab in the post office, she saw that I have great confidence, so she felt she can do it too. It is a positive influence.” In the same way, Hadia (19 years old, Glasgow, student, and worker) mentioned that what made her experience easy at her workplace was the fact that her manager is a Hijabi Muslim woman “At work, my manager is a Hijabi and a Muslim, so she is the manager of the area and of the pharmacy. People already treat her with respect, so it was easier for me to get the same respect as her.”

From the above statements, identity representation is important for the participants because it made them feel empowered and confident. Regardless of whatever positive or negative feelings the participants had regarding wearing the Hijab, most of them eventually self-identified as empowered and confident. In addition, they referred to Islam as a feminist religion that granted them their rights and constantly compared it with the concepts of patriarchy, sexism, and oppression. As a result, the following chapter will discuss how the participants relate their Hijab to the notion of feminism and what they think about gender equality.

7.2.2. The Hijab and Feminist Identity:

This section deals with the participants’ attitudes and beliefs about the relationship between the Hijab, feminism, and gender equality. From their experiences, most of the participants stated that they feel equal to men, while some of them hold alternative interpretations of what being a feminist meant to them.

The term feminism was not directly defined the researcher to enable the participants to associate it with what they understood themselves and to derive it from their lived experiences. Some interviewees argued that they feel they are equal to men. They were constantly providing examples by comparing and relating themselves to their parents, brothers, and husbands. One individual stated that wearing the Hijab is primarily a submission to God and not to satisfy anyone “I wear it proudly to identify my Islamic faith and to show adherence to my God’s commandment. I wear it for God not to please the community where I live” (Zizi, 28 years old, Glasgow, Algerian, single, PhD student). This alluded to the idea that the participant did not see that the Hijab made her unequal to the other gender. It was also suggested that she viewed Islam as a feminist religion that granted her dignity and values “Hijab was and still is a symbol of dignity that values Muslim women and does not mean submission”. To further illustrate, Zizi explained gender equality by relating to her father “My father’s opinion is important to me, and it has a positive influence over my decision. Yet, I have the power to say either yes or no, and wearing the Hijab was one of my choices.”

One interesting finding was that she believed the Hijab made her feel more a devout Muslim than her brother because she considered herself practicing an important part of her religion. “Absolutely not, in Islam Muslim men and women are equal. I think when a Muslim woman wears the Hijab, she is even more precious and better than a Muslim man in status. I mean if I am wearing the Hijab and practicing my Islam well, I guess I will even be better than my

brother, it depends on being committed to Deen (religion)". This finding shows the importance of the Hijab in defining the devout Muslim woman to Zizi. According to Aghafli, Hatch and Marks (2014), many Muslims consider the Hijab as a sign of strong religious belief. Furthermore, Zizi believed that the inferiority of women is not related to Islam, instead, it is a matter of traditions, patriarchy, and literacy. "Hijab sometimes can be cultural more than religious, especially as I said in places where literacy is high and traditions are followed blindly, I totally reject it". Muslim women are often perceived as "ignorant, submissive, oppressed and almost totally enslaved by women-hating men" (Badawi 1995, p. 43). However, as per the Islamic Cultural Centre of Ireland (no year available), these stereotypes are the result of the position of Muslim women in some parts of the Muslim world, in which some practices oppress Muslim women, that is why "one should not confuse the culture of some Muslim countries with Islam" (The Islamic Cultural Centre of Ireland, no year available, no page). Moreover, many Muslim government appropriate Islamic texts to justify discrimination against Muslim women and to impose social and legal restrictions of women's rights and freedom.

Likewise, Sousou (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, PhD, Student, Engaged) strongly opposed the idea that women who wear the Hijab are submissive to men. To support her position, she used herself as an example "Uhm, I think the point of the Hijab is not to underestimate women's respect or independence. if I take myself as an example, I do not see myself as oppressed or inferior because I wear the Hijab. You know many Muslim women generally do not travel with *Mahram* and I am all supported by my family and brothers. I was never stopped from achieving my dreams". The participant utilized the example of traveling alone to Scotland to explain how Muslim women are powerful and can achieve their goals with the support of their families. Like Zizi and Sousou, Muna (43 years old, Glasgow, Married, housewife, employed) blamed some traditions and patriarchy for Muslim women's inferiority. To explain gender equality, she used the same approach that Lina (44 years old, Glasgow, a Muslim, revert, married, worker) applied to show that both genders are required to wear the Hijab, thus both are equal.

Among the twenty participants, Lina (44 years old, Glasgow, Scottish revert, employed) was the only one that directly identified herself as a Muslim feminist. When asked to explain what it meant, she compared two types of feminism.

you know that kind of thing the feminist movement... like to be a feminist you must reclaim your body and wear revealing clothes without being attacked, I am a feminist, and for me to be a feminist is being the woman you are regardless of what you are wearing! Being a feminist is being able to wear what you want to wear and being able to take the power and the strength of my choices.

It is evident that the participant perceived covering her body to reclaim her rights. The importance of making a choice, no matter what type of clothes the woman wears, was a crucial aspect of Lina's viewpoint.

In other responses to the idea of wearing the Hijab as a sign of male subordination and gender inequality, some participants explained their stances regarding gender equality from their unique understandings. For instance, Naz (37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistan, housewife) explained feminism as a biased movement that considered the Hijab as a sign of oppression "It is also their own social groups. These feminists side sometimes with the banning of the

Hijab. So even Muslim women are not into wearing the Hijab now, this may be due to globalization and modernization. They consider the Hijab as old-fashioned". She added that Muslim women have lost their respect and values by following feminism "As women, we have put ourselves in a lot of trouble by following modernization and women's rights movements". To exemplify that, she gave the example of women waiting in the queue as the other men "If there is a man whatever number it is and there is a woman coming, they used to free space for her, whatever the place is a bank, a hospital. Now with her saying I am equal to men; she has lost that respect. So, if you are equal to men, go ahead and do the same things they are doing now". Furthermore, Naz disagreed with the idea of gender equality, instead she referred to the idea of gender equity "Islamic dress does not imply that women are inferior to men, but I do not believe in equality." Alternatively, she believed that genders are prescribed distinct roles in society, and they complete each other "In religion, there is no such thing, men have their own rights and duties and women too". To explain further, the participants used figurative language to manifest the difference between men and women "You cannot compare fruits with vegetables, you cannot compare sunflowers with roses". When asked to further illustrate what the participant meant by this comparison, the participant described herself as being simultaneously independent and dependent on her husband. Seeking her husband's permission or opinion did not seem to irritate her. She believed that taking her husband's permission or opinion on something was not a matter of power structure but of respect and commitment. As she put it:

That power structure thing is created by society and culture, not religion. I mean in Islam; women do discuss with their men not to get permission from them. Some serious things require permission, but not daily routine things. It is more about respect and commitment in the relationship.

From Naz's perspective, marriage in Islam is based on mutual respect and the dominance of women is created by society. In a discussion on the rights, dignity, honour and status of women in Islam, Patoari (2019), states that Islam does not allow the domination of men on women, rather it validates and supports the respect, honours, dignity of women by ensuring gender equality and equality of rights for both men and women.

Another result was Naz's frustration about gender equality in Muslim and non-Muslim countries. She stated that gender equality has taken a very wrong path. The image of women as nurturing and emotional beings did not mean being weak to her. Instead, she seemed to celebrate and support this image "Because the woman is a very emotional and strong being, we are soft-hearted because we give birth to children, but society how is making these things negative, our girls need to fall prey for this equality concept. This fake image is destroying our relationships". Therefore, according to Naz, gender equality and women's rights movements are incompatible with her ideas about gender relations.

In the same vein, Shay (38 years old, Edinburgh, Pakistani, Married/Employed) explained that being a Hijabi does not make her submissive to a man; she provided another explanation for gender roles "In our Islam, there is the concept that women need to be under the wing of men for protection and provision. This does not mean that women cannot be in the position that they want. The Hijab does not stop her and make her submissive to men." From Shay's statement, men are prescribed to provide and take care of their women in Islam and not oppress them. Both participants, Naz, and Shay, argue using the "protectionist approach"

(Musawah, 2017, p.1) to gender equality understanding in Islam. This approach does acknowledge gender equality between men and women in their relationships and obligations with their creator. However, it argues that this spiritual and ontological equality does not mean they are equal in social and legal domains (Musawah,2017). The protectionist approach views men and women based on gendered ideas about the nature of men and women. In other words, they view men as strong and rational and women as weak, emotional and in need of protection. This approach is like the concept of equity, which considers the difference men and women. Nevertheless, in practice, gender equity is criticised for perpetuating hierarchical relationships between men and women and denies women equal rights to full their aspirations. The protectionist approach is challenged by the egalitarian³⁵ approach to equality in the contemporary Muslim thoughts. Hana's (36 years old, Yemeni, Edinburgh) interpretation was slightly different from Naz's. Hana mentioned that gender equality does exist in Islam, nevertheless, she took a spiritual approach by explaining that all human beings are equal and in Islam what makes someone better than another is the concept of *taqwa* "Obviously we are all equal are not we, we are all humans, we are all men and women. The only thing that distinguishes us is *taqwa*³⁶".

Explaining how they navigate their agency and power of choice, some of the participants mentioned examples from their lived experiences. Most of them were about their relationships either with their parents, husbands, brothers or at work. Talking about gender relations and agency, Nima (43 years old, Scottish, Edinburgh, Revert, Employed) appeared to be satisfied with her husband's treatment. She explained that her husband supported her career by saying "I am really fortunate to have a husband to support me and encourage me", and "I am free to do whatever I want, and my husband does not keep me behind closed doors". Using the expression "I am free to do whatever I want" suggests that, unlike widespread images that portray Hijabi Muslim women as "weak, oppressed, repressed, or victims" (Ahmad, 2018, p.4), Nima seems to enjoy her freedom of choice. In the same vein, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. Student, single) gave her opinion on gender roles by explaining that her brothers support and protect her.

I think it is what society dictates like the male is more powerful than a female and it is pressure on both sides. My brothers are open-minded and supportive of me, I believe I see their power as a good thing, they are protective over me! I believe in this case power for men is positive... but there are some cases where men have issues against women. It is called misogyny.

Employing "Misogyny" suggests that the participant was familiar with some feminist concepts, which indicates her educational level. In addition, Mimi described her brothers as "open-minded and supportive" of her decisions. Furthermore, the term "power" was accompanied by the adjective "positive", which means using power in a way that did not make her feel unequal or oppressed. The positive use of power also signifies being protective over her.

Some participants used their positions at the workplace to explain how successful they are. For instance, Hadia (19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, student) explained that she felt proud and successful with the Hijab and that the Hijab has no negative effect on her position as a student. "I do not think it affects my position because within the university I managed to become a student rep for my course, but there are quite some of us Muslims and non-

Muslims. I was the only Hijabi and I managed to be the student rep, so I do not think it does an impact on my position”. Both, Nima and Hadia, appear to be empowered and aware of their agency. Both participants displayed both intrinsic and instrumental types of agencies. For instance, using the expression “I am free to do whatever I want” by Nima, is an example of intrinsic agency, which means the woman’s awareness of her rights and power within. The other type is instrumental agency, which suggests the individual’s ability to make choices and have an influence in various kinds of decisions or on formal and informal political actions and that is manifested in Hadia’s case, which managed to be a Hijabi student representative.

Some scholars argue the level of agency and empowerment are measure by proxies like women’s health, schooling attachment and knowledge (Agarwala and Lynch, 2006). However, other believe that these proxies are not enough to measure one’s agency. They suggest more direct measures like decision making process Malhotra, Schuler, and Boender (2005). However, both approaches fail to consider women’s interpretation of measured items, which underestimate the informal side of decision-making process. For example, “women frequently negotiate with household members to reach decision, a very important aspect of agency that current measurements fail to capture” (Qutteina et al, 2019, p.35). The importance of negotiating some decisions with family members is manifested in Naz’s and Mimi’s relations with their male relatives. Consequently, it is important to consider Muslim women’s understanding of agency because “Agency and empowerment measures items may vary with different cultural, and temporal contexts” (Qutteina et al., 2019, p.36).

This section reviewed the aspects of feminism, gender equality, oppression and agency as defined by the participants. Three major aspects were raised. Some participants identify themselves as equal to men and others believe the genders are equal, yet they are different. The surprising aspect is that some of them did not praise feminism and the gender equality movement and believed it is impossible for both genders to be equal because they are different. In addition, most of the participants did not identify themselves directly as a feminist, except one. This section also provided examples from their lived experiences about their gender relations to support their arguments. After discussing how the participants defined and identified themselves, the next section will deal with how they felt they were perceived by people around them. In addition to the media portrayal’s influence on their lived experiences.

7.2.3. Interpersonal Perception and Media Representation of the Hijab:

7.2.3.1. Interpersonal Perception:

Most of the participants considered themselves empowered and strong while wearing the Hijab, however, some of them showed how they felt they were portrayed by others. They shared that based on either their daily interactions or with a reference to media representation of the Hijab and dominant discourses on Hijab and Muslim women. To begin with, most of the participant’s comments regarding how they are perceived by others were mostly negative. They used terms like “terrorists, backward, uneducated, oppressed, and narrow-minded” to describe how they believe others perceive them. As one interviewee argued, “They believe that Islam and Hijabi women are terrorists, close-minded, strict not ready to share any kind of discussion or conversation with a male” (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student) Using the pronoun “they” referred to the idea of the *Other*³⁷ and feeling different from those who perceived her. In addition, Mimi suggested that these perceptions are the result of the media’s representations “I feel they are careful about approaching a Hijabi

woman, we need to mention that because they got a wrong idea about Muslim women and that is because of media.” According to Staszak (2008), the concept of *Otherness/Other* is the outcome of the discursive process by which the dominant group (in-group) builds one or many dominated groups (out-groups) by stigmatizing a difference, real or imagined, introduced as a negation of identity and thus a motive for potential discrimination.

The negative association of the Hijab with terrorism and female oppression was also discussed by Noun (48 years old, Pakistani/British, Edinburgh, Housewife), who shared her concerns regarding her daughter wearing the Hijab at high school “No, I am not afraid at all, it is just that I believe it is much worse now. In my time you were simply different because you wore a scarf on your head, now my daughter, I think she is right. Now you are not only wearing a scarf. You are a terrorist.” The interviewee made a comparison between the time when the Hijab was only a piece of fabric and now that is invested with negative associations like being labelled a “terrorist.” As demonstrated by Alexander (2016), though Islamophobia existed prior to 9/11, this event directed people’s attention towards the Hijab. Furthermore, Haddad (2007, p. 255) points out that among the excuses to gain military support for their campaign against Taliban and El Qaida, the Bush administration promises that their campaign would “bring civilization to the uncivilized Muslims” and “lead to the empowerment of Muslim women”.

Some participants shared how they feel they are perceived as Muslim converts who decided to wear the Hijab). As a Muslim revert, Lina (44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, Muslim, revert, worker) believed some people perceived her as a “terrorist” because many reverts ran to become ISIS Bride “Because I am a revert and there was a woman who was a revert and ran over to become an ISIS bride, so people presume that I may be a terrorist”. As per Ussif, Ussif and Yussif (2020, p.40), “The situation of born Muslim women is very different from Muslim convert”. In a study conducted by Robert (2006), it was revealed that the new Muslim women/converts after adopting the hijab/veil mentioned that one of the particularly challenging aspects of the religion is wearing the Hijab. The difficulty lies in the perceptions that people have about the Hijab and the treatment that Muslim converts receive when deciding to wear the Hijab. Additionally, the participant mentioned that many people view her as “uneducated” or a “refugee” who did not understand English “At the same time wearing Hijab often when you walk into the room people may presume that you are uneducated or you are the wee volunteer who is there to learn English or like that and no I am the regional manager for the org, I held a senior position within my work... so yeah I had that few times. People will just presume that I am uneducated because of it...”

Similarly, another interviewee shared an uncomfortable anecdote where she was perceived by someone as uneducated because of her Hijab “I was having a problem in our flat, it was a rat problem... and the agent that they sent to investigate the problem by the pest company asks me if I saw a mouse or a rat, I said it was a rat, he kept like insisting that I am wrong” (Nana, 27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, PhD student). Consequently, most of the participants believed that they were perceived negatively by stating examples from their experiences. Furthermore, almost all stated that these perceptions are fuelled by the media representations of the Hijab. According to Mastro (2016, p.3),

A traditional Muslim woman is perceived as oppressed, likely uneducated, and helpless. Because of these stereotypes, many westerners approach a woman of an

unfamiliar culture as a project, as someone who is incapable of understanding how poorly she is being treated and whose only saviour is the West - which can help her see the 'truth'

The media may play an important role in perpetuating these stereotypes and images of the Hijabi Muslim women as “weak, uneducated and powerless” (Saqib, 2024, no page) by focusing on the oppressive conditions of women in societies that are governed by “radical hardliners” (Saqib, 2024, no page). Despite this, some of the participants noted that media representation is becoming neutral and there is an improvement compared to the past. Having discussed how the women in the study perceived themselves and how they are perceived by others, the final part of the findings of this chapter deals with how the interviewees viewed and debated the media’s portrayal of the Hijab.

7.2.3.2. The Media’s Portrayal of Hijabi Women:

This section presents the participants’ perceptions on media’s portrayal. Most of the adjectives, mentioned by the participants, were negative like being called a “terrorist, uneducated, and oppressed”. Almost all mentioned the role that the Western media played in the proliferation of these stereotypes especially post-9/11. Talking about the negative side of the media, Nes (52 years old, British/Pakistani, Dundee, Married, employed), said “I think the media does capture all the negativity”. To illustrate that she gave an example of a program where a Hijab is forced on a girl “It was recently that I watched a program, it was about a young girl who wore the Hijab, but she will take it off as soon as she is away from home”. The participant appeared irritated by the portrayal especially because she believed it had an influence on how non-Muslims viewed women with the Hijab.

Some participant related these portrayals to the prominent event of 9/11. Zizi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student) referred to the Hijab as a “clash of cultures” over the past few decades. When asked to illustrate more, she explained with an upset tone that a link between the Hijab, terrorism, and extremism has been established. Like Nes, she alluded to the idea that most non-Westerns are impacted by what the media dictates. Unexpectedly, she mentioned that not only non-Westerns are impacted, but also Muslims with weak personalities because they fall prey to the media’s images and end up removing their Hijabs. In addition to mentioning events like 9/11, Naz (37 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, housewife) believed that the “War on Terror” also contributed to these stereotypes “I mean the war in Afghanistan and some places in the Middle East have promoted these images that Muslim women are oppressed”. Furthermore, the participant expressed confusion on whether these portrayals promoted by the media are true or not by saying: “We do not really know the reality, but as you see the media says Afghanistan and the Taliban are not allowing girls to go to school! So, this enhances the idea that Muslim women are oppressed and need saving.” This expression suggests that oppression may be enacted, however this leads to a generalization and homogeneity of Muslim women who practice the Hijab.

In fact, many women in Afghanistan are enforced to wear the veil and deprived of their basic human rights. According to Medica Mondiale (2023), the lack of women’s rights in Afghanistan becomes a state policy. Many women are suffering from restriction of freedom of movement and restrictive dress code, no protection from violence for women and girls, forced and child marriage, losing the rights to education, high rates of infant and maternal mortality, and discrimination against the Hazaras³⁸. However, many researchers argue that there is a homogeneity in the media representation of Muslim women. As per Elgamri (2010),

the coverage of the world important events the four decades such the Iranian revolution (1979), the Rushdie Affaire (1989), the massacre of foreign tourists in Egypt, and the 9/11 attack- progressively universalised Islam as monolithic entity with religious hysteria. Regarding the British media, Poole (2011) examines the Muslim visibility in the British media before and post-9/11. The results show a continuation of certain dominant discourses in the British media such as relating Muslims with terrorism, extremism, and cultural difference.

Some interviewees gave instances from movies, series, and social media regarding the portrayal of the Hijab. Nana (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student) elaborated by saying “Yes, so many examples on Netflix, once I saw on TikTok like a woman was wearing only a scarf while naked and saying in the name of God and drinking alcohol, this is a very very unreal portrayal”. The participant mentioned TikTok as a platform that, according to her perspective, promotes false and unreal images of Muslim women. However, TikTok and other social media platforms are regarded as different from mainstream media because they can be used by Muslims to reconfigure and confront dominant discourses “TikTok offers unique possibilities to confront the neoliberal imaginary and open a space for debate, incorporating political viewpoints and establishing itself as a new communication scenario” (Civila et al., 2023, p.144). Furthermore, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student) used an instance from Netflix by referring to the Spanish drama *Elite*³⁹ which she believed portrayed Hijabi women negatively, however, she explained that this portrayal helped others understand the struggles of women who practice the Hijab “I think the series was telling the truth and transferring reality about how others think she is inferior to them like at the beginning the administration calls her to ask her to take it off, she took it for some time and wore it again.”.

In addition, the participant referred specifically to the French media. She described it as “biased” in its representation of the Hijab, Islam, and Muslims. The tone of the participant sounded so serious while saying: “I find their news so biased”. When asked to illustrate more, she provided this example: “If there is a fight between someone who is Muslim and a non-Muslim, we see a lot of exaggeration in transferring this news and how they make the Muslim the bad guy even if he was right! But if we see anything similar for non-Muslims like if he is the one hitting or insulting or anything, they keep being silent about that.” In France, Muslim women became a media issue in 1989 with the first “headscarf affair”, however issue re-surfaced in the year 2003 during the last “headscarf affair” (Moya, 2016, p. 23). This incident re-kindled many controversies in the media and political spheres, which resulted in the introduction of some policies such as the legal prohibition of religious symbols in primary and secondary schools. Although Muslim women were the heart of public debate, mainstream media treated them as subjects not as agents. In other words, they were not given a chance to speak for themselves; their voices were silenced (Trevanian et al., 2008). Instead, “Journalists, experts, mainstream feminists, and intellectuals talked in lieu of Muslim women. They progressively created a collective imagery on Muslim women, and especially on Muslim veiled women” (Moya, 2016, p. 23).

In contrast, some participants believed that the media’s portrayal, at the present, is either neutral or improving. As argued by Muna (43 years old, British/Pakistani, Glasgow, housewife) “I think now the portrayal is neutral for me so it is neither positive nor negative, yet it has been negative, I can see a certain improvement, when I say improvement, I mean when I was 12 and I was here, like it was quite negative”. In addition, Muna demonstrated

that the negativity of the media's representations plays a remarkable role in the way people perceive her" media plays a big part, they portray us as oppressed, forced to wear it, it influences how people perceive us even if we are highly educated, it could be different opinion to someone else, but this is my opinion. As per Bullock (2000), due to the ubiquitous portrayal of the veil as a symbol of oppression or violence, veiled Muslim women in the West find often encounter discrimination, harassment and even assault.

Likewise, Hope (54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, Worker) noted that the media's portrayal is "double-edged and two-faced". The participant explained that the media has both negative and positive sides to the representation of the Hijab "It can be with you or against you. I mean it helped in giving voices to many people that is one thing. It gives chances to many people to show off and defend it as a way of life. It is a message that needs to be told to many people." In a study by Masud (2005), on the experiences of Muslim women in Scotland, the participants believe that the way media represents Islam is the one to blame for the miseducation of the mass public, the violence towards Muslim women and fuelling the anger of Muslim, especially Muslim youth. However, one participant was specific about the Scottish media and praised it for their inclusion of Muslims by broadcasting Islamic celebrations like Eid "Here in Scotland, sometimes in the Eid time, they bring some Muslim women and men, not with Hijab sometimes and they introduce our culture, and they speak about Eid, they speak about Manasik Hajj (Pilgrimage steps), I see that in Eid al-Adha (One of the Islamic festival), I do not know if u see that on BBC Scotland, I feel like they are very nice people" (Shay, 38 years old, Palestinian, Edinburgh, Employed). This signified that the participant felt satisfied and happy about being included and represented.

Interestingly, there was a mention of non-Western media. As for some participants, Hijabi women are depicted as "illiterate and given small roles" in movies and series "they always give leading roles, let us say in Turkish series to women who are not Hijabies, and those who are Hijabies, only have secondary roles. They mostly portray them as illiterate or as old women" (Sousou, 27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, PhD Student, Engaged). Karavar (2019) argues that Turkish women with Hijab are less visible in Turkish soaps⁴⁰ and usually given secondary roles; in fact, they are inaccurately represented, as they are shown with quite uncommon clothing or headscarves. Overall, this part reviewed the standpoints of the participants regarding the media's representation of the Hijab. It demonstrated three major points where media was described as mostly negative, neutral, and positive. The following section deals with the participants' roles in changing their attempts to change these perceptions.

7.2.3.3. Changing the Dominant Narrative (Negative Perceptions and Stereotypes):

Having discussed the perceptions and stereotypes of Muslim women both on the interpersonal level, Western and non-Western media, this section seeks to understand the participants' contributions to changing the negative perceptions about the Hijab. To begin with, Hadia (19 years old, British/Pakistani, Glasgow, student, single) expressed frustration about how the Hijab is perceived by others and how she is trying to make a change "Yeah, I think so. Because, generally, the Western idea about Hijab is that we are oppressed from wearing it, most of us as Hijabis are doing whatever we can on our Hijab on our heads to change this perception". Employing the plural personal and possessive pronouns "we and our" alluded to the feeling of unity and solidarity with other Hijabi women. Many Muslim

women in the West reclaim their religious identity by wearing the Hijab to defend themselves against the reductive images of the veil in the media. Bullock (2000, p.22) states that “Since the late 1970s scores of Muslim women, from Arabia to Asia to the West, have been voluntarily covering. The re-covering movement challenges the reductive image of the veil as a symbol of Muslim women’s oppression”. In the same vein, Zaynab (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student, single) believed that having a conversation with non-Muslims helped in reducing the tension of media representation, therefore, changing perceptions “Yes but the time you start speaking and interacting with that person, he will subsequently realize that ... so through Hijab I am giving information and correcting the wrong perceptions that others have about Hijab, Hijab really empowers my position if I may say” .

Changing perception, from Nounou’s (37 years old, Scottish/Pakistani, Edinburgh, Worker) perception, can be more effective through the media. She gave an example of a Muslim chef, who she believed played a key role in changing perceptions about the Hijab.

I follow Nadia Jamir Hussain she is a fantastic cook, she is basically English if you know what I mean, she cooks British food, she is Muslim and she wears Hijab on tv, she is on British Bake Off and now she has her own BBC program and she is done few other shows I have read somewhere that she has influenced the positive portrayal of Muslim woman than the organizations have.

The participants expressed their roles in countering the negative perceptions, stereotypes, and narratives on the Hijab. Mehdi (2018) and Alexander (2016) demonstrate that Muslim women are beginning to reclaim the narrative, demolishing the stereotypes, and speaking for themselves. Furthermore, Mehdi (2018., no page) gives examples of some Muslim female figures who represent stories of “courage, resilience and conviction”, such as “Iran’s Olympic gold medallist Kimia Alizadeh, Pakistani teenage activist Malala Yousufzai, Muslim American fencer Ibtihaj Muhammad, Yemeni journalist and Noble Peace Prize winner Tawakkul Karman, Malaysian feminist Zainah Anwar, Afghanistan’s first female prosecutor general Maria Bashir, to Kashmiri activist and APDP chairperson Parveena Ahangar” (Mehdi, 2018, no page). Having discussed the different opinions of the participants regarding different issues relating to gender and the Hijab. The next section will offer a discussion using the already existing knowledge and theories.

7.3. Discussion:

7.3.1. The Hijab as a Tool of Empowerment:

The first part of this chapter discussed thoroughly the views of the participants regarding the Hijab and its relation to feminism and gender equality. Most of them stated that they felt empowered while wearing the Hijab, however, they also mentioned how they felt misrepresented in the media and expressed the consequences of these representations on their lived experiences. As mentioned above, two representations were extracted from the participants’ responses, the way they felt about themselves and how they are portrayed and perceived by others. As previously mentioned in the theoretical framework, feminist standpoint theory (Harding, 2004) claims that the positions of subordinate, marginalized, and minority groups are more accurate than those of the dominant group, which is referred to as strong objectivity.

Strong objectivity (Harding, 1987) maintains that starting the inquiry from the lived experiences of those who have been left outside the institutions, in which knowledge is generated and classified is crucial. Furthermore, it argues that the perspectives of the dominant group are less accurate and complete than those of the subordinate group (Wood, 2012). This is manifested in most of the participants' responses, they stated that how they felt about themselves is incompatible and different from how the dominant group perceived and defined them. For example, some of the adjectives that they used to refer to themselves as Hijabees were mostly positive like "powerful, strong, and confident." Nes (52-year-old, Dundee, Married, employee), for instance, referred to herself and Muslim women in her circle by using these adjectives. In addition, Zaynab believed that the Hijab empowers her to show her Muslim identity in public "It really has that power, it really, really empowers me, it gives me the power to show my identity". On the other hand, they mentioned how they are perceived and depicted by the hegemonic group and most of the adjectives were negative like "terrorists, backward, oppressed, and uneducated", for instance Mimi stated that "They believe that Islam and Hijabi women are terrorists, close-minded, strict not ready to share any kind of discussion or conversation with a male" (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student).

Power relations create this opposition of views. Power relations are regarded as a disruption in the process of knowledge production because they dominate the discourse. Wood (2012) expresses that Feminist standpoint theory attempts to deconstruct this discourse by disputing the privilege of men and men's interests that seeks to devalue, marginalize, and harm women and their interests. Furthermore, Wood (2012) provides an example to illustrate this point. An analogy can be made in this regard, Wood's point is that women are expected by society to be nice and soft. Thus, when the women are assertive are labelled as "Bitches" (Wood, 2012, p.2). Therefore, Hijabi women are represented by society as oppressed, backward, and uneducated, as mentioned by the participants, consequently being seen as powerful and strong is unexpected by the hegemonic group.

Existing research recognizes the importance of standpoint theory in critically examining the various positions on the Hijab in the American context. Droogsma (2007, p. 294) uses it to redefine the Hijab from Muslim women's cultural position "Although powerful discourses attempt to define women on the "margins" of society, women's cultural positions provide them with heightened understandings of the contradictions between their experiences and the ways the dominant group defines them". The results show that the Hijab serves various purposes in women's lives and even empowers them unlike what is stated by the dominant discourses. Similarly, a recent study by Marzouk (2021) explains that the negative portrayal of the Hijab in the West is due to the lack of knowledge about the subject, which leads to discrimination against Muslim women who choose to practice it. In addition, the findings of the study maintain that the participants chose Hijab out of religious matters and feel empowered practicing it. Consequently, the theory helped in understanding and redefining the concept of the Hijab from the perspectives of the women who wear the Hijab in the Scottish context. By examining how they feel about it and how they feel they are defined and represented by the dominant discourses. The results showed that most of them feel empowered and confident by wearing the Hijab. The following section provides a discussion on the relationship between the Hijab, feminism, and gender equality by establishing links between the findings and the existing studies on the topic.

7.3.2. The Hijab, feminism, and gender equality:

While the Hijab is regarded as a symbol of emancipation to some, it is considered an oppressive tool by others “Dangerous, scary, intriguing, threatening, intimidating, oppressive, irritating, aggressive, traditional, conservative, and reactionary” are some of the adjectives commonly used in Europe concerning hijab (Amiriaux, 2007, p.124). Not only that, but it becomes a powerful symbol of the cultural, religious, and political division between the West and Islam, especially post-9/11 (Byng, 2010, Haddad, 2007)

When referring to Western societies, masculine cultural norms often decide the appropriate fashion for women like tight clothes and high heels (Borisoff and Merrill, 2003). In contrast to these norms, the Hijab covers most of the women’s bodies, which makes it a way of resistance to these patriarchal standards (El Guindi, 1999). This is manifested in the way most of the participants tried to resist the negative stereotypes by changing the narrative as is manifested in Hadia’s interview “Most of us Hijabies are doing whatever we can to change this perception” and Zaynab’s “through the Hijab I am giving information and correcting wrong perceptions that others have about the Hijab”. This was demonstrated in their attempts to prove themselves in the Scottish context by wearing the Hijab at their universities, their jobs, or in public. Furthermore, most of them identified themselves as powerful, however, not all of them agreed with the Western concept of feminism.

As the findings demonstrated, most of the participants possessed various understandings of what feminist identity and gender equality signify. The participants had different views on the concept of equality. Those who adopted the feminist identity and regarded themselves as equal to men, like Zizi (28 years old, Glasgow, Algerian, single) and Muna (43 years old, Glasgow, married, housewife), and those who believed that equality is impossible because men and women have different roles, thus adapted the concept of equity, for instance, Naz (37 years old, Glasgow, Married Housewife) and Shay (38 years old, Edinburgh, Pakistani, married, worker). Only one participant (Lina, 44 years old, Edinburgh, married/revert, employed) directly referred to herself as a feminist and demonstrated that covering herself is a way of feminist resistance. This aligns with Trinh (1990), who believes that the performance of veiling and unveiling is linked to the act of resistance against the dominant culture. It is a symbolic political resistance such as politicizing the hair. According to Rashid (2023, p. 275),

Hair is a highly politicized topic anyway, especially when it concerns women—the curly hair of Black women, short hair on girls, shaved heads of women activists, greying hair on women, etc. Long, straight hair represents a woman’s conformity to the accepted ideals of femininity while a shaved head marks a disruption to her normative function in a patriarchal society.

In addition, some of the participants criticized Western feminism for being “too biased and calling for the banning of the Hijab,” which leads to a discussion on the relationship between feminism and the Hijab. The relationship between feminism and the Hijab is complicated “The discourse on feminism is sharply polarized between those who regard hijab as essentially debilitating and those who see it as an enabling tool for dignity, self-worth, and freedom” (Hassan, 2018, p. 24). This polarization is due to the nature of the relation that feminist studies have with religion. Some participants referred to themselves as equal to men in Islam and regarded it as a feminist religion that valued women such as Zizi (28 years old,

Glasgow, Algerian, single), who stated that “In Islam men and women are equal” and viewed the Hijab as an act of submission to God not to men as explained “Hijab was and still a symbol of dignity that values Muslim women and it does not mean submission”. However, feminist studies have a long history of disinterest and hostility toward religion because the latter is considered biased against women and the root of gender inequality and oppression (Hassan,2018). Radical feminism which is a part of second-wave feminism has largely furthered the perceived gap between feminism and religion. According to Thompson (2018, no page), Radical Feminists emphasize the patriarchal nature of some mainstream religions such as Catholicism and Islam. They argue that such religions have developed in patriarchal societies and have been ‘hijacked ’by men. In fact, Hope (54-year-old, Libyan, Dundee, worker) believed that gender inequality is the product of men’s dominance and control, and this is manifested in the interpretation of religious texts “Even our religion is interpreted by men. The Fiqh and Sharia are interpreted by men... so men have their own perspectives about religion. All scholars are men, so how do you expect them to side with you”. In addition, Mimi (28-year-old, Algerian, Glasgow, PhD student, Single) attributed the gender inequality and oppression not to religion, but to society and culture “That power structure thing is created by society and culture, not religion”. Men have interpreted religious doctrines to justify their positions of power. The mutual exclusion and the incompatibility of religion and women’s studies are referred to by Brouwer (1992) as “Unacknowledged Quarantine”, which signifies that they effectively quarantine each other. Thus, including religion in women’s studies is considered a betrayal and patriarchal cooperation.

Unfortunately, there is a tendency to consider only [women’s] negative experiences [with religion] as accurate, and all positive ones, by definition, as a kind of patriarchally induced false consciousness. Judgments such as these pose serious problems for scholars interested in both women and religion because work that attempts to be more nuanced is sometimes read as betrayal or as patriarchal co-optation (Bullock,2002, pp. xxx)

The reason for this quarantining is that religions are suspected of being a significant source of adherence to patriarchal values (Ozturk, 2022). According to Bruce (2008), religions are accused of justifying gender inequality and roles as orders from God (Bruce, 2018). Hassan (2018) adapts the term “feminist quarantine” to describe mainstream feminism’s reluctance to accept and include both positive and negative associations of the Hijab. Although most of the participants (Zizi,28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single, student and Hadia, 19 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, single, student) regarded Islam as a feminist religion, Islam is seen as exacerbating gender inequality “Islamic religious heritage is one of the most powerful barriers to the rising tide of gender equality” (Norris and Ronald ,2003, p.71). In fact, patriarchy and misogyny are not limited to Islam because they are the oldest forms of group discrimination in human history (Nolan and Lenski,2009). “Gender inequality belongs among the most prevalent forms of social inequality and exists all over the world, with different effects in different regions” (Klingorova and Havlicek, 2015, p. 2). This is manifested in the struggles and barriers to gender inequality that still face women’s empowerment around the world (Hurst et al.,2019).

However, Ozturk (2022, p. 173) believes that “Religious Fundamentalism” is the central driver of patriarchal values; it makes both Muslims and non-Muslims more inclined to patriarchal values. As per Peel and Kindermann (2022), Fundamentalist beliefs are often

related to extremist and radical beliefs or terrorist ideologies, in addition to terrorism radicalization and violent extremism. Furthermore, it is defined by Munson (2019) as a religious movement, like American Protestantism or Islam, that is characterized by strict adherence to sacred texts. These patriarchal values emphasize the appropriateness of women's subordination to men (Alexander and Welzel, 2011) and enhance gender roles by assigning reproductive and domestic functions to women. Furthermore, this gender role assignment comes with a rigid control of female sexuality, which leads to the obsession with women's chastity (Jung, 2016). Religion plays a crucial role in preserving these patriarchal values and men are the main beneficiaries (Riesebrodt, 2000).

Gender inequality is not limited to Islam, nevertheless, it is Islam that occupies the central stage in both academic and public debates (Lussier and Fish, 2016). According to Esposito (1998, xi), "Few issues in Islam and Muslim culture have attracted more interest and yet proven so susceptible to stereotyping as issues involving women's subjugation and second-class citizenship probably best describe the perception of Muslim women in the West. It is argued that Islamic fundamentalism perpetuates and brings attention to the Islamic patriarchal nexus, especially since the Iranian revolution of 1979 and post-9/11 (Ozturk, 2022). Thence, rendering Islam a patriarchal religion. Islamic fundamentalists allow discrimination against women and tolerate domestic violence. Examples of Islamic fundamentalism are privileging men in divorce the strict segregation of women in public spaces and banning girls from attending schools like in the Taliban era (Ozturk, 2022; Fish and Lussier, 2016).

Among these fundamentalist practices is forcing women to wear the Hijab. According to Fish and Lussier (2016, p. 31), "non-Muslims regard the wearing of the hijab as an act of enforced modesty and note the absence of an equivalent prescription for Muslim men". Consequently, these stereotypes about Islam are enhanced by these practices as mentioned by some of the participants in the study "Such negative perception of Islam concerning gender issues together with the projection of "fear" in populist politics and in "security" discourses has spilled over into the discussion of hijab" (Hassan, 2018, p.25).

This resulted in the feminist attitudes towards the Hijab as a restriction and implementation of oppression against women and its banning is sought, advocated, or supported by feminist theorists (Tarlo, 2010). This is manifested in one of the findings, where Naz (37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistan, housewife) argued that some feminists call for the banning of the Hijab "These feminists' side sometimes with the banning of the Hijab". There is no room for negotiation for the issue of the Hijab according to mainstream feminism. To them, the Hijab is associated with two polarized meanings, either freedom or women's submission (Hasan, 2018). Not only in feminist literature but also in orientalist and colonial literature. positive and extrovert interpretations of hijab are, constantly, undermined by the more dominant negative resonance encountered on the streets and in the press, resonance fared by the complex legacies of "orientalists, imperialists, secular and feminist discourses as well as by the contemporary political situation" (Tarlo, 2010, p.37)

In addition, some of the participants (Hadia, 19 years old, Glasgow, student, Pakistani) pointed out the idea of using religion to control women and forcing them to wear or remove the Hijab, which they considered unethical and oppression towards women. They distinguished between Islam and patriarchy and some of them refer to Islam as a feminist

religion that granted them their rights (Nima, 43 years old, Scottish, revert, worker, married).

Western feminists are not the only feminists who perceive the Hijab as an oppressive tool, some non-Western feminists view the Hijab as so. According to Mir-Hosseini (2019), during the 20th century, many Muslims viewed the traditional interpretations of Islamic religious texts as unjust and discriminatory because the Muslim legal tradition does not treat men and women equally. At the heart of its unequal construction of gender rights lie two key assumptions: one theological – that God has given men authority over women; the other sociological, reflecting an ancient premise – men are strong, they protect and provide, while women are weak and obey (Mir-Hosseini, 2019, p.108). By the 1980s, the movement had gained the label of Islamic feminism, which seems contradictory (Mir-Hosseini, 2019). These Islamic feminists argue for justice and inequality from inside the Muslim traditions, which means they attempt to modify traditional Islamic discussion on gender. Among these discussions on gender equality is the Hijab.

Different figures advocate or oppose the Hijab. For instance, the Moroccan academic Fatema Mernissi, Egyptian feminist Nawal El Saadawi, and Pakistani scholar Riffat Hassan called for female emancipation. They rightly view the Hijab as a symbol of oppression and subservience. El Saadawi, for instance, believes that the Hijab emphasizes women's sexuality and "veils her mind" by fixating it on "the danger of her body" (Cook, 2001, p. 134). Although they seem to have the same stance, Mernissi (1991) is often mentioned in opposition to El Saadawi because she grounds herself in Islamic referents (Ghadbian, 2000). Mernissi (1991) criticizes the patriarchal interpretations of the Hijab, where the gendered dimension of the Hijab is highlighted at the expense of the spiritual one. These patriarchal interpretations are hidden by the mask of the Hijab, which is regressive and oppressive. Additionally, the Mernissi (1991) speaks of the Islamist acceptance of the Hijab as an indicator of men's desire to control women and the lack of women's democratic values. Like El Saadawi and Mernissi, Qasim Amin, who is an Egyptian thinker and actively advocates for women's liberation in the Islamic world, believes that the requirement of the Hijab in the Shariah needs reconsideration. According to Bachtiar (2023), Qasim Amin believes that the Hijab is not a religious requirement, but a matter of traditions and cultures. Additionally, it restricts women's freedom and, thus, hinders social progress.

From the previous discussion, the Hijab is discussed from the perspectives of Western and Islamic feminists who see it as an oppressive and regressive tool. A growing number of both Western and Muslim feminists defend it. Berger (1998) explains that Muslim feminists today see the Hijab as a symbol of Islamic freedom or invest it with an individualized meaning. In contrast to the previous opinions, some Islamic feminists, like Leila Ahmed, criticized Western feminists for pressuring Muslim women to choose between their Muslim identity and feminist identity. She describes it as a choice between "betrayal and betrayal" (Ahmed, 1984, p. 122). In addition, Ahmed (1992) believes that the Hijab is no longer a symbol of a woman's brainwashed submissiveness and lack of agency. As opined by Azadah (2011), many women are wearing the Hijab, especially post-9/11 to show opposition to Islamophobia and solidarity with the Palestinian cause.

Like Ahmed (1992), feminist philosophers like Lucy Irigaray note that the veil can take on the role of empowerment regarding a woman's sexual difference from a man. The Hijab, in this case, acts as a celebration of sexual identity and femininity. Some of the participants, like Shay (38 years old, Edinburgh, Pakistani, married, worker) and Naz (37 years old, Glasgow, Pakistani, housewife), explained that feminist identity is the celebration of gender differences and roles. She believed that being emotional and nurturing was a strong trait that she was proud of. Additionally, feminists, like Takolia (2012, no page), link the Hijab to having power over who can reach women's bodies "telling the world that my femininity is not available for public consumption...and I don't want to be part of a system that reduces and demeans women".

Among the growing number of feminists who defend the Hijab, there is a term that signifies the individual choice to embody Muslim identity against the conflicting pressures and competing cultural values of the dominant opposing feminist, Neo, and post-colonial feminist discourses, which typically essentialized the Hijab as signifying, respectively gender oppression and resistance to imperialism (Phipps, 2014, p.67; Bilge, 2010, p.19; Yegenoglu, 1998), which is known as "New veiling" (Macleod,1991). The "New Veiling" phenomenon started in Egypt but continued to spread all over the world (Nasser,1999). Macleod (1991) refers to this phenomenon as an "accommodate protest" (Nasser,1999, pp.408), which means that it represents "a double-edged message." While it is a form of "protest," it is also a form of "accommodation" or "acquiescence" (Macleod,1991, p.137-138).

The new veiling is defined as a middle ground for lower-middle-class working women to reconstruct their identities through balancing their conflicting roles, which are "traditional mother and wife roles" and the working women", which is referred to as "The clash between traditions and modernity" (Macleod, 1991, p. 11). This phenomenon functions as a resistance of unequal power relations in three main contexts, the familial, the class, and the global contexts. Within the Family, Hijab validates their roles as "good woman," "good wife", and "good mother, while working outside and helps to maintain their power in this context. Additionally, it helps them upgrade from lower-class to middle-class working women. Globally, it acts as an affirmation of their cultural and gender identity by protesting "the loss of traditional values" caused by the rise of "modernization and development" (Macleod,1991, p. 135). In fact, Naz related the influence of modernization and globalization on the Hijab "So even Muslim women are not into wearing the Hijab now, this may be due to globalization and modernization. They consider the Hijab as old-fashioned." Consequently, Muslim women wearing the Hijab is a sign of rebellion against the loss of traditional values.

The term "the New Veil" (Nasser,1999, p.408) is like the concept of "double consciousness" (Du Bois,1903), which is introduced previously in the conceptual framework. "Double consciousness" or "behind the veil" suggests that women, as members of an oppressed group, have developed a double consciousness, which signifies a heightened awareness not only of their own lives but of the lives of the dominant group as well (Brooks,2011). The aim of this heightened awareness is to protect themselves and ensure their survival in a world that is dominated by men (Nielsen,1990). Accordingly, these are manifested in the participants' awareness of their positions, how they are perceived by the dominant group, and the way they are working on changing these perceptions by navigating between the two worlds of modernity and traditions.

This section has reviewed the relationship between the Hijab and feminism. Based on the participants' responses, two polarized types of feminism were mentioned. Feminism views the Hijab as an oppressive tool, and one regards it as an empowering mechanism. The next part of the chapter will deal with the role of the media in either the negative or positive portrayal of the Hijab.

7.3.3.-Media's Representation of the Hijab:

Another important aspect of the participants' responses was the media representation of the Hijab and its influence on their lived experiences. The media representations play a crucial role in the people's perceptions. According to Van Dijk (1993), media representations build up socially shared knowledge, ideologies, norms, and attitudes that inform the public mind thereby creating common sense. Therefore, the media has an influential role in creating and framing public conversations about Muslims in general and Muslim women in particular (Mohanty, 1984; Mishra, 2007; Greenberg & Miazhevich, 2012). Three major descriptions were assigned to the media representations, namely, negative (Mimi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, PhD student; Noun (37 years old, Pakistani/British Edinburgh, housewife; Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, revert, worker), positive (Shay, 37 years old, Palestinian, Edinburgh, worker), and neutral (Hope, 54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, Employed). In addition, most of the participants provided some examples to support their arguments.

Multiple works have criticized the Western portrayal of Muslims and the Middle East in the last three decades (Terman, 2017). These works are influenced by the groundbreaking book by Edward Said, "Orientalism" (1979), where he criticized the West for the representation of Muslims, Middle Eastern culture, religion, and society. For Said (1979), Orientalism transformed from a mere representation to a form of knowledge production that asserted Western and cultural superiority, consequently, justifying the colonial invasion of Muslim lands in the name of modernity, civilization, and progress (Terman, 2017, Cooke, 2002; Stabile & Kumar, 2005; Zine, 2006). Although Orientalism did not concentrate deeply on gender, it was utilized by feminists who negotiated women and gender in the relationship between power and representation in orientalist discourses (Abu Lughod, 2001). The concept of portraying Muslim women by the West is extracted from the term Orientalism and referred to as "Gendered Orientalism." Gender orientalism is specifically concerned with the representation of women and gender relations in orientalist discourses (Terman, 2017, no page). In addition, it is an important aspect of the colonial and imperial projects that define Western-Muslim relations in the modern era (Terman, 2017).

The gendered orientalist representations depend on dichotomies that consolidate power relations between the West and the Orient. These dichotomies are divided between the civilized and moral masculinity of the West and the barbaric, oppressive, deviant masculinity of the brown man, the free Western woman, and the oppressed, subjugated Muslim woman" (Nayak, 2006). Therefore, establishing gendered and racial hierarchies where the oppressed brown men and women are on the bottom scale (Khalid, 2011, p. 20). Among the images that work to stigmatize Islam as a barbaric, violent, and undemocratic religion are the contemporary portrayals of Muslim women. These representations align with this study findings as some of the participants referred to the media's representation as mostly negative. For instance, Nes (52-year-old, British/Pakistani, Dundee, married, employed) believed that the media "does capture all the negativity" about the Hijab. In addition, Zaynab (28-year-old,

Algerian, Glasgow, single, PhD student) mentioned the role of the media in influencing other people's perceptions by exaggerating when portraying Muslim women "I think that the media has a great influence on how people perceive things, like in this case they gave wrong idea about Hijab, the media exaggerated in portraying Muslim women as backwards and terrorists".

One example is utilizing the images of "the veiled Afghan woman" to highlight the barbarity of the "male Eastern Other" to justify the military invasion of Afghanistan. In the months after 9/11, the number of media stories on Afghan women sharply increased, and pictures of women wearing burqas appeared on the covers of widely read magazines such as "New York Times, Business Week, Newsweek, and Time", alongside reports of their subjugation (Khalid, 2011, p. 21). The image of the veiled women has been demonized and portrayed as oppressed and helpless in the oriental discourses. Some of the participants, such as Naz (37 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, housewife) referred to the homogenous representation of Hijab due to certain events like the War on terror in Afghanistan.

Because the context of the study is Scotland, it is important to have a discussion on the portrayal of hijabi women in the British media in general and the Scottish media in particular. Waterson (2019) explains that most coverage of Muslims in the British Media has a negative direction. This is according to a major analysis conducted by the Muslim Council of Britain, which indicates that these stories, promoted by the media, are the biggest contributors to Islamophobia. Amongst the different British magazines, *Mail on Sunday* had the most negative portrayal and coverage of Muslims with "78%" negative depiction of Muslims. Other magazines like *New Statesman*, *Observer*, and *Guardian* were categorized as the least likely to portray Muslims in a negative light (Waterson, 2019, no page). Furthermore, Garcia (2020) analyses the headlines of electronic British media using critical discourse analysis and Van Djik's framework (1991). The results show that the description of events is rarely positive when it comes to the Hijab. It is often negative and sometimes neutral. The lexical style of the Right-Wing press is intense and antagonized compared to the Guardian. Garcia (2020) describes the headlines used by the Guardian as softer and more considerate when dealing with minorities. Moreover, A landmark monitoring conducted by the Muslim Council of Britain where they extensively analysed over 48,000 online articles and 5,500 broadcast clips, has shown that almost 60% of online media articles and 47% of television clips associate Muslims and/or Islam with extremism and terrorism (Muslim Council of Britain, 2021).

According to a recent study by Kasirye (2021), women, in general, have been marginalized and depicted in all sorts of images in the media, especially Muslim women. To understand how they are portrayed, Kasirye analyses the depiction of Muslim women in the content of two Western magazines, the *New York Times*, and the British magazine *Guardians*. The results show that Muslim women are represented as terrorists who have relations with Qaeda because of their dress code (Hijab) or as extremists because of the way they practice their religions. Another study by Abdi (2023) explains that the British media has a history of demonizing Muslim communities through misleading and inaccurate reporting that is filled with inflammatory language and dangerous stereotypes. In addition, these promoted stereotypes are more likely to affect the public opinion of British viewers against the Muslim population. Furthermore, Abdi (2023) calls for the inclusion of Muslim voices to tell their stories from their standpoints. Muslim journalists in the UK form just "0,4 percent" (John

Schofield Trust, 2020, no page) of journalists in the UK, which is unfair to the “4 percent” of Muslims in the UK (Census, 2021). One Muslim journalist, Zahra Warsame, called for the importance of including Muslims in journalism by saying “We need more Muslim journalists across broadcast, print, radio, digital. We need to make sure they are supported and empowered in their newsrooms.” (Abdi, 2023, no page) Because for the communities to tell their own stories, they need to have more access to industry. Including Muslim figures in the media is seen by some participants as important to promote a good picture of Muslim women. For instance, Nounou’s (37 years old, Scottish/Pakistani, Edinburgh, Employed) made a reference of a chef who wears the Hijab on the British TV, who she believed has a good influence on the representation of Muslim women “I follow Nadia Jamir Hussain she is a fantastic cook, she is basically English if you know what I mean, she cooks British food, she is Muslim and she wears Hijab on tv”.

When talking specifically about the Scottish media, one significant work examines the engagement of Muslims with the mainstream Scottish media (Munnick, 2017). The author explains that Muslims are neglected in the Scottish media, yet this neglect is referred to as “Benign neglect or approach” (Munnick, 2017, p. 219), which means avoiding talking about them so as not to involve them in bad news. Furthermore, Munnick (2017) believes that the hostility towards Muslims that is often found in the British press is muted in the Scottish media, which means the organizations that serve primarily the Scottish audience. When discussing the journalist’s knowledge of Muslims, Munnick (2017) states that most of the journalists in the study’s sample show some tension on when to use the term “Muslim” in sources and stories. Some of them explain that they prefer to avoid using the term unless the issue is about religious affairs.

Although the idea of terrorism is highly associated with Muslims (Said, 1979), the Scottish journalists “showed a general goodwill to Muslims and a curiosity about what might make Muslims in Scotland particular and unique. None of them were ‘out to get Muslims, in either a professional or a personal capacity” (Munnick, 2017, p. 222). However, they were not determined to build up any stronger connections with communities. The study also shows that Muslims who are active in their relations with journalists demonstrate a desire for more representation of Muslim stories in the Scottish media. Only one participant was specific about the Scottish media. Shay (38 years old, Palestinian, Edinburgh, married, worker) mentioned some positive examples of the Scottish media “Here in Scotland, sometimes in the Eid time, they bring some Muslim women and men, not with Hijab sometimes and they introduce our culture, and they speak about Eid they speak about Manasik Hajj (Pilgrimage steps), I see that in Eid al-Adha, I do not know if u see that on BBC Scotland, I feel like they are very nice people”.

Different examples were mentioned by the participants regarding the negative portrayal of Muslims in the Western media, for instance, in Netflix movies and series. Khan (2020) criticized several Western movies and series for the negative portrayal of Muslim women in the Media. For instance, one of the most markable roles for a Muslim woman in the BBC in the past few years, specifically in 2018, was the role of *Nadia*. *Nadia* is portrayed as a victim who needs to be saved from her husband. However, the plot twist shows that she is the terrorist mastermind. The issue is that this series has gained notable recognition from the Bafta and the Emmys, which seem to acknowledge and support these regressive roles. Furthermore, it enhances the oriental stereotypes that were discussed before of the

“Oppressed Muslim woman” and the “Barbaric and oppressive brown man”. Thus, maintaining the hierarchies (Khalid, 2011, p.16). Another important and controversial Netflix series is the Spanish drama *The Elite*. This series uses the idea of removing the Hijab as a way of breaking free from religion and adopting Western freedom. In this drama, the character *Nadia* removes her Hijab before going to drink Alcohol and have sex with a white man (Khan, 2020). One of the participants, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Ph.D. student), made a reference to this series, yet she also showed the positive side of this portrayal and described it as showing the struggles that Muslim women must endure to be fit in the Western societies.

This section has reviewed the representation of the Hijab in Western Media with a specific focus on the Scottish media. There are different opinions regarding the representation, however, a lot of work is required to improve the portrayal of Muslims in general and the Hijab in particular.

7.4. Conclusion:

The second chapter dealt with an important aspect of the Hijab, which was gender. The first part of the chapter was dedicated to the findings, where the views and opinions of the participants were examined. It discussed their opinions regarding how they felt when wearing the Hijab, their views regarding the concept of feminism and gender equality, and how they felt they were perceived by others and represented by the media. The second part of the chapter established a conversation between the participants' views and the already existing theory and literature. The following chapter deals with the challenges that encounter Muslim in Scotland.

8. Chapter Eight: Gendered Islamophobia Experiences in Scotland

8.1 Introduction:

This chapter deals with the female Muslims' experiences of gendered Islamophobia in Scotland. It will seek to examine specifically the types of Islamophobias they experienced, and how it affected their lives. The practice of wearing the hijab is the most visible demonstration of being a Muslim in the public sphere. Nevertheless, the hijab is viewed differently by those who practice it and those who oppose it. As discussed in the previous chapters, the meaning of the hijab encompasses various cultural and religious connotations like a sense of religious piety, a means of protection from sexual gazes, public modesty, and a sense of liberation and empowerment. However, some may perceive the Hijab as a symbol of radical Islam and extremism and is considered a sign of gender inequality, Islamic terrorism, oppression, and self-segregation as explained in the second chapter. In this context, Hijabi Muslim women are more likely to encounter a higher risk of hostility and abuse due to the nature of their visible identity. The participants in this study shared their experiences of Islamophobia including various forms that they encountered in different spaces and places that ranged from verbal and physical to a covert way that is embedded in their everyday interaction with their environment.

8.2. The nature of the Islamophobic victimization in Scotland:

8.2.1. Verbal Abuse:

During the interviews, most of the participants demonstrated familiarity with the simple meaning of Islamophobia, which is hostility towards Islam and Muslims. Some of them did not understand the concept but related the incidents they had experienced to the practice of wearing the Hijab, in addition to other identities like race, nationality, language, and disability. Diverse types of Islamophobic incidents were reported by the participants including verbal abuse.

Verbal abuse, in various public spaces like streets, public transport, and shopping centres, was a common experience among the participants. Out of the various types of verbal abuse were sexual harassment, swearing, and catcalling. Most of the perpetrators were described by the participants as white people, in addition to other characteristics like old, teenagers, drunk, and under the influence. Furthermore, the comments did not only target their Muslim identities, but they were also of a sexist and racist nature. Moreover, some of the participants provided explicit and direct examples of the language used by the abusers.

Nana (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Single, PhD student) shared her experience of being chased by a drunk person who was shouting sexist and sexual slurs "It was three o'clock that I was walking down the street looking for a pharmacy. Out of the blue, a drunk man started chasing me. I was running, my heart started pounding, and I looked behind from time to time. I cannot describe how horrible it was. He started using terms like Bastard Muslim sisters and Muslim whores, he was white and had a Scottish accent." The abuser was not only targeting the participant for her Muslim identity but attached it to other terms that degraded her gender identity. Furthermore, employing the plural form "sisters" "whores" alludes to the idea that the perpetrator targeted the participant based on her belonging to the Muslim community. It is important to consider the identity and the state of the abuser, Nana described it as a white, Scottish male who was under the influence, which brings about the idea of race,

and being under the influence explained that the abuser might not be aware of what he was doing. Thus, the verbal abuse happened based on both her visible Muslim and gender identities.

Like Nana, other participants related the verbal incidents they experienced to the performance of their Muslim, gender identity, and race identity. The element of race played a significant role in defining how the abuser viewed them. Three participants believed that the abuser related the wearing of the Hijab and their skin colour to South Asian identity. As a result, they were called the racial slur “Paki,” even though some of them were not from Pakistan. As one interviewee said “For instance last week, I was in a different area and somebody open their car window and they said like PAKI because I was wearing Shalwar Kamiz and I just put my thumbs up (recreating /illustrating the scene by raising her thumbs), I could have said something bad and do the same, so that’s probably ruined his day, not mine, I just smiled”(Muna, 43 years old, Pakistani/British, Glasgow, married). To illustrate more, the participant was asked to describe what she was wearing and why she believed the perpetrator targeted her “I think it has to do more with my race and ethnicity because I am brown and I was wearing Shalwar Kamiz with hijab, which is our traditional clothes”. *Shalwar Kameez* is a traditional Pakistani cloth that is worn, sometimes, with a veil. The abuser did not only target her because of her Muslim identity and gender, but also because of her Pakistani background.

Likewise, Hadia (19 years old, Pakistani/Scottish, Glasgow, single, student) reported getting “Paki” comments from strangers “If you are a Pakistani, they are going to call you a Paki for sure and if you are speaking in your language, they are going to say that you must speak English. Yup, I have encountered people throwing around the Paki word”. It was not only the appearance that contributed to that racial slur, speaking in a different language furthered the experience of discrimination, which is referred to as linguistic discrimination. Furthermore, Hadia expressed the irritation of the obligation to use the English language not to offend other people. Hadia’s (19 years old, Pakistani/Scottish, Glasgow, single, student) case shows an example of the intersection of different identities including the Muslim, gender, racial identity, and language. In contrast to Muna and Hadia, some participants were not from Pakistan. However, they were called “Paki” based on their appearance. For instance, Hana (36 years old, Yemeni/Arab, Edinburgh, Married) stated that “I got random comments from teenagers calling me a paki (an ironic tone), I was walking through the neighbourhood, and they started shouting and calling me that. So, I said to them, I am not a Paki, I am an Arab, they saw me wearing Hijab and assume that I am from Pakistan. They are not educated (laughing) not every Pakistani wears a Hijab. I mean I don’t know about their education and upbringings like they could have heard wrong and negative things about it”. The participant used irony to mitigate the intensity of the situation by explaining to the teenagers that she was an Arab. In addition, she assumed that the teenagers used that slur because they thought she was Pakistani, thus investing the Hijab with a racial meaning. The participant also assumed that the boys were not educated enough about the Hijab.

In the same way, Fati (53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, Edinburgh) was called a “Paki” by a little boy “One boy like was saying like look at this PAKI and you can hear this and that. Apart from one or two incidents that happened in 6 years”. The participant seemed unbothered because the person, using the term, was a “boy,” which signified immaturity. However, the idea that the child had on his mind is that every woman who wears the Hijab

was a “Paki.” Using a racial slur was not the only way abusers discriminated against Muslim women in the study, some women expressed how they were targeted based on their national identities.

Despite identifying as British, Noun (48 years old, British, Pakistani, married, Edinburgh) shared her experience of being verbally abused by a woman at a shopping centre. The perpetrator assumed that Noun was not British because of her Muslim appearance. She noted:

I had an issue in the past, it must have been 5 years ago. When I got shouted at when I was at the centre, out of the blue a woman started to scream in my face and called me a terrorist and told me to take off my scarf and asked me why I was wearing it. I said it is my religion and she said like get off my country and I said it is my country as well, I was born here, she was white and she was screaming her head off and I got the security and they came and I asked if they can refrain her, but they could not, but what they could do was calling the police and I said and I have said like I would like their surveillance camera on her to get a good picture of her to give to the police and they have heard the conversation, I was telling the woman that what she was doing was illegal

Unlike previous cases where most of the persecutors were described by the respondents as white males, the harasser, in Noun’s case, was a white woman, who displayed superior behaviour when ordering Noun to take off her Hijab. Instead of ignoring the verbal abuse, Noun decided to respond by defending her identity and belonging to Britain by saying “It is my country as well,” in addition to reporting the incident to the police. The order to take off the Hijab was opposed by an action by the respondent, which created a dialectical ⁴¹ (superior/inferior) and power tension between the abuser and the abuser. Furthermore, using the term “terrorist” gave an indefinite example of the pre-assumptions that the abuser had on the idea of wearing the Hijab. Therefore, Noun was perceived as both a terrorist and a foreigner.

One of the interesting findings was that the participant reported the incident, not because she wanted financial compensation, but to ensure that no Muslim woman will experience the same issue, which is a sign of solidarity and belonging to the Muslim community “She was fined 255 pounds because it was her first offense, I did that because my mom goes shopping at the centre and my mother’s language is very basic and there are a lot of Hijabi women who go there I felt like if I allowed this woman to get away with it if she is going to ever see another Muslim woman, she will do the same, so I did that to stop her. but after that, it has never been another incident, and I don’t think anyone else has gotten into the same incident either”. Like Hadia (19 years old, Pakistani/Scottish, Glasgow, single, student), Noun expressed how language might be a factor in furthering the experience of discrimination “My mother’s language is very basic”. The participant’s statement “she will do the same” showed a concern that this incident may repeat itself in the future.

The issue of national identity was also tackled by Nima (43 years old, Scottish, married, Edinburgh, Employed), who identified herself as White Scottish, explained how people asked her to remove her Hijab because it is incompatible with the Scottish identity “I find people commenting here in Glasgow I had once or twice people when they hear me speak, they suddenly tell me get that out of your head. Because they think that as a Scott, I should not be Muslim. It is their interpretation that Muslims are foreigners”. The abusers created tension

between her Scottish identity and Muslim identity by regarding them as incompatible. Thus, although Nima's national and racial identity are Scottish, their intersection with her visible Muslim identity, from their abusers' point of view, denied her the Scottish identity because both identities are incompatible and different.

Participants experienced verbal abuse in different forms. They mostly related it to their Muslim identity; however, the comments did not only target their Muslim identity but intersected and crossed with other identities including gender, racial, and national identities. Verbal abuse was an obvious and direct form of discrimination shared by the participants. Nevertheless, some interviewees shared severe and intense forms of abuse that they believed were related to their Muslim identity, which were physical assault and violence.

8.2.2. Physical Violence and Assaults:

Within the study, the participants identified another form of Islamophobia, which involved a physical aspect where there was direct contact between the abuser and the abused. The physical aspect of Islamophobia encompassed various actions such as pulling off Hijabs, physical attacks, murder attempts, and threats. It was challenging discussing these aspects with the participants because it revived some past traumas. Due to the sensitive nature of this theme, the researcher was considerate of the participants' emotional expressions by being careful with letting the participants express themselves without interruption.

One informant (Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed) reported that she was nearly attacked by a drunk man at a train station "I thought I would be attacked in a train in Falkirk, the guy was very drunk he was coming for me. And he started screaming at me to go home. He called me a terrorist and the b-word I thought that he was going to hurt me at some point. And that is why I prefer not to take public transport. I just do not feel public transport is safe at all." The unsuccessful attack led the abuser to use other forms of violence like calling her a "terrorist" and the "b-word" (Lina, 44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed). Although the participant identified as a white Scottish woman, wearing the Hijab denied her the Scottish identity in the abuser's eyes. The abuser's violence caused Lina a traumatic experience, which was manifested in her avoiding public transport.

Like Lina, Zizi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) shared her experience of being harassed by a man she believed was either drunk or mad.

The other incident happened to me when I was walking on the street and someone tried to scare me and grabbed me, I did not know whether he was normal or drunk I am not sure of that I mean he verbally abused me, for a minute I thought he was a mad person. But he did not seem mad. I mean the street was full of people, why would he only choose me among them to attack me? So, I thought because I was different wearing my Hijab.

This incident implied that the respondent was surprised by the sudden attack, and this caused her to question the state of the abuser to figure out why he attacked her in the first place "I thought he was a mad person". She concluded that the attack was related to her Hijab because none of the people around her was wearing one.

Amongst the common physical Islamophobic attacks was Hijab pulling. Talking about this issue, two participants had an experience of Hijab pulling, while one participant shared her

relative experience. For instance, Muna (43 years old, British/Pakistani, Glasgow, married) demonstrated how the experience of pulling her Hijab off when she was a teenager still affects her well-being.

I was very very very (emphasizing) like for example that experience of my hijab being pulled is still giving me a kind of trauma I still remember that even now, I was only young, I was at school, I was thirteen or fourteen. It did not hurt me, but it hurt me inside. It was not easy when somebody pulled my hijab off in front of everybody! It was a boy, and we were waiting in line to get lunch at a school restaurant, he thought it was funny when he pulled my Hijab off, they started laughing and I just left right away.

The tone of the participant conveyed disappointment when narrating this incident. At some point, the participant could not find the words to describe her traumatic experience, and this can be illustrated through the repetition of the word “very” at the beginning. Even though the incident happened years ago, the participant expressed how she is still affected by “Until now like this is the only incident that is still with me. This affects me a lot”. Muna (43 years old, British/Pakistani, Glasgow, married) also shared an incident where she was spat at by a client “I do remember another incident. I was at our own business, and somebody threw something at me, I think it was money, and I found it disrespectful. I did not like it; I was at a cash desk and that girl spat on me! And she called me some racist words, I called the police, and they ended up arresting her, unfortunately, she was underage.”

Similarly, Noun (48 years old, British/Pakistani, Edinburgh, married, employed) experienced the same issue post-9/11 event. She was speaking in a stressful tone.

Yes, there was another incident that was right after the 9/11 incident, so I used to walk to work from Glasgow to the city centre my workplace was based in the city centre, before that event, I had never had an issue nobody ever said anything to me I was very comfortable and this is used to take me about 40 mins from where I was, three weeks after the event, I had someone, one of the boys tried to grab my Hijab and pull it off and I could manage to grab it back and because I grab it with such a force he got frightened and the two of them run off and they got scared.

Although the 9/11 event did not take place in Scotland where the Hijab pulling action took place, the participant believed it was because of 9/11 because she never went through such a situation before. The expressive statement “I had never had an issue nobody ever said anything to me I was very comfortable” alluded to a transformation in people’s perceptions and actions towards Hijab post 9/11. Furthermore, using the term “boys” gave a hint of the abuser’s age. The participant's response to the abuse was active, instead of ignoring it, she decided to resist and grab back her Hijab.

Physical and verbal abuse are more direct and overt forms of gendered Islamophobia. The participants, in this study, shared various forms of verbal and physical abuse including Hijab pulling, sexual assault, racial slurs, and physical attacks; however, it is crucial to consider the covert forms of gendered Islamophobia. The following section will deal with how other covert or hidden forms of gendered Islamophobia operate in everyday life, according to the participants’ lived experiences.

8.2.3. Covert Forms of Islamophobia (Non-verbal Islamophobia / Institutional Islamophobia)

8.2.3.1. Non-verbal Forms of Islamophobia:

As was mentioned in the previous section, several participants related some non-verbal actions and treatments to their Muslim visibility. Some of these gestures include being ignored, being monitored at shops, and receiving dirty looks and stares. Although these actions were not straightforward, the respondents felt a sense of exclusion, difference, and sometimes shame. One of the participants described how she felt irritated and uncomfortable by the stares she received. Nes (53 years, British/Pakistani, Dundee, married) noted: “Not really. But sometimes you feel that people stare and the first thing they see is your Hijab, which is quite natural, I am not being subjected to any kind of discrimination, but you do feel that there is slight discrimination. It is quite difficult to explain. You do feel people’s faces are not pleasant when you travel by train.” The first thing that people noticed about Nes was her Hijab, which explained the visibility of her Muslim identity. The participant referred to this type of discrimination as “slight,” which was passive and less direct compared to a verbal or a physical act. However, the statement, “you do feel people’s faces are not pleasant when your travel by train”, alluded to the idea that the participant felt internally judged by others through the changes of their facial expressions.

One interesting point is the avoidance of using public transport due to the fear of being abused. Nes expressed how she avoided using public transport because of hearing other people’s stories of Islamophobic abuse “Not really! People have generally been nice. I go out mostly by car, so I don’t really because I have heard some incidents of people using public transport that have had some verbal abuse. They wear Hijab! Most of them are friends, that makes you feel a bit worried”. The stress and anxiety of being subjugated to abuse, make the participant use a strategy to protect herself, which is avoiding public transport.

In the same vein, Nima (43 years old, Scottish, married/revert Edinburgh) believed that getting weird or strange looks from strangers was not a result of her Muslim identity only but involves her family’s various identities “So we are very visibly noticeable. My opinion about it is that people get weird when they just see me. When a random person sees me, he sees a white face in hijab in a wheelchair with a Black man and with 21, 19, and 4-year-olds. And they are busy trying to work out, that is how it feels, they are always trying to work that on their heads.” The expression “people get weird when they see me” suggested how the participant was constantly aware of how other people stare and silently judge her. In addition, although the participant identifies as a Scottish white woman, she was still perceived as “weird” and foreign because of the intersection of her Muslim identity, national identity, and disability. One interesting idea is including the visibility of her family. Nima explained that the visibility of her “Black Husband,” who used a different language also contributed to their experience of discrimination “But when I am with my Husband and he speaks Bengali on his phone, people will be irritated, and he is loud as well. I do not know if he is loud, or it is the issue of the language.” Discrimination because of displaying cultural mannerisms that are different like using a different accent or a different language was manifested through this example. However, one of the respondents explained that the intersection of her Muslim identity with her Scottish identity helped her deal with some incidents of discrimination.

Although being a Muslim Pakistani who wears the Hijab, Noun (54 years old, British/Pakistani, married, Edinburgh) noted that her Scottish accent and fair complexion helped her deal with a non-verbal Islamophobic incident.

Yes, I do. I think if you are a coloured person, you will encounter that. Although I am Pakistani, I am fair-skinned, so I think I get away with a lot of things than a dark-skinned Pakistani! I believe when you have a dark skin colour and language issues that makes it far worse for you. I don't think they are bad to me as compared to if I have an accent or colour skin. Noun (54 years old, British/Pakistani, married, Edinburgh)

She described how her Scottish accent and fair complexion saved her from being discriminated against in the following anecdote.

There was a very small incident, I parked in Asda and a guy gave me a very dirty look. I don't know why! So, I said to him with a Scottish accent is there an issue? And he was shocked at my accent. And he said in a Polish accent no...no...no! But I believe if I had an accent, I believe they think that women with accents and dark skin colour are inferior. I become superior because of my skin colour and once I speak. I have noticed that.

The dialectic relation (superior/inferior) was also repeated in this case. Noun believed that if she was a woman of a darker complexion with a Hijab and a different accent, she would have been an easy target of discrimination. Once again, the perpetrator is described as a white person. Noun also mentioned receiving some dirty looks from the parents at her son's school, which led her to think of removing her Hijab,

I always feel proud to be a visible Muslim but when I came to Livingstone and started taking my children to school, it was just the mothers giving me literally dirty looks. Even those who were in my children's classes. When you walk past them, they would roll their eyes. And they knew me they knew that my child was at their school. I knew because of My hijab. So, I felt like taking it off. For the first time in my life, I felt like taking it off because I felt it was causing this negativity, and I wanted to take it off for that reason.

The actions of eye-rolling and dirty looks were primarily because of Noun's Muslim identity. This led her to consider the idea of taking off her Hijab to be included and accepted by the student's parents. Thinking of taking off her Hijab was a result of social pressure and internal shame of being a visible Muslim, which is referred to as internalized Islamophobia. In other words, the participant did not do anything wrong, yet she felt that something was wrong with her because of wearing the Hijab.

Likewise, Naz (37 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, married, housewife) shared a feeling of being avoided at a birthday party. She believed that the action was directed towards her racial and religious identities. The actions of the woman made the participant question if there was something wrong with her. When asked to describe the woman, the participant explained that she was a white old Scottish lady. In addition, using the expression "maybe" signified the confusion of which identity led to the action of avoidance and ignorance.

Once I went to a birthday party with my kids, it was a very sunny day. So, we sat outside and when getting hotter we went inside. There was an old lady, I went inside and sat next to her, she did not say anything, she just went outside so quickly. I did not notice it for the first time, but it happened twice or thrice. When I am outside, she goes inside, and vice versa. So, I said like okay there is something wrong. I felt her reaction. She was a white Scottish old lady. It was more about the actions here. I was the only one there with a Hijab and who had brown skin. So maybe it was directed to both my Hijab and skin colour.

Being followed and monitored at shops was also discussed by some of the interviewees. Although they believed it was not a direct action, they felt it was targeting them because of their visible Muslim identity. For example, one interviewee said: “I was shopping with my friends at a supermarket, and I noticed that the security man was following us everywhere. I was sure that I had not got anything yet, we were still looking around for some stuff to celebrate. It was so disappointing because the security man was only following us, not other people. I swear at some point I suspected that I had stolen something. So, we decided not to buy anything and headed home” (Zizi, 28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, PhD student). The participant expressed how she felt confused and disappointed in being excessively monitored by the security man to the point that she suspected herself of stealing something.

As previously explained, gendered Islamophobia takes various forms, among them were the microaggressions shared by the participants, which consist of receiving dirty stares, being ignored, excluded, and monitored. Nevertheless, the participants also mentioned other more covert or manipulative forms of Islamophobia that operate at structural and institutional levels. The following section discusses gendered Islamophobia in some sectors and institutions in Scotland.

8.2.3.2. Institutional Islamophobia:

As discussed in the previous chapter, interpersonal Islamophobia took different shapes according to the experiences of the participants. It can be verbal, physical, and indirect. Unlike the previous section, this section deals with Islamophobia at the institutional level. It looks deeply at the responses of the interviewees regarding the discrimination and exclusion they faced at various institutions including the workplace, the educational sector, and airports. The types of discrimination that they shared included examples like being rejected after job interviews, having a challenging time finding jobs, choosing between their hijab and jobs, and feeling excluded and treated differently at the workplace. Although it was not a direct rejection, one participant suspected that her visible Muslim identity was the primary reason for rejection after many job interviews.

I think one of the times you feel that you are wearing Hijab is when you apply for jobs and when you have job interviews, so I went through a phase when after the university, after my first degree, I was applying for jobs, I was getting a lot of interviews and then I would go and then I would not get any of these jobs. Even though it was not direct, I was not told that I got rejected because of my Hijab. But I have to say, that that time it was one of the few times I felt that maybe, maybe! It was because of my Hijab (San, 40 years old, Palestinian, Edinburgh, married)

When asked if she ever encountered any direct form of rejection because of her visible Muslim identity the participant shared the following example followed by stressed laughter “At one of my job interviews, I was asked about my Hijab and I was like this is an interview, why you are asking me about my Hijab? They asked me if I wear this all the time and if it would prevent me from going to work and I was like what is this (stressed laughter).” The expression “they asked me if I wear this all the time” suggested that the person who conducted the interview had less or no knowledge about the practice of the Hijab.

The assumption that the Hijab might be an obstacle to work was also shared by Dr Zee (34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married, employed) “The lady at my work was trying to say something about my Jilbab ⁴² like it was not smart enough, but I think because it is large and quite spacious! Because some people believe that when you do not wear trousers you are not smart enough.” Like San, the issue was not directly tackled by her supervisor, however, the participant tried to find excuses for this action by relating it to attractiveness “So, I just let her know that it is not going to affect my job. I think the lady already had a negative idea about jilbab, I just feel it is a negative bias, maybe she does not feel like it is something attractive enough. But honestly, I did not let that bother me.” In the same vein, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) shared the experience of one of her friends, who got refused because of her visible Muslim identity. Mimi made a comparison between two different institutions.

My friend wanted to work as a supervisor at a primary school, she thought that she had the right experience and degrees, but they were not excited about her working at that place because she wore a Hijab. They have not told her that directly to her face, but the refusal was not justified! No reasons were mentioned. I think that this may happen to me one day as well! Yet I know some Hijabi women who work in health sectors such as NHS (National Health Service), and they are fine.

As explained above, the participant made a comparison between the education and the health sector in Scotland based on her experience. When asking the participant to clarify more, Mimi explained that the education sector was more selective when choosing the right candidate because the parents may be concerned that their children may be influenced by the Hijab “Yes, I have said there are some sectors, for instance, a primary school would not let Hijabies to teach their children because they were concerned their children may be influenced by Muslim ideologies. One intriguing point was comparing the tolerance of different ideologies at primary schools “I have heard a lot of parents letting their children being taught about sex (sexual education) *LGBTQ* and other things, like if they are seeing this as right, they receive this as normal, they are tolerant to other things. I think they should keep the same energy towards the Hijab”.

Experiencing systematic Islamophobia was also discussed by Noun (48 years old, British/Pakistani, Edinburgh, married). The participant believed her son was a target of discrimination, to the point where he felt depressed, primarily because of her Hijab “It was when I first moved to Livingstone, my son was 9 and half years old and went to P6 in school, he started to be picked on by the teacher, that’s what surprised me! He was very clever in England, so when he came over, we started to notice a decline, he was very keen to learn things and to start school.” Moving to Livingstone seemed to signify a turning point in her

son's life because she described his performance at his previous school in England as "a keen learner."

To keep the conversation open and the interviewer pitched about her and her son's experience of systematic Islamophobia, the participant employed phatic language "That's what surprised me". Moreover, Noun expressed an internal feeling of shame by explaining to her husband that her son is going through that discrimination essentially because of the Hijab "I remember saying to my husband I do not think it is Ismail, I think it is my Hijab! I think it is me that she does not like. I remember saying to her that the match that you are giving to my son is very easy and she said: he is not clever". Furthermore, Noun shared an anecdote where the teacher gave her and her kids blackface stickers "My son was coming down the stairs and I saw a blackface sticker and it was the first sticker that he has ever gotten and I asked him why he was given it and he said I don't know and she came up and give me the same sticker and she put one in my daughter, I don't know why. I started to panic because I thought omg, she is a racist". The participant seemed dissatisfied and puzzled with the teacher's action attributing that to racism and describing it as a "derogatory action." Although the participant identified as British/Pakistani, she believed that the black sticker targeted her race. In addition, the dialectic superior/inferior was also mentioned by Noun, where she demonstrated that the teacher regarded her and her husband as inferior and unintelligent "so she just had to portray that she was better, she just wanted to put us down, I believe she could not take the fact that there is no way that she wants to comprehend that we are better, she was white. Absolutely white".

Instead of ignoring the situation, Noun revealed that she battled the teacher's action by reporting her to the principal. However, she expressed frustration about being neglected by other teachers and the head teacher and decided to contact other organizations "I tried to meet with the head teacher and the other teachers, but everyone was blanking me". The only solution was to change her son's school "It is a shame because it just took me one teacher to put me off and I never wanted to send him to school again." The expression "It is a shame" alluded to an internal anger on, what Noun believed, was a discriminatory action. In addition, the decision to never send her son to school again was a traumatic reaction to what she and her son had experienced.

Some stories of negative experiences at airports were also shared by some participants. Fati (53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, employed) shared one instance of airport security checking that she believed was unusual and uncomfortable.

She is only covering her hair because she is hiding something or there is a man hiding. You know when we were going to Dubai three years ago and the security guards and they ask me to go to the security room, so I asked them why? They told me that a woman needs to check if you are a man or a woman, it was so stupid because I was wearing my Hijab, I looked like a woman. I have big breasts. And you want me to go to that room so a woman can check up if I am a man or a woman.

Assuming that the gender of the participant because she was covering was an action of misgendering⁴³. The expression "I looked like a woman; I have big breasts" showed the attempts of the participant to confirm her gender identity. Furthermore, when inquiring about the participant's way of covering, she explained that she was not wearing a *niqab*⁴⁴, which involved covering the face "I would not say anything if I had *niqab* on. My voice can tell that

I am a woman. I was so offended. I made a complaint, but nothing was done about it”. Thus, Fati demonstrated that she had no problem being checked if she was wearing the *niqab*. Like Noun’s case, Fati took an active approach by reporting the action. However, she reported that she felt offended because nothing was done about her situation “I made a complaint, and nothing was done about it, and the man said that it was his security call that he must do”.

Equally, Zizi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) linked her visible Muslim identity to being overtly checked at one of the Scottish airports “I was taken to a room to be checked, I stayed there for six minutes. I was panicked because I thought there was something wrong with me. I felt so upset that I left my laptop in the scanner, but I managed to take it back.” This statement demonstrated the feeling of panic and shame that the participant had to encounter while traveling. In addition, the expression “I thought something was wrong with me”, showed a state of questioning and doubting herself.

In contrast, Nana (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) mentioned a positive experience at Scottish airports “My experience at the Glasgow airport was so positive. When we arrived at the office to authorize our entry, the security woman was very friendly and asked us if we enjoyed our trip and if we were feeling happy in Scotland. Personally, I felt content because before that I experienced an uncomfortable situation in the Frankfurt airport”. When inquiring more about the experience at the Frankfurt airport, the participant explained “I have been searched a lot, the security woman immersed her hand a lot inside my breast and kept pushing. It was so painful, there was nothing hidden there, I felt ashamed and that hurt my pride. I stayed there so long; I nearly lost the plane”. The statement implied that the participant did not feel the physical pain only, however using the idiom “That hurt my pride”, alluded to experiencing both emotional and internal abuse.

Despite the Islamophobic experiences shared by some of the participants, others believed that their experiences in Scotland were smoother and better than their experiences in other countries. Thus, the following section will examine the positive experiences shared by the participants in Scotland and how they compared them to their experiences in other countries like France, Belgium, and England.

8.2.4. Positive Experiences in Scotland Compared to Other Countries:

Despite the Islamophobic experiences mentioned above, some participants shared some positive aspects about living in Scotland. In addition, they discussed their views of secularism in Scotland and compared it to their experiences in other countries like France, India, and Turkey. Despite the previous Islamophobic experiences, most of the cases described Scotland as a Welcoming and inclusive country, however, some of them believed that Scotland is improving compared to past years. One interesting point was that Scotland was constantly compared to England by some of the participants who had the experience of living in both places for a considerable amount of time.

Talking about this issue, one participant shared a positive view about Scotland “I think Scotland is a good country to live in as a hijabi” (Shay, 38 years old, Edinburgh, Palestinian, married). However, she compared Glasgow to Edinburgh “Even comparing Edinburgh to Glasgow, I feel Edinburgh is safer. I feel like Edinburgh is well-organised and its people are easy to deal with. There are not a lot of homeless people, this is what my personal experience is about.” Besides comparing Edinburgh to Glasgow, the participant compared her

experience in Scotland to England “My experience in Scotland is more comfortable than England. I could not adapt there; it was strange because people would not respond to you.” According to the participant, the feeling of inclusion was an important factor in her experience. Feeling integrated and included was a measure that the participant employed in her comparison. Similarly, Hope (54 years old, Libyan, Dundee, married, Employed) referred to Muslims who live in Scotland as Lucky “Scotland is so safe, anyone who is a Muslim is lucky to live in Scotland”. In addition, she believed that racism is perpetuated by difference and is a part of human nature “Racism is everywhere, sometimes you can be racist yourself without knowing”. Moreover, the participant alluded to the idea that the Hijab is hard to accept because it is strange and different “You are not going to force them to love the Hijab, because they are unfamiliar with it.” The acceptance of the Hijab, according to Hope, was a product of unfamiliarity and ignorance instead of hate.

Scotland was also compared to other countries in term of safety and islamophobia. Several interviewees had the opportunity to visit some other countries. They often made a comparison between their experiences in Scotland and other countries. For instance, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single, PhD student) explained “If I am to compare Scotland with France, I would say here there is a lower level of discrimination according to my experience”. When inquiring about the reasons behind this comparison, she proceeded to answer “Scottish people are friendly even if they are convinced of Islam or Hijab, they do not show that. They treat you according to your behaviours. In France, I believe, it is worse because they are against the Hijab”. However, the participant argued that Islamophobia was and is still a real issue that operated at the street and institutional levels “To be fair, I would say that they are tolerant, but to some extent, because you still can find Islamophobia at street level and in some sectors”.

Like Shay, Mimi demonstrated that her experience in Scotland was more comfortable than in England. To explain more, she shared an anecdote, which she considered a traumatic experience, that took place in London “As I have mentioned, it was not here in Scotland, it was in England and precisely in London, so I was lost because it was the first time I came here, I did not whether to catch a train or a bus. so I went to a man to ask him about that he said the f-word and insulted me so badly. He told me “Fuck off!” he was white, he was English. I could tell that by his accent, and he was about 45 years old”. The incident made her alter the way she wore Hijab, so she cannot be exposed to that again “Just to mention that I have altered the way I put Hijab on. I started wearing a turban, I felt it was better for my safety”. Changing the Hijab’s style is an indication of the internalized shame and Islamophobia that the participant felt after being exposed to that experience. In the same vein, Wino (40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, Employed) discussed an Islamophobic incident that took place in England “Not in Scotland, but in England. I was sitting at the Manchester train station with my kids, there was a girl next to me who said a very bad comment, this is a woman who has a bomb, she made sure that I was the only one that heard it because she said it in a soft voice”. The abuser employed a verbal abuse technique to make sure no one heard her except the participant, which was a low voice to manipulate the victim. Once more, associating the Hijab with terrorism is manifested in the expression “a woman who has a bomb.” The participant also believed that there were other elements that contributed to that incident like having a different accent and race “I think there are other elements that contribute to that such as being a foreigner with a different accent and race.

In contrast, Wino felt that her experience in Scotland is positive. To confirm that she related to the experience of her friend who lived in Belgium “I think Scotland in comparison to France and Belgium is much better. I have a friend who was forced to take her Hijab off because she is teaching there and using it after school. It is sad for me that women do not have the right to choose what to wear.” The participant’s tone was upset while narrating her friend’s experience. Having the right to choose what to wear was a critical issue to Wino.

Some participants shared similar experiences in England. Both Sousou (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, engaged) and Zaynab (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) experienced verbal abuse in England. What made their experience similar was that they both experienced that at transport. Sousou narrated the following incident “I have not received any great challenges here in Scotland, but in England, when I first came here, there were a lot of British men and women, they started looking at me in a strange way, they started later cursing us and swearing at us and cursing Islam and Hijab with bad words. There was a guy there at the airport who told them to stop doing so.” Similarly, Zaynab recounted a negative experience in London “Here in Scotland, no. Yet in London (England), I did experience some kind of harassment. I was with my friends, we were on the bus, and most of my friends were wearing a Hijab. and there was a British, white woman who said do not take pictures of my country. the woman started screaming and saying these Muslims are going to kill me. She was like speaking to the driver and screaming. She was really abusing us at that time”. Although their experiences were similar, however, the intervention of the bystanders ⁴⁵, in Sousou’s case might have mitigated the effect of the Islamophobic abuse.

Some interviewees, who identified as Scottish, expressed pride in Scotland’s efforts to battle Islamophobia. For instance, Lina (44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, Employed) demonstrated that although Islamophobia was and still is an issue in Scotland, there are some efforts to battle it. The participant showed some awareness about the nature of Islamophobia in Scotland, and this is due to her work position. Moreover, Lina did not deny the existence of Islamophobia in Scotland, which suggested an objective perspective on her country.

there is a lot of Islamophobia and negativity, but the Scottish National Party has passed a resolution to see if the Islamophobia definition is to be adopted at the government level. so, I know that our gov is moving to make sure that these communities are protected. So, I think living in Scotland I would say it is easier than other countries Like France where they ban Hijab. However, I believe Islamophobia is still an issue for Muslim women who wear hijabs. It is at the street level and institutionalized Islamophobia. Trying to access jobs and services.

Likewise, Nima (43 years old, Scottish, Edinburgh, married, Employed) expressed pride in her Scottish national identity by making a comparison between Scottish and English. Using the personal pronouns “We” and “Our” signified her keen sense of national belonging and pride. Moreover, the participant differentiated between being Scottish and English by explaining that Scottish people have more sympathy and can relate to the struggles of Muslims. Unlike English people whom she referred to as “oppressors.”

We are used to having taken the media with a pinch of salt, to think what the real story is. We also are learning to think with ourselves. Our people were displaced for generations. Thus, we have empathy with other people who are Muslims and cannot

go home like we get. The English did not go through that, so they do not have that understanding, the English have always been the oppressors, this is not how Scotland works.

This section discussed the positive experiences shared by the participants in Scotland in comparison to other places they visited. To illustrate that, some participants employed comparison to manifest how their experiences and engagement in Scotland were much smoother and better than in other countries. However, the issue of Islamophobia is said to be an existing issue in Scotland and needs to be addressed. The following part of this chapter will tackle the findings considering previous research and theory on Islamophobic experiences in Scotland.

8.3. Discussion:

8.3.1. The Nature of Islamophobic Victimization in Scotland:

8.3.1.1. Verbal Assault:

The findings of the first section of this chapter divided the nature of Islamophobic experiences into subordinate themes, which include interpersonal, institutional, and disciplinary Islamophobic experiences. Most of the participants mentioned at least one experience of Islamophobia that they thought was directly related to their Muslim identity, in addition to the intersection of other identities, which made their experience, in some cases, worse.

The first subordinate theme was mainly dedicated to verbal instances of Islamophobia, where participants mentioned various types of verbal abuse including sexist slurs and some negative comments related to racial and national identity. The interviewees were not targeted because of their Muslim identity only, but due to the intersection of other identities with their Muslim identity. Because the verbal abuse targeted different identities at once, it is important to view the findings from an intersectional lens. As discussed in the theoretical framework, Crenshaw (1989, p.149) views intersectionality as a metaphor, in which an analogy is made between traffic and discrimination “Consider an analogy to traffic in an intersection, coming and going in all four directions. Discrimination, like traffic through an intersection, may flow in one direction, and it may flow in another.” In other words, intersectionality, in its simple meaning, is a way of looking at how different social categories like gender, race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender identity, disability, class, and religion intersect and overlap to create a unique experience of discrimination and inequality.

As explained above, most of the participants mentioned at least two identities that they think contributed to the verbal abuse they received. For instance, using the expression “Bastard Muslim sisters” alludes to the idea that the abuser targeted the participant based on her Muslim and gender identity. This is what is referred to as gendered Islamophobia. Gendered Islamophobia is defined by Zine (2006), as the various stereotypes and discrimination that Muslim women face. This finding aligns with previous studies that argue that Muslim women face a higher rate of Islamophobia compared to Muslim men. Ahmed’s report (2018, p.4), on Muslim women’s Islamophobic experience in the Greater Toronto area, and Zempi (2019) explain that Muslim women are more likely to experience Islamophobia because they are more visible. Not only that but due to the stereotypes that Muslim women are “easy targets” and “weak”. Similarly, Allen (2010) and Zempi (2014) demonstrate that there is a significant

relationship between Islamophobia and Muslim visibility. Similarly, a recent study uses the intersectional lens to address the impact of Islamophobia on Muslim women living in Belgium (Mescoli, 2022). Mescoli (2022) explains that Muslim women comprise a diverse group and are often the target of multiple discrimination and subordination. Talking about the Scottish context, a recent study shows that Muslim women are more likely to experience Islamophobia compared to men by 56%. In addition, 58% of residents of Glasgow believe that Muslim women are more at risk (Hopkins, 2023 and Hopkins, 2021, p.16).

According to the findings of this study, the intersection of religious identity and gender identity are not the only categories that create oppression. As shared in the findings section some participants, like Muna and Hana, were labelled the racial slur “Paki” because they wore the Hijab and, in some cases, Asian clothes like *Salwar Kameez*. In fact, considering Islamophobia as a form of cultural racism⁴⁶ is still a subject of discussion in the UK. According to the National Secular Society (2023), all British political parties adopted the definition of Islamophobia, except the conservative party. In the spring of 2018, the UK All-Party Parliamentary Group on British Muslims defined Islamophobia as “rooted in racism and is a type of racism that targets expressions of Muslimness or perceived Muslimness” (Muslim Council of Britain, 2021, no page).

Modood (2023) supports the idea that Islamophobia should be understood as a form of cultural racism even though it targets a religious group, which is Muslims. Equal to other religious and ethnic groups, Muslims can be a target of belonging to their community membership, rather than biology. However, this definition was rejected by the National Secular Society (2019, no page) because it is “unfit to the purpose”. The definition is seen as a conflation between racism and legitimate criticism of the Islamic doctrine which leads to considering it as a blasphemy code. In addition, the National Secular Society wrote a letter, where it called for the rejection of this definition for so many reasons. Some of these reasons were that Islamophobia poses a threat to the freedom of speech and shuts down discussion, thus rendering anyone who criticizes Islam and Islamist ideology, an Islamophobic. Also, it does not recognize Liberal Muslims who have different opinions about Islamic practices (National Secular Society, 2023). The NSS (2023) and Singh (2023) suggest the term anti-Muslim hatred instead of Islamophobia because no religion should be protected from criticism. Consequently, changing the term “Muslimness” to “Anti-Muslim” is much more appropriate. “The concept of Muslimness can effectively be transferred to Muslim practices and beliefs, allowing the report to claim that criticism of Islam is instrumentalized to hurt Muslims” (NNS, 2023, no page).

The concept of “Muslimness” is seen by many as a problematic concept due to considering a faith as an ethnic identity or a race, thus rendering any criticism of Islam unacceptable. Drawing from Bourdieu, Moosavi (2012, p.115) explains that Muslimness can be understood as a religious-based habitus, “an Islamic habitus”, rather than a class-based habitus. Thus, being an authentic Muslim who possesses the quality of Muslimness is more than just a performance, it is internalizing a set of characteristics, which is captured in the term habitus⁴⁷. In the same vein, Sayyid and Vakil (2021) believe that Muslimness is no different than Jewishness or Britishness. They describe it as a cluster of characteristics that are seen as having the quality of being a Muslim, for instance, names, food, clothes, mannerisms, and habits.

As mentioned above, defining Islamophobia as targeting Muslimness, or the expression of Muslimness was heavily criticized and rejected, mainly because of the term “Muslimness.” For instance, Greer, an expert in criminal justice, human rights, law, and counterterrorism at Bristol University, refers to “Muslimness” as a fake concept that attempts to attribute an ethnic identity to a faith (Singh, 2023). Likewise, Baroness Falkner demonstrates that treating a religion or a belief system as a set of characteristics “Muslimness” and dealing with it as a race, which is biological, does not work. In other words, basing islamophobia on biological features makes Muslims racially homogenous. Thus, neglects the experiences of white European Muslims like Bosnians, Kosovars, Albanians, and converts to Islam, who will have no protection under religious hate crimes (Sheikh ,2018).

Although considering Islamophobia as a form of racism does not seem right to many critics, the participants, in the study, were called the racist slur “Paki” based on their appearances, even though some of them were not from a Pakistani or a South Asian background. In this case, the perpetrators believe that whoever wears a hijab is from a South Asian background. Race and physical appearance play a crucial role in the act of discrimination. Reports by Hopkins (2021; 2023) show that those of South Asian heritage are more like to experience Islamophobia followed by those of Arabic backgrounds. In contrast, those of Eastern European background are the least likely to encounter islamophobia. One of the participants, Muna (43 years old, Pakistani/British, Glasgow, married), was subjugated to verbal abuse due to wearing Shalwar Kameez. In fact, Hopkins’s report (2021, p.16) demonstrates that considering whether phenotypical features can put a person at greater risk, the percentages of exposure to danger are as follows: “Wearing a headscarf (91%), Asian clothes (77%), having a brown complexion (76%), having a beard (73%), and attending a mosque (68%)”.

When defining Islamophobia, a part of it explains that it is also racism against those who are perceived to be Muslims. In fact, some studies show that Islamophobia is increasing due to the misrecognition of some minorities as Muslims. For instance, a study was conducted by Hopkins et al., (2017) focuses on the experiences of ethnic and religious young minority people who are mistaken for being Muslim in the Scottish context. The sample includes diverse young people from different religious and racial backgrounds like Sikhs, Hindus, and Black young people. The results show that misrecognition was constructed through geographical events, media representation, homogeneity, and the lack of visibility of non-Muslims. Similarly, Awan and Zempi (2020) examine the experience of non-Muslim men who suffer from Islamophobia because they were mistaken for Muslims. Their study (2020) show that the racialization of Islamophobia led individuals who have a similar disposition to Muslims, such as similar appearance, ethnicity, or race to be a potential victim of Islamophobic hate crime.

As explained above, the statistics show that Eastern Europeans are the least likely to experience Islamophobia compared to other ethnicities. This aligns with one of the findings where the participant, Noun (48 years old, British, Pakistani, married, Edinburgh), explained that having a white complexion was an advantage because it saved her from some Islamophobic encounters. In the same vein, one interesting study conducted by Moosavi (2015) explores the post-conversion experiences of white converts. The study demonstrates how their whiteness acts as a marker of dominance and respectability “The Muslim community ’in Britain is predominantly postcolonial South Asian community and as a result, Islam in Britain is conflated with South Asian ethnicity and culture. In contrast to non-white

converts, white converts are often beneficiaries of white privilege” (Moosavi,2015, p. 1919). However, this does not mean they do not experience difficulties such as exclusion. In this study, Nima (43 years old, Scottish, Edinburgh, married, revert) explained that she was denied her Scottish identity because of wearing the Hijab. In fact, Moosavi’s (2015) study also shows that upon converting to Islam, white people can lose access to whiteness and, therefore to white privilege. Another study was conducted by Alam (2012), which explains that whiteness and Islam are seen as incompatible by both non-Muslims and Muslims. This is also obvious in Noun’s (48-year-old, British, Pakistani, married, Edinburgh) case. Considering the white advantage, the participants stated an interesting point about the race of most of the perpetrators. As explained in the findings section, there was a dialectical relationship between the abuser and the abused, which is a superior/inferior relationship. In most cases, the abuser is a white male. Hopkins's (2016) study shows that white men are usually defendants in both racist and religiously motivated hate crimes in the UK. In addition, Hopkins (2016) gives examples of right-wing groups, like the EDL ⁴⁸, that are usually dominated by white men who impose specific acts of masculinity and white supremacy with their victims being Muslim women and men who assumed to follow the Islamic faith.

Overall, the analysis of the verbal comments such as “Paki” and “Bastard Muslim sister showed the intersection of different identities” like religion, race, gender to create discrimination against the Muslim women who wear the Hijab in Scotland. The next section of the discussion will deal with more overt forms that were discussed by the participants, which include physical violence, threats, and attacks.

8.3.1.2. Physical Violence and Assault:

Participants, in this study, reported diverse types of physical violence and assault that they related to their visible Muslim identity. Amongst these forms of violence were physical attacks, sexual assault, and Hijab pulling. The participants’ reactions to the acts of violence and assault differed from one to another. However, some of them reported suffering from the traumatic experience to the present day. In the matrix of gendered Islamophobia, Muslim women encounter Islamophobia in different domains. Facing physical abuse in public places belongs to the interpersonal domain. The interpersonal domain is defined as “the everyday experiences of Muslims, including the double sword of oppression that Muslim women experience with sexism in Muslim communities and gendered Islamophobia in public spaces, including violence” (Ali-Mahomed Wilson ,2020, p. 654). This is consistent with previous works on Islamophobia which consider physical violence and assault as serious issues. The first public inquiry into Islamophobia in Scotland shows that a “fourth-fifth” of Muslims in Scotland have directly experienced Islamophobia with Muslim women more likely to experience ⁴⁹ it than men. In addition, the respondents warned that physical and verbal abuse is escalating, especially in public transport (Tell MAMA UK, 2021, no page)

In fact, some participants, like Lina (44 years old, Scottish, Glasgow, married, employed), avoided using public transport because of the traumatic experience she faced. De Nolf, D’Haenens and Berrada (2021) identify various coping mechanisms that young Muslim women use to deal with Islamophobia. Among them is avoidance. In their study, some participants prefer to stay away or avoid any situation that might lead to hostility towards them, including places where they have experienced anti-Muslim sentiment, which is like Lina’s coping mechanism.

In a recent report, Hopkins (2021) shares a submission by one of the Muslim organizations called MEND⁵⁰, in which it explains that the second largest form of Islamophobia is physical acts of violence. They include various forms such as being spat on, shoved, slapped, thrown to the ground, and women having their hijabs pulled off. The organization shares an example of the victim saying: “I feel so paranoid walking the streets, I feel like everyone is out to attack me. I’m super self-conscious in public now” (Hopkins, 2021, p.16). This aligns with Muna’s (43-year-old, British/Pakistani, Glasgow, married) case, who explained that she is still affected by the traumatic experiences that she encountered when her Hijab was pulled off and she was spat on by a customer.

The action of Hijab pulling is an example of how gender and Islamophobia intersect because it targets directly Muslim women and girls who choose to express their identity publicly. This is apparent in previous works like the experiences of School girls in Edinburgh (Dean, 2017) and in another work on the experiences of Muslim women in Scotland (Scotsman, 2019). Another reported point was pulling the Hijab after the 9/11 event. Noun (48 years old, British/Pakistani, Edinburgh, married) shared her experience of Hijab pulling with a specific reference to 9/11. Indeed, it is particularly important to consider the geopolitical events that might lead to Islamophobic experiences. According to Hopkins (2016, no page), Islamophobic experiences are strongly attached to geopolitical events such as 9/11, the 2005 London bombings, the 2013 Woolwich incidents, and the ongoing conflicts in Syria. Thus, the experiences of Islamophobia and racism rise shortly after each event before declining gradually.

The rise of Islamophobia is a crucial point to tackle in the political context of this study. Some recent reports show that there is a rise in Islamophobic and antisemitic experiences in the EU. According to Shankar (2023), an EU official, charged with combating Islamophobia, explains that Muslims are often wrongly perceived as being involved in violence amid the Israeli-Hamas conflict. Similarly, London police explain that the antisemitic and Islamophobic attacks escalated after the event with Islamophobic offenses rising to 140% in the wake up of the 7th of October 2023 (Reuters, 2023). This led to the interfaith leaders in the UK calling to not allow the conflict to spill into the UK communities (Rimi, 2023). Thus, it is especially important for communities to be safe especially those who are visible such as Muslim women. Gokarisksel (2009) believes that veiled women are usually the centre of attention because of their head covering, their gender, and their relationship with specific spaces in society and state institutions. Furthermore, it is important to consider the post-traumatic effects of the Islamophobic experiences of the participants because it might lead to various consequences like emotional distress, isolation, and avoidance. A study shows that “A common misbelief is that physical violence causes more serious and long-term harm than emotional violence. In fact, the imprints of emotional abuse are similarly real and long-lasting” (Imer, 2023, no page). This is obvious in Muna’s case in which she mentioned that the experience of Hijab pulling happened years ago, however, it still affects her mental wellbeing.

Violence and physical assaults can range from small acts to more intense and severe acts. A study by Zempi (2019) shows the various physical assaults on Muslim women in the UK. Zempi (2019) explains that the participants, throughout individual and focus group interviews, described incidents of attempted and actual physical assaults including, taking off

the veil, pushing, shoving, being spat at, throwing eggs, water bombs, and takeaway food at them, and even extreme levels such as running them over by cars.

This section shed light on another direct form of Islamophobic experiences. Physical violence comes in different forms and might lead to severe circumstances. Among these circumstances are the emotional and post-traumatic experiences that are, as explained by Imer (2023), more serious than the actual attacks. Physical and verbal abuse are more direct and overt forms of gendered Islamophobia; however, it is crucial to consider the covert forms of gendered Islamophobia such as behavioural microaggressions including eye rolling, change in facial expressions, dirty stares. Thus, the following section will deal with how other more subtle or visible forms of gendered Islamophobia operate, according to the participants' lived experiences.

8.3.1.3. Covert forms of Gendered Islamophobia (Non-verbal and Institutional Islamophobia)

8.3.1.3.1. Non-verbal Islamophobia:

Islamophobia takes different forms Amongst the various forms that the participants mentioned were some less hidden, covert, and indirect forms. These types of actions are referred to as microaggressions. Microaggressions are defined as actions that negatively affect and target a marginalized group or individuals (Haghighi, 2023). They tend to leave the targets questioning whether it was because of race, or whether to confront the abuser (Nadal et al., 2012). Behavioural microaggressions were mentioned by several participants as a hidden type of Islamophobic discrimination. For instance, Nes (53 years, British/Pakistani, Dundee, married), Nima (43 years old, Scottish, married/revert Edinburgh), and Noun (54 years old, British/Pakistani, married, Edinburgh) mentioned receiving some dirty looks, change in facial expressions and eye rolls in public. In addition to being avoided at social events or monitored at shops as in the examples of Naz (37 years old, Pakistani, Glasgow, married) and Zizi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow). These types of microaggressions might be done intentionally or unintentionally, and they are referred to by Nadal et al., (2012, pp. 24) as “the pathology of the Muslim religion”. The pathology of the Muslim religion refers to the conscious, and sometimes unconscious, idea that there is something abnormal with someone of a different religion or faith, which leads to behaviours that cause punishment, judgment, or maltreatment (Nadal et al., 2010).

Some of the participants, like Nes, attributed these behaviours to the visibility of their Muslim identity. Others, like Noun, believe it because of the intersection of her race and religious identity. However, some participants like Nima went further and explained that it was a collective of her family's different identities that made them more noticeable and more likely to receive dirty stares. Furthermore, some of the participants expressed confusion about receiving certain microaggressions. For instance, the action of avoidance that Naz received from the old lady led her to question what the problem was. The participant was confused about whether it was her race or her religious identity. In fact, according to Nadal et al., (2012), microaggressions can lead to targets feeling angry and confused if race is involved in the interaction or whether to confront the abuser or not. Thus, they might lead the victim to be emotionally, physically, and psychologically drained, often leading to stress and poor mental health issues (Nadal et al., 2011; Rivera, Forquer, and Rangel, 2010; Sue et al., 2007).

The consequences of micro-aggressive behaviours, such as eye-rolling and dirty stares, are obvious in Noun's case. Due to the parents' behaviours at her son's school, Noun thought of removing her Hijab. The action of thinking of removing her Hijab is an example of how microaggressions might push someone to feel shame about their identities, which is in this Noun's case, internalized Islamophobia. According to Hilal (2022), internalized Islamophobia implies the phenomenon of Muslims absorbing dominant narratives that the followers of their religions are inherently violent, terroristic, repressive, uncivilized, uniquely patriarchal, and against liberal democratic ideals. In addition, it makes Muslims endure collective responsibility for the condemned acts of violence committed by Muslims while simultaneously denying, minimizing, and eradicating Muslim victimhood. Thus, the pressure, that Noun faced, led her to feel ashamed of her visible Muslim identity, consequently thinking of removing her Hijab to be socially included. Gendered Islamophobia takes various forms, among them were the microaggressions shared by the participants. However, the participants shared other covert or manipulative forms of Islamophobia that operate at structural levels. The following section discusses gendered Islamophobia in some sectors in Scotland.

8.3.1.3.2. Structural/Institutional gendered Islamophobia:

According to the theory of gendered Islamophobia (Alimahomed-Wilson,2020), the structural domain emphasizes institutionalized islamophobia, which refers to the exclusion and restriction of Muslim women that leads to an unequal outcome in social institutions such as labour, family, education, media, politics, and the legal system. Multiple participants shared their experiences in different sectors. For example, San (40 years old, Palestinian, Edinburgh, married) shared her experience of being rejected multiple times after job interviews. The participant explained that she was not told directly it was because of her Hijab, however, she was once directly asked about wearing her Hijab. The same happened with Dr Zee (34 years old, Nigerian, Glasgow, married) who believed that the lady at her work thought the Hijab might affect her work. These findings are consistent with previous works on Muslim women's employment in the UK. According to Welsby and Evans (2020), the employment rate was significantly lower amongst Muslims compared to other religious groups between 2012-2018, due to Muslim women's economic inactivity "over half of whom 56% were economically inactive in 2018" (Welsby and Evans, 2020, p.11).

Similarly, Seta's (2016, p.19) work demonstrates that "50 %" of Muslim women believed that their Hijab was the primary reason for their religious discrimination at work, especially in decisions taken or career advancement. In addition, the study (2016) shows that the threat of discrimination for manifesting religious identity was an important reason for Muslim women choosing to work in their own community or to undertake their own business. Hopkins' (2021), report on Islamophobia in the major Scottish cities, demonstrates that "86%" of the respondents believe that Islamophobia in Scotland has an impact on Muslims and those who are perceived as Muslims, employment opportunities. It is important to consider the gender disparity in employment. According to Coalition for Racial Equality and Rights (2020), the employment rate between Black and Minority Ethnic (BME) and white people in Scotland in 2019 was 16.4%, and for Black and minority ethnic groups women it was 22% compared to 9.5% for men (Cited in Hopkins,2021, pp 50). In addition, BME women's employment rate was lower than white women by "20%" (Scottish Parliament, 2020), which means that race also can contribute to the lower rate of employment amongst Muslim women.

Participants in this study also shared experiences of discrimination in other sectors like education. For instance, Noun (48 years old, British/Pakistani, Edinburgh, married) believed that her religious and racial identities intersected to contribute to her son's exclusion and discrimination by his white teacher at his school. One critical point was the decline in her son's academic performance due to the Islamophobic act. According to Hopkins (2021, p.46), "Islamophobia has an impact on the educational outcomes of Muslims (and those perceived to be Muslim) in Scotland, according to 74% of survey respondents and 77% of Muslim respondents". Despite the participant's efforts to report the discrimination, "everyone was blinking me out", her voice was not heard, thus she decided to change her son's school where the headmaster was a Muslim. In fact, the respondents in Hopkins '(2021) study believed that children's exclusion from educational activities leads to poorer life decisions and withdrawal from education.

Participants also shared being overtly checked at some of the Scottish airports. Fati (53 years old, Mozambique, Dundee, married, worker), for instance, explained that she was misgendered⁵¹ at the airport security checkpoint and was asked to prove that she was a woman. As demonstrated in the findings, the participant had no problem justifying that she was a woman if she had a niqab on, which is a face covering. In the same vein, Zizi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) showed irritation and discomfort with being held for six minutes and nearly missing her flight and laptop at the scanner. Excessive checking at airports might be the result of the United Kingdom's counter-terrorism policies, including the "Prevent⁵² program launched in 2003", which are said to be contributing to Islamophobia and discrimination against Muslims by pointing out their religion as the reason for security problems. This can be categorized in the disciplinary domain of gendered Islamophobia. According to Ali-Mahomed-Wilson, (2020), the disciplinary domain of power concentrates on surveillance, monitors, targets, and inculcates the societal ethos of monitoring Muslims because of their assumed inclination towards terrorism.

The intersection of gender, sexuality, and religion was obvious in Fati's and Zizi's cases. This view is supported by previous works about the experiences of Muslims at Scottish airports. For instance, Blackwood et al., (2013), in their work on the role of racism and Islamophobia in Muslims' encounters with airport authorities, note that those who had encounters with airport authorities stated explicitly that their treatment was based on being a Muslim of fitting in Muslim stereotype. Similarly, Bagheri (2018) investigates the experiences of Islamophobia in different Scottish airports (Glasgow, Edinburgh, Dundee, and Aberdeen). It is noted that Islamophobic encounters were not only experienced by those who were Muslims but even those who were mistaken for being Muslims. In contrast to Fati and Zizi, some participants, like Nana (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single), believed that her experience was positive at the Glasgow airport. Which might signify an improvement in treatment. However, the participant stated that her experience at the Frankfurt airport was uncomfortable. Despite the Islamophobic experiences shared by some of the participants, others believed that their experiences in Scotland were better than their experiences in other countries. The following section will examine the positive experiences shared by the participants in Scotland.

8.2.1.3.3. Comparing Scotland to Other Countries in Terms of Islamophobia:

The experience of living in Scotland by some of the participants like Mimi, Wino, Hope, Zaynab, Sousou, in this study was described as mostly positive compared to other countries

they visited. Multiple participants used the comparison to show the difference between Scotland and other countries they have been to, such as France and England. In addition, they mentioned several reasons for preferring Scotland such as the friendliness of the Scottish people, smooth integration and inclusiveness, and Scottish efforts to tackle Islamophobia.

As explained above, different participants compared Scotland to England. For example, Mimi (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single), Sousou (27 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, Engaged), Wino (40 years old, Indonesian, Edinburgh, married, worker), and Zaynab (28 years old, Algerian, Glasgow, single) stated that their experience in England was difficult compared to Scotland because of encountering Islamophobic incidents. In fact, various studies compared the experiences of Muslims in both Scotland and England. For instance, Bonino (2016, no page) explains that “lower settlement numbers, fewer worries about terrorism, and the welcoming disposition and sociability of Scots” made Muslim settlement in Scotland easier than in England. Similarly, Hussain and Miller's (2006) study shows that Islamophobia was significantly higher in England compared to Scotland. In addition, they believe that English nationalism encourages Islamophobia, unlike Scottish nationalism. Thus, these previous studies' findings align with some of the participants' experiences in England and Scotland.

Furthermore, some interviewees described their experiences in Scotland as better compared to other countries such as France. In a recent report, on the restriction of Muslim women's dress in 27 EU countries, the Open Society Justice Initiative (2022) explains that despite the rise in Islamophobia in the United Kingdom, it is distinctive from mainland Europe in its acceptance of religious symbols in education, employment, and public spaces “Despite various attempts to date as described below, the UK has not enacted any legal ban on face veils or headscarves” (OSJI,2022, p.152). One example of the UK's efforts to deal with discrimination and inequality in employment is the Equality Act 2010. This act enhances the protection of female and religious employees by combining and replacing different laws, which include sex, religion, and belief under the characteristics that require the protection of public authorities. However, Cannon (2023) criticized the law. As per Cannon (2023), the intersection of gender and religion is a crucial reason that disadvantages Muslims in the market. In addition, the author believes that despite the importance of addressing the issue from an intersectional lens, the domestic equality law in Britain still adopts fixed classifications of status inequality, which leads to undermining protection for Muslim women in the workplace. In other words, gender and religion are regarded as separate protected characteristics under the British domestic equality law, which frustrates the development of discourse on the interaction between gender and religion. This section presents a comparison of Scotland to other countries that the participants visited. The results show that their experiences in Scotland were mostly positive compared to other places such as France. The following section is dedicated to the conclusion of this chapter.

8.4. Conclusion:

This chapter tackled various forms of Islamophobia that participants shared with the researcher. Firstly, it discussed the interpersonal or everyday Islamophobic victimization that ranged from a direct form, which included verbal and physical abuse, such as Hijab pulling, sexual assault, and Racial slurs to some covert and micro-aggressive forms, for instance, receiving dirty stares, being ignored, excluded at social events, and monitored at shops.

Secondly, this chapter dealt with gendered Islamophobia at institutional and structural levels, in which the participants shared experiences of being rejected at job interviews or having a hard time finding jobs. Thirdly, despite the negative Islamophobic experiences, the participants also shared some positive aspects about living in Scotland by using comparisons to prove their points. After stating the findings, the discussion section is dedicated to discussing the findings by relating the research findings to previous research and theory. The following chapter represents the concluding chapter of this thesis. It briefly summarises the main findings chapters, provides some limitations that challenges the researcher, identify some implications and includes some recommendations for future studies in the same area of research.

9. Chapter Nine: General Conclusion

9.1. Introduction:

This study attempted to explore the experiences of female Muslims wearing the Hijab in three major Scottish cities, namely Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee. This chapter summarises the main research findings by referring to the key research questions, which are as follows:

1. What does wearing Hijab mean to Muslim women living in Scotland?
2. What are the motivations and purposes of wearing a Hijab in Scotland?
3. How do media representations, stereotypes of Muslim women, and global policies on Hijab affect the experiences of Hijabis in Scotland?
4. What are the main challenges faced by the wearers of Hijab in Scotland?

This study is divided into three main chapters where three main themes and sub-themes were explored. Firstly, it attempts to understand the meaning, motivations, and purposes of the Hijab from the participants' points of view. Secondly, it explores the relationship between the Hijab and feminism through using a feminist lens. Lastly, it has investigated the concept of Islamophobia and how it operates in their lives at various levels such as the interpersonal and institutional levels. This chapter is structured as follows. To begin with, it discusses the main findings and highlights key contributions. In addition, it deals with the implications of the research's findings and reviews the limitations of the study. Lastly, it suggests recommendations for future studies.

9.2. Summary of the Main Findings:

9.2.1. The Significance, Motivations, and Purposes of Wearing the Hijab

Using interpretive phenomenological analysis (Smith et al., 2009), feminist (Harding, 2004), and intersectional theory (Crenshaw, 1989) as methods of analysis, this chapter demonstrates a deeper and unique understanding of the experiences of Muslim women who practice the Hijab in this study. The findings reveal that the process of wearing the Hijab is typical and unique to each woman in the study, however, the participants shared some similarities. Several themes emerged from the analysis of twenty semi-structured interviews with twenty Muslim women from different racial and cultural backgrounds and from three major Scottish cities where Muslims are highly concentrated.

One of the main aims of the study is to explore the significance and the motivations that the participants attribute to the Hijab. The results indicate that participants viewed the Hijab as having both cultural and religious meanings. In addition, one surprising finding is that some participants related wearing the practice of the Hijab to some psychological reasons, for instance, body image, psychological well-being, marital status, and motherhood. The decision to wear the Hijab, in most cases, is related to cultural, geographical, and spatial aspects. The results reveal a difference between women who were raised and born in Muslim countries and those who spent most of their lifetime in Scotland or reverted to Islam. For instance, some participants started covering because they lived in countries with most Muslims, such as Algeria, Yemen, and Saudi Arabia, where the Hijab is common and worn by women around them when they reach a certain age, which is, to some of them, puberty. Thus, the Hijab was regarded as a part of their environment and culture. This finding aligns with Gill's

(2007) study which explains the practice of the Hijab in a Muslim-majority context is not a contested issue and, as a result, is not questioned, which makes it a natural and a normal element of the participants who grew up in a country with a majority of Muslims “Culture is precisely that what we experience to be natural”(Baerveldt, 2015, p. 536). Although the reasons seem more cultural and social than religious, the majority explained that their decision and process of wearing the Hijab has undergone various changes, that in some cases, developed from a cultural understanding to a religious one. Moreover, the participants explained that they were either supported or opposed by their families. There were multiple reasons for this. For instance, a few participants explained that their families resisted their idea of wearing the Hijab because it made them look older, it was an extreme type of the Hijab, or they were too young to wear it. On the other hand, some of them felt that initially Hijab was imposed on them because it was “Culturally expected” for them to wear it at the age of puberty as explained above.

The findings show that religious motives were also important in the choice of the Hijab. Some participants wore It primarily out of their complete understanding of its religious significance; They understood it from the beginning as a religious garment and chose to wear it themselves. Most of them were born and raised in Scotland, which made them “second-generation Muslims” (Hengameh, 2017, p 158). In addition to their religious motives, the Hijab functioned as a physical representation of their racial or ethnic identities, which is referred to by Visconti et al (2014) as a “Hyphenated identity” (Cited in Visconti et al,2012, p. 12). Having discussed the findings concerning the participants’ meanings and purposes of wearing the Hijab, the following section deals with important findings regarding the participants' understanding of the Hijab from a feminist lens with a focus on dominants’ discourses discussions on the Hijab and the veiled Muslim woman.

9.2.2. Hijab, Gender relations, and Media’s Portrayal

The second aim of the study deals with the participants’ views on the image of the Muslim veiled woman created by dominant discourses, such as Western feminist and orientalist perceptions of Hijabi Muslim women, and how they resist and redefine themselves. In addition to their perspectives on the portrayal of the image of the veiled Muslim woman in the Western media. It highlights the necessity of starting the inquiry from the lived experiences of those who have been left outside the institution, in which knowledge is produced (Harding,1989), who are Muslim women wearing the Hijab, in this case. The findings show that most of the interviewees related wearing the Hijab to female empowerment and feminist identity, which contradicts the stereotyped Hijabi Muslim women as being oppressed and controlled by men. Furthermore, the participants’ approaches to understanding equality between men and women varied and contradicted some Western feminists’ concept of feminism, which regards religion as incompatible with feminism (Hassan, 2018). Some believed in equality between men and women, while others offered a different explanation of equality based on Islamic understanding. The latter explained that men and women are not equal in the sense that they are different, and they serve different responsibilities. However, most of them did not directly identify with feminist identity, only one participant referred to herself as a feminist.

This study also explores the participants’ perception of Western media with a specific focus on the Scottish media. As some of the previous studies have shown (Garcia, 2020.,

Kasirye,2011., Abdi,2023., MCB,2021) the portrayal of Muslim women and the Hijab in the United Kingdom is mostly negative. The participants in the study believed that the portrayal of Muslim women in Western media is still mostly negative and needs a lot of work to appropriately portray Islam and Muslim people. However, few participants expressed that the media nowadays is either neutral or improving compared to some periods when hostility towards Muslims was at its extreme due to geopolitical events such as 9/11. Some views were mostly positive regarding the Scottish media's representation of Muslims. However, past research (Munnick,2017) concerning the Scottish representation of Muslims has revealed that the hostility that is usually found in the British press is muted in the Scottish media. In other words, Scottish journalists avoid talking about Muslims because they do not want to involve them in bad news. This approach is referred to as "Benign neglect or approach" (Munnick,2017, p. 219). The following section presents important findings concerning the challenges faced by the wearers of the Hijab in Scotland.

9.2.3. Gendered Islamophobic Challenges in Scotland

This study is dedicated to investigating the lived experiences of gendered Islamophobia (Zine,2006) in the Scottish context. It shows that most of the participants faced a certain type of discrimination because of wearing the Hijab, however, the physical manifestation of their religion was not the only issue. The intersection of some identities, such as gender, race, ableism, and sexuality also contributed to their negative experiences. Consequently, using Crenshaw's concept of intersectionality (1989) has provided a useful lens through which the participants' experiences were approached. Furthermore, different types of Islamophobias were mentioned, which differed in the level of directness and intensity. Verbal and Physical Islamophobia were the most direct types of gendered Islamophobia, such as sexual, racial, and sexist slurs, physical attacks, and Hijab pulling, and they took place mainly in public places.

On the other hand, more covert forms were also tackled, for example, receiving micro-aggression behaviours, such as changes in facial expressions, eye-rolling, and dirty stares. Some participants expressed feelings of shame, anger, and deteriorating mental health issues due to some of these behaviours. This finding affiliates with some studies that tackled micro-aggression behaviours and their negative influence on mental health (Nadal et al,2011; Forquer and Rivera,2010; Sue et al,2007). In addition to the previous types of Islamophobias, institutional Islamophobia (Alimahomed-Wilson,2020) negatively affected some of the participants' lived experiences. Most of them reported some examples such as having difficulty finding a job and being overtly checked at the airport. Despite the negative Islamophobic experiences, the participants also shared some positive aspects about living in Scotland by using comparisons to prove their points. The comparison was based on comparing their experiences in Scotland to other places they visited or lived in such as France and England. Furthermore, a comparison was also made between Scottish cities such as Glasgow and Edinburgh. Overall, their experiences in Scotland were reported to be better than in other places such as England. Locally, some participants believed Glasgow is worse than Edinburgh when it comes to Islamophobia. After mentioning the main findings of this study, the next section states the key contributions of this study by locating it in the broader scope of existing literature.

9.3. Key contributions to Knowledge:

The most important and unique contribution to knowledge in this body of work is the use of Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a method of data analysis along with feminist and intersectional theories. This allowed for a deep and close insight into the subjective lived experiences of female Muslim women who wear the Hijab in contemporary Scotland. The reason for utilizing IPA stems from its ideographic nature, which helped in understating how each participant made sense of the practice of the Hijab in the Scottish context. In addition, IPA focused on the shared experiences of the participants by targeting a homogenous sample that has some characteristics in common. For the purposes of the current study, the participants were females, Muslims, wearing the Hijab, and living in Scotland for a period of at least of two years. Moreover, based on hermeneutics, IPA offered a new and useful approach to examining the experiences of the participants because of its focus on double hermeneutics, which suggested that the researcher attempts to make sense of how the participants make sense of their own lived experience (Montague et al., 2020). As a result, the analysis of the data required extensive reading and re-reading of the transcripts to make sense of the participants' experiences. To understand the participants' perspectives from gender-specific and intersectional perspectives, some feminist and intersectional theories were employed. For instance, the use of Feminist Standpoint Theory suggests that although dominant and powerful discourses attempt to define women “on the margin of society” (Droogsma, 2007, p.294), women’s cultural positions offer them a heightened awareness of the contradiction between their experiences and the way dominant discourse attempts to define them. Therefore, this theory allowed for the emergence of alternative definitions of the Hijab from the standpoints of Muslim women instead of relying on dominant discourses. Using feminist theory is also supported by intersectional theories. Both the theories of intersectionality (Crenshaw,1989) and the matrix of gendered Islamophobia (Alimohamed-Wilson,2020) examine how different social identities intersect to create either a system of privilege or oppression in the lived experiences of veiled Muslim women in the Scottish context. This study allowed for the rise of unique empirical data, which is summarised in the following sections.

9.3.1. Understanding the Meanings and the Purposes of The Hijab:

This study contributed to the understanding of how Muslim women’s experiences of the Hijab varied from one another. In other words, while dominant discourses present Muslim women as a homogenous group (Koopmanschap ,2010, p. 1), the current study argued that their experiences and decisions to wear the Hijab were shaped and re-shaped through time and location (spatial context). For example, while some participants wore the Hijab as a cultural garment that was shaped lately into a religious one, others decided to wear the Hijab for religious reasons. The decision to wear the Hijab, in most cases, was shaped by the context from which everyone came, for instance, those who came from predominantly Muslim countries wore the Hijab without a prior understanding of its religious motives, while most of the participants who lived most of their lives in Scotland wore it out of religious understanding. Another important empirical contribution was understanding the Hijab as a medium for Muslim women’s well-being. Some participants related the Hijab to some significant and emotional events in their lives, such as losing a family member to cancer and becoming a mother. Moreover, different opinions were shared regarding the concept of modesty, attractiveness, fashion, and body image. Most participants expressed the importance of the Hijab in maintaining their modesty. They also discussed some points regarding the

Hijab and their body images, some participants believed that the Hijab protected their body images, and others felt less attractive with the Hijab.

9.3.2. Understanding Gender Issues in Relation to the Hijab:

This research contributed to the understanding of the Hijab in Scotland from a gendered perspective. The findings demonstrated an understanding of how Muslim women viewed the Hijab from a feminist lens. It discussed different ideas like female empowerment, gender equality, media stereotyping, and portrayals. Unlike dominant ideas of the Hijab as a symbol of oppression (Amiriaux,2007; Mitchel,2019; Bullock,2010), most women in the study identified themselves as strong, confident, and powerful while wearing the Hijab. Moreover, the results indicated that Muslim women possessed varied and contradictory understandings of what a feminist identity and gender equality are. This chapter also added to the existing literature by discussing the perspectives of participants on how they are portrayed as Hijabi women by the Western media with a specific focus on the British media.

9.3.3. Exploring the Different Challenges and the Impacts of Islamophobia on Muslim Women in Scotland:

Finally, this study contributed to the literature on the experiences of Muslim women in Britain by examining the phenomenon of gendered Islamophobia in Scotland. The theory of intersectionality (Crenshaw,1989) provided a useful lens through which the participant's experiences were approached. As previously explained, while Muslim women are viewed as a homogenous group, this research argued for the importance of recognizing differences among them, which lied in the intersection of other identities with their gender identity, including religion, race, ableism, and language. Moreover, Muslim women in this study identified various types of Islamophobias. It is important to mention that the intensity of Islamophobia varied from more covert⁵⁵ forms of islamophobia to more direct forms. Examples of these types were discussed in the third chapter which include verbal and physical attacks such as insulting and Hijab pulling, micro-aggressions like unpleasant facial expressions, and institutional Islamophobia, for example, having difficulty finding a job and feeling excluded from social interactions and events. Additionally, Muslim women compared their experiences in Scotland to England and other places they visited such as France, Moreover, it showed that the experiences differ even at the local level, for example, the difference between Islamophobia in Edinburgh and Glasgow.

To sum up, this thesis sought to add to the existing knowledge of the practice of the Hijab in the Scottish context. There is significant literature about Muslim women in Scotland. Hengameh 2017), for instance, has explored the intergenerational relations between Muslim women in Scotland by studying the differences, similarities, and transformations between Muslim generations. Syswerda (2017) also studies Muslim women in Scotland by examining the role of "Other" women in shaping the subjectivities of recent migrant Muslim women. however, few focus on the practice of the Hijab (Siraj,2011; Hopkins and Greenwood,2013). Unlike previous research on the Hijab, this study focused mainly on Muslim women who practice the Hijab in Scotland. Thus, this study is important in the current context, essentially because the number of Muslims in Scotland is set to double according to academics in this decade (El Shayal, 2016; Donnelly, 2017), which requires understanding the needs and the challenges of veiled Muslim women, especially due to the rise of Islamophobia in Scotland (Barrie, 2021; Hopkins, 2023). The study also acknowledged the importance of gender and

other intersectional identities in defining the experiences of Islamophobia. Although his study contributed to the existing literature on the Hijab in Scotland, like any other study, it has some limitations.

9.4. Limitations of this Research:

Despite the extensive accounts provided by the participants through using interpretive phenomenological analysis, which involves using in-depth semi-structured interviews and has a particular focus on the individualistic and ideographical experiences of the participants (Moses and Knusten, 2012), and how they make sense of a certain phenomenon within the context of personal and social worlds (Smith and Nizza, 2022) there are various limitations to this PhD study. The analysis of a large amount of data was a time-consuming process and this is due to the hermeneutic nature of IPA, which involves the researcher making sense of and interpreting the participant's accounts (Voicedocs, no date).

In addition, one limitation relates to the sample size. As explained in the methodology chapter, the sample size was chosen based on certain criteria due to the use of purposive sampling (Smith et al., 2009). Consequently, women in this study were Muslim women who wore the Hijab for a considerable time in Scotland, this allowed to give a deep insight into the practice of wearing the Hijab from individualistic perspectives. However, the sample size was not enough to represent all the Muslim women who practice the Hijab in Scotland because it covered three cities, Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee. The choice was based on the density of the Muslim population in these cities (El Shayal, 2016, p. 8) to allow access to more participants. Furthermore, although the initial plan was to seek a sample balance between the three cities, most participants who agreed to participate were from Glasgow and Edinburgh, and only three participants were from Dundee. This limitation can be related to the existence of the highest population of Muslims in Glasgow and Edinburgh.

As mentioned above, the sample size cannot be generalized to the entire population of Muslim women living in Scotland because it centred around a specific age group, which was 18 years old to 56 years old. This study has contributed somehow to understanding how this specific age range in Scotland gave meaning to the Hijab, nevertheless concentrating on the underaged Muslim population and children who wear the Hijab would contribute to a more diverse and rich understanding of the practice of the Hijab in Scotland. In addition, this research intended initially to involve the voices of Muslim women who stopped wearing the Hijab. All the participants were wearing the hijab at the time when the interviews were conducted, yet some of them stopped wearing the Hijab or altered the way they Hijab at some point in their lives. Lastly, because this research involved the use of purposive sampling, as part of interpretive phenomenological analysis, it could not involve other voices, such as non-practising Muslims. To capture Muslim women's and girls' diverse experiences, it would have been more fruitful to involve the experiences of non-practicing (liberal/secular) Muslim women because nearly all the participants were faith-oriented and practicing Muslim women. Furthermore, most of the interviews showed a positive perspective on the Hijab, as explained above, this research was based on the individualistic experiences of the participants, it does not generalize because some Muslim women may have some negative views on the practice of wearing the Hijab.

The pandemic, COVID- 19, posed a challenge for collecting the data through using in-person interviews. As a result, most of the interviews were conducted online via Zoom application.

Most of the participants preferred to turn off their cameras, however, their expressions and emotions were mostly understood through their voice tone. Only three interviews were conducted face to face ensuring the participants' and the researcher's safety. To achieve that, the participants were asked if they had COVID-19 before conducting the interview, and masks were worn during the interviews for safety purposes. Consequently, the second limitation of this study was the lack of face-to-face interaction and proximity between the researcher and the participants. In addition, it impeded the ability of the researcher to pick on non-verbal cues, facial expressions, and emotions such as signs of distress. However, these emotions were detected through listening and re-listening to the tone of the participants. Moreover, online interviews present several challenges concerning privacy and confidentiality (Varma et al., 2021), therefore, it was challenging and important for the researcher to protect the participants' privacy.

Given the nature of the chosen sample, this PhD research has been restricted to investigating the individualistic and subjective perspectives of Muslim women. Consequently, Muslim men's voices have been left out. Using the feminist theory has provided an insightful lens through which the participants' women's lived experiences were analysed. This lens is restrictive because it only examines the phenomenon of the Hijab from the viewpoints of women. Consequently, examining the issue of the Hijab from a male perspective will generate more knowledge about this phenomenon. After discussing the limitations of the study, the next section provides implications for the current findings.

9.5. The Implications of the Findings:

These results are important because they demonstrate the multi-faceted nature of the reasons behind wearing the Hijab in Scotland. The first chapter's findings suggest the need to view Muslim women who wear the Hijab from an individualistic and heterogeneous perspective because the reasons how they come to wear the Hijab are unique and different. Wearing the Hijab is seen by most of them as a complex and lengthy process that develops over time and involves different changes. As a result, this could help to raise awareness about Muslim women's choices to cover and how they feel when wearing the Hijab.

Furthermore, most of the participants expressed the importance of modesty in their lives. Understanding the needs of Muslim women is crucial. Some participants shared the challenges they faced when living in the accommodation, for instance, and being exposed to the other gender without their Hijabs. Therefore, different sectors, such as the educational sector, need to take into consideration the gender aspect when dealing with veiled Muslim women. Hospitals and clinics also need to consider Muslim women's religious and spiritual beliefs. One suggestion is striving to employ female care providers and physicians who can deal with Muslim women who prefer not to be exposed to males. Moreover, some patients and physically disabled Muslim women might not be able to bathe or do wudhu⁵³ (ablution) and require the care of female care providers. As a result, this study proposes issuing and developing a guide on how to deal with veiled Muslim women patients which includes instructions on how to help a Muslim disabled woman doing ablution.

The second chapter offers vivid and rich accounts of how Muslim women view and navigate gender equality and feminism concerning their Islamic beliefs, ideologies, and practices. This finding is important because it highlights the need for Western feminism to be more inclusive and accepting of the choices of Muslim women regarding their Hijab. The findings show that

Muslim women's understanding of the concept of equality is unique and different from one another. Some of the participants adopted the Western notion of equality and argued that men and women are equal. Others explained it from an Islamic point of view, which suggests that men and women are equal, but they serve different gender roles. As a result, gender relations should be understood from their perspectives.

Another research implication calls for more accurate and positive representations of Muslim women in the British media and media in General. One suggestion to achieve this is through the inclusion of Muslim voices in the Scottish media with specific consideration of gender and other intersectional elements. Furthermore, based on some of the participants' suggestions, organizations, for instance, need to organize and conduct campaigns to raise awareness of the practice of the Hijab and why some women choose to wear it.

The third chapter's findings provide insights into the challenges that face Muslim women in Scotland. These findings can be used by policymakers and criminal justice practitioners to tackle, understand, and respond to the needs of veiled women as potential victims of Islamophobia. The first implication of this chapter suggests the need for re-considering the approach 'one size fits all', which may not afford an effective tool for tackling the intersectionality of the potential victims of gendered Islamophobia. Muslim women who practice the veil may be more vulnerable in certain places. In other words, gender is an important aspect to observe by service providers, because un(veiled) Muslim women may experience Islamophobia differently. Additionally, it is advisable and useful for service providers to deliver services that are informed by faith and cultural sensitivity. For instance, recent immigrants, who wear the Hijab and do not understand the language, might be an easier target of discrimination. Consequently, providing training and language services would be useful for their inclusion and integrity in Scottish society. Another crucial implication is considering the challenges that are faced by veiled Muslim women with physical disability. One participant, with physical disability, expressed how she was a target of hate crimes and had her wheelchair blocked by people because of her visible religious identity. As a result, it is important to provide services that consider the intersection of gendered Islamophobia and physical disability when dealing with Islamophobic incidents.

Considering the influence of institutional Islamophobia on Muslim women, it is crucial to examine the challenges and the issues that face women in the Scottish labour market. Some participants mentioned having a tough time finding a job because of their Muslim visible identity. In fact, The Cross-Party Group (2020) for Tackling Islamophobia's recent inquiry was that "36.6%" of Muslim respondents reported being abused at work (cited in MEND, 2021, p.31). However, gender plays a vital role in Muslim women facing issues in the labour market. MEND (2021, p.32) refers to this as the "Triple penalty", which means facing more discrimination due to the intersection of gender, ethnicity, and religion. Therefore, the research implication of this finding is calling for further investigation and support of Muslim women who face rejection and discrimination at work due to their identity performance.

Furthermore, some participants reported some distressed incidents where they felt isolated and alone when reporting hate crime incidents. This research implication proposes that police officers, justice criminal systems, and support systems raise awareness and refer victims of Islamophobia to support organizations for continued and additional support. Many victims might choose to stay silent because they are not aware of how they get support.

Consequently, it is crucial to raise awareness of reporting hate crimes by relevant organizations and authorities. Additionally, many Islamophobic victims might feel threatened by being battered by the abuser after reporting a hate crime. Thus, it is important to ensure they are safe after reporting a certain incident.

Several organizations in Scotland provide support to Muslim women in relation to tackling violence, employability, adult learning, and creative well-being, such as *AMINA*⁵⁴, the Muslim Women's Resource Centre. Providing these organizations with adequate support, such as donating goods, vouchers, and services, and raising awareness about these organizations, will help in providing and understanding Muslim women's needs, especially women with no recourse to public funds. At last, geopolitical events can have a major influence on the lived experiences of veiled Muslim women (Hopkins,2016, no page). As mentioned previously, many participants experienced Islamophobic incidents because of events such as 9/11. In the current context, some studies and reports show that there is a rise in Islamophobic incidents due to geopolitical events such as the Palestinian conflict (Rimi,2023; Shankar,2023; Reuters,2023). Therefore, providing adequate and effective support to veiled Muslim women is vital. Having discussed the implications of the findings, the coming section suggests recommendations for further research on the area of Muslim women and the practice of the Hijab in Scotland.

9.6. Recommendation for Future Research:

Following the implications and the limitations of this PhD study, it is vital to suggest future recommendations that may help in investigating the phenomena of the Hijab in the Scottish context further. The findings of this study propose several avenues for further study. Using the qualitative approach to investigate the practice of the Hijab in the Scottish context has offered some rich and fruitful data. Three important chapters have investigated the Hijab from individualistic and extensive accounts. However, using a quantitative method like a survey can allow a large sample of the lived experiences of women who wear the Hijab in Scotland. One suggestion is to use questionnaires to investigate the diverse types of Islamophobic experiences from the perspectives of those who wear the Hijab. This method, for instance, will be more inclusive and could generate objective and new knowledge.

Another recommendation is based on one of the findings, which concerns the intersectionality of different identities with the Muslim identity. This is an important aspect through which phenomenological research can start. As explained above, Muslim women are not homogenous and their experiences are different, so investigating the practice of wearing the Hijab from a certain perspective would be interesting. For example, the intersection of disability and Muslim identity would be an interesting study, in which the voices of disabled Muslim women can be heard. In addition, as mentioned in the findings and discussion chapters, cultural differences, language, skin complexion, accent, and gender can all contribute to either having the privilege or being discriminated against. As a result, starting research by considering one of these aspects may help in a deeper understanding of disabled Muslim women's lived experiences.

Taking gender as an example, Muslim women and men may experience Islamophobia differently in the Scottish context, so investigating this matter is crucial for future research. As an example, conducting a phenomenological study into the experiences of Muslim men who wear religious clothing and analysing it by using interpretive phenomenological analysis

could allow some new perspectives to arise. Moreover, Scotland is a multicultural country, and Muslims are from various cultural and ethnic backgrounds. As a result, investigating the practice of the lived experiences of Muslim women who wear the Hijab from cultural-specific perspectives could be an important extension of this research because women in this study were from diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds. Furthermore, some non-Muslim women who practice veiling such as Sikh, Christian, Amish, and Jewish women can be a target of Islamophobia due to them being mistaken for Muslim women. Consequently, it is useful to examine their experiences. Some studies, such as (Hopkins et al.,2017), have shown that non-religious groups can be mistaken for Muslims, thus they might experience Islamophobia as mentioned in the third chapter.

This phenomenological research study has highlighted a perspective of the meanings, structures, and essence of the lived experiences of Muslim women in three different Scottish cities. This one limited qualitative study cannot explain all phenomena, A more fully realistic view of these lived experiences needs a more expanded effort for examination, exploration, and understanding. Thus, including other views is important. For instance, investigating the Hijab phenomenon in Scotland from the age perspective is necessary as children who wear the Hijab and teenagers may generate new knowledge for future policies. Moreover, research is also needed to tackle the lived experiences of non-Muslim women and men who are mistaken for being Muslims, and as a result, might have experienced Islamophobic attacks.

9.7. Conclusion:

This PhD thesis explored the experiences of Muslim women wearing the Hijab in three major Scottish cities, namely Glasgow, Edinburgh, and Dundee. This chapter summarised the main research findings by referring to the key research questions and aims and stated the contribution of this study to the existing literature on the Hijab in Scotland. This study was divided into three main chapters where three main themes and sub-themes were explored thoroughly. Firstly, it attempted to understand the meaning, motivations, and purposes of the Hijab from the participants' points of view. Secondly, it explored the relationship between the Hijab and feminism through using a feminist lens. Lastly, it investigated the concept of Islamophobia and how it operated in their lives at various levels such as the interpersonal and institutional levels through using intersectional theory. After discussing the findings, this chapter stated the implications of the research's findings, reviewed the limitations of the study, and proposed recommendations for future research on the Muslim population in Scotland.

10.Endnotes:

1-The original sin: The original sin means the innate corruption of mankind that, in Christianity, is linked to the sin of Adam and Eve in the Garden of Eden. The original sin is thought to be transferred from Adam and Eve to the following generation of humans (Pike,1951). However, this argument is countered by the idea that the sin cannot be transferable, which means if one's ancestors committed some "punishable, blameworthy wrong, it does not follow that their children should be punished" (Taliaferro, and Marty,2012, p.168).

2-According to (El Shinawy, 2021, no page), Haya (Modesty) serves different meanings including "conscientiousness, shame, modesty, bashfulness" and all similar feelings that prevent someone from behaving indecently.

3-The Hijab: "(Arab) any partition which separates two things (e.g. that which separates God from creation), but usually the veil worn by Muslim women. The Quran commands modesty in dress ("They should not display their adornment, except that which is apparent of it",24,31)", however, the level of how much must be covered is not explicitly stated in the Quran (Bowker, 1997, p.428).

4- "The concept of Awrah in Islam holds significant importance as it delineates the parts of the body that should be covered in front of others. Awrah goes beyond mere physical appearance; it embodies a profound spiritual and cultural significance in the Islamic way of life" (Islamversity, 2023, no page).

5- "A madhab represents the entire school of thought of a particular Mujtahid (a Muslim theologian and legal expert who in the Middle Ages possessed the ijihad – the right of independent interpretation of religious and legal matters) Imam as its foundation and centuries of studies and research has been built upon it" (Wahid, 2023, no page).

7-Re-Islamization or Islamic Revivalism: seeks to expand the operation of Shari'ah (Islamic law) to the main areas of social economic, cultural, and political activity. Contemporary Islamic revivalists attempt to revive doctrines, dogmas, and practices from the Pristine Islamic era and modify them in consideration of pragmatism. The revival of these elements serves as a as protection for ordinary Muslims from falling into the abyss and the threats of modernity (Ali,2023).

8-Prevent: "Prevent is a part of the national counter-terrorism strategy, CONTEST. Prevent helps to protect society from terrorism by supporting people who are at risk of radicalization and offering them appropriate interventions". (Royal Greenwich, no year available).

9-Muslimness: designates any visible marker of Muslim identity; it identifies the different targets of Islamophobia that are related to Muslim identity, be it visible Muslims or Muslims identifiable due to Muslim identity markers, such as their clothes, names, or actions (Bhatti,2021).

10-Hijabo-phobia: "The fear of veiled women, a gender-specific form of Islamophobia" ([Al Rumaithi,2019](#), no page)

11-Note this data will hopefully be updated to Census 2022 (Scotland) data in time for the submission of the PhD thesis in 2023.

12-“Devolution puts power closer to the citizen so local factors are better recognised in decision-making. Thanks to devolution, Scotland has two governments which are responsible for different areas. Devolution has not stood still – there have been major additions of new powers for the [Scottish Parliament](#) since 1999. This has included the Scottish Parliament becoming more accountable for the revenue it raises to spend on providing public services” (Delivering for Scotland: NP) See: <https://www.deliveringforscotland.gov.uk/scotland-in-the-uk/devolution/#:~:text=In%20September%201997%2C%20there%20was,powers%20previously%20held%20at%20Westminster>.

13- Harlots: “a person who has sex with someone in exchange for money: prostitute” (Meriem Webster Dictionary,2024, no page).

14- Hierodule: “a slave living in a temple and dedicated to the service of a god” (Meriem, Webster Dictionnary,2024, no page).

15-“Eunuch, castrated human male. From remote antiquity, eunuchs were employed in the Middle Est and in China in two main functions: as guards and servants in harems or other women’s quarters, and as chamberlains to kings” (Britannica,2024,no page).

16-Mahram: “a person with whom marriage is prohibited because of their close blood relationship, because of radaa'ah (breastfeeding), or because of being related by marriage” (GIWPS,2022, p.1).

17-Hadith , “corpus of the sayings or traditions of the Prophet [Muhammad](#), revered by Muslims as a major source of religious law and [moral](#) guidance” (Sayeed,2024, no page).

18- War on Terror: “a term used to describe the American-led global counterterrorism campaign launched in response to the [terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001](#)” (Jackson,2024,no page).

19- TellMAMA UK: is a national project which measures and records anti-Muslim incidents in the United Kingdom (TellMAMA,2024).

20-“Data from 2022 Scottish census shows secularism increased sharply over decade, from 36.7% of population to 51%” (Carrell,2024, no page).

21-Chaves (1994) describes the process of secularisation as the declining scope of religious authority. Another definition is provided by Cosanova(2015) who believes that secularism is the transformation of people, things, or meanings from ecclesiastical or religious to civil or lay use.

22- Harriet Jacobs “was an abolitionist, but she was better known as an African American writer. She wrote her autobiography entitled *Incidents in the Life of a Slave Girl* under the pseudonym Linda Brent. She also composed letters to the New York Tribunal and contributed to Family Papers, and became a relief worker to help runaway slave” (Harkin,2021, no page)

23- Bell Hooks: “Black feminist author and social activist bell hooks has inspired many generations of academics and non-academics alike, due not only to her commitment of creating and producing pedagogy rooted in anti-racist and anti-patriarchal practices” (Herrington,2022,p.2).

24- According to Rogers (2010), the concept of the *Outsider Within* signifies how gender and race commonly shape and define insiders and outsiders in organizations controlled by white males.

25-Jilbab is “a long piece of clothing worn by some Muslim women. It is worn over other clothes and covers the whole body, sometimes including the head” (Cambridge Online Dictionary,2024., no page).

26-Jubbah/ Dishdasha: is a long, loose-fitting traditional robe with long sleeves and a high collar that is typically worn with a head covering.

27-A revert: “Muslims use the word “revert” to refer to someone who has embraced Islam”. (DanniDubai,2023, no page).

28-Appadurai (1996) explains that Hyphenated identity refers to the ethnic identity position of diasporic people (i.e.) migrants who simultaneously identify with the culture of putative ethnic culture (delocalized ethnicity) by ancestry and with the new host culture (cited in Visconti et al, 2014)

29-PAS: Dion et al (1972) explain that PAS means that people are more likely to designate positive qualities to more physically attractive people and negative traits to less attractive people.

30-Sheen et al (2022,p.12) refer to the idea of perceiving someone as attractive because of cultural belonging as Cultural Attractiveness Stereotype.

31-Awrah is an Arabic term that refers to the parts of the body that require covering in public and in the presence of others. In Islamic traditions, certain body parts are viewed as private and should not be exposed to others except in certain situations (Suhail,2022).

32-“The hijab often fosters a sense of belonging to a larger community. Muslim women who wear the hijab may find support, friendship, and a sense of sisterhood among others who share their faith and experiences. This community can be a source of strength and unity” (Angela, 2023., no page).

33-“Derived from the word haraam, which literally means something that is prohibited, mahram in fiqh (Islamic jurisprudence) refers to a person with whom marriage is prohibited because of their close blood relationship, because of radaa’ah (breastfeeding), or because of being related by marriage” (Geotown Institute for Women Peace and Security, no year available, no page). Mahram is also defined in relation to the Hijab and kinship. According to Afshar (2016), there is a difference between Mahram (close male relative with whom less covering is required) and nan-Mahram (distant male relative with whom full covering is required).

34-Gender equity: “The concept recognises that women and men have different needs and power and that these differences should be identified and addressed in a manner that rectifies the imbalances between the sexes. This may include equal treatment, or treatment that is different but considered equivalent in terms of rights, benefits, obligations and opportunities” (European Institute for Gender Equality, no year available, no page).

35-As per Musawah (2017), the egalitarian approach challenges the protectionist approach to gender equality in Islam. While admitting the biological difference of men and women, this

approach argues that equality is required and possible even if both genders are biologically different. Advocates of this approach argues that for equality of women in all fronts and insisting that law and practice reflect the egalitarian values of Islam.

36-Taqwa is an [Islamic](#) term for being conscious and cognizant of God, of truth, of the rational reality, “piety, fear of God” (Slife,2010, no page).

37-The Other: “Opposing Us, the Self, and Them, the Other, is to choose criterion that allows humanity to be divided into two groups: one that embodies the norms and whose identity is valued and another that is defined by its faults, devalued and susceptible to discrimination” (Stazack,2008, p.1).

38-“The Hazaras are a distinct ethno-religious group living in Afghanistan, Iran and Pakistan who have been systematically oppressed, persecuted and subject to ethnic cleansing campaigns since the 1800s” (The Hazara Research Collective, 2020 ,p.4).

39-“When it comes to “Elite,” we see another girl named Nadia. This intelligent scholarship student wears a hijab in the first season of the series, and then the second season shows her removing her hijab and walking into a bar with a very sexy look. The problem here is not whether she wears a hijab or not (as this is completely a woman’s personal decision) but the series clearly implies that Nadia became free only after removing her hijab” (YAŞAR, 2021, no page)

40-According to Cambridge online dictionary (2024), a SOAPS/ Soap Opera is a series of TV or radio programs about the lives and the problems of group of characters; it continues over a long period of time and is broadcasted several times on weekly basis.

41-A dialectic is a relationship between two opposing concepts that constantly push and pull one another (Martin and Nakayama, 2010).

42-Jilbab is a form of Islamic covering. Unlike the Hijab, the Jilbab offers more coverage “Here’s the difference between hijab and jilbab. Conforming with the strictures stated in Islam, the jilbab is a loose and long outer modest clothing. The clothing is recognized as a religious dress with a mention in the Noble Quran. Unlike hijabs, it covers the entire body from the neck down - leaving only the hands and feet open” (Urban Culture, 2022, no page).

43-Misgendering: According to Hodshire (2023, no page) “Misgendering occurs when you intentionally or unintentionally refer to a person, relate to a person, or use language to describe a person that doesn’t align with their affirmed gender. For example, referring to a woman as “he” or calling her a “guy” is an act of misgendering”.

44-According to the WION Web Team (2022, no page) “Essentially, the niqab is a veil that covers the face, but leaves the eye area uncovered. An eye veil may accompany it. Usually, it is worn with a headscarf. It is often worn by Muslim women as part of the hijab”.

45-The bystander effect occurs when the presence of others discourages an individual from intervening in an emergency situation, against a [bully](#), or during an assault or other [crime](#). The greater the number of bystanders, the less likely it is for any one of them to provide help to a person in distress. People are more likely to take action in a crisis when there are few or no other witnesses present.

46-Cultural racism: dates to the Enlightenment period, cultural racism signifies the combination of racist policies and ideas that enhance racial discrimination. In other words, it is the belief that one culture is superior to the culture of other racialized groups (Shah,2020).

47-Developed by Pierre Bourdieu, the term habitus means the norms, values, attitudes and behaviour of a particular social group or social class (Totur4u, no year available).

48-English Defence League: Formed in 2009, EDL is a far-right Islamophobic organization. Its focus is on the Islamification of Britain. It uses street demonstrations as its main tactics, which have often turned into violence. (Rogers,2020).

49-According to Hopkins (2021,p.15) Muslim women are significantly more likely to experience physical assault than men with “11 %”.

50-Muslim Engagement and Development: “is a not-for-profit company that helps to empower and encourage British Muslims within local communities to be more actively involved in British media and politics” (MEND, no year available, no page).

51-According to Nomina (2023,np), “Misgendering occurs when someone is addressed or referred to using pronouns or gender identities that do not align with their self-identified gender. It can happen deliberately or unintentionally, but the consequences for the person being misgendered remain significant.

52-“Launched in 2003, the Prevent strategy has evolved against the background of increased public fears over the threat of “homegrown” terrorism. The strategy in its current form aims “to stop people becoming terrorists or supporting terrorism” (Singh,2016,p.15).

53-“Wudu is the Muslim procedure for cleaning certain parts of the body in preparation for important acts of worship including prayer, touching the Quran during recitation, performing rites of pilgrimage” (Ibn Ismail,2020,no page).

54-Amina – “The Muslim Women's Resource Centre (Amina MWRC) is an intersectional organisation, based in Scotland, which empowers and supports Muslim and BME women by serving as a vital link between them and the barriers they face every day” (Amina-MWRC, no year available, no page).

55- The term covert is used to designate the different manipulative ways used against Muslim women that is related to wearing the Hijab. They might not openly acknowledge or displayed, but they have a profound influence on the victims.

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12.Appendices:

12.1. Appendix One: Consent Form

School of Education

Paisley Campus

Consent form

Title of the research project: *The Experiences of Muslims wearing Hijab in Scotland*

Name of the researcher: FEZZIOUI AMINA

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - a- Participate in an interview (approx. 60-90 mins).
 - b- Be audio-recorded during the interview.

- 4- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

- 5- I consent to being a participant in the project

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Name of the Researcher: FEZZIOUI AMINA

Date: _____ Signature: _____

12. 2 Appendix Two: Participants Information Sheet

School of Education

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study: The experiences of Muslims wearing Hijab in Scotland

Introduction

This research project is run by *FEZZIOUI AMINA*, PhD student in the school of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research study is aimed at exploring the experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland. It investigates the significances, the motivations and the purposes of wearing Hijab. In addition, it explores the challenges and the effects of wearing Hijab on their daily lives, for instance, if they have ever experienced discrimination or Islamophobia that are directly related to their Hijab. It also questions the role of media representations and global events in affecting their lives as Hijabis or Hijabers.

Do you have to take a part?

Taking part in this research project is completely voluntary and those who choose to be involved will have the right to withdraw at any point of time during the data collection without penalty of any form.

What will you do in this research project?

You will be asked to take part in a semi-structured interview for 60-90 minutes maximum, which is about the significances, the motivations, the effects and the challenges of wearing Hijab in Scotland.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part because you are a Muslim woman between the age 18-56-year-old that is wearing Hijab in Scotland.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project. Yet, there are some questions that may be upset to you due to traumatic experiences in the past. In this case, you are allowed either not to answer the question or to withdraw from the interview. The questions will be provided to you beforehand.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

Data provided by participants will be entirely confidential and all activities will be undertaken anonymously. Completed data will be securely stored within my university computer that is protected by a password.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What will happen next?

If you are happy to be involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. The project is extremely grateful for your involvement. Thanks are also expressed to those who have taken the time to read this information sheet but who now choose not to take part.

Once the project is complete, you will be given a short written report of its findings, with the option of further verbal communication.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

Lead supervisor details:
Professor Colin Clark
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
Room: 1.109

Researcher contact details:
Amina Fezzioui
School of Education and Social Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus, Scotland, UK

Personal details withheld.

12.3. Ethics Approval Letter:

17/09/2021

Dear Amina Fezzioui,

Your application 16727: The Experiences of Muslims wearing Hijab in Scotland , submission 14028, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. The following comments from the reviewers are intended to improve the study.

Title	Comment
Re. the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	The potential for researcher bias has not been indicated, there appear to be many a priori assumptions embedded in the RQ's. Discuss this with your supervisor, and consider in addition to IPA as a mode of data analysis, completing a narrative diary of researcher thoughts and opinions before during and after the interview encounters.
Re. summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	The potential for researcher bias has not been indicated, there appears to be a priori assumptions embedded in the RQ's. Discuss this with your supervisor, and consider in addition to IPA as a mode of data analysis, completing a narrative inquiry diary of researcher thoughts and opinions before during and after the interview encounters.
What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?	90 minutes duration. This seems like a long time for an interview that explores simple research questions. What is the justification for the amount of time required for interview?

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

12.4. Appendix Three: Interview Questions

1. When did you first begin to cover and wear Hijab?
2. Were you forced to wear Hijab?
3. What does Hijab signify to you? In addition, has this significance changed over time?
4. What would you say motivates you to wear Hijab?
5. What are the practical purposes of wearing Hijab to you? DAILY LIFE PURPOSES
6. What are the faith-based purposes of wearing Hijab to you? RELIGIOUS PURPOSES
7. How has wearing Hijab affected, if at all, your own body image?
8. Do you work or study? If yes, do you think that Hijab has an influence on your position in society? Can you please tell me more about your experience as a worker or a student?
9. What do other people that you know – such as friends and family or work colleagues - ask you about wearing the Hijab?
10. What do you think of the media's portrayal of Muslim women in general and those who wear Hijab in particular? Has such media coverage influenced your choices and experiences?
11. How do you feel about wearing Hijab in public places in Scotland?
12. What are the challenges that you have faced wearing Hijab in Scotland?
13. Have you ever felt pressure from other people to remove Hijab or to wear Hijab in a certain way?
14. Sometimes women who wear Hijab are portrayed as oppressed and having no power over their choices. What do you think of this portrayal? do you think Islamic dress implies that women are submissive and/or inferior to men?
15. Have you ever been subjugated to any kind of verbal abuse, harassment, or discrimination due to wearing the Hijab in Scotland? If yes, are you able to share your experiences with me? Moreover, do you think there are other elements like gender, race, culture, ethnicity, language that contribute to experiences of discrimination?
16. Scotland is a largely secular society. Do you think this fact is an obstacle or supports women who choose to wear Hijab and why?
17. Thank you for your time. Finally, is there anything you would like to add, that we have not covered in this interview?

12.5. Appendix Four: Letter of Introduction

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

9th May 2022

PhD Researcher: Amina Fezzioui

PhD Topic: The experiences of Muslims wearing Hijab in Scotland

This letter of introduction is for Amina Fezzioui. Amina is a PhD student in the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Amina has been studying at the University since November 2019. Her project is funded by the Algerian Government.

I write as the lead supervisor/director of studies for Amina's project. She is also supervised by Dr Anna McKeever and Dr Kallia Manoussaki at UWS.

Amina is currently engaged in fieldwork and data collection for her project. Please note she has full ethical approval for this research (application number 16727, submission reference 14028). Any assistance you can give to Amina for her study, especially in relation to her fieldwork and data collection, would be very much appreciated.

If you have any questions about Amina's doctoral research, please contact me as her lead academic supervisor. My contact details are below my signature. Please note we are currently working off campus due to COVID-19 restrictions.

Thank-you for your time and support for Amina's important PhD work.

Yours sincerely,

Personal details withheld.

Colin Clark, PhD

Professor of Sociology and Social Policy

School of Education and Social Sciences

12.6. Appendix 6: Research Invitation Poster

**AN INVITATION TO PARTICIPATE IN PHD RESEARCH
AT THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND :**

Title of project: The experiences of Muslims who wear Hijab in
Scotland

PhD Researcher: Ms Amina Fezzioui

What is the study about?

This research study explores the experiences of Muslim women who wear Hijab in Scotland. It investigates the significance, motivations, and purposes of wearing a Hijab. In addition, it explores the challenges and the effects of wearing Hijab (Islamic veil) on their daily lives, such as experiences of discrimination and/or Islamophobia that are directly related to their Hijab. It also questions the role of media representations and global events in affecting their lives as Hijabies.

Who can participate?

You have been invited to take part because you are a Muslim woman between the age of 18-56-year-old who wears Hijab in Scotland.

For more information, please contact the researcher:
Amina Fezzioui

To discuss this study with the project supervisor, please contact
Professor Colin Clark

[Redacted contact information]

Personal details withheld.

12.7. Appendix 7: Transcripts (Examples)

exploratory notes

describing the way the weaving of Hijab as a process that developed through the journey to full time

unique to a point of feeling safe with Hijab from other (dis)abled Hijab in challenge or for safety

the impo of being safe

disability

linguistic

deceptive

metaphor

relating the experience of Hijab to the journey of a Muslim

expressing a feeling

Exploratory notes

When did you first begin to cover and wear Hijab?

A1: "I started at the Islam festival in 2015. I was part-time covering and then I started full covering and started to go to the mosque and learn from then to now. I just increased the amount of covering when wearing the Hijab, so I was fully covered in 2015/16."

FIQ: what do you mean by fully covered?

"I was wearing it sometimes and removing it other. My issue is as a wheelchair user, that is why I thought my case will be so interesting for you. Because when I am trying to prepare my wheelchair, it is really difficult when you get the fabric, that is why I wear the same ones because they move with me when I am moving my head. The loose scarves are more likely to cause myself an injury... so I had to work that out because my safety is important when I am on a wheelchair it is important to Allah... so what I was doing before that, if I am going to the mosque, I would have my Hijab in my bag, I would put one on the side of my wheelchair and others will be safe on the building. At home, I put it when I am praying... so I increased it as a way to make it work for me."

FIQ: Mashallah... Mashallah... Sister could you please tell me about the feeling you had when you put it on for the first time?

A1: "When I first went to the mosque... I came from Christianity, so I understood about some people choose to cover and others being cultural and in Christianity you could often find it... because to many people it was her for me! I had really thought about it before, so when I came to Islam and of course I was going to the circle, a weekly circle at Edinburgh Central mosque... laughing, which I consider my rescue... The sisters there were really inviting, they were really friendly, but there was no pressure... because I went for the first time without my Hijab to the mosque. When you first starting to cover you feel... you feel mixed? You feel the fact that you have made a decision that you

Describing the way she was introduced to Hijab and Islam by sisters at the mosque in no pressure

personal / emotive language

personal choice (subject)

the effect of other people's perceptions on her

her experience of discrimination is worst because of her disability

Agency to make her own decisions

know it is the right decision for you... obviously for me... there was then when an anxiety about the fact that I was not sure what I was doing and that was scary, but also a sort of societal aspect about what other people will think... and I am not... I don't care what anyone thinks about me... if it is their attitudes, then it is not my problem I think it is the hardest part when you are faced by random comments in public, and the issue is that I am a wheelchair user and I cannot run away and avoid them. They literally stand and hold me or hold my wheelchair! And that can be quite abusive... it is actually a hate crime that you are picking on a wheelchair person... (a stressful laugh)... I would happily stand up for myself and say leave off my chair and it is my choice... we have freedom of religion... we have freedom of choice! So I cannot just back off and let them abuse me... it can be at times... feel a bit intimidating"

FIQ: How about the enforcement around you... let say your family, friends... what they thought about you wearing it?

A1: "Well, I am the only Muslim person in my Scottish family who followed a religion for decades (Christianity) and then changed my religion (Islam). My grandfather who died last year... he just accepted the fact that I like to do what I want to do! I am not Muslim or SB. When I reverted, he was actually driving me to the mosque, and he knew that he can help me get there on time! And he just say I will drive you there... because he is not judgemental or nasty... so when I got married, my husband is a black person from Bangladesh! And that was a cultural shock for my family too and he is Muslim... Laughing... when they got to know each other, my grandfather, though my husband was amazing... Alhamdulillah he makes me happy! It is not the norms in terms of what my family considers normal, but my family has eventually agreed with my decision. My grandfather was worried that if he opposed me I would actually go and that thing! He knows that the best thing he can do is not to tell me that I cannot do

Expressing a feeling

Expressing the power to do whatever she wants

Agency to make her own decisions

2 | Page

she must wear Hijab on Zoom too

Hijab as a time saver

Hijab is also obliged when doing a zoom call.

informative language about the religious reasons purposes of wearing the Hijab

the importance of circles in teaching and raising awareness about Hijab and Islam

feeling satisfied with the degree of covering she had on - as burqa is extreme for her?

an emotional response that describes going through lots of surgeries and lots of extra skin body image → body dysmorphism

emotionless

The influence of her body image on her mental wellbeing

7. How has wearing Hijab affected, if at all, your own body image?

"As I said already, I was 32 stone in weight! I had a tumour, [was huge, massive] I have had lots and lots of surgery... So I had my tumour removed to be of more normal size! But I have lots of extra skin, having lost a lot of weight that means I have a condition that is called body dysmorphism! So when I look to the mirror I still see 32 stone! You still see the worst bit! It is not delusional, but you still cannot get past it. So your body image is quite worked in that respect! In order to do these surgeries I have to do some mental evaluation to be able to know if I am sane to undergo these surgeries! And one of that is around body image! It is very clear whenever I do those questionnaires, I struggle with my body image now! Hopefully by the time I undergo all these surgeries I will be able to

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E/TA

feeling well when being modest wearing large clothes (especially outfits with her body image)

still difficult finding modest clothes that fit her size

identifying the importance of visibility (being Hijabi and disabled)

Hijab protects her from body dysmorphism

it is quite immediate - describing how the feeling of happiness and satisfaction

internal peace when thinking of being the best version of herself in the Revelation

Expressing satisfaction with her body image when Hijab is on

that melt away → personification

the difficulty of finding modest clothes.

The importance of representation for other Hijabis (disabled ones) to get their rights and their voice to be heard

heal from it... but when I look to the mirror with my Hijab on I do not see the body dysmorphism... it is quite incredible!

And because Allah says in the Quran: We will be the best version of ourselves in Jannah inshallah! For me when I think of being the best version of myself, I am happy I am normal, I am in very lovely shape, I do not have any issues with my body image and for me if Allah can do that! Even if I am not getting surgery, the fact that Allah will fix it... That's amazing... I got the taste of that now when I have my Hijab on! And the body dysmorphism image just melt away! As a Hijabi, you are not supposed to keep up with trends and fashion, your priority is to stay modest!! think when people see that, they feel uncomfortable because you are subjected to the same social pressure but equally the things does not equally matter to you! You always find short sleeves, in modest clothes! The clothes are not in the shop to just go and try on! It is even a big problem when you do not fit a standard size!.."

8. Do you work or study? If yes, do you think that Hijab has an influence on your position in society? Can you please tell me more about your experience as a worker or a student?

A8: yes I am a [redacted] other people access their rights! That is actually voluntary I am not actually paid for that! I am involved with the Scottish gov experience panel which is actually 10 thousand people across Scotland! Is one of the handful people who wear the Hijab that are on panel! So that representation when they are considering how to interview and how to get the information that may be able to benefit them, I am always very clear if they are going to ask for face to face! A Muslim lady may not be comfortable with a male! So they may require a female to meet their case! For me the fact that I can articulate that helps makes a system that is going to be fair to Hijabis!.. and that is awesome! The other parts that I do is kind of linked with that! The other organization that I am

the idea that being modest is prior to be fashionable

making change

changing the system

Middle ground
↓
There are difficult options to wear Hijab

T/E

The performance of identity helps other women towards Hijab

Having a positive attitude on how Muslim should be treated changing policies

the importance of being visible to encourage other Muslims to wear Hijab.

Feeling young and different

being a visible Muslim at that position helps in allaying the different policies about disability and inclusivity / privacy

The idea that she had a positive impacts on those Muslims raising awareness about Muslim esp. Muslim women

Laughing

part of... living and there is another Muslim lady there, but she does not wear the Hijab, she is much more of cultural Muslim but she also said she likes to get back to her faith! So the fact that I am Muslim and I am very visible Muslim, she is comfortable to have these conversations with me! She may even be able to have the courage to wear the Hijab at some point! That is my hope! I make dua for her... I mean you have to take that slowly... laughing... One of the reports I am involved in is about... who are... social workers to make the system for self directed support as a disabled person work better across the whole of Scotland! And how to train social workers so what they do is fair dignified and appropriate! And there is about 50 of us when we get together for that! And I am the only Muslim in the room! That is why representation really matters! So that insurance law policies are going to work within Scotland! The never think about sending a Muslim woman when the patient is a Muslim woman! Social worker they should not send a man! There should be more care if there is a Muslim that you are going to see if I had the opportunity to say this, Mashallah that's lovely! I also so a different... similar thing within the NHS! They looked at my patient experience and how that is going to be improved! I get to give the NHS suggests and feedback that have relation with Islam! Like for instance prayer room needs to be accessible! And also when I ask for some writer to make wudu (ablution) to educate the people who will help me do wudu... I cannot move my arms during wudu... I need help with that to be able to, but the staff need to be educated about what wudu is at least for 40 mins lecture..."

9. What do other people that you know - such as friends and family or work colleagues - ask you about wearing the Hijab?

A9: "I think the standard question is are not you hot in that... laughing... And I say

the importance of representation

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E/T

Some brands are inclusive of Muslim women (Hijab) Nike

Glasgow London

Edinburgh facing double standards when Hijab is being shed

Direct use of language

feeling happy of being included in the market of gym wear (inclusivity) As a disabled person Nike as an example

Compared to Glasgow and London her supervisor seems better in Edinburgh why?

Expressing discomfort with people interacting with her choice to wear Hijab

The participant expressed people taking advantage of her being in a wheelchair by placing her way in disability worse her experience as a person. Edinburgh Glasgow

Expressed and showing complacency between her Scottish identity and Muslim identity

interpersonal / referential factor

minority events from the past of people expressing her because of Hijab and pointing out that she is no more with Scottish

the very standard answer like I am in Scotland and it is freezing... laughing... actually I have the Nike Hijab to the gym, it is an ear fit one so it fits... the fact that companies like Nike they get to the point that they realized that there is a market that the technology they have to be able to make sports easier because you are not going to sweat that much! It is amazing, they still done something about it although it is not a Muslim company! Less in Edinburgh... but in Glasgow and London, I had people be very in my face about my Hijab! What in earth is going to do with you, get you hands off me! Do not block my way because they stand in front of me because I am on a wheelchair... how dare you telling me because I am Scottish! No one ever is going to tell me what to do if I do not feel like doing it! It is like they are telling me if you are putting the Hijab on you are no longer free and you are no longer Scottish! Because Scottish women are portrayed as fierce, and protective of their family and independent... no one is going to tell a Scottish woman what to do! And suddenly I put my Hijab on and people think that everyone can tell me what to do just because I put my Hijab on! That clothes on my back does not change who I am! I still do not allow anyone to tell me what to do! I do not think that they think on the first place, that is the problem... laughing!"

11. How do you feel about wearing Hijab in public places in Scotland?

A11: "I have already covered that... it is matter of representation... I never had an issue... I had an issue more when we go on south! With people feeling like they can comment and such more! I have had once had a comment in Glasgow! But in Edinburgh where I live... no body has ever told me to take it off! And in terms of wearing your Hijab in certain way, there are certain utopic channels that show you how to put that that is a style thing that is not Hijab if you using that you are not doing what Allah has asked us to do! It is more about fashion! I mean they are still modest with it... but it is like being a peacock... a

Scottish identity + Muslim identity

Expressing discomfort with people

plastic of Glasgow in Glasgow with a Hijab

Expressing struggle and discomfort with Islamophobic

ET

Hijab
Fashion
original
my
group
attacker
Critic

Overall
feels
super
scotland

incompatible
identities
scotland
vs
Muslim

feeling
left out

being
visible
to
challenge
stereotypes
identity

feeling
empathy
towards
Muslims

Hijab should (must) be modest. should not be so attention grabbing.
Modesty as a requirement
personal function of buying
Expressing comfort and safety going out in Scotland as a disabled Hijabi
England Glasgow, again (repeats).

incompatible identities - feeling both left out because of choosing to be a visible Muslim
A stereotype that Muslims do not belong to the West.
interpersonal function - expressing a desire to rebel against the stereotype as it is being visible?
MEDIA
Using We to refer to her identity - A sign of belonging - identity work with a group of people
11. "those people who are" Muslims - referring to Muslims using "they" - confusion
The feeling of empathy because of relation to others - Scotland

peacock is being modest... it is a bit of contradiction here! I mean I love colors, I do not wear it all black... but I would be so uncomfortable if I am going like look at me look at me! Overall, I feel comfortable going out in Scotland!
10. What do you think of the media's portrayal of Muslim women in general and those who wear Hijab in particular? Has such media coverage influenced your choices and experiences?
13. Have you ever felt pressure from other people to remove Hijab or to wear Hijab in a certain way?
A13: "I think in England had people asking me to take my Hijab off and I am not obviously from there! I've been there for a trip... it is weird that you get off the train there in England and find people commenting and here in Glasgow I had once or twice people when they hear me speak they suddenly tell me get that out of your head! Because they think that as a Scot, I should not be Muslim! It is their interpretation that Muslims are foreigners! I challenge that stereotype so that is why I got them to comment! There is a difference between England and Scotland in that respect for sure... you only got to look at the refugees situation, we are busy telling them you are welcome, while in England they asked them to take them back! And here we have a welcoming parties at the mosque, we have set up clothing banks to make sure people feel welcomed! That is a part of the difference between being Scottish and English! That is a long-standing thing. That is not just about Islam!"
Faq: What do you think of the difference between being Scottish and English in relation to Islam?
A13: "we are used to having take the media with a pinch of salt, to think what the real story is! We also learn to think with ourselves! Our people were displaced for generations... so we have that empathy with other people who are Muslims and do not go home like we get that! The English did not go through that so they do not have that understand, the English have

Scotland as more tolerant compared to England
Again, a comparison between England and Scotland. The participatory seems to be Scotland as more inclusive than England

ET

England
A
Scotland

Having
the
agency
to
make
her
choices

Gender
relations

Primarily
Male
dominance
Islam

Media
Negating
portrayal

oppression

Referring to England as the oppressor and England as Scotland.
A directive function of being visible - disagreement with the portrayal
A sarcastic tone - puns
Expressing confidence and power over her choices
Gender relations - Expressing a positive stance towards the relationship with her husband.
Using adjectives like protector, supporter to refer to him
Gender relations, primarily Male dominance of Islam Saudi Arabia / Iran
The role of the media in spreading binary stories about Islam - cultural + political agendas
The dangerous effect (difference) of the media on ppl's minds

always been the oppressors, this is not how Scotland works!
14. Sometimes women who wear Hijab are portrayed as oppressed and having no power over their choices. What do you think of this portrayal? do you think Islamic dress implies that women are submissive and/or inferior to men?
A14: "I disagree with that portrayal... a sarcastic tone... I would like to see anyone trying to tell me what to wear! We discussed that. I think the issue with me is that I see a lot and lot of abayas, but they do not fit me because they are Asian sizes, which mean that my Islamic choices are limited! I wear cardigans, long sleeves! My husband helps me check if everything is covered before I go out! He will tell me not to be controlling, but to make sure I am covered (he is my protector so he makes sure that I am covered properly) so he tries to help me maintain my modesty! When it comes to things like eid for example he is from Bangladesh from a family that gets new clothes every eid, but he also understands that this issue can be so stressful for me! He tries to plan early and make sure to get the money so he can, when it comes to oppression that is a patriarchal thing, like for instance in Saudi Arabia, the ruling people are males, so they do not understand the struggles of Hijab, but is that about Male dominance, not Islamic male dominance, they want to do what they want! That is not about Islam that is about their free will! The same for Iran, there is no compulsion in Islam! Because if you look at the media and see these stories, you will say that's Islam... what! That is people think Islam oppresses women! That is not Islam, that is the cultural and political agendas! People do not understand that there is a difference!
The problem is that people do not understand the history of these countries, they barely understand the history of their countries! I have people that do not understand the importance of clarences for example! And if you do not understand the history of your own country how can

body may struggle to fit
overweight - limited Islamic choices
Modesty
Baby
Judge
culture vs Islam
A Sarcastic tone

Eff

Media also runs a stance

hurry singles and power in Islam Gender RISH

Media Brain wash people

intends and community are impacted

Expressing negative feeling (stance) about the media representation of the media who runs a positive side (Malala)

A confusing stance informative / representative language that shows her power / capability (she understands her rights in Islam) Brain washed / Metaphor that shows the influence of the media on how people perceive Muslims

The attachment with Muslims give a clearer picture about them

Islam vs Political Hijab as a political symbol of oppression Misplaced anger

you possibly understand the history of other people's country? The media has a role in increasing Islam, but the Western side is a point in representing people like Malala for all the things that she does people think that is amazing! They are showing that they are not hiding it for discussion about Islam, but I think it is really difficult for people to understand it and that just the reality of it because, it is tricky to decide whether it is against or with, people do not have access to all the information so they will think that Muslim men oppress their women! And that is not allowed Islamically, if my husband does that, I will divorce him! It is only because they read it or see it somewhere! They are brainwashed, I think if the law is about banning the Hijab the same will happen to what happen to the disabled persons during the 50s and 60s, during this time disabled people as a part of the inclusion movement they chain themselves to buses to explain the fact that they have no access to buses! People were just annoyed that people on wheelchair were having injustice and they were concerned about going to work, I think the same like they will get annoyed at the fact that people are making a fuss about it and it is getting on their way! I think people will see what they want to see but in reality they are not Muslim and they do not understand this! I think it only start to impact people when they interact with Muslims! Or come across someone like me who would highlight why Hijab is so important to me! I think the situation in Iraq is when they do not believe Islamically, this is going to confuse people who are here further! They see that a no decide that is part of Islam! This is not Islam and this not what Allah wants! People when they do these things they forget that these instructions come from Allah SWT, the people who are banning it they are not annoyed with Allah's instructions, they are angry with the political system, so burning a symbol which is from Allah, Hijab is a misplaced anger! Just imagine in the day of

Men oppress women

copying two seats that make relates to

The ban of the Hijab and the movement of disabled people

interacts

13 | Page Hijab as a symbol of oppression political Hijab is dangerous

Eff

forcing?

cultural Hijab is oppression

understand Hijab and good interact we speak

Islam is essential

The importance of understanding Hijab (for wearing it) As a cultural thing? without understanding? the importance of a good introduction to Hijab Oppression is a part of patriarchy and it is socially constructed in Islam

Referral fractions reports by Muslim Politicians that relate to her Hijab people take advantage of her other ability mostly from men

difference otherness

A sense of belonging solidarity

judgement being asked why did you burn your Hijab? Well because we felt oppressed! So why did not reached me for help and make duaa? It is a misplaced anger! It influences women who wear Hijab especially if they are uneducated about Hijab! It is a cultural thing over there! They only asked to be covered like you must covered you must covered, they do not really understand it! Allah asked us to wear it and that you are safe from Satan's gaze! I think it may sound like a way of oppression to women who are asked not to leave their houses by their husbands who are probably uneducated about Islam! And who think it is right because they watched their fathers, grandfathers do to their wives! That is the problem like some of them needs Islamic education to guide them in their life! A5: Have you ever been subjugated to any kind of verbal abuse, harassment, or discrimination due to wearing the Hijab in Scotland? If yes, are you able to share your experiences with me? Moreover, do you think there are other elements like gender, race, culture, ethnicity, and language that contribute to experiences of discriminating? A15: "It happened on the 1st of October, it happened people blocking my wheelchair, I've had people telling me to take my hijab off! And I had people looking at us as a family and thinking that my two daughters are actually my husband's wife's just because I am on a wheelchair! Or thinking that I am their grandma! It is difficult to guess the age of someone when there is a hijab on! But that is just people's ignorance! You are less likely to get an issues from women, like make sure to always smiling at Hijabees so they know that they are identified and someone is watching to keep eye on them! It is a solidarity thing and it is very

Engage

older?

body merge

an oppression

14 | Page solidarity to other Hijabees

married this an introduction; it is not a match making service! I mean who are you that what I need to know as an introduction. I mean I am not interested about it I mean I am still identified. That is just bizarre. I speak Scottish and there are a lot of languages... I am very fortunate because I am one of the people who has been invited to Moroccan and Afghan weddings... but when I see my husband and he speaks on the phone, people will be like and he is from as well I don't know if he is loud or it is the issue of the language! It is hard to tell, but he is also Black! So we are very very visible! noticeable! My personal opinion about it is that people get really used when they just see me when a person comes to see me and sees a white person and they think that they are going to put it on their heads! They always think they got something wrong! And then I suddenly speak and I got to tell them what to do, this is not what I expected!

Scotland is a largely secular society. Do you think this fact is an obstacle or supports women who choose to wear Hijab and why?

A16: "genuinely I think people here are accepting. One of the adverts before the referendum in 2014 shows a muslim lady with a flag scarf and that was all over the media! We got the coverage from the level that was literally everything in run-up I think it is hard for people to feel it is old! There are still individuals who are racists and ignorants who prefer that we rather take our Hijabs off, because they do not understand. I cannot tell you how many people who I met that who think that Hijab is forced! When I see that is not allowed in Islam, it is my choice... people cannot believe that this is Islam! So the fact that Scotland is largely secular people will not care if you got nose rings or tattoos, why would they care if you got your Hijab on! Whenever I feel uncomfortable when people stand and block my way I am not on my own someone will come and say can I help you! I am not sure if it happens anywhere, know it is very a Scottish thing! I think if it is secular then that helps as long as I can demonstrate what Islam is! And be a positive example! That change the narrative about Hijab! I think saying better is a difficult word! I think Scotland is more accepting than France for instance! Scotland has no plan to ban it for example! We hold our freedom very high! France believes that 'barabare and freedom are never superior than theirs! That is not how it works here... laughter I think in Scotland... not sure in England we have muslim ministers in such like in the parliament that representation matters! We have a first minister (Nicola) who always says eid Mubarak! Who were hugely apologetic that the exams last year were during Ramadan! and that understanding is really refreshing! Islamophobia requires a lot of work that does not happen overnight! And people who are Muslims are actually involved in the processes!"

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Not section of that identities

increase of identities

The feeling of being visible and different worries about how people work out the different identities in her family.

Her family has various identities they go out and are visible

Scottish man inclusive and tolerant with

the Scottish gov in minority

Not at street level

passes stereotypes

low people perceive (or forced)

social must apply to all

+ EXP

perception

your Hijab on! Whenever I feel uncomfortable when people stand and block my way I am not on my own someone will come and say can I help you! I am not sure if it happens anywhere, know it is very a Scottish thing! I think if it is secular then that helps as long as I can demonstrate what Islam is! And be a positive example! That change the narrative about Hijab! I think saying better is a difficult word! I think Scotland is more accepting than France for instance! Scotland has no plan to ban it for example! We hold our freedom very high! France believes that 'barabare and freedom are never superior than theirs! That is not how it works here... laughter I think in Scotland... not sure in England we have muslim ministers in such like in the parliament that representation matters! We have a first minister (Nicola) who always says eid Mubarak! Who were hugely apologetic that the exams last year were during Ramadan! and that understanding is really refreshing! Islamophobia requires a lot of work that does not happen overnight! And people who are Muslims are actually involved in the processes!"

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feeling proud of being Scottish

feeling proud of being Scottish

The act of resistance as a part of changing stereotypes

A lot of work need to be done to battle Islamophobia.

change the narrative about Muslim women and Hijab

still a lot of work to be done to battle Islamophobia

pride!

good people

+ example!

gov is working on Islamophobia

It was entirely my choice. My parents did ask me, but you must wear it. *expressing the importance of choice in the decision making process (agency), there is a contribution*

youngest
YOUNGEST PARTICIPANT

1. When did you first begin to cover and wear Hijab?
A1: "I first started started university"
FUQ: Can you tell me about the day you decided to wear it?
A1: "I don't know, I just woke up and decided to wear it, I just put it on and felt right. I just put it on the 1st day of the university, I just woke up and decided to put it on. I cannot really describe how I felt about wearing the Hijab for the first time, maybe because I was determined about wearing it. I did not feel any negative thing. I just felt happy in my heart like I was satisfied with that. And that is what matters the most."
FUQ: "Could you tell me about your parents' or friends' reaction?"
A1: "My parents were so happy with my decision, they have always wanted me to wear it because my mom does, my entire family wears it and most of my friends do, so they have always wanted me to wear it. I just was not ready because I did not have the confidence to. I was in high school, and I was not prepared for all the questions and looks from people, so I just wanted to wait until I enter the university to avoid all that!"
2. Were you forced to wear Hijab?
A2: "No, it was entirely my choice. Like my parents did ask me, but they said it is totally your choice whenever you feel comfortable wear it, so we are not going to tell you that you must wear it right now! I have always dressed modestly; I did not cover my hair. That was the only difference! I kept the same style now, I am just covering my head. I do consider that my Hijab is a proper and modest Hijab."
FUQ: could you please describe the way you wear Hijab?
A2: "I make sure my hair is covered, I wrap my Hijab around my neck and my chest area. When I am wearing baggy clothes then I just like my hair and neck are covered. I wear a lot of hoodies and they are large and baggy (laughing)!"
FUQ: Can you remember when your parents asked you to start wearing the Hijab?
A2: "I do not remember when my parents asked me to wear it. I think it was around high school, but I do not know exactly when it was. I think it was around high school, but I do not know exactly when it was. I think it was around high school, but I do not know exactly when it was."

describing the 1st time of wearing Hijab
I cannot really describe how I felt about wearing the Hijab for the 1st time - expressing confusion in making such a decision
felt slight? why? was she feeling uncomfortable not pitying hijab on?
describing her feelings of wearing the Hijab
determined / Happy satisfied - expressing satisfaction with the decision
1st day of the uni - a mature age to decide?
My mom does. Using the figure of mom as a role model
The influence of the environment on the decision making process
They have always wanted me to wear it - skin a pressure?
I did not know the confidence
expressing the fear of being excluded
High school - why exactly the stage?
The fear of being judged

a desire to of her style
That was the only difference
The transition from a New wearer of Hijab to a wearer of Hijab not that big
does it signify difference of being strange
deciding how she wears the hijab
Modestly
The impact of dressing modestly without of

A3: I do participate shows that she used to follow be modest even before the Hijab. The only difference is covering her hair. Her power has not been taken away.

A2: "Yes, when I started puberty as you know when the girl reaches that time it becomes compulsory that she wears Hijab"
FUQ: What do you think about the idea of forcing women to wear Hijab?
A2: "Well, I don't think it should be forced! I mean it is compulsory in Islam, but there is no way that women should be forced to wear it. We should be able to make our decisions when we are comfortable wearing them! I think when forcing women to wear Hijab must do more to do with men's power and culture. I feel like it has to do with men's thinking that they have the authority to do so."
FUQ: What does Hijab signify to you? In addition, has this significance changed over time?
A3: "For me Hijab has more of a religious meaning because it does help me stay closer to my religion and go closer to God and it is like holding a high value in my life, it signifies my strength and courage to be able to start wearing it and this has not really changed. This significance has not changed because for me it was more of a confidence thing to start wearing it. I needed the confidence and putting it shows that I have great strength that I have managed to put it on. From 2019 until today, I still have the same feelings about my hijab."
FUQ: So you are not thinking of removing it?
A3: "No, never! I made that commitment to myself that is why it took me so long to put it on. Cause for me I was like if I am going to put it on, it is going to stay for life and that is why I took a long time to decide. Hijab also shows my identity to the rest of the world, but for me, it also shows the religious, confidence and strength part! Cause for me it shows the strength to be able to take steps though."
FUQ: would you explain that more?
A3: "Sure, because before I put it on, I was scared that people will look at me differently or treat me differently. So strength for me is taking the courage to put it on."
FUQ: And do you think that Hijab makes you powerful?
A3: "I do not think I have changed that much, the only thing that has changed is my hair is covered now, you cannot see it. So, I believe my power is not boosted or gone low, it is at a normal level (laughing)."

Hijab as a marker Muslim identity
sense of belonging
sheds up the skin to Hindu
strength
commitment
sheds up the skin to Hindu
Hijab as a tool of empowerment
a strong step to put Hijab on

Hitting puberty
Compulsory - signifies the importance of wearing the Hijab in Islam
Again stressing the importance of Hijab in Islam, yet that showing the significance of choice & plays in women's decision to wear it.
from singular to plural
what does this signify? unity?
sisterhood
men's power and culture
The use of the term power. Power relation
Authority
Hijab and religiosity
closer to my religion
Hijab as a reminder of her faith
constant
holding a high value in my life
Personification - referring to the Hijab as a woman who holds a dear place to her heart.
The idea that there is an emotional connection between her and the Hijab
The fear of being judged or excluded by others
The importance of being satisfied with wearing the Hijab
commitment
it took me so long to put it on
stay for life

repetition of strength
Taking a step to wear Hijab according to her power which she can do anything
Assertive language

Hijab
= cannot protect you all the time why is being a woman in danger? (3)

Contradiction
Secular

4. What would you say motivates you to wear Hijab?

A4: "My motivation did come from my family and friends because I have seen them wear it. They have been wearing it for years now, even my younger cousins, they started the year I started, but they started before me and for me it was like a great push because I felt like I am their positive role model and they should not be the first to cover first, so that also pushed me to put it on! And that was a part of my motivation"

FUQ: Could you give me their ages?

A4: "They are about 12 and 13 years old, they started wearing it the first year [redacted]"

As I have told you did not want to be the same age as them but [redacted]"

questions. I went to [redacted] is not like they are going to look at me differently, it was just all the questions. You know when it gets too much and some of them can be silly and you just do not want to answer these questions. You have just done something and there is a change in yourself, I felt like if I start university, I won't anybody, so nobody knows how my life was before, so I can totally get away with this (laughing)"

5. What are the practical purposes of wearing Hijab to you? DAILY LIFE PURPOSES

A5: "To be honest I do not have bad hair days (laughing). Generally, I feel more secure and covered. I know people say it does not matter how you dress anything can happen regardless, but I feel within the community I am living in because I live in a very populated Pakistani Muslim area, it just makes me a bit secure that I am covered, and no one is looking at me in a different way. It saves time as well"

FUQ: You have said that you live in a very populated Pakistani Muslim area. Were you uncomfortable going outside in that area without a Hijab on?

A5: "Yup, most of them go outside wearing Hijab, so you may feel like you are the only one who is not putting Hijab on! So I felt it may be a good thing if I have just worn it too. Does that make sense? I avoid judgment from the community there as well because they all know my family and it is a bit uncomfortable to go around with my hair uncovered (laughing). Hijab also protects me from sexual gazes,

The idea of an external influence on the decision making of the participant

did come from my family and friends. younger cousins? feeling guilty or ashamed for not wearing it before her younger cousins?

positive role model - is it a pressure? to be such a model?

"They should not be the 1st to cover" - stressing the importance of sanitation in constructing identity

"I was afraid of all the questions" "can be silly" The fear of being excluded or judged?

The idea of moving from oneself to another self (transforming) (change in yourself)

"Nobody knows how my life was before" - Afraid of judgment? / otherness? external influence? pressure

Assumption
Contradiction
Others
The
community

Abstract
laugh

More secure and powerful
Hijab as a tool of empowerment
protection

different way?
what does it mean?
a pressure from the Muslim community too?

reputation
religious
reputation

people do not look at you in that sexual way, you know what I mean?"

6. What are the faith-based purposes of wearing Hijab to you? RELIGIOUS PURPOSES
 A6: "I KNOW THAT Hijab is compulsory, and it is our way to be closer to God. It shows our identity, it shows that we are Muslims. It gives me the confidence to practice my religion openly as well and be visible. I have read verses from Quran about Hijab and covering, and I just don't remember them. So, I was summarized first about the A hadith and Quranic verses about covering"

7. How has wearing Hijab affected, if at all, your own body image?
 A7: "I do not think that Hijab affects it because I used to dress modestly all the time. Some people refer to Hijab as covering their whole body and some people just refer to it as their headscarf. But I used to dress modestly before because I was never comfortable wearing something that is not modest myself. I am still dressing the same, just with a scarf! I believe it kind of protects me from Western beauty standards, that I believe they are way too much. I believe Hijab dresses you in a manner that makes you simple and seen and not worrying about that I have to fit in this and I have to fit in that because you are doing it for yourself and for your religion. I believe it covered my body so people do know my body shape and weight. But I believe in some ways people still look at you and say that you look so skinny, people still comment on you regardless!"

FUC: So, do you feel beautiful with Hijab on?
 A7: "Internally yes, I know like everyone outside is like you look nice and so on. For me, it has never been a beauty thing for me. Because nowadays, there is also Hijabi beauty standards. You can see that Hijabis are wearing loads and loads of makeup and there is nothing wrong with that I am not against that, but there is a Hijab beauty standard that I don't think I fit in. But I do feel more beautiful with my Hijab on! Because you know even if I take it off at my house I feel like something is missing (laughing) it just does not look right. I feel like Hijab makes me beautiful"

8. Do you work or study? If yes, do you think that Hijab has an influence on your position in society? Can you please tell me more about your experience as a worker or a student?
 A8: "I do both, I study and I work a part-time job. I do not think it affects my position because within the uni I managed to become a student rep for my course, but there are quite a few Muslims and non-Muslims. I was the only Hijabi and I managed to be the student rep. So I do not think it does an impact on my position. At work, my manager is a Hijabi and a Muslim, so she is the manager of that area of the pharmacy. People already treat her with respect, so it was easier for me to get the same respect as her. I am expecting to get some challenges in the future with my Hijab as you know I started wearing it only two years ago! I know the journey is not going to be easy, I think my manager paved the way for me and made it easier to deal with my Hijab in a work position because she has been here for years and everyone knows her. So, it is not something strange for me to go to that workplace wearing a Hijab because people there when seeing her already get used to the idea of it. We are the only two wearing Hijab there!"

FUC: Do you think you want to change the Western opinion about Hijab?
 A8: "Yeah, I think so! Because generally, the Western idea about Hijab is that we are oppressed from wearing it. Most of us as Hijabis are doing whatever we can on our Hijab on our heads to change this perception"

FUC: Do you think that Hijab has an influence on how people perceive you?
 A8: "It does!"

FUC: Do you think that people find you attractive?
 A8: "To be honest no! because I do not give that energy out to be approachable in that manner that they find me attractive or something. I feel that Hijab protects me from that! It depends on the person, but people tend not to approach you when you are wearing a Hijab"

FUC: What do other people that you know - such as friends and family or work colleagues - ask you about wearing the Hijab?
 A9: "Most of my friends are from the Muslim community and I have only two friends that are not Muslims. They ask me loads of questions about Islam as you know already. They just ask"

informative language - giving evidence from their religion
Hijab as a way to increase religiosity
"Our identity" - Muslim identity
Using the term "Our" - shift from singular to plural
Assign of a feeling of belonging to a large community of Muslims
The importance of being visible and expressing religion openly to the participant
I was convinced - along the participant's nature and self-fulfilling decision
Hijab and religion as a simple of belonging
The idea of being modest is repeated - Hijab refers to modesty
Hijab as a protector of the body image and internal peace? Follow your own standards
Western beauty standards - does Hijab contradict these standards?
"Fit in this" - Otherness?
Hijabi beauty standards ≠ Western beauty standards?
Modern Hijab?

informative language
religious language
religiosity
modesty
Hijab as a protector
body image
internal peace
standards
Western beauty standards
does Hijab contradict these standards?
"Fit in this"
Otherness?
Hijabi beauty standards
Western beauty standards
Modern Hijab?

5

→ The idea that Hijab is a constraint for women achieving success - a confidant/happy tone

My manager is a Hijabi and a Muslim - the importance of representation in nearby women Rep confident - feeling more confident with the existence of another Hijabi

"expect some challenges" "isn't going to be easy" "why assuming that?" "paved the way" etc

importance of a role model representation and people being familiar and knowledgeable about the Hijab

strange = we -> Many plural form to show the same experience

The idea of expressing a belief and shared feeling with other Hijabis

Western idea about Hijab that we are oppressed - that we are oppressed - stereotype (deconstructing it?)

The importance of perceived or her experience

releasing a position of power
the importance of representation
changing the perception
A pressure responsibility
Hijab as a tool to protect from being approached by others

Hijab as a part of her look & identity of the nation

me questions like why are you wearing it and for what reasons! And my colleagues they haven't really asked me because I believe they may ask questions to my manager! They ask with it lol and if I was forced to wear it... (laughing) don't feel offended, I am always happy to answer questions about Hijab

10. What do you think of the media's portrayal of Muslim women in general and those who wear Hijab in particular? Has such media coverage influenced your choices and experiences?

A10: "Media portrays Hijab as a very bad thing! In some cases, women are forced we know that ourselves, they are a minority compared to most of us who choose to cover up and live a modest life. You would not say to someone who choose not to cover that they are forced not to cover up because that is their choice and it has never impacted how I feel because it is my connection with God regardless of what others in the media portray, so I feel like when putting on is just a way of breaking these barriers and stereotypes that you are forced to wear it because everyone around me knows that it was my decision to wear it. Media portrayal is mostly negative, I am sure you know the Netflix movies, they always end up removing the Hijab characters (laughing). Non-Muslims who are influenced by the media just perceive it as we are oppressed and we are being forced to do it, so in some movies they portray Muslim women that they are taking off their Hijabs behind their parents, I feel like it is not fair on us as well, because we have chosen to wear it for a specific reason and we are happy to wear it and the media just keep portraying it as a very bad thing! People in that case will start looking at you differently. As I grow up to decide that I am going to wear the Hijab, I don't think that the media messages now has an influence on my confidence to wear it. If I am a teenager I think it would possibly influence me, but I feel like as I grow up my family has my back. I believe that the upbringing also affects decision making process. So my family always say that I do not need to care about what other people think of me, just do what you think it is best for you, so even if I was younger I will always be happy with my choice! Also, I think it is necessary for people who want to learn about Hijab to learn from trustful sources and do not rely heavily on media! That thing is very important, so if they asked us why we choose to wear it, it would be great!

11. How do you feel about wearing Hijab in public places in Scotland?

A11: "I had maybe one encounter, but it was not... I was in Tesco's, I felt like someone mattered under their nose, but it was not right to my face and did not feel the need to approach them or anything... so I just walked off, so that was the only bad experience that I have had. He was a white man"

FUC: How do you feel now about wearing Hijab in Scotland, because you have switched from a Hijabi to a non-Hijabi?

A11: "I think I feel fine! For me, it is my choice, so I don't really think of what people think of me outside, I don't feel scared or anything. There are of course the odd racist few people here, but I have never encountered one my entire life, I feel safe because Scotland is like whatever you like kind of country"

12. What are the challenges that you have faced wearing Hijab in Scotland?

A12: "Just that one that I have mentioned"

13. Have you ever felt pressure from other people to remove Hijab or to wear Hijab in a certain way?

A13: "I have never felt the pressure to remove it from the part of a non-Muslim community, I can say I felt that from my dad's side of the family! But I have not had it from the non-Muslim community. They live in Pakistan, so for them like you are being an extremist, but you are not really! They do not want me to wear it because they think that I am still young and I need to live my life. They do not wear Hijab, they have cultural attire and they wrap a scarf on their heads when they go out! I don't know what exactly their problem with me, I mean I wanted it that way! They just want to put me off it! I don't know why maybe because they know that my mom's side of the family wear it, so I think it has to do with their mentality! I think because their daughters do not wear it so they think that I may be better than them, so it is more of a cultural and status thing, I believe they are influenced by globalization and may be better than them - Hijab degree of religiosity in conservative ...

Why are you wearing it and for what reasons? - I don't signifi... then I've st... in leaving about Rev... They might ask my manager - Does the existence of Rev... Rev's experience at the work place move... silly questions - why does she consider it as silly, do they consider Rev... of an bold... I disagree with it. The lack of knowledge about Hijab. Forced to wear it - The power of perception in making assumption... I am always happy to answer questions about Hijab. I desire to change people's perception about Hijab. describing how media portrays Hijab - an extreme expression of how media portrays the Hijab! A respectful tone. The difference promotes moving from the third party promoted (they) refer to the experience of women who are forced to wear Hijab to "be a part of us", our choice to

with my choice! Also, I think it is necessary for people who want to learn about Hijab to learn from trustful sources and do not rely heavily on media! That thing is very important, so if they asked us why we choose to wear it, it would be great!

11. How do you feel about wearing Hijab in public places in Scotland?

A11: "I had maybe one encounter, but it was not... I was in Tesco's, I felt like someone mattered under their nose, but it was not right to my face and did not feel the need to approach them or anything... so I just walked off, so that was the only bad experience that I have had. He was a white man"

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... describing a bad experience describing in comparison to think that she relates her to Hijab. A woman - power relations - superiority? It's implicit? "I feel fine" a participant experienced both wearing and not wearing the Hijab in Scotland. "I do not feel scared" - expressly comfort going out wearing Hijab in Scotland. "Odd", "Racist", "Race concluded have?" "Whatever you like to do country?" showing the respect that Scotland have for diverse background. Feeling pressure to remove it from her Muslim family (Dad's side) "I am still young" - relating Hijab with being old and restricting her ability to live a full life. "I don't know what exactly their problem with me?" - expressly confusion

Hijab is not MODERN

modernisation over there, they think that not wearing the Hijab is a modern move! They are heavily influenced by Westerners and their lifestyle is not Islamic 100 per cent (not a very Islamic leading life), that is weird getting it from a Muslim people!
 FUC: What do you think about the Muslim community here?
 A13: "The Muslim community over here really encourages you to wear it, the area that I live in most of them wear Hijabs. But some people sometimes find your Hijab unproper and they judge the way you wear Hijab because there are some areas where they wear it with their hair showing, that would be the older generation that would judge them for that, and there are some from my own generations that judge this as well. I haven't received any, but I know people who have"
 FUC: Can you tell me about your mom is she a Hijabi?
 A13: "She started wearing it when they moved here in 1990. So at that time Hijab was not a common thing, so when she started wearing it she received criticism from some both Muslim and non-Muslim communities. Because it was not something that out there before! You can only see an odd few people wearing Hijab back then. Now is totally fine! I mean you always see a person that you know wearing it, which is kind of a relief!"
 14. Sometimes women who wear Hijab are portrayed as oppressed and having no power over their choices. What do you think of this portrayal? do you think Islamic drags implies that women are submissive and/or inferior to men?
 A14: "I think that is wrong, I believe women who wear Hijab has power over choice. I believe it is the culture that dictates that. I believe Islam does preach that we have our rights and we can make our own minds and we have our free will. I think we need to get rid of the cultural toxicity and the patriarchy. When forcing women to wear Hijab, I think it has more to do with the cultural part, they kind of use religion the way they want to impose their power on women... I don't think that Hijab implies that women are inferior to men"

Expressing pressure from the Muslim community for not wearing the Hijab properly
 older generation - different perspectives
 Sherry Rev mother experience.
 The Hijab was a rare costume (1990)
 odd few people - why odd (strange) to express the inferiority of people with Hijab
 Comparing both periods
 Now Hijab is more common
 which is a kind of relief - being more comfortable with the existence of other hijabees
 power over their choice.
 The agency of Muslim women who wear Hijab
 "Culture" - binary culture for inequality

Feeling judged and pressured from Muslim community
 Relating to how non-Muslims affect us
 Islam is culture
 Hijab does not equal inferiority

Then = Men

15. Have you ever been subjugated to any kind of verbal abuse, harassment, or discrimination due to wearing the Hijab in Scotland? If yes, are you able to share your experiences with me? Moreover, do you think there are other elements like gender, race, culture, ethnicity, and language that contribute to experiences of discrimination?
 A15: "It was that one encounter that I told you about earlier! But I know some cases. I know someone that has had a bad experience. Well, they were walking through a shopping centre. That was around that time when there was that Muslim hate day, they were punishing Muslims. I was not a Hijabi at that time. You could have that tiny bit of fear that it might actually happen to you. But I think that if you show that fear people may take advantage of it so you need to mind your own business so people would not care then. I also think that the hate against Muslims intensified at times like 9/11 and like the Manchester bombing, the racism is heightened around this time of the year in a way I feel afraid to go outside when the memories of these events get back in my mind when 9/11 comes each year, I am usually at the house... and yeah I think that other elements contribute to that experience like race, ethnicity and language does a big part because like if you are a Pakistani they are going to call you a Paki for sure and if you are speaking in your own language, they are going to say that you must speak English... Yup I have encountered people throwing around the name word"
 16. Scotland is a largely secular society. Do you think this fact is an obstacle or supports women who choose to wear Hijab and why?
 A16: "I think most of Scotland does support women who wear Hijab because they are a very open country, they are supporting other religious beliefs, LGBTQ+ community, you are free to do whatever you want... For me, I haven't encountered any kind of racism yet because it has only been 2 years that I have started wearing it. I don't think it is a very big obstacle to start wearing it. I mean they do support your decisions! I think gendered Islamophobia here is low compared to England especially because you can hear people are being pushed off to trains, there is constant

describing an uncomfortable situation (Islamophobia) at school level
 "They were punishing Muslims"
 The pronoun (they) - who do they mean by using they?
 The state of being always aware and cautious
 The feeling of fear about how to overcome it (a coping mechanism)
 Sherry discomfort and concern at 9/11 time of the year - why? did it still influence her with this tie?
 The memories of this event get back - still haunted by the influence of 9/11 still on display in the intersection of other elements like Race and language - not only appear
 Does Paki relate to the Hijab?
 Describing Scotland as a welcoming country that accepts difference

Islamophobia
 fear
 the experience of the events like 9/11, Manchester bombing
 using the word a yet - is the equality still? hard to report

comparing Scotland to England and discussing the current situation

(17)

10

racism there every single day and France also is horrible with the Hijab ban and all these policies. I feel like Scotland is more open and supportive of it compared to these other countries"

17. Thank you for your time. Finally, is there anything you would like to add, that we have not covered in this interview?

A17: "I think Hijab now becomes more about fashion; it has lost some of its significance. I THINK NOW THERE is a hijabi beauty standards. They are all over social media like Instagram, tiktok. These Hijabies now are being sexualized for wearing Hijab that way. Like they are seeking attention, it has become more about fashion especially for the men and the boys... I feel like now they target Hijabis more than non-Hijabis. I think this gives a bad idea about how Hijab should be. Hijab is not for fashion, the whole purpose of it is to cover ourselves and to be protected from Fitnah and to make us closer to god, you can see that they do not respect it on tiktok, they dance with it sometimes! I would say that Hijabies should be confident with their choices and you should not let anyone's opinions, especially the media get to, if you are happy to do something just continue with it! I don't think we should follow this Hijabi beauty standards either to fit in this society... it may push Muslim women who are younger to wear it but in this case for the wrong reasons. The positive side is getting people to wearing it, but the negative side is it loses its meaning. Also families should not force their daughters to wear it.. I was so happy with the way my parents introduce me to Hijab, they gave me the choice, the only thing they told me is that we would be happy if you choose to wear it and if you don't we won't be angry or upset! Hijab needs to be introduced in a positive manner because I know that those who are forced to wear it, they will remove it when their parents are not around... Men also do have Hijab they also need to cover their awrah and lowering their gaze .

desiring the experience in Scotland as mostly positive and giving examples of other countries that wear Hijab there, probably to her is difficult!

"These Hijabies" -> using this plural pronoun to describe those who wear Hijab for the sake of fashion -

The idea that Hijab now is mostly worn for the wrong purpose, is stressed by the participant giving examples of social platforms that show the wrong way of wearing the Hijab (TikTok Insta)

The younger generation are the most to be influenced - stressing the importance of good introduction to the life! Expressing satisfaction and joy with wearing it - stressing the importance of lowering the gaze for both genders

side

side

the importance of good introduction to Hijab

